

- CROP WEATHER
- CHEMISTRY
- PLANT PHYSIOLOGY
- SOIL MICROBIOLOGY
- STATISTICS
- PLANT PATHOLOGY
- SOIL CHEMISTRY
- AGRONOMY
- AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING
- AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS
- VARIETAL IMPROVEMENT
- ENTOMOLOGY

70

INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR 1970

the international rice research institute annual report for 1970

The International Rice Research Institute was established jointly by The Rockefeller Foundation and the Ford Foundation in cooperation with the Republic of the Philippines. It was incorporated in 1960 and dedicated in 1962 when the research program began. This annual report, the ninth to be published by the Institute, presents a detailed account of the work done in 1970.

Data in the report are given in metric units, e.g., "t/ha" means metric tons per hectare. Grain yield of rice is calculated in rough rice at 14 percent moisture. "Control" means untreated control unless otherwise stated. A single asterisk means significant at the 1% level; a double asterisk means significant at the 5% level.

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The International Rice Research Institute Annual Report for 1970

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Mail Address: P.O. Box 1300, M.C.C. Makati, Rizal D-709, Philippines City Office: IRRI, Manila Hotel, Manila

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Violeta G. Cordova, B.S., research assistant
Cristina M. Crisostomo, A.B., research assistant*
Abraham M. Mandac, research assistant
Rodolfo D. Reyes, B.S., research assistant*
Israel P. Carlos, B.S., research aide*
Ricardo A. Guino, B.S., research aide
Eloisa-M. Labadan, B.S., research aide*

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J. Bart Duff, M.S., associate agricultural economist*
Fred E. Nichols, B.S., evaluation engineer*
Edwin S. Shepardson, M.S., consultant*
Emilio O. Casem, M.S., assistant agricultural engineer
Philomelo A. Cabanos, B.S., assistant design engineer
Antero S. Manalo, M.S., assistant agricultural engineer
Nestor C. Navasero, B.S., research assistant
Norberto L. Orcino, B.S., research assistant
Abdul I. Amilhussin, B.S., research assistant
Edgardo G. del Rosario, B.S., research assistant
Reynaldo P. Eder, B.S., research assistant
Fernando S. Cabrales, B.S., draftsman
Feliciano C. Jalotjot, draftsman

AGRONOMY

Surajit K. De Datta, Ph.D., agronomist
H. Keith Krupp, Ph.D., associate agronomist
Emmanuel T. Floresca, M.S., assistant agronomist
Servillano N. Balaing, B.S., research assistant
Jesus T. Magbanua, B.S., research assistant
Carmelita P. Magnaye, B.S., research assistant
Pablo M. Zarate, B.S., research assistant
Ernesto L. Aragon, B.S., research assistant
Paul C. Bernasor, B.S., research assistant
Rene Q. Lacsina, B.S., research assistant
Wilma N. Obcemea, B.S., research aide

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Bienvenido O. Juliano, Ph.D., chemist
Gloria B. Cagampang, M.S., assistant chemist
Lyda C. Baun, B.S., research assistant
Bernardita V. Esmama, B.S., research assistant
Benjamin P. Gapud, B.S., research assistant**
Leni P. Lontok, B.S., research assistant**
Ruth U. Monserrate, B.S., research assistant*
Evelyn P. Palmiano, B.S., research assistant

Consuelo M. Perez, M.S., research assistant
Angelina L. Ang, B.S., temporary research aide*

ENTOMOLOGY

Mano D. Pathak, Ph.D., entomologist
V. Arnold Dyck, Ph.D., associate entomologist*
N. Sethunathan, Ph.D., visiting assistant pesticide chemist**
Fausto L. Andres, B.S., research assistant
Gerardo B. Aquino, B.S., research assistant
Tomas D. Cadatal, M.S., research assistant*
Jose I. Calderon, B.S., research assistant
Denis T. Encarnacion, B.S., research assistant
Arlando S. Varca, B.S., research assistant
Carlos R. Vega, B.S., research assistant

EXPERIMENTAL FARM

Federico V. Ramos, M.S., associate agronomist and farm superintendent
Orlando G. Santos, B.S., associate farm superintendent
Juan M. Lapis, B.S., research assistant
Eladio M. Baradas, B.S., research assistant
Filomeno O. Lanting, B.S., research assistant

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Mieko Honda, B.A., indexer (in Japan)*

MULTIPLE CROPPING

Richard Bradfield, Ph.D., agronomist
Gordon R. Banta, M.S., visiting associate agricultural economist*
Anacleto B. Guevarra, M.S., assistant agronomist
Wilhelmino A. T. Herrera, B.S., research assistant

PLANT PATHOLOGY

Shu-Huang Ou, Ph.D., plant pathologist
Keh Chi Ling, Ph.D., plant pathologist

* Arrived during year.

** Left during year.

Masao Goto, Ph.D., visiting scientist**
Fausto L. Nuque, M.S., assistant plant pathologist
Celestino T. Rivera, M.S., assistant virologist
Vladimarte M. Aguiro, B.S., research assistant
Jose M. Bandong, M.S., research assistant
Manolito P. Carbonell, B.S., research assistant
Toribio T. Ebron, Jr., B.S., research assistant
Silvino D. Merca, B.S., research assistant
Marina B. Paris, B.S., research assistant
Sonia P. Ebron, B.S., research aide

PLANT PHYSIOLOGY

Shouichi Yoshida, D.Agr., plant physiologist
Benito S. Vergara, Ph.D., plant physiologist
Kenji Kurashima, B.S., visiting assistant scientist**
Yoshikazu Ohno, Ph.D., visiting scientist*
Aurora M. Mazaredo, B.S., research assistant
Francisco T. Parao, B.S., research assistant
Patria H. Perez, M.S., research assistant
Corazon M. Ramirez, B.S., research assistant
Romeo M. Visperas, B.S., research aide

RICE PRODUCTION TRAINING AND RESEARCH

Vernon E. Ross, M.S., rice production specialist
Inocencio C. Bolo, B.S., assistant rice production specialist*
Florencio Macapugay, B.S., rice production technician
Romario S. Necesario, B.S., rice production technician
Eustacio U. Ramirez, B.S., rice production technician
Andres V. Foronda, B.S., rice production technician
Eduardo E. Perdon, B.S., rice production technician
Arturo N. Pesayco, B.S., rice production technician**
Leonardo T. Almasan, research aide

SOIL CHEMISTRY

F. N. Ponnampuruma, Ph.D., soil chemist
Ruby U. Castro, M.S., assistant chemist
Rhoda S. Lantin, M.S., research assistant
Elsa R. Guevarra, B.S., research assistant
Myrna R. Orticio, B.S., research assistant
Oscar C. Reyes, B.S., research assistant
Juana Ingrid I. Garcia, B.S., research assistant

SOIL MICROBIOLOGY

Tomio Yoshida, Ph.D., soil microbiologist
Rosabel R. Ancajas, M.S., research assistant
Teresita F. Castro, B.S., research assistant
Diana C. del Rosario, B.S., research assistant
Benjamin C. Padre, Jr., research aide

STATISTICS

Kwanchai A. Gomez, Ph.D., associate statistician
Rosalinda A. Graham, B.S.A., research assistant**
Vicente B. Lasmarias, B.S., research assistant**

Emerito V. Tipa, B.S., research aide
Cesario G. Umali, B.S., research aide
Ernesto D. Lantican, B.S., research aide
Antonio L. Oña, B.S., research aide*

VARIETAL IMPROVEMENT

Henry M. Beachell, M.S., plant breeder
Te-Tzu Chang, Ph.D., geneticist
Surdev S. Khush, Ph.D., plant breeder
Chukichi Kaneda, B.S., visiting assistant scientist
Rodolfo C. Aquino, M.S., assistant plant breeder
Lucila P. Aspiras, M.S., assistant cereal chemist**
Esperanza H. Bacalangco, B.S., research assistant
Normita M. de la Cruz, B.S., research assistant
Agapito M. Gonzalvo, Jr., B.S., research assistant
Rizal M. Herrera, B.S., research assistant
Jose C. de Jesus, Jr., B.S., research assistant
Genoveva C. Loresto, B.S., research assistant
Carmen M. Paule, B.S., research assistant
Oscar O. Tagumpay, B.S., research assistant
Alicia A. Capiral, B.S., research aide
Vicente T. Librojo, Jr., B.S., research aide
Eugenio S. Sarreal, B.S., research aide
Espiridion T. Torres, B.S., research aide
Reynaldo L. Villareal, B.S., research aide

STAFF IN INTERNATIONAL PROGRAMS

Wayne H. Freeman, Ph.D., plant breeder, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India
William G. Golden, Jr., M.S., rice specialist, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Ceylon
Hillenius ten Have, D.Sc., agronomist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India
Robert I. Jackson, Ph.D., rice adviser, Ford Foundation, Indonesia*
Harold D. Kaufmann, Ph.D., plant pathologist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India
Paul C. Lippold, Ph.D., assistant rice adviser, Ford Foundation, East Pakistan
John A. Lowe, Ph.D., entomologist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India**
Gordon McLean, Ph.D., rice adviser, Ford Foundation, West Pakistan
Hiroshi Sakai, Ph.D., plant physiologist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, India
Rufus K. Walker, M.S., rice adviser, Ford Foundation, East Pakistan

* Arrived during year.

** Left during year.

Director's Introduction

A major event in 1970 was the joining of the United States Agency for International Development as a major partner in supporting the Institute. Before 1970 the Institute's only regular and substantial financial contributors were its founders, the Ford Foundation and The Rockefeller Foundation. In 1970, however, the Institute received \$750,000 from each of the foundations and also from USAID. The help of the United States Government is welcomed by the Institute not only because of the size of the grant, but also because the USAID did all that it could, within the scope of its policies and regulations, to make the grant free of restrictions.

Field research in 1970 was hampered by several severe typhoons and unusually heavy rainfall during the monsoon season. The unfavorable weather reduced yields substantially through the direct effect of winds, rain, and cloudy skies and also as a result of serious outbreaks of the rice blast disease brought on by the humid environment.

Program highlights

The two new rice varieties, IR20 and IR22, named in late 1969, made their impact felt in 1970.

In early 1970, because of the success of previous trials of IR20 in East Pakistan, the Government of that Province bought 1,800 metric tons of IR20 seed for planting during the monsoon season. Early reports indicate that essentially all of the seed was used and that the yields were substantially higher than those of the traditional local varieties.

In the Philippines, the Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources recommended IR20 for nation-wide planting and it is now gaining acceptance by farmers faster than any other variety.

The Government of India approved the release of IR20 for planting in West Bengal and Eastern Bihar where a tungro-like virus disease is appearing. In Indonesia and South Vietnam, vigorous efforts are now being made to multiply seed of IR20 and to distribute it to farmers.

A broad spectrum of disease and insect resistance, good grain quality, and wide adaptability in the tropics seem to be the principal reasons for the acceptance of IR20 by farmers. Furthermore farmers find that IR20 yields somewhat better at lower levels of soil fertility than do several of the other short-strawed, new varieties.

The future of IR22 is yet to be determined. It has the best grain quality and appearance of any Institute variety and it commands top prices on both the Philippine and international markets. It has a high yield potential and strong resistance to the bacterial blight disease. Hence, it will compete well with many of the new varieties now being used in India, most of which are rather susceptible to bacterial blight. The high yield potential of IR22 is attested to by the results of a contest in the Philippines to select the outstanding farmers for 1970: among the top five winners in the rice category (based on yield per hectare), four grew IR22 and one grew IR8.

Unfortunately IR22 is susceptible to the tungro virus disease and to the vector of the disease. Furthermore, it did not inherit the broad-based resistance of one of its parents, Tadukan, to rice blast. However, its high yielding capacity, its excellent plant type, its resistance to bacterial blight, and its superior grain quality will allow it to serve as an important variety until its successor is created.

A genetic line, now designated as IR661-1-140-3-2, shows promise of being the next variety the Institute names. It was identified as being superior in 1968, but because of need for further purification, particularly with respect to grain quality, its evaluation was delayed. Widespread testing in India and the Philippines shows that the line is consistently high yielding. A superior new selection from the IR661 cross (IR8 x [Century Patna 231 x SLO 17]) will be multiplied in 1971 to provide a substantial amount of pure seed for distribution to government agencies and private seed growers.

This selection has fine, translucent grain with high milling recovery. It is resistant to the green leafhopper and has some resistance to the brown plant-hopper, both vectors of important virus diseases. The amylose content of its grain is lower than that of IR8 and IR5, and thus it will have softer texture when cooked. That should make it quite acceptable to Filipinos and Indonesians who seem to prefer a softer rice than do the Indians and Pakistanis, for example. Yield trials conducted for the past 2 years have proved that it can produce from 4 to 9 metric tons per hectare, depending upon weather and management conditions. In nation-wide yield trials in the Philippines in 1969 and 1970, among the five top yielding varieties were IR20, IR22, and IR661-1-140-3-2. The IR661 selection was also the winner in a trial of some 64 slender-grained selections in India in the wet season of 1969.

The new short, stiff-strawed varieties continue gaining in popularity among farmers. During the months of July, August, and September 1970, 44 percent of the land area planted to rice in the Philippines was occupied by the high yielding varieties. In 1969 the corresponding figure was 34 percent.

Accurate data on area planted to the new rice varieties are difficult to obtain, but estimates indicate that substantial gains in the area of rice land planted to the new high yielding varieties are occurring in many countries, particularly in India, Pakistan, Ceylon, Malaysia, South Vietnam, and Indonesia.

In general, IR5 has proved to be more popular among farmers than IR8, and IR20 is getting acceptance more rapidly than IR22. These facts indicate that farmers prefer varieties with high insect and disease resistance. The Institute's breeding program is now geared to producing varieties in the future that have the good grain quality and yielding potential of IR20 and IR22, for example, but with greatly increased disease and insect resistance.

The agronomy department continued its intensive studies of chemical weed control for both transplanted and direct-seeded flooded rice and for upland rice which, of course, is always direct seeded. As reported last year, 2, 4-D continued to be the least expensive effective herbicide for transplanted lowland rice. During 1970, however, two new chemicals came to the fore as highly selective herbicides that can be used on both transplanted and direct-seeded flooded rice. One of these is benthocarb, which is manufactured in Japan and carries the trade name of "Saturn". The other is a product of Monsanto Chemical Co. designated originally as CP 53619 and now sold under the trade name of "Machete."

Chemical weed control in upland rice is difficult. During the 1970 monsoon season, the most promising chemicals tested were a Japanese product, provided to the Institute under the designation NTN 5006, and Machete. These materials were the most effective when sprayed before the emergence of weeds at the rate of 2 kg/ha of active ingredient, when the rice seedlings were in the one- to two-leaf stage.

The most effective insecticide tested in 1970 proved to be carbofuran (marketed as Furadan). When applied every 3 weeks in granular form at the rate of 1 to 2 kilograms per hectare it provides good protection against rice stem borers, leaf rollers, green leafhoppers, and brown planthoppers. The economics of its use is yet to be determined. However, the compound will be marketed commercially in the Philippines in 1971 and soon its profitability can be assessed on farmers' fields.

As mentioned earlier, the Institute is making a strong effort to incorporate insect resistance into the new varieties. This work is being done jointly by the entomology and varietal improvement departments. Genetic lines from several promising crosses are now in the fourth generation and it is possible that selections can be made from these populations that have resistance to bacterial blight disease, to many races of the rice blast disease, to green leafhoppers and to brown planthoppers. These qualities, coupled with good grain quality and high yielding capacity, will constitute the next major advance in rice technology because they will make it possible for many farmers to grow rice successfully without the use of expensive insecticides and fungicides.

The agricultural engineering department has developed both a six-row and an eight-row seeder which are now being manufactured in the Philippines. These implements are drawn by one man and are designed for direct sowing on the mud surface of the puddled paddy soil. One hectars can be planted in 5 hours, which is about 20 times faster than transplanting. The cost of the machine is equivalent to US\$60. The seed cleaner developed last year has been further improved and will soon be manufactured commercially. Work continues on the design and testing of a rapid rice dryer, a field harvester, and a high volume thresher.

A major contribution of the soil microbiology department is its finding that several of the organochlorine insecticides such as DDT, BHC, and heptachlor, are degraded rather rapidly in flooded paddy soils while they are quite persistent in well-aerated upland soils. This indicates that some of these materials can be safely used by lowland rice farmers even though they may leave harmful residues in upland soils.

Studies by the agricultural economics department indicate that mechanization of rice farms in the Philippines has not displaced labor and in some cases has actually intensified the labor requirement where modern cultural practices and the new varieties have been used.

The Institute's training program continued to receive major emphasis. More than 500 persons from over 25 countries have been trained at the Institute in some field of rice research, in rice production techniques, or in multiple cropping. As we visit graduates of the Institute's training activities in their own countries it becomes evident that they are contributing greatly toward improving the quality of rice research in the developing countries and that those trained in extension methodology are having a real impact in increasing yields on farmers' fields.

Staff changes

Dr. H. Keith Krupp joined the agronomy department early in 1970 as an associate agronomist, serving as a water management specialist.

In June, Dr. V. Arnold Dyck was added to the entomology department as an associate entomologist. He is a specialist in insect ecology.

During the last quarter of 1970, two additions were made to the agricultural engineering department under its contract with the USAID. Mr. J. Barton Duff became an associate agricultural economist and is studying the economic aspects of machinery development, and Mr. Fred E. Nichols joined the staff as an associate evaluation engineer. The duration of these appointments will depend on the continuation of USAID support for the mechanization project.

The Japanese Government is providing the Institute with two scientists who are fully funded by Japan. One is Mr. C. Kaneda, a plant breeder, and the other is Dr. Y. Ohno, a plant physiologist.

The Canadian Government has furnished one scientist to the Institute. He is Mr. Gordon Banta, an agricultural economist, who is studying the economics of multiple cropping. He arrived in September 1970 and he will remain for a year or two, depending upon the progress of his research effort.

Trustees

Dr. Juan C. Salcedo retired from his post as chairman of the National Science Development Board of the Philippines, and thus automatically retired from the Board of Trustees of the Institute. His position as a trustee was filled by his successor on the NSDB, General Florencio Medina.

The 4-year terms of Dr. B. P. Pal and Dr. M. O. Ghani expired on December 31, 1970.

Finances

Cash grants received by the Institute during 1970 amounted to US\$2,444,639.

1. *The Ford Foundation* gave \$1,134,075. Of this amount, \$750,000 was toward the operating and capital expenditure needs of the Institute. The remainder was in support of the rice research and development programs in three countries: East Pakistan — \$166,000 which is part of a 6-year grant of \$996,000; Ceylon — \$153,825 which is part of a 4-year grant of \$552,000; Indonesia — \$64,250 which is part of a 2-year grant of \$257,000.

The Ford Foundation also supported the rice research program in West Pakistan, and contributed substantially toward the development of the East Pakistan Rice Research Institute. The last payments on these grants were released in 1969. The amounts are shown in last year's annual report.

2. *The Rockefeller Foundation* granted the Institute \$817,205 during 1970. Its contribution toward the operating and capital expenditure needs of the Institute amounted to \$750,000, of which \$494,000 was received in cash and the balance of \$256,000 represented the value of its manpower contribution. The Rockefeller Foundation also supported the Institute's accelerated research and training program on cropping systems for tropical areas, under the direction

of Dr. Richard Bradfield. For this purpose a grant of \$182,500 over a 3-year period was made in 1968, of which \$52,205 was released during 1970. Furthermore, The Rockefeller Foundation supported a joint Ph.D. training program between the Institute and the Indian Agricultural Research Institute. For this purpose the sum of \$15,000 was released during the year.

3. From various grants, the *U.S. Agency for International Development* released to the Institute a total of \$667,125 during 1970. In April 1970, a 1-year grant of \$350,000 was made toward the operating and capital expenditure needs of the Institute, and when USAID decided to join the Ford Foundation and The Rockefeller Foundation as an equal partner, an additional grant of \$750,000 was made. At the same time the grant was extended 1 year. By the end of 1970 the Institute had been reimbursed in the amount of \$174,411.

The Institute received a 4-year grant of \$360,000 from USAID in 1966 for a project entitled "Research on Farm and Equipment Power Requirement for Production of Rice and Associated Food Crops in the Far East and South Asia." This project was renewed in 1970 for a 2-year period with a budget of \$404,600. From these two contracts the sum of \$87,962 was paid to the Institute in 1970.

Another contract between the Institute and USAID supports a project for the acceleration of rice research and training programs in India. This contract which took effect on June 13, 1967 has a budget of \$143,116 for 1970 which is in addition to an Indian rupee budget managed by the USAID mission in India. During 1970, \$88,000 was released to the Institute in connection with this contract.

From \$400,000 provided by USAID in 1968 for the expansion of the Institute's training and consultation services relating to rice growing in the Far East, South Asia, Latin America, and African regions, \$279,628 was released to the Institute during 1970.

USAID contributed towards the training program of the Institute by supporting scholars from various countries where USAID has an active program. The sum of \$37,124 was received by the Institute for this purpose in 1970.

4. Three years ago, the Institute entered into a contract with the *National Institutes of Health*, to study the possibility of increasing the protein and essential amino acids of the rice grain through plant breeding. During 1970 \$48,284 was released by NIH to the Institute for this project.

5. The *United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization* awarded its Science Prize for 1970 to the International Rice Research Institute and the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center in Mexico. The Institute received a prize stipend of \$2,000 which was applied toward the Institute's operating costs.

6. *Dow Chemical International* contributed \$1,280 toward the weed control research program of the Institute and \$4,600 toward the post-doctoral training of one IRRI fellow.

7. *Shell International Chemical Co., Ltd.*, provided \$5,000 for partial support of the insecticide program of the Institute.

8. *Union Carbide Asia, Ltd.* gave \$3,000 to assist in the rapid dissemination of the Institute's research findings, particularly in the field of entomology.

9. *CIBA, Ltd.* gave \$2,000 toward the insecticide and herbicide research program of the Institute.

10. The sum of \$2,000 was received from *Eli Lilly and Co.* to support the weed control program of the Institute.

11. *Stauffer Chemical Co.* provided the sum of \$1,000 to partially support the Institute's weed control research program.
12. The sum of \$2,071 was received from the *International Potash Institute*, toward the soil fertility studies of the Institute.
13. *Gulf Research and Development Co.* gave \$1,000 in support of the research on the chemical control of grasses and weeds.

Crop Weather

The weather data collected at IRRI during 1970 were compared with the average of the previous 4 years. Figure 1 shows the rainfall recorded at the Institute farm. The data for solar radiation is recorded at the Institute by a pyrheliometer (fig. 2).

The rainfall in May was lower than the 4-year average for the month, indicating that monsoon started later than usual. During 1970, the total rainfall was 2,244 mm compared with, 1,376 mm during 1969. The 4-year average is 1,703 mm. During 1970 most of the rain fell from September to November which is the ripening period for the wet season crop. In the same months, two tropical storms and two tropical depressions occurred (Table 1). The tropical storms that occurred on October 13 and on November 19 were particularly damaging to the ripening wet season crop. The maximum velocity of the storms recorded at Los Baños was lower than that of the typhoon that occurred on November 3 and 4 in 1967, however.

The high rainfall during the 1970 wet season (July to November) was favorable for upland rice, which depends entirely on rain.

1. Rainfall in millimeters (3-point moving average), for IRRI, Los Baños, Laguna.

2. Solar radiation curve (3-point moving average), for IRRI, Los Baños, Laguna.

Table 1. Maximum velocity of winds recorded at the College Weather Station, Los Baños, Laguna, 1970.

Date	Maximum wind velocity (km/hr)
Sept. 1	26
Sept. 11	32
Oct. 13	88
Nov. 19	96

The solar energy values were lower during the year than 4 years average, primarily because the pyrheliometer was recalibrated at the beginning of the year. Less solar energy was received during late March and most of April than during the same period in 1969. The amount was lower than the 4-year average too. The dry season crop ripens from April to June. The amount of solar energy received in October and November 1970, was also lower than that in the previous 4 years. The low solar energy during this period, in addition to two tropical storms, generally reduced the grain yields of the 1970 wet season crop.

Chemistry

Tests with human subjects showed that high protein milled rices have similar color scores to rices with normal protein content but better nutritional value. High protein and low protein semidwarf lines were screened for use in breeding, genetic, and biochemical studies of grain protein.

The bleeding sap from the culm during grain development tended to have more free amino acids in high protein lines than in low protein lines. Presumably, the high protein lines break down nitrogen in the vegetative tissues and translocate nitrogen to the developing grain faster than low protein lines.

Cooperative testing demonstrated that amylose content is a sensitive and reproducible index of cooking and eating quality of milled rice. Studies on elongation of the rice grain during cooking showed that gelatinization temperature tended to be more important than amylose content in the extreme elongation of the Basmati-type lines tested. In a study of the interactions between amylose content and gelatinization temperature and grain properties, high amylose content in nonwaxy lines was found to be related to large molecular size of amylopectin or small molecular size of amylose, or both.

As starch accumulated in the leaf sheaths and culm, the starch granules increased slightly in size but their gelatinization temperature decreased. Among the enzymes of starch synthesis, only the level of adenosine diphosphate glucose-starch synthetase that is bound to the starch granule paralleled the level of starch. Alpha-amylase is probably the enzyme involved in the degradation of starch in the leaf sheaths and culm during grain development.

Among the hydrolases produced during germination, α -amylase showed the greatest increase in activity. Alpha-amylase activity 4 days after germination is a useful index of varietal differences in rates of germination.

Improving protein content

Breeding for high protein. The goal of a long-range study in cooperation with the plant breeders is raising the protein content of IR8-type rice 2 percentage points above the 8 percent usual for IR8 brown rice (at 12% moisture). By screening for crude protein content, several high protein varieties have been identified in the IRRI world collection of rice varieties. From crosses between IR8 and six high protein varieties, 40 lines have been selected that have a yield potential and a plant type similar to IR8 plus at least 2 percentage points higher protein content than IR8 through several generations.

Replicated yield trials were made in both the dry and wet seasons with these promising lines. In the wet season, however, 23 lines with BPI-76 or BPI-76-1 a photoperiod-insensitive selection, as a parent were also included.

In the dry season crop, yields of the high-protein lines ranged from 2.1 to 8.7 t/ha rough rice (mean: 4.7 t/ha) with protein levels (brown rice) ranging from 10.2 to 14.2 percent (mean: 11.8%). The IR8 control yielded 6.1 t/ha and had 11.4 percent protein. The 25 kg/ha N applied at panicle initiation in addition to the basal application of 120 kg/ha N may account for the high protein level of the IR8 control.

Yields were low in the wet season crop due to severe typhoon damage. The yield of the high protein lines ranged from 1.3 to 3.7 t/ha rough rice (mean: 2.4 t/ha) and the 23 BPI-76 lines ranged from 1.7 to 3.8 t/ha (mean: 2.7 t/ha). IR8 yielded 1.5 t/ha and BPI-76-1, 1.2 t/ha. The protein content of brown rice in the high protein lines ranged from 8.6 to 13.5 percent (mean: 11.0%) and in the BPI-76 lines from 9.2 to 11.3 percent (mean: 10.9%). IR8 had 8.2 percent protein and BPI-76-1 had 11.4 percent. The crop received a basal application of 80 kg/ha N.

The F₆ line that gave the highest yield, 8.7 t/ha, with 11.0 percent protein in the dry season corresponded to the F₇ line that had one of the higher yields, 3.6 t/ha, in the wet season, but the latter's brown-rice protein content was only 8.6 percent. The highest yielding line in the wet season crop (3.7 t/ha) had 11.7 percent protein. This is a selection from the F₆ line

which yielded 4.2 t/ha in the wet season and had 11.3 percent protein. The results of the yield trials have so far been inconclusive: they have not shown whether the lines are already as high yielding as IR8 with at least 2 percentage points higher in protein content.

The panicle/straw ratios of the lines in the 1970 wet season yield trial ranged from 0.7 to 1.6 (mean: 0.9) for the crosses between IR8 and six high-protein cultivars, and 0.7 to 1.3 (mean: 0.9) in the lines with BPI-76 or BPI-76-1 as a parent. IR8 and BPI-76-1 both had panicle: straw ratios of 0.78.

In the pedigree nursery, 1,441 lines were grown in the 1970 dry season. From these lines, 1,685 plants were selected, their brown rice was analyzed for protein, and they were grown in the 1970 wet season. About 525 of these lines were sister lines of the improved lines included in the yield trial. In the wet season, three plants each from 310 lines were selected and analyzed for Kjeldahl protein.

Screening for protein content. Other sources of high protein content continue to be screened. Selections in the varietal improvement department's yield trials are being routinely analyzed for protein content. The selection IR480-5-9-3-3 was verified to have a high protein content and will be included in next year's dry season yield trial.

Four high protein mutants from the Institute of Radiation Breeding, Ohmiya, Japan developed with γ -irradiation were confirmed to have high protein levels (13.4 to 16.2% in brown rice). However, the lysine content of the protein was normal (3.7 to 3.8%) and not 5 percent as claimed. The two mutants with the highest protein content, 14.8 and 16.2 percent, have smaller grains (100-grain weight of rough rice: 1.2 g) than the two lower protein (13.4%) mutants, IRB4 and IRB5 (100-grain weight: 1.9 and 2.0 g).

Low protein, unimproved varieties are unsatisfactory as controls in genetic and biochemical studies with high protein improved varieties. So we screened crosses between Intan and IR8 for low protein. Intan is a traditional variety that has low protein content in farmers' fields, although at the IRRI farm it has the

same protein content (8%) as IR8. Some low protein lines from the crosses between Intan and IR8 may be used as controls in experiments next year.

Sources of variation in protein content. A detailed study of sources of variation in sampling grain for Kjeldahl protein was undertaken on IR8 rough rice grown in the dry season with 0 to 120 kg/ha basal N. A 10-grain sample was optimal for Kjeldahl protein. It showed less variance than a five-grain sample and was comparable to samples with up to 100 grains. Among the sources of variation examined for the unfertilized plots, variation in protein content among panicles from the same hill was high (6.0% of the mean) and was in the same magnitude as that among hills. The variation in protein content from branch to branch within each panicle was 3 percent. In the plots fertilized with 120 kg/ha N, the variation among panicles within a hill was considerably larger than that among hills. The results indicate that for protein analysis the sample should be taken from the total threshed grain harvested from the hill, since there is no representative panicle. We have been using this sampling technique in our protein screening.

Screening for high lysine rices. Five of the better yielding, high protein lines included in the 1970 dry season trial were analyzed for amino acid composition. The milled rice samples had 11.4 to 11.8% protein and 3.3 to 4.0% lysine, 3.4 to 4.1% threonine, 0.9 to 1.2% tryptophan, and 3.0 to 4.6% sulfur amino acids in the protein. The three lines with Chow-sung as the high protein parent (IR1103) and the line with Crythroceros Korn as parent (IR1104) had higher levels of these amino acids in their protein than the line with Omirt 39 as parent (IR1101).

Because of these genetic differences in amino acid composition at similar protein levels, brown rice of varieties in IRRI's world collection is being screened for lysine based on dye-binding capacity (DBC), using an AutoAnalyzer for diluting the supernatant dye solution and recording its color. The brown rice is ground in a Wig-L-Bug amalgamator and large particles are removed by sieving. Then the ground rice is

shaken with Orange G dye solution. Studies in 1969 showed that DBC values correlated with the lysine content of rice protein. From the linear regression equation of DBC (absorbance) as a function of protein content, entries are being selected that have higher DBC than the mean value from the regression equation at their protein levels. The lysine content of the selected entries (less than 1% of 3,000 entries so far analyzed) will be rechecked by direct chemical methods.

Protein content of farm-grown rice. Protein content of brown rice from farmers' fields in Laguna, Philippines was again analyzed from samples obtained by the statistics department. In the 1970 dry season, the brown-rice protein at 12% moisture was IR8, 5.8 to 10.7% (mean: 8.0%); Intan, 5.8 to 7.8% (mean: 6.8%); IR20, 7.4 to 10% (mean: 8.9%); and C4-63, 8.3 to 9.6% (mean: 8.9%).

In the 1970 wet season crop, the brown rice protein content was: IR8, 5.7 to 9.8% (mean: 7.5%); IR5, 6.2 to 9.0% (mean: 7.4%); IR20, 7.2 to 8.9% (mean: 8.1%); IR22, 7.0 to 8.2% (mean: 7.5%); C4-63, 7.3 to 9.9% (mean: 8.5%); Malagkit Sungsong, 7.7 to 9.2% (mean: 8.5%). All were improved varieties except Malagkit Sungsong. These data represent 36 farms in nine towns, 19 of which were grown to IR8. The mean of 7.5 percent for IR8 brown rice protein represents the lowest level found in five seasons of analyzing rice from farmers' fields in Laguna. The mean values for the previous four seasons was 8.0 percent.

Protein content and eating quality. Milled rice that has more than 3 percentage points higher protein content than normal may have a darker tan color in both raw and cooked forms than a sample of the same variety with normal protein content. So a taste panel at the home technology department, University of the Philippines College of Agriculture was asked to assess the eating quality of milled rice of F₇ lines differing in protein content using paired lines with similar amylose contents.

The taste panel gave similar scores for color to the low protein and high protein lines, despite differences in protein content of 4 percent

Table 1. Taste panel scores for color of lines and varieties differing in protein content.

Selection or variety	Protein ^a (%)	Amylose ^b (%)	Mean color score ^c
IR1100-185-7-4	9.1	26.2	2.2
IR1100-89-2-6	11.1	23.1	2.2
IR1103-64-4-1	8.8	27.1	1.5
IR1103-15-8-5	11.6	25.2	2.2
IR1103-15-9-8	12.9	25.0	1.8
IR8	9.9	26.0	1.5
BPI-76-1	10.0	26.2	2.8
LSD (5%)			1.3

^aAt 12% moisture. ^bDry basis. ^cBy a panel of six judges. Numerical scores from 1 to 9 were assigned: "1" represents white; "3," cream; a score of "9," brown.

(Table 1). Correlation coefficients between protein content and taste panel scores for all samples were also not significant. The significant differences in color between IR8 and BPI-76-1 samples with similar protein and amylose content confirm our earlier observation that BPI-76 rice has a darker color than other rices. This experiment indicates that an increase in protein content of 2 percentage points has a negligible effect on the color of cooked milled rice.

Protein content and nutritional value. Previous cooperative studies with Dr. R. Bressani at the Instituto de Nutricion de Centro America y Panama in Guatemala showed that three rice samples differing in protein content gave linear growth-response curves in weanling rats fed diets with 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 percent protein. Lower growth responses, however, were obtained with higher protein levels. Verification of the non-linear response to diets that have over 5 percent protein was made using BPI-76-1 with 14.3 percent protein. Both casein and BPI-76-1 showed lower growth slopes in rat diets containing more than 10 percent protein.

Because of the high protein efficiency ratio (weight gain per unit weight of dietary protein intake) of the rice samples relative to casein at the low dietary protein levels (Table 2), rat carcasses were analyzed for nitrogen and fat content after a 28-day feeding period. We found that carcasses of rats fed milled rice had less nitrogen (protein) and more fat content than carcasses of rats fed casein. Hence, protein

quality indexes based on weight gain, such as protein efficiency ratio, net protein ratio (protein efficiency ratio corrected for loss of weight with a 0% protein diet), and nitrogen growth index (slope of regression lines of weight gain as a function of dietary protein intake) over-estimated the quality of milled rice protein because they are based on the assumption that the rat body has the same composition in the various diets.

The nitrogen balance index (slope of regression line of carcass nitrogen as a function of dietary protein intake) showed that the protein quality of milled rice is lower than that of casein. Using only the data showing weight gain, nitrogen growth indexes for milled rice were lower than that of casein. Based on a relative quality value of 75 for casein, the protein values for milled rice in the diets with 5 percent protein or less were similar to biological values of 70 to 75 percent for milled-rice protein whereas protein values for the high-rice diets were similar to the relative nutritional values, 44 to 50 percent of lactalbumin, reported for milled-rice protein by Hegsted.

All the protein quality indexes (Table 2) showed a less-than-proportional decrease in protein quality with an increase in protein content of milled rice. In reality, humans will consume equal amounts of rice regardless of protein content. Hence, the protein efficiency ratios of 1.84 to 2.04 for the four milled rice samples for high-rice diets reflect the greater dependence of the nutritional value of milled rice on its protein content.

The apparent utilizable protein of the four milled rice samples (protein content multiplied by relative nutritional value) is 2.7% for Intan; 3.2% for IR8 (7.3% protein); 4.2% for IR8 (9.7 protein); and 6.0% for BPI-76-1. The corresponding net protein value (net protein ratio multiplied by 16.8 multiplied by protein content) is Intan, 2.3%; IR8 (7.3% protein), 4.1%; IR8 (9.7% protein), 5.0%; and BPI-76-1, 6.2%. These two indexes again show that the nutritional value of milled rice increases with its protein content.

A sample of the milled rice of BPI-76-1 (14.5% protein) was also compared in human subjects with a 7.9 percent protein Bluebonnet

Table 2. Protein quality indexes for four milled rice samples and casein.

Protein source	Diets with 0 to 5% protein						High rice diets ^a			
	Protein content (%)	PER ^b of 5% protein diet	Net protein ratio	Nitrogen growth index	Relative quality ^c	Nitrogen balance index	Relative quality ^c	PER ^b of 90% rice diet	Nitrogen growth index	Relative quality ^c
Intan	5.68	2.56	3.71	3.49	80	0.49	69	2.04	2.37	47
IR8	7.32	2.20	3.36	3.25	75	0.47	67	2.02	2.30	46
IR8	9.73	1.94	3.07	3.04	71	0.36	51	2.02	2.17	43
BPI-76-1 ^d	14.3	1.50	2.57	2.47	57	n.d.	n.d.	1.84	2.12	42
Casein	—	2.20	3.36	3.23	75	0.53	75	—	3.78	75

^aDiets giving a net weight increase. ^bProtein efficiency ratio. ^cBased on a value of 75 for casein. ^dCorrected for differences in casein values from the two experiments.

rice by Dr. Helen Clark at Purdue University (U.S.A.). When equal weights of milled rice of each variety were fed to seven adults for a week, BPI-76-1 rice, which contained 1.8 times as much protein, caused a highly significant improvement in nitrogen retention. The mean nitrogen balance was +1.41 g/day N for BPI-76-1 rice, +0.24 g/day for Bluebonnet rice, and +0.48 g/day for Bluebonnet rice plus enough nonspecific nitrogen to give it the same nitrogen content as BPI-76-1 rice. Addition of supplementary nitrogen to Bluebonnet rice did not influence retention significantly. The subjects retained more nitrogen from the BPI-76-1 rice because it had the higher level of all essential amino acids per unit weight of rice as shown by amino-acid analyses. These results verify that the high protein rice is nutritionally superior to rices with normal protein content.

Protein metabolism

Previous studies on the biochemistry of protein accumulation in the developing rice grain showed that lines that had a high protein content in the mature grain incorporated amino acids faster than lines low in protein, and had more free amino nitrogen and ribonucleic acid. Physiologists believe that the nitrogen of the grain is derived mainly from the breakdown and translocation of nitrogen already present in the rice plant at flowering.

Free amino acids of culm sap. From crosses between IR8 and high protein varieties, seven pairs of F₅ plant lines differing in protein

content were grown in pots. Ten days after flowering the culm was cut off at the internode closest to the panicle. Bleeding sap was collected overnight for 12 hours and the content and composition of free amino acids in the sap was analyzed. The concentration of total free amino acids in the sap and in the developing grain of the high protein lines tended to be higher than the concentration in the sap and grain of the low protein lines. The mean soluble amino nitrogen content of the sap was 11.7 μg/g in the low protein lines and 15.0 μg/g in the high protein lines. The 10-day grain of low protein lines had 6.25 μg mean soluble amino nitrogen and 0.94 mg mean protein content while that of the high protein lines had 8.67 μg soluble amino nitrogen and 1.25 mg protein.

The composition of free amino acids in the sap and the grain also was different, indicating that more than one amino acid pool was present in the developing grain. Histidine was the principal amino acid in the sap. The sap had higher levels of asparagine than glutamine, possibly because we collected the sap at night at which time plants produce asparagine from the breakdown of proteins.

Nitrogen translocation during ripening. Since high protein rices translocate more amino nitrogen to the developing grain, a study of the source of this nitrogen with five varieties and lines that differ in protein content was begun. Plants were collected at flowering and 21 days later. The levels of amino and nitrate nitrogen, protein, and protease in the leaf blades and Kjeldahl nitrogen in the leaf sheaths and culm were analyzed. Protease in the leaf blade had an

optimum pH of about 7 with hemoglobin as substrate. The protease activity of the leaf blades decreased during grain development. The leaf blades contained only traces of nitrate nitrogen. Although the nitrogen levels in the vegetative tissues were similar in the five samples in the 1970 wet season crop, the total protease activity of leaf blades per tiller tended to be higher in the high protein line, IR480-5-9-3-3, than in the others, both at flowering and 21 days later.

Free amino acids of the sap and cells of the upper three leaf blades were analyzed in IR8 plants 10 days after flowering. The sap was extracted with water after vacuum infiltration of shredded leaf blades. The cell extract was obtained by ultrafiltration of a homogenate of the washed leaf blades. Our preliminary results showed that the two extracts had similar levels of free amino acids per gram of fresh leaves. The extracellular sap, however, contained higher levels of arginine, γ -aminobutyric acid, taurine, and ammonia than the leaf cells, but lower levels of histidine, hydroxyproline, leucine, and tryptophan.

Nitrogen content of seedlings. The nitrogen content of rice seedlings (leaves and culm) was determined at transplanting (21 days after seeding), at maximum tillering, at flowering, and at 21 days after flowering in four sister pairs of F_6 plant lines (from crosses between IR8 and high protein varieties) differing in grain protein content. The nitrogen content of the seedlings at transplanting was lower in all the high protein lines when expressed as percent nitrogen per plant, but it was lower in only three of the four pairs when expressed as milligrams of nitrogen per plant. The nitrogen content of these organs became similar for each pair as the plants matured, however. Why the seedlings from high protein seeds had less nitrogen is an interesting biochemical problem. However, when we made a preliminary attempt to duplicate this trend with IR8 seeds that had a protein content between 8 and 11 percent, all the seedlings showed about the same nitrogen content.

A study on rice prolamins indicated that a pure preparation may be obtained by extracting milled rice with 70 percent ethanol and then

precipitating the extract with acetone. A critical concentration seemed to exist below which the prolamins do not precipitate, however. The prolamins prepared had the same amino acid composition as the prolamins prepared by ethanol extraction after the removal of albumin and globulin with salt solution.

Grain quality

Test for cooking quality. A survey made in 1969 of 31 rice scientists and technologists showed that tests for cooking and eating quality of rice need to be standardized.

Since tests which involve actual cooking are difficult to standardize, amylose assay was considered for cooperative testing in different rice laboratories. Potato amylose standard and head rice of four IRRI lines differing in amylose content were sent to cooperating laboratories and analyzed for amylose level by a simplified method developed by IRRI. The method is based on the colorimetric amylose-iodine assay of Williams and co-workers. It consists of gelatinizing the starch for 5 minutes at 100 C and acidifying the rice to below pH 6. Normally, amylose analysis involves defatting the rice with methanol before gelatinizing the starch for 2 days at 4 C and lowering the pH to 10. The laboratories titrated with sufficient hydrochloric acid to neutralize the alkali used for dissolving the starch. But subsequent trials showed that adding a fixed amount of acetic acid (about 100% excess) gave solutions of about pH 4.5 due to the buffering action of acetate. The samples were also subjected to the cooking quality tests usually done at each laboratory.

The amylose data from the standard and the simplified methods were essentially the same for samples that had above 25 percent amylose (dry basis). Nonwaxy rices with low amylose content gave higher values (up to 4% more) by the simplified method because of the higher absorbance of the amylopectin-iodine complex at low pH values. A waxy sample showing 1.4 percent amylose by the standard method gave 7.7 percent amylose by the simplified method. The standard method at pH 10 gave a deep blue color for the starch-iodine complex; the

simplified method gave a greenish tinge. The wavelength of maximum absorption of the starch-iodine complex tended to increase as amylose content increased. The maximum occurred at lower wavelengths in the simplified method. The difference in amylose value may be reduced by using 650 $m\mu$ instead of 590 $m\mu$, although lower values are obtained. Since blue values are determined at 680 $m\mu$, which corresponds essentially to amylose content, amylose contents of rice starch determined from absorbance at 590 $m\mu$ are certainly higher than those obtained at 650 or 680 $m\mu$ because of the greater interference from the amylopectin-iodine complex at 590 $m\mu$. The potato amylose standard used in the assay had maximum absorption at about 650 $m\mu$.

A sample size of 10 grains gave about the same standard error for amylose content as a sample of 2 g. Similar results had previously been obtained for Kjeldahl protein analysis of the rice grain. So the Wig-L-Bug amalgamator which readily grinds 10 grains into a 100-mesh flour in 40 seconds may be used for preparing rice samples for both amylose and Kjeldahl assay. Such grinding also makes the starch granules amorphous as shown, when viewed under polarized light, by the loss of birefringence by most of the granules.

Partial results from the cooperative tests from 11 laboratories in 10 institutions showed consistent differences between the low and high amylose samples, except for the very high value of 28 percent reported in one laboratory for IR661-1-140-3. The amylose values calculated by the rice quality laboratory and the chemistry department of IRRI were different by 1 percentage point despite the use of the same flours and similar colorimeters and conversion factors. The amylose values found by the 11 laboratories were IR661-1-140-3, 12.1 to 19.3% (28% excluded); IR140-136, 12.9 to 21.0%; IR788-21-6-2, 21.1 to 30.3%; and IR579-160-2, 23.3 to 31.5%. The differences in amylose values from one laboratory to another were due not only to differences in analytical techniques and equipment, but probably also to the various mills used for converting the head rice to 40-mesh flour. The degree of fineness of the rice flour affected the rate of gelatinization of milled rice.

In addition, the amylose standard that was dissolved at 100 C for 5 minutes had a higher absorbance reading than amylose dissolved at room temperature for 3 hours.

The cooperative cooking quality tests also verified that amylose content was the most reliable and sensitive index of eating quality. The ranking of the four rice samples based on volume expansion or water absorption during cooking was not consistent. Amylose content correlated with texture scores and doneness scores of the cooked rice and with the swelling numbers of Pelshenke and Hampel.

A tentative procedure was developed for adapting the simplified method of amylose analysis to an AutoAnalyzer module. Ten milligrams of milled rice were manually dispersed at 100 C in a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. The AutoAnalyzer mixed the starch solution with the iodine-and-acetic-acid reagent and recorded the color of the starch-iodine complex. A major problem in this automated procedure was that the starch was incompletely dispersed at first. We solved the problem by storing the starch solution at room temperature for 3 hours or overnight at 4 C. The starch-iodine color became progressively darker during the first 3 hours after the starch gelatinized. This trend was not observed with the manual method probably because it involved two shaking steps instead of only one.

Limited trials with other reagents for gelatinizing the starch showed that anhydrous and 90 percent (aqueous) dimethyl sulfoxide did not disperse the starch efficiently at room temperature. At 100 C, the starch particles clumped in these solvents. Sodium hydroxide at a concentration of 5 N can gelatinize rice starch (including starch with high gelatinization temperature) at room temperature in 1 to 2 hours.

Amylose content and starch properties. In a continued investigation of the effect of differences in amylose content and gelatinization temperature on starch properties, starches of four pairs of nonwaxy lines differing in amylose content were studied. These pairs were used previously in the biochemical and eating-quality studies. X-ray diffractograms of the starch granules showed that the members of each

pair had similar degrees of crystallinity. All except one sample were easily fractionated. In all four pairs, the molecular size of the amylose of the high amylose sample (as indexed by intrinsic viscosity) was smaller than that of the low amylose sample (Table 3). In two of the pairs, the molecular size of the amylopectin of the high amylose sample was larger than that of the low amylose sample. Thus at the same gelatinization temperature, an increase in amylose content of the rice starch granule corresponded to a larger amylopectin molecular size or a smaller amylose molecular size, or both. Our previous studies on lines of similar amylose content showed that starch with high gelatinization temperature has a small amylopectin molecular size, a large amylose molecular size, or both. Hence differences in amylose content and gelatinization temperature have opposite effects on the molecular size of the starch fractions.

The starch from these four pairs from the same crosses which were grown together did not show the same relationships as starch from different varieties grown in different seasons and locations. Variety and environment affect the molecular size of the starch fractions. Also differences in ambient temperature during ripening may change the molecular size of the starch fractions of samples of one variety, since a higher ambient temperature decreases amylose content but increases the gelatinization temperature of the starch. These changes in starch properties may increase the molecular size of amylose and decrease the molecular size of amylopectin. A low ambient temperature during ripening has the opposite effect on the molecular size of these fractions of starch.

Acid-corrosion and water-absorption values of the starch granules of the four pairs of nonwaxy lines were also taken. The 4-day lintnerization losses of the four pairs were not correlated with amylose differences within each pair (Table 3). The pair with the highest final gelatinization temperature (Century Patna 231-SLO x Sukanandi) had lower lintnerization losses than the other three pairs. These results confirm the inverse relationship we have observed between lintnerization loss and gelatinization

temperature. The water-absorption curves of the high amylose samples showed lower values at the higher temperature (90 to 95 C), although the percentage of solubles was about the same within each pair.

To verify these interactions between amylose content, gelatinization temperature, and other properties of the rice grain and starch, nonwaxy lines from IR841 (IR262-43-11 x Khao Dawk Mali 4-2-105) were selected showing all the possible combinations of amylose content and gelatinization temperature except a combination of high amylose content and high gelatinization temperature. Two crops of these selected lines are being studied. In the 1970 wet season crop, the molecular size of amylopectin was higher in the lines that had a final gelatinization temperature of 74 C or higher than in those with lower gelatinization temperatures, regardless of amylose content.

Grain properties and elongation during cooking.

Little is known about the extreme elongation that occurs during cooking of such rices as Basmati 370 of India and Pakistan, D25-4 from Burma, and some Iranian cultivars. In a preliminary study the grain elongation during cooking of lines from crosses between Basmati 370 and Taichung Native 1 or IR8 from the 1969 wet season and the 1970 dry season crops and other selected samples was examined.

Soaking the rice in cold water for 30 minutes gave the greatest elongation when the samples were cooked. Longer presoaking periods resulted in less elongation upon cooking because the rice curled and split.

Unfortunately, the lines from crosses between Basmati 370 and Taichung Native 1 or IR8 gave a narrow range in elongation ratios (length of cooked grain compared with length of raw grain), 1.63 to 2.09. One reason was the similar elongation ratios of the parents: 2.19 for Basmati 370, 2.03 for Taichung Native 1, and 1.81 for IR8. Because of the narrow range of elongation ratios for the Basmati 370 lines, elongation ratio did not correlate with such properties as volume expansion and water absorption during cooking, number of cracks formed during presoaking at 30 C, density of milled rice at 30 C, size of starch

granules, or alkali spreading and clearing values.

A screening was made of the properties of Pakistani and Iranian varieties and the Burmese variety D25-4 which has an elongation ratio of 2.91. D25-4 had the lowest density, 1.431, probably because of its large white core. The other varieties ranged in density from 1.441 to 1.455. Basmati 370 has a density of 1.441; IR8, 1.445; and Taichung Native 1, 1.444. The rice flours gave higher densities (1.448 to 1.464) especially in the samples with white belly and white core, which results from loosely packed cell contents.

The mean granule size of 15 samples ranged from 4.0 to 5.9 μ . Basmati 370 had the smallest granule size; another Pakistani variety, Palman (elongation ratio of 1.39), had the largest granules. The mean starch granule size of seven Basmati 370 crosses ranged from 4.1 to 5.6 μ ; IR8 starch granules were 5.4 μ ; and Taichung Native 1 starch granules were 5.2 μ . D25-4 starch had a mean granule size of 4.9 μ . Both Basmati 370 and D25-4 did not have any granules with diameters over 8.0 μ .

Thus the elongation ratios of high amylose varieties with low gelatinization temperatures, such as IR8 and Taichung Native 1, may approach that of Basmati 370. By contrast a variety with low amylose and high gelatinization temperature, Century Patna 231, gave an elongation ratio of only 1.60. Since short-grain samples from Iran (*japonica*) that have low amylose and low gelatinization temperature also gave high ratios (2.1 to 2.3), while Palman (high amylose and intermediate to high gelatinization

temperature) had the lowest ratio, 1.39, physical properties of the raw starch and the grain, such as gelatinization temperature, are probably more important in determining elongation ratios than chemical factors, such as amylose content.

Further work on this problem should involve lines from crosses between varieties differing widely in elongation ratio.

Starch metabolism in leaf sheaths

High yielding, improved varieties, such as IR8, accumulate starch in the leaf sheaths and culm even with high levels of nitrogen fertilization. This storage starch contributes to the carbohydrate content of the rice grain. The leaf blades contain little storage starch. Changes in the enzymes involved in starch metabolism and in the content and properties of starch were studied in the 1970 dry season crop of IR8 grown by the agronomy department with a basal application of only 30 kg/ha P_2O_5 at transplanting.

Levels of starch plus dextrin increased in the leaf sheaths plus culm from 6 to 10 weeks after transplanting, with the highest level (10% of dry weight) occurring 10 and 11 weeks after transplanting. After the booting stage (11 weeks after transplanting) and through flowering and grain development, starch was depleted rapidly and, presumably, translocated to the developing grain. Free sugar content was highest, 20 percent, 8 weeks after transplanting and was generally higher than starch content except at about booting stage when they were about the same.

Table 3. Physiochemical properties of rice starch from low amylose and high amylose lines from different crosses.

Cross	Amylose content (%)	Final gelatinization temperature (C)	Intrinsic viscosity ^a (ml/g)		4-day lintnerization loss ^b (%)
			Amylopectin	Amylose	
Chianung 242/2 x Peta	18.9	62	180	242	55
	34.4	62	193	145	58
CP231-SLO x Sukanandi	18.4	70	172	237	42
	31.4	70	173	190	45
IR8 x FF36	15.7	60	184	219	60
	30.4	60	194	94	53
IR8 x (Yukara x Taichung Native 1)	16.1	63	178	200	55
	29.8	62 ^c	221	99	54

^aSolvent: 0.15N potassium hydroxide at 30 C. LSD (5%, amylopectin) = 12.4 ml/g; LSD (5%, amylose) 8.4 ml/g. ^bLSD (5%) = 1.2%.

^cDifficult to gelatinize in dimethyl sulfoxide.

As starch accumulated, the starch granules of leaf sheaths increased slightly in mean size from 5.9 to 8.1 μ , but their gelatinization temperature decreased from a range of 71 to 79 C to a range of 67 to 74.5 C. The amylose content, as indexed by blue value at 680 m μ , remained at 30 to 32 percent and the molecular size of the starch fractions in the culm and leaf sheaths was nearly the same. The sedimentation constant was 3.1 Svedbergs for leaf-sheath amylose, 2.8 Svedbergs for culm amylose, 116 Svedbergs for leaf-sheath amylopectin, and 118 Svedbergs for culm amylopectin. Starch fractions from 10-day developing grain had sedimentation constants of 2.0 Svedbergs for amylose and 111 Svedbergs for amylopectin. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the starch from the culm and leaf sheaths was A-type which is characteristic of endosperm starches of cereals. The culm starch had a smaller mean size (7.6 μ) and a higher gelatinization temperature (70.5 to 78 C) than the leaf sheath starch.

Starches from the leaf sheaths and culm of two waxy selections were verified to have the same amylose content (30%) as the starch of IR8 which is nonwaxy. Presumably starch in the leaf sheaths and culm of rice has a constant amylose content of about 30 percent regardless of the amylose content of the grain endosperm.

Changes in the level of soluble protein paralleled changes in starch level in the IR8 leaf sheaths. Among the enzymes of starch synthesis, only the level of adenosine diphosphate glucose-starch synthetase that is bound to the starch granule paralleled the level of starch in the leaf sheaths and in the culm. Adenosine diphosphate glucose but not uridine diphosphate glucose was utilized as a glucosyl donor by this starch synthetase. The starch granules prepared by the standard acetone washing method had 10 to 20 percent protein. Removing this surface protein with an alkaline solution of sodium lauryl sulfate resulted in starch granules with only 35 percent of the synthetase activity of the starting granules. Presumably lessened activity may be due to the denaturing action of the solvent on the bound enzyme or the removal of surface-adsorbed soluble enzyme.

Synthetase activity during the period of starch accumulation ranged from 0.07 to 0.13

$\mu\text{mole glucose mmole}^{-1} \text{ starch min}^{-1}$ in leaf sheaths and culm. By contrast, the corresponding activity in the developing rice grain was 0.17 to 0.20 $\mu\text{mole glucose mmole}^{-1} \text{ starch min}^{-1}$. The higher activity of starch synthetase in the grain starch may be attributed to the higher amylose content (35%) in the endosperm starch and the smaller size (6 μ) and greater surface area of endosperm starch. We previously found that synthetase activity is directly correlated to amylose content. If surface-adsorbed soluble synthetase contributes greatly to the observed activity of the starch granule, the greater surface area of endosperm starch explain why it has higher activity than culm and leaf-sheath starches. The nature of affinity between starch synthetases and their substrate needs further elucidation.

Phosphorylase and Q-enzyme (branching enzyme) also increased during starch accumulation, but the increases did not parallel increases in starch level as closely as those of synthetase bound to the starch granule. Only during starch accumulation were the levels of soluble starch synthetase high enough to be measured. The use of dithiothreitol in place of glutathione did not improve the low activity of soluble synthetase. R-enzyme showed no trend, but β -amylase dropped in activity about 11 weeks after transplanting. No maltase activity was detected in the leaf sheaths and culm. The activity of α -amylase increased more sharply, during starch depletion, in the culm than in the leaf sheaths. Presumably α -amylase is the enzyme involved in starch degradation in these tissues. Phosphorylase, Q-enzyme, and starch synthetases decreased in activity during starch depletion.

The zymogram of the leaf sheaths and culm showed only five bands: one α -amylase band, one β -amylase band, two phosphorylase bands, and one Q-enzyme band.

Biochemical changes in the seed during germination

Germination consists of a series of biochemical events that allow the rice embryo to establish itself in its environment using the nutrient

reserves of the endosperm. Knowledge of the time sequence of metabolic events of release of metabolites, enzymes, and substrates may be of value in studying grain dormancy and seedling vigor.

Varner and co-workers have shown that in germinating barley seeds, gibberellic acid from the embryo triggers the synthesis of hydrolases, such as α -amylase, protease, and ribonuclease, in the aleurone layer. These hydrolases are required to degrade the nutrient reserves of the endosperm into the soluble forms needed by the growing plant.

A study of the changes during the first week of germination was started using the variety IR8. Changes in the levels of substrates and enzymes of the endosperm were generally more rapid in the dark than in the light in seeds germinated on moist filter paper at 30 C. Because of the similarity of results under the two conditions, only the data obtained in diffuse light is discussed here.

Starch content decreased progressively but started to decrease more rapidly 6 days after germination accompanied by an increase in the content of free sugars. The activities of R-enzyme, α -amylase, and β -amylase were initially low but started to increase within 3 to 4 days. Phosphorylase activity was initially high but dropped during starch degradation. Other workers have shown that α -amylase is the major enzyme of starch degradation in the endosperm of germinating rice. Polyacrylamide-gel electrophoresis confirmed the appearance of a new, fast migrating α -amylase band 4 days after germination. The activity of α -D-glucosidase decreased during germination; β -D-glucosidase showed maximum activity within 5 to 6 days.

The level of endosperm protein started to decrease rapidly 3 to 4 days after germination, accompanied by an increase in free amino nitrogen. Similarly protease activity increased progressively and reached a maximum within 4 to 5 days of germination. Electrophoresis of extracts of IR8 grain in 14 percent starch gel containing 0.3 percent hemoglobin in 0.03M aluminum lactate buffer (pH 3.4) showed the presence of three protease bands in the developing grain (fig. 1). The mature grain retained only one protease band, which was of slightly slower

1. Zymogram of proteases of the rice grain in 14 percent starch gel containing 0.3 percent hemoglobin in 0.03 M aluminum lactate buffer (pH 3.4). Stain: Amido Black 10B.

mobility than the slowest protease of the ripening grain. During germination, the width and intensity of this protease band increased, but its mean mobility was similar to that of the ungerminated grain. Similar results were obtained using 8 percent polyacrylamide instead of starch. The protease of ripening grain had an optimum pH of 6.0 with bovine serum albumin as substrate in contrast to the protease of germinating grain, which has an optimum pH of 3.5. We later found that hemoglobin was a better substrate for the protease of germinating grain than casein, which in turn was better than serum albumin.

Other enzymes so far analyzed include phosphatases, esterase, and peroxidase. Monophosphatase and diphosphatase activities increased within 4 to 5 days of germination. Esterase only increased slightly in activity 5 days after germination; peroxidase activity showed an increase 4 days after germination.

The rate of synthesis of hydrolytic enzymes may differ between varieties. IRR1 physiologists have compared the level of gibberellic acid in tall and short plants of the same variety. They found that short Century Patna, created by irradiation, had about the same content as tall Century Patna, but a short, early Peta line (Peta/3 x Taichung Native 1) had a lower level than its tall counterpart. Our preliminary data on activity of α -amylase taken 4 days after germination show that tall and short Century

Patna have similar activity, while activity in the short Peta line is about one-fourth that in its tall counterpart. Although the extent of α -amylase synthesis in the 4-day samples was consistent with the reported gibberellic acid levels in these lines, IR8, which is also a dwarf variety, had higher α -amylase activity than any of the four samples. The dwarf character of IR8 (Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen) was obtained from Dee-geo-woo-gen, a dwarf Taiwanese variety similar to Taichung Native 1.

Biochemistry of insect resistance

Because of the importance of pest and disease resistance in the rice plant, a study was begun in cooperation with Dr. S. Rodolfo of the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture on the

content of polyphenols of rice plants in relation to resistance to leafhoppers. Our first efforts are aimed at developing a way to extract and analyze polyphenols and their glycosides as they occur in rice plants.

In another experiment, bleeding sap obtained by cutting the leaf blades of 1-month-old seedlings of selected varieties ranged from pH 6.4 to 6.6. Sap of the susceptible variety Taichung Native 1 had the highest level of free amino nitrogen, 140 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Other sap samples ranged from 47 to 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Amino acid analysis of the sap showed that the Taichung Native 1 samples had the highest asparagine level, 74 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. IR8 had 57 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; Mudgo, 42 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$; and Pankhari 203, 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. Total carbohydrate content ranged from 0.24 to 0.44 mg/ml of sap, and soluble protein (Lowry) from 84 to 149 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

Plant Physiology

Measurement of the respiration of a canopy provided a physiological explanation for the presence of a critical leaf area index in improved rice varieties. Assimilation of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ before flowering under field conditions gave direct evidence that the accumulated carbohydrate is actually translocated into grains during the ripening period. Growth analysis of early maturing varieties indicated that insufficient leaf area index is a major limiting factor for grain yield of early maturing varieties at a conventional spacing. This can be overcome by use of vigorous varieties and close spacings. Zinc concentration, bicarbonate, organic acids, and pH were shown to affect zinc absorption and hence zinc deficiency of rice in flooded soils. High tillering, vigorous varieties perform better than low tillering, less vigorous ones in zinc deficient soils because the former recover from zinc deficiency at later stages of growth faster than the latter.

A reexamination of the photoperiod sensitivity of IRRI varieties showed that IR8 is the most insensitive.

Detailed studies were made on the temperature response of IR8 to better understand its performance in different rice growing areas.

Respiration of a rice canopy

Last year we reported that IR8, an improved, short, erect-leaved variety, has no optimum leaf area index (LAI) but it has a critical LAI.

Existence of optimum LAI in a rice canopy has been explained by the curvilinear increase in total photosynthesis and the linear increase in respiration with increasing LAI. There is little doubt that the photosynthesis of a rice canopy increases hyperbolically with increasing LAI. The plateau-type response of IR8 in relations between LAI and crop growth rate suggests that the respiratory rate is not a linear function of LAI.

We measured the respiratory rate of IR5 in the wet season at booting stage. Individual leaves were detached and their respiratory rate determined with an infrared gas analyzer using an open system. The respiratory rate of the detached leaf sheath plus culm was also measured.

The leaf area index values ranged from 3.1 to 7.2. The greater part of the LAI value was almost equally distributed between leaves 2, 3, and 4 (counting from the top downwards). Leaf 5 contributed less than 8 percent of total leaf area and leaf 1 about 12 percent.

Although the respiratory rate at individual leaf positions was quite variable, respiratory rate per unit leaf area tended to decrease as LAI increased at all leaf positions. The mean

1. The relationship between respiration (R) and leaf area index (L) of IR5 at the booting stage. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

rate was greatest for leaf 3 (0.77 mg CO₂ dm⁻² hr⁻¹) and least for leaves 2 and 4 (0.56 to 0.58 mg CO₂ dm⁻² hr⁻¹).

The respiratory rate of the sheath plus culm (per unit dry weight) also decreased with increasing LAI. On a unit weight basis, leaf blades and the sheath plus culm had similar respiratory rates (1 to 2 mg CO₂ g⁻¹ hr⁻¹). The sheath plus culm was about 75 percent of total weight and accounted for 62 to 77 percent of total respiration. The relative proportion of respiration from sheath plus culm and leaf blades showed no consistent trend with LAI.

The respiration of the canopy increased at a decreasing rate as LAI increased (fig. 1). A hyperbolic function is well fitted to express this relation.

By using a simulation technique (based on Duncan's model) further support was gained for the plateau-type response of improved varieties (fig. 2).

Thus, the physiological explanation for the critical LAI of improved rice varieties is that the respiration is not a linear but a hyperbolic function of LAI.

Accumulation of ¹⁴C-labeled carbohydrate before flowering

To obtain a direct measure of the contribution of carbohydrate accumulated before flowering to grain carbohydrate in the field, IR8 plants grown at 30 x 30 cm spacing with 100 kg/ha N and enclosed in a mylar chamber were allowed to assimilate 200 μC ¹⁴CO₂ 10 days before flowering.

Distribution of ¹⁴C in the plant. The distribution of total ¹⁴C in the plant was 1.5% in dead leaves and tillers, 22.3% in leaf blades, 41.7% in sheath plus culm, and 34.5% in husk plus rachis at flowering (fig. 3). By maturity, 16.0 percent of total ¹⁴C was translocated from sheath plus culm and leaf blades to the dehulled grains, and 4.8 percent was lost by respiration.

Translocation and respiration. To estimate how much of the ¹⁴C-labeled carbohydrate that accumulated in the plant before flowering was

2. Photosynthesis (by simulation), respiration (measured), and estimated dry matter production of IR5.

translocated from the vegetative parts to the grains and how much was lost by respiration, plant parts were analyzed for sugars and starch (Table 1), and ^{14}C activity was measured in each fraction (Table 2). Loss by respiration was estimated by two methods: by measuring the difference in ^{14}C activity in carbohydrate between flowering and maturity and by measuring directly the $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ respired by the plants.

Most of the ^{14}C incorporated in carbohydrate was present in the sheath plus culm at flowering. Little of ^{14}C -carbohydrate remained in the vegetative part at maturity. Loss of ^{14}C -carbohydrate from the vegetative parts exceeded the gain of ^{14}C -carbohydrate by the grains, indicating that some portion of the ^{14}C -carbohydrate lost from the vegetative parts was

respired. By this procedure, we estimated respiratory loss at 3.51×10^6 dpm/hill. The direct measurement of respired $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ indicated that the stored carbohydrate was actually respired; the rate of ^{14}C release decreased almost linearly with time. A linear regression, $Y = (331 - 11.5t) \times 10^3$ ($r = 0.91^{**}$) where Y is dpm hill $^{-1}$ hr $^{-1}$ and t is days after flowering, was used to estimate total ^{14}C loss by respiration which was 4.8×10^6 dpm/hill. The direct measurement gave a slightly larger estimate of respiratory loss than the first method, but the difference between the two is small. The difference may be partly due to errors of measurement and partly due to re-assimilation of respired $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ during the day.

3. Distribution of ^{14}C in IR8 fed 10 days before flowering. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Table 1. Carbohydrate content of plant parts of IR8 at flowering and harvest. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Plant part	Carbohydrate content (g/hill)						Change carbohydrate April 10-May 10
	Sugar		Starch		Total		
	April 10	May 10	April 10	May 10	April 10	May 10	
Sheath plus culm	7.7	0.5	6.2	0.7	13.9	1.2	12.7
Leaf blade	1.6	0.3	0.1	0.1	1.7	0.4	1.3
Panicle	0.3	—	0.9	—	1.2	—	1.2
Dehulled grains	—	1.0	—	41.5	—	42.5	—
Total ^a	9.6	0.8	7.2	0.8	16.8	1.6	15.2

^aWithout dehulled grains.

Table 2. ^{14}C in the carbohydrate fraction of IR8 at flowering and harvest. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Plant part	^{14}C content (10^6 dpm/hill)						
	Sugar		Starch		Total		Change
	April 10	May 10	April 10	May 10	April 10	May 10	April 10-May 10
Sheath plus culm	8.75	1.21	4.57	0.00	13.32	1.21	12.11
Leaf blade	3.54	0.68	0.07	0.13	3.61	0.81	2.80
Panicle	0.93	—	0.88	—	1.81	—	1.81
Dehulled grains	—	0.27	—	12.98	—	13.21	-13.21
Total	—	—	—	—	18.74	15.23	3.51

The efficiency of translocation,

$$T = a/b \quad (1)$$

respiratory loss,

$$L = c/b \quad (2)$$

and percentage residue,

$$R = 100 - (T + L) \quad (3)$$

where

T = Efficiency of translocation.

L = Respiratory loss.

R = Percentage residue.

a = ^{14}C -carbohydrate gained by the grain.

b = Total ^{14}C -carbohydrate in vegetative parts at flowering.

c = Loss in ^{14}C -carbohydrate from the plant.

can be calculated using the data from Table 2: efficiency of translocation, 68 percent; respiratory loss, 20 percent; and percentage of residue, 12 percent. The estimated efficiency of translocation of ^{14}C -carbohydrate is very high,

comparable to the growth efficiency of seedlings and the efficiency of conversion of glucose to ATP by microorganisms. The contribution of accumulated carbohydrate before flowering to grain carbohydrate can be calculated by

$$C = A \times T/B \quad (4)$$

where

C = Percent contribution.

A = Amount of carbohydrate present in vegetative parts at flowering.

B = Net gain in carbohydrate in grain during ripening period.

Using the translocation efficiency (T) and the data in Table 1, the contribution of accumulated carbohydrate before flowering is 26 percent. Since grain yield in this experiment was 7.8 t/ha, the contribution is equivalent to 2.0 t/ha of grain. Figure 4 summarizes the fate of accumulated carbohydrate and its contribution to grain yield.

The ^{14}C -assay vs. the chemical method. The chemical method based on change in carbohydrate content of the vegetative parts and grains at flowering and maturity can be used to estimate the contribution of the stored carbohydrate to grain production.

In our experiment use of the chemical method gave 34 percent as the amount of contribution compared with 26 percent by ^{14}C -assay method. Since the chemical method involves the assumption that no respiratory loss occurs, it tends to give an overestimate of the contribution of the stored carbohydrate to grain yield.

Our study demonstrates that carbohydrate that accumulates before flowering is translocated to grains during the ripening period and that the percent contribution obtained by chemical analysis can be useful if the appropriate correction is made.

4. Accumulated carbohydrate in vegetative parts at flowering and its contribution to grain yield.

The appropriate correction, in our study, can be made by multiplying the total accumulated carbohydrate at flowering by 0.68 or by multiplying the change in carbohydrate in vegetative parts between flowering and harvest by 0.77, i.e., $26 \div 34$.

The experiment also shows that most grain carbohydrate comes from photosynthesis after flowering. But in farmers' fields where yields may be low due to disease and pest attacks and shortage of water, the contribution of stored carbohydrate equivalent to 2 t/ha of grain, may be more significant and may tend to stabilize yields.

Growth of early maturing varieties

With conventional agronomic practices, varieties that mature in 130 to 140 days usually yield more than those that mature earlier or later. The achievement of high yields by growing early maturing varieties is a highly desirable goal because it would result in a more efficient daily production of carbohydrate, because it would promote more efficient land utilization, and because the crop would be exposed to natural hazards such as diseases and pests for a shorter time.

We studied the limiting factors in the grain yield of early maturing varieties and attempted to determine if cultural manipulation can overcome these barriers.

It has been reported that use of young seedlings improves performance of early maturing varieties. It is also reported that upland nursery grown seedlings are less damaged during transplanting and thus establish quicker than seedlings grown in a wet-bed nursery.

To test effects of seedbed practices on grain yield, we compared four methods in combination with two spacings in the dry season. Two lines were used: IR747B2-6-3 and IR154-18-2. IR8 was grown conventionally as control. The IR747 line has an open tiller habit and early vigor, and it matures in 100 days. The IR154 line has a compact tiller arrangement and it matures in 110 days. The two lines and IR8 are short (90 to 110 cm). Since the amount of solar energy received at late growth stages is very important

for grain production, the planting date was arranged so that all plants flowered at about the same time.

The grain yield of the IR747 line ranged from 7.23 to 7.92 t/ha and that of IR154 line, from 6.75 to 7.23 t/ha compared with 8.61 t/ha for IR8 (Table 3). Different seedbed practices had little effects on grain yield. In general, plants at the close spacing produced distinctly more dry matter and slightly higher grain yield.

The IR747 line has two superior characters: high harvest index values (ratio of grain to total dry matter) and high grain production per day. The IR747 line started in a wet-bed nursery and planted at 10 x 10 cm produced 7.92 t/ha in 98 days (from sowing to harvest) or 102 kg ha⁻¹day⁻¹. Although the IR747 line has an open tiller habit, which is supposedly an undesirable plant character, apparently it has not a drawback at the close spacing.

Analysis of yield components (Table 4) showed that the IR747 line was very high tillering and at the closer spacing it produced a distinctly larger total number of grains per unit land area than at the wider spacing with no decrease in grain weight. This indicates that increasing plant density is the most important cultural practice for raising yields of early maturing varieties.

In another experiment, to further test the effects of close spacing on growth performance of early maturing varieties, three varieties were grown at spacings of 5 x 5, 10 x 10, and 20 x 20 cm. Spacing had little effect on grain yields of IR8 and IR22 (fig. 5, Table 5). But the IR747 line, an early maturing rice, had about 1.5 t/ha difference in grain yield between spacings of 5 x 5 and 20 x 20 cm. At 20 x 20 cm, the IR747 line yielded less than IR8 and IR22, but at 5 x 5 cm, the IR747 line yielded more than IR8 and IR22.

The low yield of the IR747 line at 20 x 20 cm was caused by insufficient leaf area development (fig. 6). At 20 x 20 cm, the IR747 line had an LAI of only 4 at heading. In IR8, an LAI value of 6 is considered critical for maximum grain production. At 5 x 5 cm, the IR747 line achieved an LAI of about 7 at heading and yielded more than IR8 and IR22. The critical LAI value for IR8 apparently also applies to IR22 and the IR747 line (fig. 7).

Table 3. Effect of nursery method and direct seeding on grain yield, total dry weight, and harvest index of three varieties. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Nursery method ^a	Spacing (cm)	Growth duration ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total dry weight (t/ha)	Harvest index ^c	Grain production per day in main field (kg/ha)
<i>IR747B2-6-3</i>						
Wet-bed	10 x 10	98	7.92	14.1	0.48	102
	20 x 20	98	7.23	12.1	0.51	93
Upland	10 x 10	102	7.48	15.5	0.42	91
	20 x 20	102	7.32	12.5	0.50	89
Dapog	10 x 10	102	7.88	14.7	0.46	87
	20 x 20	102	7.61	13.9	0.47	84
Direct seeding	10 x 10	98	7.36	14.0	0.45	75
	20 x 20	98	7.37	13.3	0.48	75
<i>IR154-18-2-1</i>						
Wet-bed	10 x 10	110	7.23	15.2	0.41	80
	20 x 20	110	6.98	13.8	0.43	78
Upland	10 x 10	112	6.75	14.7	0.39	73
	20 x 20	112	6.75	14.4	0.40	73
Dapog	10 x 10	110	7.22	16.1	0.39	73
	20 x 20	110	7.13	14.2	0.43	72
Direct seeding	10 x 10	102	6.89	14.9	0.40	68
	20 x 20	102	6.82	13.5	0.43	67
<i>IR8</i>						
Wet-bed	20 x 20	132	8.61	17.2	0.43	77

^aSeedlings were grown for 20 days in the wet-bed nursery and the upland nursery and for 11 days in the dapog nursery (submerged concrete-lined seedbed). ^bSowing to harvest. ^cRatio of grain to total dry matter.

Table 4. Effect of plant spacing on yield components of three varieties (mean of different nursery methods). IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Variety	Spacing (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Grains (no./panicle)	No. of grains (10 ³ /sq m)	Filled grains (%)	1,000-grain wt. (g)
IR747B2-6-3	10 x 10	7.66	831	59	49.0	91	20.2
	20 x 20	7.38	627	69	43.3	93	19.4
IR154-18-2	10 x 10	7.02	643	87	55.9	79	18.3
	20 x 20	6.92	462	108	49.9	81	18.4
IR8	20 x 20	8.61	323	113	36.5	87	28.8

Table 5. Effect of plant spacing on grain yield, total dry weight, and harvest index of three varieties. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Spacing (cm)	Growth duration ^a (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total dry weight (t/ha)	Harvest index	Grain production per day in main field (kg/ha)
IR747B2-6-3	5 x 5	95	5.62	9.9	0.49	75
	10 x 10	95	4.70	9.7	0.41	63
	20 x 20	95	4.15	7.5	0.47	55
IR22	5 x 5	114	4.92	11.5	0.37	52
	10 x 10	114	5.01	10.6	0.41	53
	20 x 20	114	4.57	10.1	0.39	41
IR8	5 x 5	124	5.32	13.1	0.35	51
	10 x 10	124	5.31	11.5	0.40	51
	20 x 20	124	5.14	11.9	0.37	49

^aSowing to harvest.

5. Grain yield (average of three varieties) in relation to plant spacing and growth duration.

Thus the low yield of the IR747 line at conventional spacing which is caused by insufficient LAI can be overcome by increasing plant density.

If the vigor of a variety is defined as the rate of leaf area development per unit time, then the IR747 line is as vigorous as IR8. If a variety has the same degree of vigor as IR8 or the IR747 line, about 85 days (from sowing to maturity) will be enough to achieve an LAI value of 6 at flowering.

Analysis of yield components shows that the close spacing in the IR747 line increased the total grain number per unit land area but did not have any adverse effects on the percentage of filled grains or 1,000-grain weight (Table 6).

At flowering the nitrogen content of the leaf blades was much higher in the IR747 line than in

IR8, but total uptake of nitrogen was about the same for both varieties (Table 7). In contrast, carbohydrate content was much lower in the IR747 line than in IR8. That shows that the grain yield of the IR747 line, which is early maturing, is much less dependent on the accumulated carbohydrate before flowering.

Apparently several different patterns of nitrogen and carbohydrate metabolism and of leaf area development make possible the same yield under a given environment. Among these, leaf area development seems to be most consistently related to grain yield when different varieties are compared.

Also, no genetic barriers seem to exist in the early maturing variety for increased grain production. To achieve high yields with early maturing varieties, efforts should focus on more rapid development of leaf area. For farmers, direct seeding may be the only practical way to increase vegetative growth per unit land area. Since a direct-seeded crop is more likely to lodge than a transplanted one, more efforts should be made to breed lodging-resistant, early maturing varieties. With such a variety, 6 t/ha in wet season and 8 to 9 t/ha in dry season with an 85-day to 100-day variety could be readily achieved.

Growth patterns in Peta lines

High grain yields in rice are correlated with high dry matter production after flowering. But under

6. Development of leaf area index in IR8 and IR747B2-6-3 at different plant spacings.

7. Grain yield in relation to the leaf area index of three varieties at flowering. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

certain environments, several different growth patterns are possible which all result in maximum dry matter production after flowering. This optimum growth pattern is a balance between plant characters, such as height, growth duration, tiller number, LAI, leaf number, and size and arrangement of leaves. Leaf area index at flowering is one of the important factors for high dry matter production. A critical LAI may be obtained by various combinations of factors such as number of tillers per unit area, number of leaves per tiller, and length and width of leaves.

The relations of these physiological and morphological characteristics to the yielding ability of the varieties have been studied before. The main shortcoming of the studies was that the correlation may have been coincidental since the experimental materials were not isogenic, i.e., the varieties used may have had important differences other than the characters in question. To test the validity of the earlier findings using different varieties, we used lines from a cross

between Peta and Taichung Native 1. The lines differ in height and growth duration but the total leaf number produced by the main culm is the same between the early, short line and the early, tall line and between the late, short line and the late, tall line.

The four lines were planted in the field at 20 x 20 cm and 40 x 40 cm. In the wet season half the plants received 80 kg/ha N and in the dry season half received 150 kg/ha N. The rest did not receive any added nitrogen.

In the wet season the early lines (115 days) produced the highest yields at both the nitrogen levels and spacings used (Table 8). During the dry season, the late lines (137 days) produced the highest yields. The longer growth duration of these lines gave a better growth pattern. The advantage of a longer growth duration was especially marked at the low nitrogen level and the wider spacings.

During the wet season, the early, short line yielded best when planted at close spacing and with high nitrogen level. The early, tall line yielded well under different spacings and nitrogen levels. Spacing and nitrogen fertilization had no significant effect on the yield of this line. The late, short line also gave satisfactory yield at high nitrogen and close spacing, but the tall line did not give a satisfactory yield under any cultural practice during the wet season. Of the four lines, the early, tall line gave the best grain yields during the wet season.

During the dry season, the best yields for all lines were obtained at the close spacing with high nitrogen levels. The late lines gave higher yields than the early lines.

Table 6. Effect of plant spacing on yield components of three varieties. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Spacing (cm)	Panicles (no./sq m)	Grains (no./panicle)	Total no. of grains (10 ³ /sq m)	Filled grains (%)	1,000-grain wt. (g)
IR747B2-6-3	5 x 5	888	37	36.6	83	19.4
	10 x 10	700	47	33.6	88	18.7
	20 x 20	508	55	31.3	83	18.6
IR22	5 x 5	492	51	25.7	89	23.6
	10 x 10	396	62	26.4	88	22.7
	20 x 20	326	76	26.5	88	23.2
IR8	5 x 5	492	48	24.1	82	28.2
	10 x 10	328	62	22.1	84	29.4
	20 x 20	247	87	22.9	85	28.7

Table 7. Nitrogen and carbohydrate content of two varieties at three spacings at flowering. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Spacing (cm)	Nitrogen		Sugar plus starch		
		In leaf blade (%)	Total uptake (kg/ha)	In leaf sheath plus culm (%)	Total accumulated (t/ha)	Contribution to grain carbohydrate (%)
IR747B2-6-3	5 x 5	3.20	134	10.5	0.41	8
	10 x 10	3.04	110	8.1	0.30	7
	20 x 20	3.38	104	7.4	0.22	6
IR8	5 x 5	1.82	120	19.5	1.38	29
	10 x 10	1.84	115	12.3	0.73	16
	20 x 20	2.18	133	13.2	0.77	17

Thus for high grain yields, the wet season requires a different growth pattern than the dry season. Using different varieties of various growth durations, similar results have been obtained previously.

During the wet season the early lines had slightly better yields because of a better growth pattern: sufficient dry matter weight at flowering resulting in higher dry matter production from flowering to harvest (Table 9). The late line had large dry matter weights but low production from flowering to harvest. This low production may be the result of greater mutual shading as shown in the light transmission ratio (LTR) values and lower ratio of photosynthetic to non-photosynthetic plant parts at flowering (P:NP), indicating that the value for non-photosynthetic plant parts is greater. Thus during the wet season the ideal plant type for high yields is an early and preferably short variety (93 to 170 cm maximum height).

In the dry season light is not limiting. The high grain yields were the result of high LAI at all stages and better light absorption (Table 9). By flowering, the late lines had a high dry matter weight and the increase in dry matter weight was much larger than that of the early lines. The late lines which were low yielding during the wet season had the right growth pattern during the dry season.

The LAI at flowering is an important way to measure the capacity of a plant community to increase its dry matter weight. At flowering, the increase in dry matter weight is mainly the result of an increase in the panicle weight or grain yield. Figure 8 shows that LAI is positively correlated with grain yield.

Table 8. Yields of lines of Peta x Taichung Native 1, differing in growth duration and height, grown at two spacings and nitrogen levels. IRRI, 1969 wet and dry seasons.

Nitrogen level ^a	Plant spacing (cm)	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)				LSD (5%)
		Early short	Early tall	Late short	Late tall	
<i>Wet season</i>						
Low	20 x 20	4.9	5.7	4.4	3.9	0.5
High	20 x 20	5.7	5.8	5.3	4.8	0.5
Low	40 x 40	4.5	5.0	4.3	3.8	0.5
High	40 x 40	4.8	5.5	4.3	4.6	0.5
Average		5.0	5.5	4.6	4.3	0.3
<i>Dry season</i>						
Low	20 x 20	3.7	4.4	4.8	5.4	0.7
High	20 x 20	7.6	7.3	8.9	8.4	0.7
Low	40 x 40	3.3	3.8	4.4	5.7	0.7
High	40 x 40	5.9	6.7	7.7	7.0	0.7
Average		5.1	5.6	6.5	6.6	0.3

^a Low=zero added nitrogen; High=80 kg/ha in wet season and 150 kg/ha in dry season. ^b Early=115 days from sowing to harvest; Late=137 days from sowing to harvest.

8. Grain yield of Peta lines in relation to leaf area index during wet and dry season plantings.

Table 9. Grain yield and growth characteristics of Peta lines at high nitrogen level (wet season: 80 kg/ha N; dry season: 150 kg/ha N) and close spacing (20 x 20 cm).

Line	Grain yield (t/ha)	LAI ^a		Height at harvest (cm)	Dry matter (g/sq m)			LTR ^e		Tillers at harvest (no./sq m)	P:NP ^f
		PI ^b	F ^c		PI ^b	F ^c	H ^d	PI ^b	F ^c		
<i>Wet season</i>											
Early tall	5.8	3.9	5.6	167	334	978	1460	19	9	210	0.30
Early short	5.7	3.8	4.6	93	306	838	1213	27	19	290	0.33
Average	5.8	3.8	5.1	130	320	908	1336	23	14	250	0.32
Late tall	4.7	7.7	4.7	196	1021	1558	1452	14	4	198	0.20
Late short	5.3	5.2	5.0	108	705	1338	1403	26	7	220	0.25
Average	5.0	6.4	4.8	152	863	1448	1428	20	6	209	0.22
<i>Dry season</i>											
Early tall	7.3	4.2	7.4	155	360	1420	2007	16	2	325	0.28
Early short	7.6	4.2	6.5	79	358	1118	1474	21	6	380	0.35
Average	7.4	4.2	7.0	117	359	1269	1740	18	4	352	0.32
Late tall	8.4	8.8	6.5	187	982	1612	2544	4	2	330	0.25
Late short	8.9	7.1	8.6	105	830	1757	2263	6	4	380	0.31
Average	8.6	8.0	7.6	146	906	1684	2407	5	3	355	0.28

^aLeaf area index. ^bAt panicle initiation. ^cAt flowering. ^dAt harvest. ^eLight transmission ratio. ^fRatio of photosynthetic to non-photosynthetic plant parts at flowering.

The ratio of the photosynthetic to non-photosynthetic plant parts was positively correlated with grain yields. The correlation was higher in the wet season ($r = 0.44^*$) than in the dry season ($r = 0.39^*$). In the wet season, the respiration of the non-photosynthesizing plant parts is more important in decreasing the net yield than in the dry season. During the dry season, low LAI is the most important cause of low dry matter production.

During the wet season, the ideal growth pattern consists of 1) a high P:NP ratio which can be obtained by having a short growth duration or a short-statured plant, 2) a high LTR by having fewer leaves or elongated culms but sufficient LAI to have an increase in dry matter weight from flowering to harvest, and 3) a sufficient tiller number.

The ideal growth pattern in the dry season is different: 1) A high LAI, even at the panicle initiation stage, as a result of bigger leaves, 2) a high dry matter weight at flowering regardless of the P:NP ratio, and 3) to allow this growth pattern to develop, a long growth duration or much closer spacing.

These results substantiate some of the earlier findings arrived at by using ordinary varieties of different plant type and growth duration.

Comparison of rice and sorghum

Rice makes a sharp contrast with sorghum in various ways: Rice is adapted to a monsoon climate and has a relatively low photosynthetic rate but it has erect leaves; on the other hand,

Table 10. Leaf development of rice and sorghum at various growth stages in crops grown from March to May and from July to October. IRRI, 1970.

Growth stage	Crop	Leaves developed (no./main shoot)		Leafing rate ^a	
		Mar.-May	July-Oct.	Mar.-May	July-Oct.
Sowing to panicle initiation	Rice	12.4	11.0	4.0	4.3
	Sorghum	12.8	14.8	2.3	2.8
Panicle initiation to flag leaf	Rice	1.6	2.0	11.3	8.0
	Sorghum	4.4	3.9	3.6	3.6
Sowing to flag leaf	Rice	14.0	13.0	4.8	4.9
	Sorghum	17.2	18.7	2.7	2.9

^aAverage number of days required for development of one leaf per main shoot.

sorghum is adapted to dry climate and has a high photosynthetic rate but it has droopy leaves. We collected information on growth performances of these two crops under different agronomic and climatic conditions in an attempt to provide some suggestions for the further improvement of rice or sorghum.

The experiment was started in March 1970 and harvest of the two crops was completed by October. Varieties of similar growth durations were used.

Development of growth stages. Compared with rice, sorghum initiated its panicle primordia and matured earlier and it developed more leaves. Great differences were observed in leaf development for the period from panicle initiation to flag leaf (Table 10). Sorghum developed faster and had more leaves than rice during this period. Since this is the period when panicle grows, less competition for photosynthate between leaf and panicle growth seems to occur in rice than in sorghum.

Growth and grain yield. In the March-May crop, sorghum developed larger LAI values and produced more dry matter than rice (Table 11). Rice had larger harvest indices, however. As a result both crops yielded about the same. In rice, the close spacing gave a little higher yield than the wide spacing. In contrast, in sorghum, the close spacing produced more dry matter but resulted in lower grain yield.

The negative density effect and the low harvest index in sorghum may be related to more leaf growth during panicle growth, and the resulting competition for photosynthate between leaf and panicle.

In the July-October crop, the grain yield of rice was more than double that of sorghum. The low yields of sorghum was possibly due to lodging. The number of filled grains per square meter in sorghum was about the same for two crop seasons (Table 12). However, the 1,000-grain weight for the July-October crop was about half that of the March-May crop, indicating that grain-filling was probably impaired by lodging. Using the grain weight achieved by the March-May crop, the grain

yield of the July-October crop could be estimated at 5.71 t/ha which is comparable to the grain yield of rice.

The test varieties of rice and sorghum therefore have about the same yielding ability with irrigation in the dry season and under rainfed conditions in the wet season.

Zinc nutrition of rice

Zinc deficiency in the field. Last year we found zinc deficiency of rice in a farmer's field in the Philippines for the first time. The field was in Cebu on a calcareous soil. Farmers call the disorder "taya-taya." A subsequent survey has confirmed that zinc deficiency of rice is widespread on the east coast of Cebu. Typical examples of soil and plant analysis, and the results of a pot experiment are shown in Tables 13 and 14.

In San Pablo, Laguna, Philippines, we saw symptoms similar to taya-taya in rice plants in an IRRI demonstration plot. Rice in this plot grew poorly even when large amounts of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium were applied. The disorder is known as "apaya-pula," meaning "red-colored aphid" in Tagalog. The visual symptoms and low plant zinc content strongly suggested that this was another example

Table 11. Growth and grain yield of rice and sorghum in crops grown from March to May and from July to October. IRRI, 1970.

Crop	Irrigation	Spacing (cm)	Maxi-mum LAI	Total dry wt. (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Har-vest index ^a
<i>March-May crop</i>						
Rice	Irrigated	10 x 10	5.5	12.0	5.60	0.40
	Irrigated	20 x 20	4.3	11.7	5.38	0.40
Sorghum	Irrigated	10 x 10	10.4	18.8	4.63	0.21
	Irrigated	50 x 8	6.1	16.1	5.55	0.30
<i>July-October crop</i>						
Rice	Irrigated	10 x 10	7.9	11.0	5.24	0.41
	Irrigated	20 x 20	5.6	10.3	4.81	0.40
	Rainfed	10 x 10	7.7	10.7	5.00	0.40
	Rainfed	20 x 20	5.0	9.6	4.75	0.43
Sorghum ^b	Irrigated	30 x 8	10.6	10.8	1.97	0.16
	Irrigated	50 x 8	7.5	11.2	2.08	0.16
	Rainfed	30 x 8	10.1	10.4	2.03	0.17
	Rainfed	50 x 8	8.4	11.0	1.82	0.14

^aRatio of grain to total dry matter. ^bPlants affected by blight 7 days after heading and lodged 18 days after heading.

of zinc deficiency, and a pot and field experiment confirmed that it was (Tables 13 and 14).

The results of soil analysis, however, indicated that the San Pablo soil is quite different from the soils in Cebu. The pH of the San Pablo soil, at a 1:1 soil-to-water ratio, was 7.0, and the calcium content in the 0.5 N HCl extract of the soil was low compared with the Cebu soils. Therefore, the San Pablo soil was a neutral or near-neutral soil. The sodium content in the 0.5 N HCl extract and organic matter content was relatively high. But available soil zinc (extractable with ammonium carbonate and EDTA) content was low. The irrigation water for the San Pablo field had a pH of 8.0 and an electric conductance of 850 μ mhos/cm. In the field experiment, we observed that the plants growing near the irrigation inlet were noticeably more affected by the disorder. Apparently, the high pH of the irrigation water aggravated the disorder. This was the most severe case of zinc deficiency of rice we have seen. With 100 kg/ha Zn added, some plants still showed symptoms of zinc deficiency 6 weeks after transplanting.

In San Juan, Batangas, Philippines, a disorder of rice was reported from some farmers' fields. Farmers call it "pupong," meaning "sinking down" in their dialect. Visual symptoms were quite similar to those of zinc deficiency. The problem soil is calcareous. The zinc content of the plant sample was relatively low (Table 13) and the pot experiment confirmed that the disorder was zinc deficiency (Table 14).

In some experimental fields of Hualien District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan, an obscure disorder of rice has been known for more than 20 years. The disorder is characterized by brown spots. It occurs not only in fields with poor internal drainage but in well-drained fields. The disorder was originally called "chin-ku-bien" or "green blight disease," but since 1961 it has been called suffocating disease.

Many attempts have been made to correct the disorder. Application of potassium or iron material alleviates the disorder somewhat. Continuous rice cropping usually aggravates the disorder and rotation from rice to sweet potato or soybean and back to rice alleviates the disorder. The visual symptoms and a low plant zinc content strongly suggested that the disorder was caused by zinc deficiency (Table 13) which was later confirmed (Table 14).

In Chiang, Hualien, Taiwan, soil is brought from nearby mountains to reclaim land near the river's edge. Farmers who grow rice there reported an obscure disorder on some parts of the newly reclaimed fields. Plant pathologists could not isolate any pathogen from the affected plants. Visual symptoms and low plant zinc content suggested that it might be due to zinc deficiency (Table 13). The deficiency was proven in a greenhouse experiment (Table 14).

In the Pingtung area of Taiwan, what is called "suffocating disease" has been a problem. Problem fields have poor internal drainage. Rusty spots usually appear about 2 to 3 weeks after transplanting and some severely affected plants die. The severity of the disorder varies from one year to another. In general, affected plants recover somewhat at later stages of growth. Application of potassium improves growth but does not eliminate the rusty spots.

Visual symptoms observed in farmers' fields in Tungkang, Pingtung were a little different from those for zinc deficiency observed in other places. Diseased plants were characterized by tiny rusty spots. However, a greenhouse experiment produced moderate but typical zinc deficiency symptoms, and addition of zinc considerably improved rice growth (Tables 13 and 14).

These three examples from Taiwan suggest that zinc deficiency of rice may be widespread in the island. In addition, studies are needed to

Table 12. Yield components of irrigated rice (10 x 10 cm spacing) and sorghum (50 x 8 cm spacing). IRRI, 1970.

Crop	Season	Panicles (no./sq m)	Filled grains		1,000- grain wt. (g)	Grain wt. (t/ha)
			(no./panicle)	(10 ³ /sq m)		
Rice	March-May	465	66	30.6	18.3	5.60
	July-October	742	41	30.4	18.4	5.59
Sorghum	March-May	21	1209	24.8	22.4	5.55
	July-October	25	1020	25.5	11.6	2.97

Table 13. Analysis of soil and plant samples collected from problem fields.

Location	pH		Organic matter (%)	Available Zn (ppm)	0.5 N HCl soluble		Zn content of plant (ppm)	Plant symptoms of Zn deficiency
	1:1 ^a	1:5 ^a			Ca (%)	Na (ppm)		
Minglanilla, Cebu, Philippines	7.8	8.2	3.62	1.5	5.16	275	13	Severe
Argao, Cebu, Philippines	7.4	8.1	5.12	3.7	6.86	225	—	Severe
San Pablo, Laguna, Philippines	7.0	7.9	4.95	2.7	0.62	925	10	Severe
San Juan, Batangas, Philippines	7.8	8.1	3.79	1.3	1.25	980	18	Severe
Mexico, Pampanga, Philippines	7.2	7.3	0.97	0.6	0.06	305	—	Moderate
DAIS ^b , Hualien, Taiwan	7.6	7.8	2.22	1.2	2.86	90	12	Severe
Chiang, Hualien, Taiwan	7.0	7.1	1.34	0.4	1.00	365	14	Severe
Tungkang, Pingtung, Taiwan	7.7	7.9	3.41	3.1	0.99	205	16	Moderate
Udornthani, Thailand	5.8	5.9	0.51	17.3	0.01	80	33	None
Boeun, Korea	4.9	5.0	2.81	1.3	0.07	138	36	None

^aSoil-to-water ratio. ^bDistrict Agricultural Improvement Station.

re-examine causes of “suffocating disease.” It is likely that the causes of the physiological disorder of rice known as “suffocating disease” in Taiwan are different from one place to another.

In one field at the IRRI farm zinc deficiency has occurred under special circumstances. The continuous cropping experiment (four crops a year) is conducted in the field. Since 1969, early maturing varieties have been performing poorly in the field, although IR8 had been producing good yields in the field before 1969.

In December 1969, about 5 weeks after transplanting, brown spots and blotches appeared on the lower leaves of the rice plants. These symptoms are similar to those of zinc deficiency. The zinc content of the plant samples ranged from 15 to 17 ppm, suggesting the possibility of zinc deficiency. But after zinc was applied to some plots, both treated and untreated plants recovered rapidly at late growth stages so zinc deficiency could not be confirmed.

Since that time, the symptoms and the fast recovery have been observed in every crop in the field. The zinc content of shoots sampled from this field has ranged from 13 to 20 ppm, depending on the lines and the sampling time. The visual symptoms and growth performance also varied from one line to another.

The July-planted crop in 1970 was the first one to show a grain yield response to zinc application (Table 15). All lines showed similar symptoms about 4 to 5 weeks after transplanting. IR1154-243 and IR503-103-3 recovered rapidly at later growth stages regardless of zinc treatment. On the other hand, IR773-112-2 and IR773-118

were affected for a longer period, and recovery of growth was much delayed. Dipping the seedlings in 2 percent ZnO before transplanting and spraying the foliage of the plant with zinc sulfate promoted rapid recovery in the two IR773 lines. This shows that there were varietal differences in response to zinc application.

Repeated greenhouse experiments using the soil from the problem plot failed to induce zinc deficiency, however. This indicates that the soil alone did not induce zinc deficiency.

Zinc deficiency in this field may be attributed to several factors. First, the zinc-supplying power of Maahas clay is rather low. Second, because of continuous submergence, zinc level in soil solution becomes low. Third, because of continuous cropping, large amounts of rice stubble accumulate and this may increase

Table 14. Dry weight and zinc content of rice grown on problem soils in the greenhouse (plants harvested 28 to 30 days after transplanting).

Location	Dry wt. (g/pot)		Zn content in shoot (ppm)	
	No zinc	With zinc	No zinc	With zinc
<i>Zinc deficient</i>				
Minglanilla, Cebu, Philippines	0.53	1.73	19	33
San Pablo, Laguna, Philippines	0.43	2.10	11	30
San Juan, Batangas, Philippines	0.78	2.45	12	48
Mexico, Pampanga, Philippines	0.41	1.44	17	145
DAIS ^a , Hualien, Taiwan	0.66	1.59	11	36
Chiang, Hualien, Taiwan	0.94	2.34	8	69
Tungkang, Pingtung, Taiwan	0.74	1.91	17	49
<i>Zinc not deficient</i>				
Udornthani, Thailand	0.74	0.39	51	370
Boeun, Korea	3.11	3.09	42	368

^aDistrict Agricultural Improvement Station.

Table 15. Effect of zinc application on grain yield of five lines in the continuous cropping experiment. IRRRI, 1970.

Lines ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No zinc	Zinc spray ^b	Dipping in 2% ZnO	ZnCl ₂ ^c	FTE ^c
IR1154-243	4.05	4.79	4.56	—	—
IR503-103-3	4.14	4.02	4.14	—	—
IR773-112-2	2.47	4.11	4.44	—	—
IR773-118	2.62	2.91	3.34	—	—
IR747B2-6-3	3.76	—	4.16	3.86	3.89

^aPlanted on July 26 except IR747B2-6-3 which was planted Oct. 27. ^bFoliar spray of zinc sulfate at 15 kg/ha Zn after the symptoms were observed. ^cRate: 50 kg/ha Zn. FTE=Fritted trace elements.

concentration of bicarbonate and organic acids in the soil which retard zinc uptake by the rice plant. Third, the aerobic soil pH of this field has risen from 6.0 to 6.9. Fourth, frequent application of insecticides increases the pH of standing water; in one test, standing field water had a pH of about 9. This high pH could also have resulted partly from rapid removal of CO₂ by vigorous algal growth.

Factors affecting zinc deficiency. A series of experiments were conducted to study factors that affect zinc absorption and hence zinc deficiency of rice in flooded soils.

Incidence of zinc deficiency and soil properties. Studies were made to correlate the incidence of zinc deficiency with the properties of 32 samples of soil collected from Pakistan, India, Thailand, Philippines, Taiwan, and Korea.

As shown in figure 9, zinc deficiency of flooded rice occurs in soils of neutral to alkaline pH. When soil pH is low, low available soil zinc

9. Relationship between incidence of zinc deficiency, soil pH, and available soil zinc.

10. Relationship between zinc deficiency, soil organic matter, and available soil zinc (for soils of more than pH 7).

content does not necessarily induce zinc deficiency. Comparing soil organic matter and available soil zinc content for soils of more than pH 7 showed that zinc deficiency tends to occur in soil that has relatively high available zinc content when soil organic matter content is high (fig. 10). These two studies indicate that zinc deficiency of flooded rice is closely associated with high soil pH, low available zinc content, and high organic matter content in the soil.

Kinetics of zinc in soil solution. Our previous studies indicated that flooding decreases zinc uptake by the rice plant. Addition of cellulose to the soil also retards zinc uptake, thereby aggravating zinc deficiency of the rice plant.

The kinetics of zinc in soil solution was studied on three soils differing in zinc supplying power. The zinc concentration in the soil solution decreased sharply upon flooding, and tended to fall to a fairly constant level around 0.01 ppm (fig. 11). Addition of cellulose to Kala Shah Kaku soil did not change zinc concentration in the soil solution. During the first few weeks of submergence, there was large difference in zinc concentration in the different soil solutions. The difference appears to correlate with plant zinc content: 38 ppm for plants grown on Luisiana soil, 25 ppm for plants on Maahas soil, and 12 ppm for plants on Kala Shah Kaku soil. Therefore, zinc concentration in the soil solution can be considered one influence on zinc uptake by the rice plant.

But the zinc concentration in soil solution alone cannot explain why addition of cellulose to the soil aggravates zinc deficiency or why the growth of rice begins to recover about 6 weeks

11. Changes in pH and kinetics of zinc in the soil solution of Kala Shah Kaku, Maahas, and Luisiana soils with 0.5 percent added cellulose and of Kala Shah Kaku soil without added cellulose.

after transplanting when the zinc concentration in the soil solution declines. Something must retard zinc absorption by the rice plant in the early period of submergence which is removed later.

Bicarbonate and organic acids. In flooded soils the concentration of carbon dioxide and organic acids reach a maximum soon after the soil is submerged. It decreases as time goes on. Adding cellulose to the soil increases the con-

centration of carbon dioxide and organic acids in the soil solution. In neutral to alkaline soils, most of the carbon dioxide exists as bicarbonate. We studied the effects of bicarbonate and acetic acid on zinc absorption by the rice plant using ^{65}Zn . In our previous studies, we used relatively high concentrations of bicarbonate. In this year's experiment, we studied the effects of low concentrations on zinc absorption.

Within a realistic range of carbon dioxide concentration in submerged soils, bicarbonate retarded absorption of ^{65}Zn considerably (fig. 12). Acetic acid did not inhibit zinc absorption except at a high concentration (30 mM) when the culture solution was kept at pH 7.3. But when the culture solution was kept at pH 4.5 acetic acid inhibited zinc absorption even at low concentrations. So in neutral and calcareous soils, bicarbonate is likely to be a major inhibitor of zinc absorption. Organic acids can also retard zinc absorption at high concentrations. In acid soils, if the zinc concentration in soil solution is low, the accumulation of organic acids could retard zinc absorption and hence induce zinc deficiency.

Presubmergence. Based on development of zinc deficiency symptoms; the kinetics of zinc, bicarbonate, and organic acids in soil solution in submerged soils; the aggravating effects of added cellulose on zinc deficiency; and the retarding effects of bicarbonate and acetic acid on zinc absorption by the rice plant, we can develop a working hypothesis for zinc deficiency

12. Effects of bicarbonate and acetic acid on absorption of ^{65}Zn from culture solution.

of rice in flooded soils. When soils of different zinc supplying power are compared, zinc concentration in soil solution affects zinc absorption, and hence zinc deficiency. With the same soil, soil pH and concentration of bicarbonate and organic acid greatly affect zinc absorption from soil solution. To test this hypothesis, we used varying periods of presubmergence to change the concentrations of zinc, bicarbonate, and organic acids in soil solutions.

The longer the period of presubmergence, the greater the zinc absorption in all soils (Table 16). Plants in zinc-deficient soil from Kala Shah Kâku presubmerged for 0 or 3 weeks developed typical symptoms of zinc deficiency. With 12 weeks of presubmergence, however, the plant growth was quite normal and the dry weight was comparable to that of plants from Luisiana and Maahas soils.

On Luisiana and Maahas soils, zinc absorption by plants was low in the early period of submergence when zinc concentration in soil solution was quite high but pH was low (fig. 11). Organic acids probably retarded the absorption of zinc.

The recovery of growth observed at later stages on zinc-deficient calcareous soils therefore is not induced by plant age but by chemical changes in submerged soils.

This experiment supports the conclusion that pH and concentrations of zinc, bicarbonate, and organic acid are major influences on zinc absorption by the rice plant. High soil pH is often associated with low available zinc content, and it also affects the concentration of zinc in soil solution. The pH changes the modes of

inhibitory action of bicarbonate and organic acids on zinc absorption. Thus the hypothesis explains why zinc deficiency tends to occur on soils of high pH, low available zinc content, and high organic matter content, and why the affected plants tend to recover at later stages of growth.

Availability of zinc materials. The relative availability of six zinc compounds to flooded rice was compared using zinc-deficient soil in the greenhouse. Zinc sulfate, zinc chloride, and zinc oxide were about equally available (Table 17). Zinc oxide has a surprisingly high availability considering its low solubility in water. Zinc carbonate, Zn-Dowex 50-X4, and FTE (fritted trace elements) supplied less zinc to the plant, but appeared to be good sources of zinc. Because of the high rate of application in our experiment, FTE caused the plants to develop some unusual symptoms and it retarded growth. The plants supplied with ZnEDTA also showed symptoms of EDTA toxicity.

Effects of nitrogenous fertilizers on zinc uptake. Different nitrogenous fertilizers should have different effects on zinc uptake because they have different effects on soil pH.

Applying urea to plants in pots caused severe symptoms of zinc deficiency to develop. Plants supplied with ammonium sulfate showed slight symptoms of zinc deficiency. Plants supplied with ammonium chloride did not show any. These effects were reflected in dry weight and zinc uptake (Table 18). The results show that "physiologically acid" nitrogenous fertilizers have an advantage in improving zinc uptake and hence growth on zinc-deficient calcareous soils.

To test the results under field conditions, a preliminary field trial was conducted on a calcareous soil in Cebu. Ammonium sulfate and ammonium chloride produced distinctly higher grain yield than urea (Table 19). Since flooded rice often has incipient zinc deficiency, the choice of nitrogenous fertilizers alone may prevent the problem.

Distribution of zinc in the rice plant. Our previous studies showed that absorbed ^{65}Zn tended to move more to young leaves (1968 Annual

Table 16. Effect of soil submergence before transplanting on the dry weight and zinc and manganese content of 4-week-old IR22 rice plants grown in the greenhouse.

Soil	Weeks presubmerged	Shoot dry wt. (g/pot)	Conc. in shoot (ppm)		Total Zn in shoot ($\mu\text{g}/\text{pot}$)
			Zn	Mn	
Luisiana	0	3.49	38	502	133
	3	2.27	52	393	118
	12	4.61	61	220	281
Maahas	0	1.14	25	1174	29
	3	3.26	31	793	101
	12	4.25	32	923	136
Kala Shah Kaku	0	1.14	12	378	14
	3	1.10	15	509	17
	12	4.03	22	753	89

Report). To supplement this information, the zinc content of different parts of the plant was analyzed this year.

The leaf sheath plus the culm had a higher zinc content than any leaf (Table 20). When zinc was deficient, the leaves had the same zinc content regardless of position. When the zinc supply was relatively high, however, younger leaves had a higher zinc content than older leaves. This supports the previous conclusion that zinc is relatively mobile in the rice plant.

To diagnose a nutrient deficiency, the choice of a plant part for chemical analysis is often a problem. Our study indicates that the leaves and whole shoot provide the same information, so it is most convenient to take the whole shoot for diagnosis of zinc deficiency.

Varietal susceptibility to zinc deficiency. Previously we found that varietal differences in susceptibility to zinc deficiency appear to be related to faster recovery at later stages of growth rather than to higher absorptive ability (1969 Annual Report). We therefore attempted to clarify the differences in "recovery vigor."

Growth in zinc-deficient fields. We grew 21 varieties on an extremely zinc-deficient soil in San Pablo, Laguna, Philippines. No varietal difference was observed. Applying zinc is the only way to correct the problem on this soil.

In Linao, Cebu, Philippines, 12 varieties were tested on a severely zinc-deficient soil. Although differences were observed in visual symptoms such as number, size, and shape of brown spots, varietal differences in growth did not become apparent until 6 weeks after transplanting. The grain yields ranged from 0.2 to 1 t/ha. At such a low yield level, varietal differences are practically meaningless.

With moderate zinc deficiency, varietal differences become apparent (1969 Annual Report).

In a slightly deficient soil, varietal differences are highly meaningful (Table 15). Table 21 summarizes the varietal difference in recovery vigor from zinc deficiency and Table 22, the varietal difference in grain yield on zinc-deficient soils. Clearly, on soils that are extremely to moderately zinc deficient, application of zinc is the only practical way to correct the problem.

Table 17. Effect of zinc sources on the growth of rice on Kala Shah Kaku soil (applied at 100 mg Zn/400 g soil) in the greenhouse.

Zinc source	Dry wt. ^a (g/pot)	Zn content in shoot (ppm)	Total Zn uptake (µg/pot)
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.84	186	342
ZnCl ₂	1.93	184	355
ZnO	1.98	179	354
ZnCO ₃	1.83	109	199
Zn-EDTA	0.14	414	58
Zn-Dowex 50W-X4	2.07	94	193
FTE ^b	1.31	105	138
Dipping in 2% ZnO	1.71	44	75
No zinc	1.28	22	28

^aPlants harvested 1 month after transplanting. ^bFritted trace elements.

Table 18. Effects of forms of nitrogenous fertilizer on growth and zinc uptake on Kala Shah Kaku soil in the greenhouse.

Form of nitrogen	Dry wt. (g/pot)	Zn content in shoot (ppm)	Total Zn uptake (µg/pot)
Ammonium sulfate	1.28	22	28
Ammonium chloride	1.78	31	55
Urea	0.88	20	17
Ammonium sulfate + ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.84	186	342

Table 19. Effect of form of nitrogenous fertilizer on grain yield on a zinc-deficient calcareous soil. Cebu, Philippines, 1970 wet season.

Form of nitrogen	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	0 kg/ha Zn	100 kg/ha Zn
Ammonium sulfate	6.17	6.49
Ammonium chloride	5.60	6.46
Urea	4.72	5.20

Table 20. Zinc content of different parts of the rice plant (at tillering) grown in zinc-deficient and normal culture solutions and in two soils in the field. IRRI, 1970.

Plant part ^a	Zn (ppm)			
	Water-cultured		Field-grown	
	Deficient	Normal	Cebu	Maahas
Leaf 1	11	45	11	23
Leaf 2	12	27	11	20
Leaf 3	10	22	10	17
Leaf 4	11	21	11	16
Leaf 5	—	20	—	17
Leaf sheath plus culm	13	51	14	32
Whole shoot	12	38	12	27

^aLeaf positions counted from top.

Table 21. Varietal difference in "recovery vigor" from zinc deficiency under field conditions (assessed by dry weight and grain yield).

Strong	Moderate	Weak
IR8	IR154-18-2	IR154-45-1
IR22	IR773A1-36-2	IR184-67-1
IR503-103-3		IR773-112-2
IR747B2-6-3		IR773-118
IR1154-243		81B25
Bengawan		B581A6
Mestiso		CP231

Table 22. Varietal difference in grain yield on zinc-deficient soils in the Philippines.

Zinc deficiency	Place	Varieties (no.)	Yield index ^a
Extreme	San Pablo, Laguna	21	0
Severe	Linao, Cebu	12	3-10
Moderate	Minglanilla, Cebu	2	10, 32
Slight	IRRI, Laguna	4	55-100

^a(Grain yield without Zn ÷ grain yield with Zn) x 100.

When zinc deficiency is slight, varietal difference becomes quite important.

Recovery rate and tillering capacity. Varietal differences in recovery rate and, hence, in grain yield in zinc-deficient soils may be related to tillering capacity. CP231, for instance, is a low tillering variety and showed a slow recovery while high tillering varieties such as IR8, IR22, and Bengawan showed fast recovery at later stages of growth.

Figure 13 shows the relationship between tillering capacity with added zinc and relative growth rate under deficient conditions. The relative growth rate was used to express "recovery rate." The close correlations indicate that the recovery rate of the affected plant is associated with tillering capacity.

Growth duration also affects growth performance in zinc-deficient soils. If the growth duration of a variety is short, the variety may not recover enough to produce good grain yields. This is a major reason for the large difference in grain yield of IR184-67-1 grown with and without added zinc. On the other hand, IR8, which is high tillering and has a medium growth duration, produces a fairly good yield without applied zinc (1969 Annual Report).

Recovery from nutrient deficiencies in culture solution. The conclusion that the recovery rate

from zinc deficiency is associated with tillering capacity led to the idea that "apparent varietal difference" in susceptibility to zinc deficiency is not specific to zinc. Zinc deficiency could be just one instance in which tillering capacity is related to faster recovery. To test this idea, plants were grown in culture solutions lacking one nutrient for 18 days. Then they were transferred to a complete culture solution and the recovery rate was observed. The two varieties used were IR8, which was considered "resistant" to zinc deficiency, and IR184-67-1, which was considered "susceptible." The varietal difference in recovery rate from all nutrient deficiencies was consistent (fig. 14). That is, the observed varietal difference in zinc-deficient soils is not specific to zinc deficiency. When IR8 plants were transferred from a "deficient" to a complete solution, they started tillering immediately. On the other hand, the IR184 line had a lag time before producing new tillers. In other words, IR8 has more "recovery vigor" when the environment becomes favorable for growth. Therefore, under zinc-deficient field conditions what really determines varietal performance is "recovery vigor" and high tillering capacity. The two enable plants to make maximum use of a given environment in a limited time.

This conclusion adds support to the idea that high tillering capacity is a desirable trait for high yielding varieties under diverse conditions.

13. Relative growth rate (RGR) of varieties recovering from zinc deficiency 7 to 11 weeks after planting in relation to tiller count per hill 7 weeks after transplanting in plots where zinc was added.

Micronutrient uptake by rice

To collect information on micronutrient uptake by a high yielding crop, IR8 was grown in the 1969 dry season and samples were taken at different stages of growth and analyzed for six micronutrients. Figure 15 shows contents of

micronutrients at different stages of growth, and Table 23, removal of micronutrients by one crop and by 1 ton of rice.

The content of all the micronutrients was within the normal range. The content of chlorine and boron was relatively high, the content of manganese and iron was moderate and the

14. Rate of tiller production by IR8 and IR184-67-1 during recovery from nutrient deficiencies.

15. Micronutrient content of IR8 grown in the field. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

content of copper and zinc was relatively low. Among these, zinc deserves particular attention. The zinc content of IR8 ranged from 22 to 26 ppm, a little above the critical level for deficiency. On the other hand, the zinc content of samples collected previously in a survey of Asian countries ranged from 10 to 60 ppm and workers in Japan have reported a range of 75 to 120 ppm. These data indicate that Maahas clay soil has a low supplying power for zinc.

Photoperiod

Previous data on the response of IRRI varieties to photoperiod were obtained from different tests so that accurate comparisons could not be made. This year we tested all four IRRI varieties together. IR8 was the most insensitive, followed by IR22 (Table 24). The most sensitive was IR5 although it flowered even with 16 hours of photoperiod. Both IR20 and IR22 have a short

Table 23. Micronutrient removal by a high yielding rice crop. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Micro-nutrient	Nutrients removed by one crop ^a .(kg/ha)			Nutrients removed by 1 ton of rice (g)		
	Straw	Panicle	Total	Straw	Panicle	Total
Cl	78.50	12.00	90.50	8600	1310	9910
Fe	3.78	1.91	5.69	414	209	623
Mn	1.41	0.46	1.87	154	50	204
B	0.44	0.16	0.60	48	18	66
Zn	0.19	0.14	0.33	21	15	36
Cu	0.02	0.03	0.05	2	3	5

^aGrain yield was 9.13 t/ha.

growth duration and a relatively short basic vegetative phase.

Of the IRRI lines tested, IR747B2-6-3 had the shortest growth duration. Previous screenings of IRRI lines have not shown any line with a growth duration shorter than IR747B2-6-3. This line is insensitive to photoperiod and has a short growth duration even with continuous photoperiod.

RD 3 is a new improved rice variety from Thailand. It is insensitive to photoperiod and has a relatively short growth duration.

Another set of promising IRRI lines were tested for their response to photoperiod. All the lines tested flowered under the different photoperiodic treatments used (Table 25).

Temperature response of IR8

IR8 vs Fujisaka 5. Table 26 compares the responses of IR8 to temperature with the responses of Fujisaka 5, a temperate variety from Japan. At low temperatures (15 to 21 C), IR8 has shorter internodes with panicles less exerted, more tillers at harvest, higher percent sterility, greater percentage of shattering grains, and longer growth duration than it does at higher temperatures (25 to 29 C).

Resistance to low temperature is relative and varies with the stage of growth and the criteria of comparison. At germination, IR8 is more resistant than Fujisaka 5 since IR8 can germinate at a lower temperature (16 C). The percentage of germination was taken 6 days after incubation.

At the seedling stage, IR8 is more susceptible than Fujisaka 5 based on seedling height but more resistant if based on shoot weight.

Normally, selection for cold-tolerant varieties in the field is based on seedling height. This method would eliminate IR8 which is short but which has a higher dry matter weight.

At the tillering stage, IR8 is definitely more resistant to low temperature than Fujisaka 5 since it has more tillers per unit area. But IR8 can be classified as more susceptible based on height (figs. 16, 17).

Based on percentage of filled spikelets, IR8 is more susceptible than Fujisaka 5. Percentage of filled spikelets is another criterion used in evaluating temperature resistance.

Low temperature problems differ from one area to another. Low temperature might be a

Table 24. Response of IRRI varieties and promising lines to photoperiods of 10 to 16 hours.

Varieties or lines	Growth duration ^a (days)				BVP ^b (days)	PSP ^c (days)
	10 hr	12 hr	14 hr	16 hr		
IR5	93	101	130	134	58	41
IR8	101	100	109	112	65	12
IR20	76	76	103	112	41	36
IR22	69	73	101	102	34	33
IR81-105-2	71	79	111	134	36	63
IR332-2-10	98	116	148	165	63	67
IR665-48	82	84	102	102	47	20
IR747B2-6-3	68	64	77	73	29	13
IR878B2-62-2	103	102	115	114	67	13
RD 3	83	87	101	100	48	18
BPI-76	57	102	^d	^d	22	200+

^aFrom sowing to flowering. ^bBasic vegetative phase. ^cPhotoperiod sensitive phase. ^dNo panicle initiation after 200 days of growth. Sown March 30, 1970.

Table 25. Response of IRRI lines to photoperiods of 10 hours to 16 hours.

Selection	Growth duration ^a (days)				BVP ^b (days)	PSP ^c (days)
	10 hr	12 hr	14 hr	16 hr		
IR95-42-13	84	82	94	114	47	32
IR262-43-8	82	82	99	108	47	26
IR442-2-58	88	93	113	120	53	32
IR442-50-2	83	90	119	128	48	45
IR578-181-3	87	85	97	104	50	19
IR579-48-1	75	80	88	97	40	22
IR589-54-2	87	96	123	129	52	42
IR589-66-2	65	80	106	113	30	48
IR661-1-140-3-2	97	91	107	114	56	23
IR627-1-31	104	99	116	119	64	20
IR773A1-36-2	96	86	103	116	51	30
BPI-76	62	109	^d	^d	27	200+

^aFrom sowing to flowering. ^bBasic vegetative phase. ^cPhotoperiod sensitive phase. ^dNo panicle initiation after 200 days of growth. Sown October 16, 1969.

Table 26. Responses of IR8 and Fujisaka 5 to temperature^a at Los Baños, Laguna (L) and La Trinidad, Mountain Province (M), Philippines.

Growth stage	Criterion	IR8	Fujisaka 5
Germination	Optimum temp. range	19-34 C	26-34 C
	Min. requirement	16 C	19 C
	Max. requirement	40 C	33 C
Seedling growth ^b	Height	L: 31 cm, M: 24 cm	L: 37 cm, M: 31 cm
	Shoot weight	L: 283 mg, M: 130 mg	L: 371 mg, M: 120 mg
Tillering	Tillers (no./sq m)		
	30 days after transplanting	positively correlated with temp.	less than IR8 and no correlation with temp.
	60 days after transplanting	negatively correlated with temp.	less than IR8 and no correlation with temp.
	Height ^b		
	30 days after transplanting	L: 63 cm, M: 36 cm	L: 74 cm, M: 46 cm
	60 days after transplanting	L: 100 cm, M: 54 cm	L: 85 cm, M: 66 cm
Internode development	Length of internodes	great reduction at low temp.	length was increased
	Panicles	not fully exerted at low temp.	fully exerted
Harvest	Panicles ^b (no./sq m)	L: 300, M: 1010	L: 275, M: 480
	Empty spikelets ^b	L: 39%, M: 100%	L: 30%, M: 60%
	Spikelets ^b (no./panicle)	L: 111, M: 81-97	L: 50, M: 66
	Shattering ^c	L: 3%, M: 15%	high at low temp. but to a lesser degree than IR8
	Growth duration ^b (days)	L: 125, M: 215	L: 93, M: 157

^a La Trinidad: min. 9-18 C; ave. 15-21 C; max. 21-25 C. Los Baños: min. 21-24 C; ave. 25-29 C; max. 29-34 C. ^bBased on July planting. ^cHarvested in July.

problem during germination and seedling growth or at flowering stage. So, selection for tolerance to cold should be based on the stage at which low temperatures generally occur in the area where the plants will be grown.

Temperature and growth duration of IR8. Since IR8 is the least sensitive of the IRR1 varieties to photoperiod, it can be planted at any latitude and be expected to flower within a reasonable length of time. Figure 18 shows the growth

16. Tiller density of IR8 at different temperatures, 30 and 60 days after transplanting.

duration of IR8 planted in June or July at different latitudes for the main cropping season. In most tropical areas, the climate is warm and the daylength is long. The variation in growth duration of IR8 is only around 20 days for latitudes up to 27°N. At 16°N (La Trinidad, Philippines) and 23°N (Kanke, India), the growth durations of IR8 are greatly lengthened. These sites are located at high altitudes. The delay is mainly the effect of low temperature. Many workers have reported the decrease in growth duration with the increase in temperature from 15 to 32 C.

Monthly sowings of IR8 at Los Baños and at Joydevpur, East Pakistan showed that growth duration at Los Baños varied much less than at Joydevpur (fig. 19). The large variation in Pakistan can be accounted for by the low temperatures. The decrease in temperature starting in September lengthened the growth duration of IR8 planted from September to December. Shorter daylength, if daylength was important, would have decreased the growth duration of the September to December plantings.

Analysis of temperature components showed that the minimum temperature has the best correlation with growth duration (fig. 20). Minimum temperature during the growth period has a highly significant negative correlation

17. Tiller density of Fujisaka 5 at different temperatures, 30 and 60 days after transplanting.

with the growth duration of IR8 at Joydevpur, East Pakistan (data from East Pakistan Rice Research Institute); Northern Territory, Australia (data from Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation); and

Katmandu, Nepal (data from Agronomy Experimental Farm, Khumaltar). The non-significant correlation at Los Baños is probably the result of the narrow range in minimum temperature.

At 20 C, the growth duration at the Northern Territory was 125 days while at Joydevpur it was 153 days. This variation can be attributed to the difference in the maximum temperature. At Northern Territory, the average maximum temperature varies little through the year but the average minimum temperature varies greatly. At Joydevpur, both the maximum and minimum temperatures vary greatly. The maximum temperature itself is not correlated with growth duration, but it modifies the effect of the minimum temperature which may account for the big difference in the slope. The diurnal temperature range is probably important too.

In Japan, temperature summation has been used to predict growth duration. The idea is that at a given average temperature a particular

18. Growth duration (days from sowing to harvest) of IR8 planted in June or July at 12 locations.

variety will mature in a fixed number of days; if the average temperature is higher, the number of days to maturity is lower, and if the average temperature is lower, the number of days to maturity are higher. IR8, however, does not have a fixed temperature summation (fig. 21). In fact, the temperature summation increases with growth duration. IR8 is therefore unlike temperate varieties.

In introducing IR8 and similar improved varieties to other latitudes, temperature is the main influence on its growth duration. The average minimum temperature during the cropping season is the best parameter to use in determining growth duration.

Temperature requirements for germination. Rice varieties differ in the temperature ranges within which their seeds germinate rapidly and vigorously. In the range of temperatures within which seeds germinate there is usually an optimum temperature, below and above which germination is delayed but not prevented. The minimum and maximum temperatures for germination are the lowest and the highest temperatures, respectively, at which germination will occur.

So far, no studies have been reported on the temperature requirements of the improved varieties developed by IRRI. The widespread use of IRRI varieties makes it imperative to

19. Mean monthly temperatures and daylength in relation to the growth duration of IR8 at Los Baños, Philippines, and at Joydevpur, East Pakistan.

Table 27. Optimum, maximum, and minimum temperatures for germination 3 and 6 days after soaking.

Variety	Temperature ^a (C)					
	3 days			6 days		
	Opt.	Max.	Min.	Opt.	Max.	Min.
IR5	26-33	33	19	19-33	40	16
IR20	26-33	40	19	19-33	40	16
IR8	26-33	33	19	19-33	40	16
IR22	26-33	40	26	26-33	40	19
Fujisaka 5	28-33	33	26	26-33	33	19
Kulu	26-30	40	26	19-40	40	19

^a Optimum temperature was based on 100% germination while maximum and minimum temperature requirements were based on at least 10% germination.

know the critical germination temperatures for these varieties and to compare these with standard varieties.

Under field conditions 5 to 6 days is the maximum time a farmer waits for the seeds to germinate. Six days was therefore selected as the period for determining the temperature requirements.

Optimum temperature. The optimum temperature for IR5, IR20, and IR8 ranged from 19 to 33 C; for IR22 and Fujisaka 5 from 26 to 33 C, and for Kulu from 19 to 40 C (Table 27). IR22 and Fujisaka 5 have the narrowest range. The optimum range is smaller if the percent germination is determined early and becomes wider as the period is prolonged. The optimum temperature for other varieties, as reported by several workers, ranges from 15 to 37 C depending upon the duration of the germination period.

Minimum temperature. The minimum temperature for germination of seeds is frequently ill-defined because germination is so slow that experiments are often terminated before germination could in fact have occurred.

Based on a 6-day incubation period, the minimum temperature for IR5, IR20, and IR8 is 16 C while IR22, Fujisaka 5, and Kulu had a minimum temperature of 19 C. IRR1 varieties, which are tropical in origin, are more resistant to low temperature during germination than the two temperate varieties, based on the minimum temperature at which germination can occur in 6 days.

20. Relationship between maximum and minimum temperatures and growth duration of IR8 planted at Australia, Nepal, and East Pakistan.

21. Temperature summation and growth duration of IR8 planted at Australia, Nepal, and East Pakistan.

Germination did occur at 13 C but only after 9 days of incubation. IR20 had the highest germination while Kulu had the lowest germination. Fujisaka 5 did not germinate at all until the 18th day.

Maximum temperature. No variety germinated 6 days after soaking at 45 C. At 43 C only IR20 germinated and the germination was very poor.

All varieties, except Fujisaka 5, germinated at 40 C.

Generally, the IRRI varieties had a wider

adaptability to temperature conditions at germination time than the two temperate varieties tested.

Soil Microbiology

Using the acetylene-reduction method, we found that fixation of atmospheric nitrogen is more active in flooded soil than in non-flooded soil, and in soil with rice plants than in unplanted soil. Aerobic N_2 -fixing bacteria other than azotobacters were isolated from the rice rhizosphere and identified.

Tracer experiments showed that the oxidized layer of submerged soils has high nitrification activity. Coating nitrogen fertilizers with nitrification inhibitors prevented some losses due to nitrification following denitrification.

Under greenhouse conditions, we found that one-fourth of the fertilizer nitrogen applied to flooded soils is immobilized and one-half is used by rice plants by harvest. Adding organic materials to soil increased the amount of immobilized nitrogen and decreased the amount of nitrogen taken up by plants. Rice plants use more untagged nitrogen, from either the soil or the atmosphere, at later stages of growth.

Even in neutral soils, organic acids at rates as low as 5 mmole/kg soil retarded the growth of rice plants. Amending soils with green manure caused various organic acids to reach toxic levels. But applying ammonium sulfate largely counteracted the harmful effects of adding organic material to flooded soil.

Chemical reduction in flooded soil is mostly carried out by micro-organisms. We isolated some bacteria from the rice rhizosphere which were able to reduce nitrate, manganese, and iron, in that order.

In studies on insecticides considered to be persistent, we found that BHC, DDT, methoxychlor, and heptachlor are biodegradable in flooded soil. A soil bacterium isolated from soil was able to degrade the chemicals under anaerobic conditions.

We also succeeded in isolating a bacterium which actively degrades diazinon in paddy water.

Atmospheric nitrogen fixation

Fixation in the rice field. The atmospheric nitrogen that diffuses into soil is limited to a thin layer at the surface. Although soil microorganisms in the surface soil may fix nitrogen, most rice roots are located in the anaerobic soil environment below the oxidized layer. Last year (Annual Report 1969), using the acetylene-reduction method, we showed that N_2 -fixing bacteria inhabit the rice root zone. Since the rice plant is able to transport air to its roots, enough atmospheric nitrogen may be transported into the rice rhizosphere for N_2 -fixation by bacteria. If so, the interface of the root-soil system may be an important site of nitrogen fixation by rice plants.

A field experiment was carried out to study the effect of rice plants on the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen under upland and flooded soil conditions using the acetylene-reduction method to indicate N_2 -fixing activity. The experiment

1. N_2 -fixing activity in cropped (rice variety IR20 transplanted Apr. 27) and uncropped field soils under lowland and upland conditions measured by $C_2H_2-C_2H_4$ assay. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

showed that flooded soil has a greater capacity to fix atmospheric nitrogen than upland soil and that soils planted with rice have more N_2 -fixing capacity than unplanted soils (fig. 1). The N_2 -fixing activity of lowland soil started to increase when the rice plants were in the reproductive stage and reached a maximum in the ripening stage. The effect of rice roots (rhizosphere effect) on the activity was prominent under flooded conditions.

To estimate the amount of N_2 which can be fixed by planted soil, the isotope ^{15}N method was carried out simultaneously with the acetylene-reduction method at the ripening stage of flooded rice. Using the isotope ^{15}N method the N_2 -fixation in the soil measured 0.016, 0.048, and 0.059 atom percent excess ^{15}N after incubating 10 g soil for 1, 3, and 5 days respectively. The nitrogen fixed in the soil was 2.61 $\mu\text{g/day}$ after 1 day of incubation, 2.54 $\mu\text{g/day}$ after 3 days, and 2.59 $\mu\text{g/day}$ after 5 days. Using the acetylene-reduction method nitrogen fixation in the soil measured 2.64 $\mu\text{g/day}$ after 5 hours of incubation. Thus the two methods showed good agreement. The theoretical conversion factor 3:1 ($C_2H_2:N_2$) can be used to estimate N_2 fixed in the soil.

When the rice was at the ripening stage, the soil samples in the planted field (spacing 20 x 20 cm) contained many root residues. The effect of rice roots on N_2 -fixation was high particularly in flooded soil. But it is not certain whether rice plants in the field provide enough N_2 to the rhizosphere for microbial N_2 -fixation. The data, however, may partly explain how nitrogen fertility is maintained in the flooded rice paddy.

The surface water might be an important site for N_2 -fixation in the field, because it is directly in contact with the atmosphere (78.03% N_2 by volume) and with sunlight which is necessary for photosynthetic N_2 -fixing algae and bacteria. Measured by the acetylene-reduction method the N_2 -fixing activity in the paddy water was generally higher in unplanted fields than in planted fields (fig. 2). The N_2 -fixing algae probably do not grow as well in paddy water with rice plants because of shading. The sharp fluctuations in N_2 -fixing activity in the unplanted field water are explained by observations of fluctuations in algal growth and probably in

2. N₂-fixing activity in paddy water of cropped (rice variety IR20 transplanted Apr. 27) and uncropped fields measured by C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay. IRRRI, 1970 wet season.

3. N₂-fixing activity of washed rice roots (rice variety IR20 transplanted Apr. 27) after being grown in lowland or upland soil measured by C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay.

growth of N₂-fixing bacteria that are associated with the algae. In the planted paddy water, N₂-fixing activity was higher during the early stages of rice plant growth than during the later stages because N₂-fixing algae grew well while the rice plants were still small. Twenty milliliters of paddy water taken on July 1 fixed 7.64 μg/day N measured by the isotope ¹⁵N method and 7.17 μg/day N by the acetylene-reduction method. Thus the conversion factor for estimating N₂ fixed in the surface water did not agree with the theoretical factor of 3:1.

The N₂-fixing activity of washed roots (variety IR20) was higher on a weight basis than that of the soil and water (fig. 3). The roots of flooded rice showed much higher N₂-fixing activity than rice roots grown in upland conditions. From a week after transplanting the N₂-fixing activity of the roots increased as the plants grew older. This confirmed previous findings with IR8 and Peta (1969 Annual Report). Despite the higher acetylene-reducing activity of roots, the amount of N₂ which they can fix per hectare in the field is small because they weigh little compared with the soil and water.

The total estimated atmospheric nitrogen in soil and water using the acetylene-reduction method during one cropping in the wet season is 54.8 kg/ha N in planted, flooded fields; 32.5

kg/ha in unplanted, flooded fields; 7.0 kg/ha in the planted, upland fields; and 3.0 kg/ha in unplanted, upland fields.

Nitrogen-fixing bacteria. We isolated bacteria from the rice rhizosphere on nitrogen-free sucrose agar. Among these, the characteristics of nine N₂-fixing bacteria were investigated. They were all Gram-negative, pleomorphic but generally rod-shaped, not acid-fast, and not spore formers. All were aerobic but they fermented carbohydrate and produced acids without forming gas. Taxonomical studies on the isolates indicated that these bacteria may belong to *Beijerinckia*, *Azotomonas*, *Pseudomonas*, *Flavobacterium*, and *Azotobacter*.

These bacteria may become abundant and active in the rice rhizosphere as plants grow older. The acetylene-reduction method to measure nitrogen fixation by washed rice roots should be used with caution, however. The apparent K_m (Michaelis constant) of the acetylene obtained was much higher than values obtained with known nitrogen-fixing bacteria although patterns of C₂H₄ formation at different P_{C₂H₂} values in soil samples were similar to the ones reported with the N₂-fixing bacteria. Ethylene production of rice-root samples in the C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay became linear after 1 hour of

Table 1. Recoveries of C₂H₄ added to reaction flasks with rice tissues. (Three grams of fresh IR8 leaves and stems and 6 g of IR8 roots at maximum tillering stage.)

Portion of rice plant in flask	Initial C ₂ H ₄ conc. (nmole)	C ₂ H ₄ recovery after 5-hr incubation (%)
None	57.0	90.5
Leaves	54.2	89.7
Stems	55.2	87.0
Roots	55.7	0.0

incubation at a $P_{C_2H_2}$ of 0.3 atm in both upland and lowland rice roots.

Ten grams of washed fresh rice roots fixed 10.6 $\mu\text{g N}$ after 24 hours incubation at 30 C and 16.6 $\mu\text{g N}$ after 48 hours, measured by the isotope ¹⁵N method. We found, however, that when we use washed roots for the C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay, the reduction product of the assay, C₂H₄, was also degraded by the bacteria. When C₂H₄ was added to the assay flask with rice roots the recovery was zero after a 5-hour incubation, but large amounts were recovered from flasks with rice leaves or stems (Table 1). The data indicated that washed rice roots have a mechanism to degrade C₂H₄.

An experiment with rice roots grown under sterile conditions indicated that C₂H₄-degrading activity is due to microorganisms attached to the root tissues: after 24 hours of incubation 100 percent of the C₂H₄ was recovered. C₂H₄ disappearance is not due to physical absorption as shown by the differences in data for autoclaved roots and untreated roots in Table 2. The C₂H₄-degrading activity becomes higher as the plant grows older. It is also higher in aerobic conditions

Table 2. Recovery of C₂H₄ added to reaction flasks with rice roots or with Maahas clay soil after incubation for 5 hours and 24 hours.

Treatment	Initial C ₂ H ₄ conc. (nmole)	After 5 hr		After 24 hr	
		C ₂ H ₄ (nmole)	Recovery (%)	C ₂ H ₄ (nmole)	Recovery (%)
<i>Flasks with rice roots^b</i>					
Autoclaved	680	680	100.0	676	99.3
TCA-treated	764	755	98.8	746	97.7
Untreated	702	126	18.0	74	10.5
Without roots	681	681	100.0	677	99.5
<i>Flasks with soil^c</i>					
Flooded	385	385	100.0	386	99.7
Upland ^a	357	353	98.9	356	99.7
Without soil	385	384	99.7	382	99.2

^a 50% moisture content. ^b 10 g at maximum tillering stage. ^c 10 g, dry weight basis.

than in anaerobic conditions. C₂H₄-degrading activity was not found in soil. These results show that the C₂H₂-C₂H₄ assay cannot be used to measure N₂-fixation by washed roots unless a way to obtain a precise conversion factor for converting C₂H₄ formed to N₂ fixed can be found.

Nitrogen transformation

Balance of organic and inorganic N in submerged soil. We examined the transformation of added nitrogen in submerged soils by determining total KCl-extractable nitrogen, residual nitrogen, and volatilized NH₃ using ¹⁵N-tagged nitrogen. Neither the amount of volatilized NH₃ nor the amount of nitrogen incorporated into the residual fraction was large enough to account for the magnitude of the decrease in KCl-extractable nitrogen during soil incubation. At zero days, most of the tagged nitrogen in (NH₄)₂SO₄ was recovered in the exchangeable form. Most of the tagged nitrogen in alanine, however, was recovered in the form of soluble organic nitrogen (total nitrogen in the KCl extract minus exchangeable ammonium). Sixteen days after the addition of nitrogen (Table 3) 25.6 percent of the added nitrogen from (NH₄)₂SO₄ and 17.7 percent from alanine was not recovered. The amount of residual nitrogen was consistently higher in the alanine-treated samples than in the samples treated with (NH₄)₂SO₄.

In another experiment the amount of chemically fixed ammonium was determined. After 4 weeks of incubation at 30 C the amount of chemically fixed nitrogen in the submerged soils was small: 14.3 ppm with (NH₄)₂SO₄, 6.3 ppm with alanine, and 10.5 ppm in the control. So, chemical fixation of added nitrogen is small and most of the residual nitrogen can be considered immobilized nitrogen.

These results suggested that nitrification and subsequent denitrification take place in submerged soils. Thus we investigated the transformation of ¹⁵N-labeled (NH₄)₂SO₄ coated with N-Serve, a nitrification inhibitor, in non-presubmerged and presubmerged soils. About 15 percent more added nitrogen was recovered

Table 3. Changes in the amount of tagged nitrogen in the different nitrogen fractions in flooded Maahas clay treated with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and alanine.

Incubation time (days)	Amount of tagged N recovered (ppm)				Recovery ^d (%)
	Total extractable ^a	Residual ^b	Volatilized NH_3^c	Total	
<i>Soil treated with $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$</i>					
0	397	18.2	0.0	415	100.0
4	393	28.4	0.2	422	101.4
8	370	32.6	0.2	403	96.8
12	344	40.7	0.2	385	92.5
16	275	34.1	0.2	309	74.4
<i>Soil treated with tagged alanine</i>					
0	362	53.4	0.0	415	100.0
4	316	55.0	1.1	373	89.7
8	314	62.7	5.5	382	91.8
12	285	74.0	6.5	366	88.1
16	263	68.1	8.4	342	82.3

^aTotal N in the KCl extract which includes exchangeable NH_4^+ and soluble organic N. ^bDetermined on the soil left after KCl extraction. ^cCumulative values. ^dBased on the total amount of tagged N at zero time.

from the non-presubmerged soil to which coated fertilizer was applied than from soil to which uncoated fertilizer was applied (Table 4). Soils treated with coated fertilizers had more exchangeable NH_4^+ than soils with uncoated fertilizer which accounts for the higher recovery of tagged nitrogen in the soil samples treated with coated fertilizer.

In presubmerged soils, a remarkable amount of nitrate accumulated with and without N-Serve (Table 4). Although the amount of nitrogen recovered was about the same for the inhibitor-coated and uncoated $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, the N-Serve inhibited nitrate production during the incubation period. Less denitrification occurred in the presubmerged soils probably because during presubmergence at 30 C microorganisms consumed most of the available organic materials in the soil. Nearly all denitrifying bacteria use nitrate as an electron acceptor when they metabolize organic materials. The amount of tagged nitrogen incorporated into the residual fraction, which is mostly immobilized nitrogen, was much higher in the non-presubmerged soils than in the presubmerged soils, indicating that in the presubmerged soils the energy source (organic substrate) was inadequate to support heterotrophic bacteria.

Nitrification in submerged soils. In an experiment to confirm nitrification in submerged soils, 10 g

of Maahas clay soil was presubmerged for several months and then placed in 500 ml Erlenmeyer flasks and flooded with 200 ml of water containing 400 ppm N as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. The nitrate produced during incubation was analyzed colorimetrically with the phenoldisulfonic-acid method. After incubating the samples for 30 days, a large amount of nitrate, 123 ppm, was produced. We also inoculated autoclaved Maahas clay soil with pure nitrifying bacteria, *Nitrosomonas europaea*. In the experiment we found that *N. europaea* was able to oxidize ammonium to nitrate in the submerged soil.

To examine the effect of water depth on nitrification in submerged soil, soil was flooded with a solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ to levels of 0.5, 5, and 10 cm above the soil surface. A portion of the solution was analyzed for nitrate 0, 3, 6, 12, and 18 days after incubation. The effect of water depth on the denitrification was tested similarly except that a solution of KNO_3 was

Table 4. Effect of coating $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ with N-Serve on nitrogen transformations in submerged Maahas clay soil.

Incubation time (weeks)	Amount of tagged N recovered (ppm)				
	Exchangeable ammonium	Nitrate	Residual ^a	Total	Recovery ^b (%)
<i>Fertilizer uncoated, soil not presubmerged</i>					
0	407	2.9	13.8	424	100.0
1	369	2.3	34.9	406	95.9
2	337	2.1	40.8	380	89.6
3	326	3.2	52.3	381	90.0
5	171	13.4	53.8	238	56.1
<i>Fertilizer coated, soil not presubmerged</i>					
0	415	3.3	11.8	430	100.0
1	362	3.4	37.8	404	93.9
2	340	0.6	48.0	389	90.5
3	330	0.0	49.6	380	88.3
5	243	3.6	59.5	306	71.2
<i>Fertilizer uncoated, soil presubmerged</i>					
0	418	0.0	10.2	429	100.0
1	372	4.9	27.2	404	94.2
2	310	36.3	35.8	382	89.1
3	229	91.0	35.1	355	82.7
4	146	160.3	37.7	344	80.1
5	58	240.4	33.9	332	77.4
<i>Fertilizer coated, soil presubmerged</i>					
0	407	0.6	9.1	416	100.0
1	369	3.1	26.5	399	96.0
2	355	9.3	34.9	399	95.9
3	249	70.0	31.4	350	84.2
4	171	149.4	38.4	359	86.4
5	110	173.5	38.8	323	77.6

^aDetermined on the soil left after KCl extraction. ^bBased on the total amount of tagged N at zero time.

4. Transformation of tagged fertilizer coated with a nitrification inhibitor, AM or ST.

used instead of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Active nitrification was observed in the soils. After 18 days of incubation, the flask with 0.5 cm water had 5.8 mg N, the flask with 5 cm water had 4.9 mg N, and the flask with 10 cm water had 4.2 mg N. Slightly more nitrification occurred at a water level of 0.5 cm than at 5 and 10 cm. Nevertheless,

Table 5. Effect of soil depth on denitrification under submerged conditions.

Soil depth (cm)	Cumulative change in NO_3^- content (mg N/flask)			
	Incubation period (days)			
	3	6	9	12
	<i>Presubmerged soil</i>			
0.5	-0.1	+2.0	+0.9	+3.2
2.0	-2.9	-3.0	-6.9	-7.6
4.0	-3.2	-5.0	-7.9	-8.8
	<i>Soil not presubmerged</i>			
0.5	-2.2	-3.9	+0.7	+0.8
2.0	-10.4	-12.8	-14.9	-16.9
4.0	-23.2	-30.4	-35.7	-42.6

5. Effect of adding organic materials on the transformation of tagged nitrogen fertilizer in flooded soil.

there was no significant difference in nitrifying activity among any of the three water depths. No denitrification occurred at any of the three water levels.

We also studied the effect of soil depth on nitrification and denitrification in submerged soils. Presubmerged soil was placed in beakers to a depth of 0.5, 2, and 4 cm. A solution of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ or KNO_3 was added to the soils. The water level was kept at 5 cm above the soil surface. A portion of the solution was analyzed for nitrate 0, 3, 6, 9, and 12 days after incubation. In the 0.5-cm-deep soil, large amounts of nitrate accumulated: 1.26 mg N per flask after 12 days of incubation. After 12 days in soil 2 cm deep, only 0.067 mg N accumulated; in soil 4 cm deep only 0.95 mg N accumulated. The results do not necessarily mean that the nitrifying bacteria in the soil 2 cm and 4 cm deep were not functioning. The nitrate that formed may have been denitrified by denitrifying bacteria active

at those depths. The soils 2 cm and 4 cm deep showed denitrifying activity (Table 5). Also denitrification was more active in air-dried (non-presubmerged soil), probably because air-dried soil contains more available carbon for heterotrophic bacteria.

An experiment was carried out to determine to what extent the oxidized layer can develop in laboratory conditions. Nine pieces of glass cylinder (5.6 cm in diameter, 2.5 cm tall) were joined and one end was plugged with a rubber stopper. Maahas clay soil was collected from a reduced soil layer in a flooded field. The soil was placed in a glass cylinder after thoroughly mixing it with 100 ppm $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ containing 9.9 atom percent excess ^{15}N . The soil in the column was submerged under 2 cm of water and incubated at 30 C. At 4-week intervals, the exchangeable NH_4^+ , residual N, and total nitrogen recovery were measured in the soil in each section of the column by ^{15}N analysis.

By 8 weeks the oxidized layer developed mostly in the surface 2.5 cm and only slightly below that layer. From 0 to 2.5 cm deep, total recovery of tagged nitrogen was 101% at zero weeks, 65% at 4 weeks, and 60% at 8 weeks; from 2.5 to 5.0 cm the recovery was 101% at zero weeks, 97% at 4 weeks, and 85% at 8 weeks.

Two nitrification inhibitors, AM and ST, were tested in submerged soil. Figure 4 shows that both nitrification inhibitors retarded the nitrifying bacteria in submerged soil. The nitrogen recovery obtained by the isotope method indicates that AM prevented losses of 7.3 percent and ST prevented losses of 18.1 percent compared with the control soil after 5 weeks of incubation. In the field, the values would have been larger because nitrate in the soil would have been denitrified. Avoiding such nitrification losses after denitrification is important to rice farmers when they make basal or top-dressing applications of nitrogen.

Effect of incorporating organic materials. Rice root residues, rice straw, and weeds are incorporated in the paddy field before every crop. These organic materials influence the transformation of nitrogen fertilizer. To investigate the effect of organic materials on fertilizer nitrogen, green manure (dry powder of *Sesbania*

6. Accumulative uptake of total and tagged N by rice during growth as affected by addition of organic matter.

sp. containing 2.1% N) and cellulose powder were used in greenhouse experiments at a level of 0.5 percent. In addition, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ was applied at 1 g/pot N.

In 1 month, available nitrogen decreased rapidly, but the amount of immobilized nitrogen reached a maximum (fig. 5). The amounts of immobilized nitrogen were higher in the presence of organic materials. Most of the nitrogen applied with cellulose was immobilized in a month and seemed to remain unavailable to rice through harvest. Figure 6 indicates that rice plants take up more untagged nitrogen than tagged nitrogen as the plants grow older.

During rice plant growth about 25 percent of the tagged nitrogen was not recovered in all the treatments. The loss might take place in oxidized zones such as the thin surface soil layer of the rhizosphere. However, despite the losses of tagged ^{15}N , recoveries of total nitrogen at

harvest were high, particularly in presence of organic materials, indicating that the soil-plant system gains nitrogen from other sources (Table 6).

A-values, estimates of available soil nitrogen, were 157 ppm in the control soil, 303 ppm in soil treated with green manure, and 247 ppm in the soil treated with cellulose. The *A*-value of the control was 11.9 percent of the total nitrogen in the soil, 21.2 percent in soils treated with green manure, and 20.0 percent in soils treated with cellulose.

Organic matter transformation

Flooded soil is mostly in an anaerobic environment. Incorporating organic materials into the soil can adversely affect rice plant growth because anaerobic soil bacteria ferment the organic materials to phytotoxic substances. Organic acids have been widely studied and are reported to be harmful to rice at low pH. The soil pH, however, generally becomes nearly neutral within several weeks after a soil is submerged. We studied the effect of organic acids on the rice plant growth in nearly neutral soil.

Three soils, Maahas clay, Pila clay loam, and Casiguran sandy loam, were kept in the greenhouse for a month under flooded conditions

Table 6. Effect of organic materials on recovery of total nitrogen in flooded soil.

Weeks after transplanting	Total nitrogen recovered					
	Without fertilizer			With N fertilizer ^a		
	Soil (g/pot)	Plant (g/pot)	Total (%)	Soil (g/pot)	Plant (g/pot)	Total (%)
	<i>Control</i>					
0	13.1	—	100.0	14.6	—	100.0
4	11.8	0.16	90.7	12.1	0.60	87.0
8	11.4	0.31	89.3	11.7	1.08	87.9
17	12.1	0.57	96.3	13.0	1.35	98.7
	<i>Green manure</i>					
0	14.3	—	100.0	14.7	—	100.0
4	12.9	0.14	91.2	13.6	0.64	97.1
8	11.9	0.49	86.7	12.3	1.33	92.6
17	12.4	0.97	94.0	14.1	1.69	107.5
	<i>Cellulose</i>					
0	12.4	—	100.0	14.4	—	100.0
4	11.9	—	95.9	13.2	0.15	92.2
8	12.0	0.03	96.6	12.9	0.42	92.4
17	12.6	0.07	105.0	13.6	0.88	100.2

^aAmmonium sulfate at 1 g N/pot (10 kg soil).

7. Effect of organic acids applied at 5 and 10 mmole/kg soil on rice plant growth measured 22 days after transplanting in three submerged Philippine soils.

before use. Each organic acid—formic, acetic, propionic, butyric, and iso-butyric—was separately added to the soil at 5 and 10 mmole/kg soil after adjusting the pH to 7.0 with 0.1 N NaOH. The initial soil pH values at transplanting were 7.1 for Casiguran, 7.2 for Maahas, and 7.5 for Pila.

Each organic acid caused toxic effects at 5 mmole (fig. 7). The effects were accentuated at 10 mmole even though the soils were near neutrality. The acids that had high molecular weights tended to retard rice growth more. Application of ammonium sulfate greatly reduced the injurious effect of the organic acids. Table 7 shows the effect of adding ammonium sulfate on damage to the rice plant by organic acids in Maahas clay soil.

Application of other organic materials to flooded soils retarded the growth of rice, but the application of ammonium sulfate largely prevented the growth retardation under greenhouse conditions.

The amounts of organic acids produced in soil amended with green manure were toxic within 1 to 2 weeks. Under anaerobic conditions the production of organic acids was much higher than under submerged conditions.

The effect of ammonium sulfate on organic acid production was tested in Maahas clay soil and Libon soil from Albay, Philippines. Addition of ammonium sulfate retarded the formation of propionic and butyric acids, but increased the amount of acetic acids after 5 days of incubation (Table 8).

Mineral reduction

Microorganisms are the direct agents of chemical reduction in flooded soil. Reduction of minerals does not occur in sterilized soil; on the other hand adding organic matter, which is the energy source for most bacteria, greatly enhances the reduction of nitrate manganese, iron, sulfate, carbonate, phosphate, and other minerals.

Mineral-reducing bacteria are commonplace in soil and water environments. They are mostly facultative anaerobic bacteria which use oxidized components of the soil as electron acceptors for respiration when molecular oxygen is absent. As the bacteria reduce the oxidized components of the soil, they produce various kinds of reduced compounds.

Iron reduction was examined in three soils: Maahas clay (pH 5.6; organic matter, 2.4%; active Fe, 2.17%; active Mn, 0.15%), a clay soil from Kedah, Malaysia (pH 4.1; organic matter, 5.6%; active Fe, 0.58%; active Mn, 0.003%), and a silt loam from Boeun Gun, Korea (pH 5.0; organic matter, 2.7%; active-Fe, 0.46%; active Mn, 0.0034%). In the first 2 weeks, iron reduction was highest in the Malaysian soil, followed in order by Maahas clay, and the Korean soil (fig. 8). Malaysian soil had 7.3×10^4 iron-reducing bacteria per gram of soil, Maahas clay soil had 5.4×10^4 , and the Korean soil had 0.9×10^4 . After 3 weeks of incubation, however, the number of bacteria was no longer correlated with the amount of iron reduced. Adding hematite to the soil increased the amount of reduced iron after 3 weeks of incubation most in

Table 7. Effect of ammonium sulfate on rice plant growth (variety IR8, 28 days after transplanting) in Maahas clay soil to which organic acids have been added at 10 mmole/kg soil.

Organic acid added	Oven dry weight (g/plant)			
	Control		Nitrogen added ^a	
	Tops	Roots	Tops	Roots
None	4.56	1.70	5.12	1.47
Formate	4.27	1.24	4.16	0.87
Acetate	3.70	1.40	4.02	0.92
Propionate	3.54	1.00	3.79	0.90
Butyrate	2.99	0.90	4.70	1.10
Iso-butyrate	2.16	0.60	4.01	0.96
Valerate	1.20	0.29	3.04	0.82

^aAmmonium sulfate at 10 g/pot (10 kg soil).

Table 8. Effect of ammonium sulfate on accumulation of acetic (Ac), propionic (Pr), butyric (Bu) acids in Maahas clay soil and Libon soil amended with green manure (1% ground leaves of *Sesbania* sp.) under anaerobic conditions.

Incubation time (days)	Accumulation of organic acids (mmole/kg soil)					
	Maahas			Libon		
	Ac	Pr	Bu	Ac	Pr	Bu
	<i>Green manure</i>					
0	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2
3	25.0	2.7	2.8	42.4	5.5	4.3
5	29.2	4.1	0.6	41.1	12.5	4.8
7	10.6	3.1	0.3	12.3	12.4	3.0
9	5.6	2.7	0.3	4.6	12.0	<0.2
13	1.0	0.2	<0.2	2.1	4.1	<0.2
	<i>Green manure + (NH₄)₂SO₄^a</i>					
0	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2	<0.2
3	25.9	2.6	3.0	42.4	6.0	4.4
5	37.3	<0.2	<0.2	44.3	6.8	<0.2
7	21.5	<0.2	<0.2	28.1	<0.2	<0.2
9	6.9	<0.2	<0.2	25.1	<0.2	<0.2
13	1.0	<0.2	<0.2	16.7	<0.2	<0.2

^a200 ppm N solution was added to 10 g soil.

the Malaysian soil, a little in Korean soil, but not at all in Maahas clay.

Mineral reduction in the rhizosphere, where rice roots provide organic material and stimulate microbial activities, could influence the mineral uptake by rice plant. Twenty isolates of denitrifying bacteria from IR8 roots and flooded soils, and six pure cultures known as nitrate reducers were examined for the mineral reduction. Among these, 10 bacteria reduced both manganese and iron in addition to nitrate. Pure cultures of *Aerobacter aerogenes* and *Bacillus licheniformis* also reduced manganese, iron, and nitrate. Thus these bacteria may

possess an enzyme system that enables them to reduce NO_3 , Mn, and Fe in sequence under anaerobic conditions.

Pesticide residues

Anaerobic organochlorine degradation. We reported in previous annual reports that in four Philippine soils, chlorinated insecticides persist under upland conditions but not under flooded conditions. A soil bacteria identified as *Clostridium* sp. was found to degrade γ -BHC and DDT under anaerobic conditions. This year we found that the bacteria can also degrade methoxychlor and, to a lesser extent, heptachlor (Table 9). Since the three insecticides have different molecular structures the bacteria must have an enzyme system which can degrade a variety of compounds by reductive dechlorination. The bacterial degradation of γ -BHC was studied

8. Iron reduction in three soils during incubation under anaerobic conditions (N_2 atmosphere).

using γ -BHC labeled with ^{14}C . Total radioactivity in the reaction flask was small after 8 hours of incubation: The recovery of ^{14}C in the organic solvent, which was mostly γ -BHC, was small (Table 10). The amount of ^{14}C in the water fraction increased gradually during the incubation, but was too small to account for the loss of γ -BHC.

To determine how the ^{14}C labeled γ -BHC was lost, the reaction flask was connected to a trap containing alkali solution, to trap CO_2 , and a trap containing hexane, to trap volatilized γ -BHC. We found that only a minute amount of γ -BHC was converted to CO_2 , that 8.7 percent of the volatilized γ -BHC was trapped in the hexane solution, and that 17.5 percent of the γ -BHC remained in the reaction flask.

Qualitative analysis of the compounds in the hexane trap by gas chromatography showed the presence of γ -BHC and the unknown metabolite reported previously (1968 Annual Report). The deficit of ^{14}C in the biodegradation of γ -BHC must have been the result of conversion to methane or some other gaseous compound which could not be recovered in the experiment.

Table 9. Degradation of γ -BHC, methoxychlor, and heptachlor by soil bacteria under anaerobic conditions.

Incubation time (hr)	Insecticide recovered (ppm)				
	γ -BHC		Methoxychlor	Heptachlor	
	Living cells	Living cells	Control ^a	Living cells	Control ^a
0	10.8	7.4	9.2	12.8	15.5
2	7.4	0.4	8.3	11.3	15.5
24	1.4	0.2	7.2	8.2	15.3

^a Heat-killed cell.

Table 10. Recovery of γ -BHC labelled with ^{14}C during degradation by bacteria under anaerobic conditions.

Incubation time (hr)	Recovery of radioactivity (10^3 count/min)		
	Solvent fraction ^a	Water fraction ^b	Total
0	117.4	0.4	117.8
0.5	112.7	0.8	113.5
1.0	98.2	1.4	99.6
2.0	60.1	1.9	62.0
4.0	24.8	2.0	26.8
8.0	17.2	2.4	19.6

^aChloroform-ether (1:1). ^bTotal activity remaining after the extraction of chloroform-ether.

9. Persistence of endrin, DDT, heptachlor, and four isomers of BHC in sterilized and non-sterilized submerged Casiguran soil.

Organic material and biodegradation of insecticides. Previously (1968 and 1969 Annual Reports), we reported that organochlorine insecticides degrade faster in submerged soils, the higher the organic matter. We assumed that microbes in the soils with high organic matter content were more active than those in soils with less organic matter. To assess the role of microorganisms in the degradation of organochlorine insecticides, the persistence of DDT, heptachlor, endrin, and four isomers of BHC was tested in sterile and non-sterile submerged Casiguran soil (fig. 9).

Most of the DDT and heptachlor degraded in a week in the non-sterile soil but most of both insecticides was found even after 4 weeks in sterile soil.

Endrin was the most persistent chemical tested. Compared with other chemicals, there

was more difference between the recovery of endrin from the sterile soil and recovery from the non-sterile soil. The large difference suggests that autoclaving the soil influenced the fixation of endrin by modifying physical or chemical properties of the soil.

All isomers of BHC degraded in nonsterile soil, but not in sterile soil. Of the four isomers, α -BHC and γ -BHC degraded faster than the others.

Adding organic materials to Maahas clay soil generally stimulated the degradation of DDT and BHC, but adding glucose did not much influence the biodegradation of insecticides compared with other organic materials. On the other hand, adding organic materials to Casiguran soil did not stimulate the degradation of DDT and BHC (fig. 10). Adding glucose to

10. Degradation of DDT and two isomers of BHC in Maahas soil to which organic matter had been added.

the Casiguran soil retarded the degradation of BHC.

DDT converted to DDD, an intermediate of DDT degradation under anaerobic conditions, much faster in the presence of organic materials in Maahas clay soil (fig. 11). In Casiguran soil, DDD formed fast. The rapid conversion to DDD shows that DDT degraded fast. After 1 week of incubation, the amounts of DDD were, as in Maahas clay soil, lowest in the control soil followed in increasing order by the soils to which glucose, cellulose, and rice straw had been

added. Organic materials had distinct effects only early in the incubation. About 35 percent of the DDT added to the Casiguran control soil was converted to DDD after 6 weeks compared with 27 percent in the Maahas control soil.

These results indicate that organic materials enhance degradation of BHC and DDT in Maahas clay soil. In Casiguran soil which has a high organic matter content, however, effects of the additional organic materials on the disappearance of BHC and DDT were not distinct in the experiment.

Diazinon-degrading bacteria in paddy water. A bacterium which is able to degrade diazinon as a sole carbon source was isolated from paddy water using an enrichment culture method. An experiment showed that within 3 days, the bacterium degraded all diazinon added (30 ppm) to paddy water or a mineral medium solution.

Algae control

Results of screening several agricultural chemicals for use as algicides in rice paddy fields showed that Dichlone 50 WP (50% wettable powder) can control production of algal masses. We conducted a field trial to study the effect of the chemical on establishing rice seedlings. The chemical was applied in a direct-seeded rice field at 6 kg/ha (active ingredient). Copper sulfate at the same rate was used as a control. The average number of seedlings (IR8) 24 days after seeding was 90/sq m in the untreated control, 190/sq m in plot treated with copper sulfate, and 288/sq m in the plot treated with Dichlone 50 WP.

11. DDD formation during degradation of DDT (15 ppm DDT which is equivalent to 13.5 ppm DDD was added to the soil) in submerged Maahas and Casiguran soils amended with organic materials.

Statistics

Studies towards the improvement of experimentation techniques in rice were continued with emphasis on the sampling and measurement techniques of yield components and protein content.

Surveys in farmers' fields included the measurement of plant characters for prediction of rice yields and the evaluation of the variability in protein content.

The department's service functions continued to increase. With the recent use of more complex designs the department became increasingly involved also in the interpretation of experimental results.

Field plot technique

Unplanted borders. As a continuation of previous studies on the effects of unplanted borders, we collected data on plant height, tiller number and straw weight at different growth stages, and yield components in addition to data on grain yields. For all characters measured, the outermost row differed significantly from the inner rows (Tables 1 and 2). Even as early as 30 days after transplanting, unplanted borders had significant effects on both plant height and tiller number. In the second outermost row, all characters except plant height, number of filled grains per panicle, and panicle length were affected significantly. Since unplanted borders alter the growth characteristics of the border plants in almost all aspects even at early growth stages, measurements of plant characters should not be made from the two border rows of plots adjacent to an unplanted area at any growth stage.

Missing hills. Previous experiments (1969 Annual Report) showed that all hills immediately adjacent to a missing hill gave higher grain yields than normal hills. This year experiments were undertaken to establish an adjustment procedure to correct for missing hills, to examine the effects of missing hills at different dates of occurrence, and to evaluate methods of replanting missing hills.

Correction for missing hills. Experiments were conducted to find out how many surrounding hills are affected, to estimate how much of the

Table 2. Plant height and number of tillers of border rows adjacent to unplanted area at different growth stages, IR22, unfertilized. IRRI, 1970 dry season. (Data are averages of 22 replicates.)

Days after transplanting	Plant height (cm)			Tillers (no./sq m) ^a		
	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^b	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^b
30	51**	49	49	355**	300*	282
37	58**	56	56	394**	321*	305
44	62**	59	60	453**	329*	310
51	69**	64	63	517**	328*	305
58	78**	73	73	516**	322*	302
65	83**	82	82	519**	291*	269
73	84	83	84	529**	292**	267
80	84	83	83	527**	288**	266
87	83**	82	82	506**	282**	261

^aAt 87 days after transplanting, only productive tillers were counted. ^bAverage of three inner rows. **Significantly different from the center at the 1% level. *Significantly different from the center at the 5% level.

loss due to a missing hill is made up for by the increase in yield of adjacent plants, and to find out whether this effect varies with fertilizer level, variety, and season. We used IR22 and IR127-80-1-10, which differ in tillering capacity; two nitrogen levels, 0 kg/ha N and 120 kg/ha N; and a plant spacing of 25 x 20 cm.

The four hills immediately adjacent to the missing hill (positions A and B in fig. 1) always had higher grain yield and panicle number than normal hills (Table 3). The percentage increases, however, varied with variety, nitrogen level, and season. In the wet season, percentage increases in both grain yield and panicle number in the fertilized plots were lower than in the unfertilized plots. This pattern, however, was not observed in the dry season. In general, the effects of

Table 1. Grain yields and yield components of border rows of IR22 adjacent to an unplanted area in fertilized and unfertilized plots. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Character	0 kg/ha N			120 kg/ha N		
	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^a	Row 1	Row 2	Center ^a
Grain yield (t/ha)	11.74**	5.99**	5.76	13.04**	6.73	6.53
Panicle (no./sq m)	536**	320**	289	639**	338	337
Filled grains (no./panicle)	100**	83	85	97**	82	83
Unfilled grains (%)	7.7	7.9	7.4	8.6	11.5*	9.2
100-grain wt. (g)	2.21**	2.22**	2.28	2.23*	2.26	2.29
Panicle length (cm)	21.8**	20.3	20.4	21.1**	20.4	20.3
Panicle wt. (g)	2.60**	2.06**	2.16	—	—	—
Straw wt. (t/ha):						
At panicle initiation	3.40**	2.42	2.55	—	—	—
At heading	12.25**	7.22	6.48	—	—	—
At harvest	12.40**	6.00	5.79	15.08**	6.63**	6.32

^aAverage of three inner rows. **Significantly different from the center at the 1% level. *Significantly different from the center at the 5% level.

Table 3. Grain yields and number of panicles of plants (IR22 and IR127-80-1-10) surrounding a missing hill. IRRI, 1970.

Hill position ^a	IR22				IR127-80-1-10			
	Dry season		Wet season		Dry season		Wet season	
	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./plant)	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./plant)	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./plant)	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./plant)
	<i>0 kg/ha N^b</i>							
A	37.7**	16.3**	27.8**	14.0**	32.5**	8.1	27.9**	7.2**
B	33.5**	14.7**	27.0**	13.1**	33.2**	7.7	26.0**	7.1**
C	29.6	13.2	22.2	11.7*	30.0	7.6	23.1	6.6
D	28.7	12.5	20.4	10.2	30.6*	7.7	22.6	6.5
E	30.3*	13.4	21.9	11.0	28.7	6.8	21.3	6.0
Control	27.2	12.8	21.6	10.8	27.8	7.4	21.8	6.2
	<i>120 kg/ha N^c</i>							
A	48.8**	20.7**	28.3**	16.7**	41.5**	10.4**	30.0**	8.6**
B	42.6**	17.8**	25.7	15.7**	39.3**	9.1	27.1	8.0**
C	36.3	16.5	23.4	14.0	34.7	8.7	24.6	7.6
D	34.4	15.3	21.5	12.6*	34.4	8.6	25.4	7.5
E	36.1	16.3	21.0*	12.7*	37.3**	9.0	25.2	7.7
Control	34.9	15.9	23.9	13.5	32.9	8.8	24.7	7.4

^aRefer to fig. 1. ^b36 replicates. ^c72 replicates. **Significantly different from control at the 1% level. *Significantly different from control at the 5% level.

missing hills were greater with IR22, the higher tillering variety, than with IR127-80-1-10.

The percentage increases in panicle number were generally lower than the percentage increases in grain yield, indicating that yield components other than panicle number were probably affected. Of the four hills surrounding the missing hill, the two in the same row (position A) seemed to be more affected than those located in a different row (position B). Other hill positions (C, D, and E) were not consistently affected. In the dry season, position E, two hills away from and in the same row as the missing hill, gave some increases in grain yields for both varieties; in the wet season in IR22 under 120 kg/ha N, position E had lower yields.

The increase in grain yield of the surrounding plants did not always compensate for the loss caused by a missing hill. While the yield losses of IR22 caused by the missing hill were more than totally compensated for in the dry season in both the fertilized and unfertilized plots and in the wet season in the unfertilized plots, this did not happen in the IR127-80-1-10 plots.

These results show that plants surrounding a missing hill perform differently depending on variety, season, and fertilizer level. Therefore, a common procedure cannot be established to adjust for the presence of missing hills in rice experimental plots. Instead, all plants immedi-

ately adjacent to a missing hill should be excluded from the measurement of grain yield and other agronomic characters.

Date of occurrence of missing hills. In our previous investigations on the effects of missing hills, we considered only missing hills that occurred 1 week after transplanting. In actual field plots, missing hills may occur at any time.

In the dry season this year we evaluated missing hills occurring at eight different stages

1. Positions of the measured hills surrounding the missing hill (20 x 25 cm spacing).

2. Positions of the measured hills surrounding the missing hill (20 x 20 cm spacing). Hills marked C were used as control.

of growth, from 2 to 12 weeks after transplanting. The experiment was continued in the wet season and covered nine stages of occurrence from transplanting to 4 weeks later at intervals of 3 days. The missing hill was created by pulling out a plant from the center of each plot. IR22

Table 4. Grain yield, plant height, and panicle number of hills of IR22 (unfertilized) immediately adjacent to a missing hill which occurred at various dates. IRRI, 1970.

Date of occurrence (days after transplanting)	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Plant height (cm)
<i>Dry season^a</i>			
14	20.1**	10.9**	77
21	18.2	10.4	77
28	18.3	9.5	78
35	19.0	9.9	76
42	16.2	9.2	76
56	15.8	9.3	76
70	15.6	8.8	76
84	18.6	9.6	78
Normal hills ^b	16.6	9.2	77
<i>Wet season^c</i>			
0	19.6**	10.2**	95
4	18.8*	10.0**	95
7	19.0*	9.8*	94
10	21.2**	10.5**	95
14	18.9*	10.0**	95
17	19.0*	9.5	94
21	19.5**	9.8*	95
24	18.5	9.3	94
28	18.7	9.7	94
Normal hills ^b	17.3	9.0	94

^a Eight replicates. ^b Hills surrounded by living hills at all growth stages. ^c 21 replicates. **Significantly different from the normal hills at the 1% level. *Significantly different from the normal hills at the 5% level.

was used as the indicator variety; plants were spaced at 20 x 20 cm. No nitrogen was applied.

Data on grain yield, plant height, and panicle number were collected separately from each of the different hill positions surrounding the missing hill (fig. 2).

At all stages in both seasons, the performance of T₂ and T₃ did not differ significantly from the performance of the control hills. Thus, only the results from T₁, the four hills immediately adjacent to the missing hill, are presented in Table 4.

Plant height was not significantly affected. In the dry season, only when the missing hill occurred at 14 days after transplanting did the immediately adjacent hills have a significantly higher average grain yield and panicle number than the control. In the wet season, some significant effects on grain yield and panicle number were detected when missing hills occurred from transplanting to 21 days after transplanting. When the missing hill occurred later than 21 days after transplanting, the surrounding hills showed no appreciable differences.

These results indicate that all missing hills occurring within 3 weeks after transplanting should be identified. Hills immediately adjacent to these missing hills should be excluded from measurements of panicle number and grain yields. On the other hand, when missing hills occur later than 3 weeks after transplanting, the surrounding hills can be included in the harvest and the plot yield adjusted by assuming the yield of the missing hill to be equivalent to the average of the living hills.

Replanting missing hills. To reduce the number of missing hills in rice experimental plots, dead hills are usually replanted within 2 weeks after transplanting. Does the replanted hill perform differently from normal hills? To find out, experiments were conducted to compare the performance of hills replanted at varying dates with that of normal hills. At each date of replanting, the hill in the center of each plot was pulled out and replaced with seedlings taken from the original seedbed.

In unfertilized plots, we found no significant effect if the hill was replanted earlier than 13 days after transplanting (Tables 5a and 5b). In

fertilized plots, on the other hand, even the hill replanted as early as 7 days after transplanting showed significant differences from the normal hills.

The replanted hills had lower grain yields and fewer panicles, and were shorter than the normal hills. The percentage reduction in these three characters increased the later the replanting.

These results indicate that hills replanted 7 days after transplanting or later should be marked and excluded from the measurement of yield and other agronomic characters. Later than 7 days after transplanting, the only purpose of replanting dead hills is to protect the surrounding hills.

Number of plants per hill. Researchers sometimes use varying number of plants per hill in an experiment. A study was undertaken to find out if the precision of measurement of yield and yield components is affected by the different number of plants transplanted to a hill.

Experiments were conducted with IR22 in the 1970 dry and wet seasons involving the planting of one to three plants per hill without added nitrogen.

Variances among hills for tiller count increased considerably with the number of plants per hill (Table 6). This was partly because hills with more plants had more tillers (Table 7). For plant height, variances were not appreciably different except at the flowering stage (50 days after transplanting in the wet season) where the uniformity of flowering time was affected by the number of plants per hill.

Of all the yield components measured, only panicle number per hill and number of filled grains per panicle were significantly affected by the number of plants per hill (Table 8). Three plants per hill gave the highest panicle number and the lowest number of filled grains per panicle. The two components seem to offset each other, accounting for the nonsignificant differences in grain yields.

Table 5a. Grain yield, plant height, and panicle number of a replanted hill of IR22 as affected by the time of replanting. IRR1, 1970 dry season. (Data are averages of 10 replicates for 0 kg/ha N, and three replicates for 120 kg/ha N.)

Replanting (Days after transplanting)	0 kg/ha N			120 kg/ha N ^a		
	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Plant height (cm)
7	27.1	13.1	83	22.5*	13.0	92
11	25.5	12.2	83	20.5**	9.7**	94
15	9.1**	5.3**	73**	8.5**	6.7**	87*
19	10.3**	5.1**	72**	8.6**	5.0**	85*
23	7.8**	4.6**	68**	8.3**	4.7**	78**
27	5.2**	3.0**	65**	1.3**	2.0**	56**
Normal hills	26.2	12.6	84	33.0	15.1	96

**Significantly different from the normal hills at the 1% level. *Significantly different from the normal hills at the 5% level.

Table 5b. Grain yield, plant height, and panicle number of a replanted hill of IR22 as affected by the time of replanting. IRR1, 1970 wet season. (Data are averages of six replicates.)

Replanting (Days after transplanting)	0 kg/ha N			80 kg/ha N		
	Grain yield (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield ^a (g/hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Plant height (cm)
7	11.4	7.2	88	6.8	9.0	95
9	12.2	7.2	90	5.5*	8.8	85
11	10.4	7.5	87	5.5*	6.7**	89
13	8.4**	5.2**	83**	3.8**	5.0**	78**
15	8.9**	5.5*	84*	3.5**	5.2**	84*
23	3.5**	3.8**	77**	1.8**	2.5**	70**
Normal hills	12.7	8.0	88	8.5	11.0	91

^aThe low yields were due to heavy blast infestation. **Significantly different from control at the 1% level. *Significantly different from control at the 5% level.

Table 6. Variances in tiller number among hills of IR22 (unfertilized) measured at various growth stages as affected by the number of plants per hill. IRRI, 1970.

Days after transplanting	Plants (no./hill)			χ^2 -test ^a
	1	2	3	
<i>Dry season</i>				
20	0.637	1.571	2.216	71.8**
35	4.203	7.624	9.238	30.5**
50	5.943	8.769	11.254	19.5**
65	5.558	8.318	10.085	17.3**
80	4.786	6.105	8.430	15.8**
95	4.837	5.956	8.272	14.4**
<i>Wet season</i>				
20	0.939	1.294	2.151	69.1**
35	5.709	6.626	8.678	17.8**
50	4.970	4.656	7.083	20.5**
65	4.768	4.212	6.895	26.4**
80	4.232	3.724	6.157	27.4**

^aBartlett's test for homogeneity of variance. **Significant at the 1% level.

Table 7. Effect of number of plants per hill on tiller number and plant height of IR22 (unfertilized) measured at different growth stages. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Days after transplanting	Tillers (no./hill)				Plant height (cm)			
	Plants (no./hill)			LSD (5%)	Plants (no./hill)			LSD (5%)
	1	2	3		1	2	3	
20	2.1	2.8	3.6	0.4	36	38	38	ns
35	9.0	9.4	10.3	0.8	66	66	67	ns
50	8.2	8.1	9.1	0.7	72	75	78	3
65	7.6	7.5	8.6	0.6	89	89	89	ns
80	7.4	7.3	8.4	0.6	89	88	89	ns

These results indicate that the same number of plants per hill must be used in each experiment if the variability of the different measurements is to be kept at a minimum.

Residual effects of an unplanted alley. In rice experiments, plots usually are separated by unplanted alleys. These alleys facilitate the application of certain kinds of treatments and the gathering of data. At times the alleys may

also reduce the effects of inter-plot competition. The use of unplanted alleys, however, can be a source of additional soil variability in succeeding crops, since plants grown where an unplanted alley was previously may perform differently from those planted on a continually cropped area.

The residual effects of an unplanted alley were evaluated in an area previously used for three seasons. In the previous three seasons, unplanted alleys from 40 to 140 cm wide had been used to separate plots measuring 3 x 6 sq m. In all croppings, the location of each plot and of the intervening unplanted alleys had been kept unchanged. In our experiment this year we used IR22 and IR773A₁-36-2-1 as indicator varieties. Each was planted solidly to half of the area, with a 20- x 20-cm spacing.

Plants grown in the previously planted and unplanted areas differed significantly in grain yield, plant height, and panicle number for both varieties; in panicle length for IR22; and in weight of dry matter for IR773A₁-36-2-1 (Table 9). The unplanted alley of previous plantings definitely had some residual effects. This suggests that the use of unplanted alleys should be avoided in experimental fields that are to be cropped successively. If, however, unplanted alleys are needed, their size and location should be kept fixed in every planting.

Correcting for soil heterogeneity. Data from a uniformity trial can be used to reduce variability due to soil heterogeneity by adjusting yields of subsequent experiments conducted on the same site through the analysis of covariance. This procedure, however, is valid only if the fertility pattern remains fairly constant over time. To verify whether the fertility pattern remains constant, a uniformity trial was started in the

Table 8. Grain yields and yield components of IR22 (unfertilized) as affected by the number of plants per hill. IRRI, 1970 wet season. (Data are averages of six replicates.)

Plants (no./hill)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Unfilled grains (%)	Panicle length (cm)	100-grain wt. (g)
1	3.20	7.2	80	10.7	20.0	2.28
2	3.06	7.2	71	11.5	19.6	2.29
3	3.33	8.4	69	10.9	19.6	2.29
LSD (5%)	ns	1.0	9	ns	ns	ns

Table 9. Residual effects of unplanted alley: Comparison among grain yields, plant height, and yield components of two rice varieties grown on previously planted and unplanted areas. IRRI, 1970 dry season. (Data are averages of 10 replicates.)

Character	IR22			IR773A, -36-2-1		
	Previously unplanted	Previously planted	Difference	Previously unplanted	Previously planted	Difference
Grain yield (g/sq m)	741.0	641.8	99.2**	667.9	616.1	51.8**
Plant height (cm)	89.1	88.0	1.1*	81.1	79.4	1.7*
Panicles (no./hill)	15.5	14.0	1.5**	14.1	13.3	0.8*
Panicle length (cm)	23.1	22.7	0.4*	20.6	20.2	0.4
Unfilled grains (%)	7.1	8.2	-1.1	4.7	3.9	0.8
100-grain wt. (g)	2.4	2.4	0.0	2.7	2.7	0.0
Dry matter wt. (g/hill)	27.6	25.1	2.5	31.2	28.2	3.0

**Significant at the 1% level. *Significant at the 5% level.

1968 dry season and repeated for six consecutive crops. The same area, management, and cultural practices were employed in all plantings. Simple correlation coefficients between grain yields obtained from the same plots were computed for all combinations of the six crop seasons using plot sizes ranging from 1 to 36 sq m.

The correlation between grain yields from one crop to another was always high and significant (Table 10). Furthermore, the correlation coefficient did not tend to decrease as the time between any two croppings increased. This result confirms the persistence of soil heterogeneity in lowland paddy soil and the usefulness of uniformity data in the control of variability through adjustment of yields of succeeding plantings in the same area.

Applying this adjustment procedure to our data reduced all plot-to-plot variability considerably. For example, when the 1968 dry season data was used to adjust the yields of the 1970 wet season, variance was reduced by 42.4 percent in 16-sq m plots. Uniformity data seem to have a great potential for increasing the precision of field experiments with rice.

Sampling for yield components. In rice experiments, various characters related to grain yield often are measured. One common sampling procedure for measuring yield components is to select at random a number of hills from each plot and a few panicles from each of the chosen hills. To evaluate this sampling procedure, data on panicle length, grain weight, percentage of unfilled grains, and number of filled grains were collected from all panicles taken from 100

hills of IR8 planted in the 1969 wet season. Hills were spaced 20 x 20 cm apart and no nitrogen was applied. Each panicle in a hill was identified by the height of the tiller on which it was located.

The values of the yield components measured seemed to vary with the position of the panicle measured. Panicle length, number of filled grains, and weight of filled grains increased with the height of the tiller, while the percentage of unfilled grain decreased (fig. 3). That is, great variation occurred among panicles within a hill

Table 10. Correlation matrix for rice uniformity yield data from six successive crops on the same site. IRRI, 1968-1970.

Crop season	1968 wet season	1969 dry season	1969 wet season	1970 dry season	1970 wet season
<i>16-sq-m plot (n=48)</i>					
1968 dry season					
1968 wet season	0.8959**	0.6205**	0.5890**	0.8608**	0.6639**
1969 dry season		0.6673**	0.6069**	0.6748**	0.6236**
1969 wet season			0.7875**	0.8298**	0.6699**
1970 dry season				0.8351**	0.7825**
1970 wet season					0.6937**
<i>36-sq-m plot (n=24)</i>					
1968 dry season					
1968 wet season	0.9274**	0.7462**	0.6736**	0.8871**	0.7405**
1969 dry season		0.7585**	0.6766**	0.7417**	0.6558**
1969 wet season			0.8299**	0.8998**	0.7447**
1970 dry season				0.8566**	0.8645**
1970 wet season					0.7268**

**Significant at the 1% level.

for all the yield components measured. Thus, the usual method of taking random samples of panicles from a hill seems inappropriate.

An alternative would be to stratify the panicles according to their position in a hill. To evaluate the stratification procedure, the panicles from

each hill were grouped into upper, middle, and lower strata according to their individual heights. The differences among the mean values of all characters measured were highly significant (Table 11). The relative efficiency of stratification was 399% for panicle length, 279% for measure-

3. Relationships between some yield components of IR8 (unfertilized) and height of individual tillers in a hill. [RRR], 1969 wet season.

ments of grain weight, 103% for percentage of unfilled grains, and 241% for number of filled grains.

Variability in protein content

Farmers' fields. Surveys were conducted in the dry and in the wet seasons. For the dry season survey, 128 crop-cut samples of 1 sq m were taken from 32 sample farms. For the wet season survey, 144 samples were taken from 34 farms. Grain samples from these harvests were analyzed for protein content by the chemistry department. Estimates of the variance components for each season (Table 12) were obtained from analyses of variance of nested classification with unequal numbers in the subclasses.

All variances tended to be higher in the dry season than in the wet season. The rankings of the different variance components, however, remained the same for both seasons. In both seasons, the variance among farms was the highest, exceeding even that among varieties. Protein content seemed to be greatly affected by environmental factors. One important factor probably is the level of nitrogen fertilization. Of the 23 farms planting IR8 in the dry season, rice from the two farms that did not use any nitrogen had an average protein content of 7.5 percent, rice from the four farms applying 30 to 45 kg/ha N had an average protein content of 8.0 percent, and rice from the 17 farms using 50 to 85 kg/ha N had an average protein content of 8.1 percent. In previous experiments at the IRRRI experimental farm protein content increased as nitrogen fertilization was increased.

Experimental plots. The variability in protein content among hills and among panicles within a hill was examined. Protein content, number and weight of filled grains, percentage of unfilled grains, and 100-grain weight were measured for all panicles in each sample hill. Each panicle was identified by the height of its tiller.

For fertilized plots, protein content and height of tillers were negatively correlated (fig. 4). No significant association was found in unfertilized plots. Protein content and other yield com-

Table 11. Mean values of yield components of IR8 (unfertilized) determined from three panicle positions in the hill. IRRRI, 1969 wet season. (Data are averages of all panicles from 100 hills.)

Panicle position	Grain wt. (g/panicle)	Unfilled grains per panicle (%)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)
Upper	3.1	12.4	22.7	106.5
Middle	2.7	14.0	22.0	93.4
Lower	2.0	15.9	20.2	67.4
LSD (1%)	0.1	1.5	0.5	4.0

ponents varied considerably less in unfertilized than in fertilized plots. The variance among hills within a plot was 0.1759 (7.1% of the mean) for 0 kg/ha N plots and 2.0999 (16.8% of the mean) for 120 kg/ha N plots; the variance among panicles within a hill was 0.1203 (5.9% of the mean) for 0 kg/ha N plots, and 4.9119 (25.6% of the mean) for 120 kg/ha N plots. Similar trends were obtained for all the yield components measured. This partly explains the great differences in protein content within a hill in fertilized plots, where protein content was negatively correlated with number and weight of filled grains ($r = -0.7040^{**}$), weight of filled grains ($r = -0.7355^{**}$), and 100-grain weight ($r = -0.8750^{**}$); and positively correlated with percentage of unfilled grains ($r = 0.8606^{**}$).

Apparently a high sampling error was involved in taking grains from individual panicles in the sample hills for protein determination. One way to reduce the variation within a hill is to stratify the panicles according to the height of individual tillers. For the fertilized plots, the relative efficiency of stratification was 237 percent using two strata per hill, while for unfertilized plots no gain from stratification was found.

Table 12. Estimates of the components of variance in protein content of rice from farmers' fields. Laguna, Philippines, 1970.

Variance component	Dry season		Wet season	
	Estimate ^a	df ^b	Estimate ^a	df ^b
σ_v^2 (variety)	0.2531 (6.3)	4	0.1584 (5.2)	5
σ_f^2 (farm within variety)	0.7254 (10.6)	27	0.2599 (6.6)	28
σ_p^2 (paddy within farm)	0.1100 (4.1)	32	0.0908 (3.9)	34
σ_c^2 (cut within paddy)	0.3281 (7.2)	64	0.2494 (6.5)	68

^aFigures in parentheses are the variances as percentages of the mean. ^bDegrees of freedom.

4. Effect of panicle position (represented by height of individual tillers) on protein content of brown rice. IRRI, 1970.

Another source of variability in measuring protein content in experimental plots is competition effects. Three experiments on interplot competition conducted in the 1969 dry season were sampled for protein analysis. One experiment examined the effects of different widths of unplanted alley between plots. The two border rows adjacent to the unplanted alley always gave higher protein content than the inner row (Table 13). The differences however were significant only where the unplanted alleys were 100 cm or 140 cm wide, not where they were 60 cm wide.

A second experiment examined the effects of nitrogen competition by measuring the differences between protein content of the control (border rows adjacent to similarly fertilized plots) and protein content of border rows adjacent to plots receiving different rates of nitrogen. The outermost row of plots that received 0 kg/ha N and that were adjacent to plots that received 60 kg/ha N had a significantly higher protein content than its control (7.8% and 7.4%, respectively). Likewise, the

protein content of the outermost row of plots that received 60 kg/ha N adjacent to the unfertilized plots was significantly lower than the protein content of its control (7.8% and 8.1%, respectively). The second outermost row was affected similarly.

A third experiment examined the effects of varietal competition. When adjacent plots were planted with different varieties, the protein content of border rows was affected (Table 14). Border rows of fertilized and unfertilized Peta plots had significantly lower protein content and higher grain yield than the center rows, regardless of whether the adjacent plots were planted to IR8 or to IR127-80-1-10. On the other hand, the protein contents of border rows of fertilized IR8 and IR127-80-1-10 plots adjacent to Peta increased. Their corresponding grain yields, however, were reduced due to shading by Peta. For all varieties, the magnitude of the effects in the unfertilized plots was less than the magnitude in the highly fertilized plots. Only with Peta were significant varietal competition effects found in unfertilized plots.

Table 13. Mean protein content of the brown rice of IR8 (120 kg/ha N applied) in border rows adjacent to varying widths of unplanted alley (average of 10 replicates). IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Width of unplanted alley (cm)	Protein content (%)		
	Row 1	Row 2	Row 3
60	8.3	8.4	8.1
100	9.1**	8.7**	8.2
140	9.0**	8.5*	8.1

**Significantly higher than the corresponding row 3 at the 1% level. *Significantly higher than the corresponding row 3 at the 5% level.

Results from the three experiments on competition effects indicate that protein content should not be measured in grain from plants in the outermost rows of a plot adjacent to unplanted borders, to plots planted with different variety, or to plots receiving different nitrogen level.

Prediction of rice yields

For the last 2 years, surveys of farmers' fields have been made in Laguna, Philippines to evaluate a forecasting procedure based on observations and physical measurements at different growth stages of a rice crop. At each sample farm, two paddies were selected at random and in each paddy two cuts, each 1 x 1 sq m, were randomly taken. Measurements and observations were made 50, 75, and 92 to 100

days after transplanting. All data were subjected to stepwise regression analyses to identify the minimum number of measurements that allows a satisfactory prediction of yield.

At 50 and 75 days after transplanting, tiller number, plant height, and stem-borer and rat damage showed some promise for use in yield prediction. The multiple correlation coefficient between grain yield and these characters was 0.628** (n = 112) in the 1969 wet season and 0.750** (n = 128) in the 1970 dry season. In addition, we found that the percentage of tillers with three or more leaves allowed accurate prediction of the percentage of productive tillers even as early as the maximum tillering stage. These characters, however, seem to be more related to the number than to the weight of panicles. Yield prediction at these stages would therefore be significantly improved if a good indicator of grain weight per panicle could be found.

At 92 to 100 days after transplanting when some yield components could be measured, the contribution of panicle weight to the prediction of yield was significant. Observations of such general farm conditions as water depth and weed count also increased the accuracy of prediction.

These preliminary findings seem to indicate that predicting rice yield before harvest may be possible by measuring some plant characters and by observing the surrounding environment.

Table 14. Brown rice protein content in border rows of three rice varieties as affected by varietal competition. IRRI, 1969 dry season.

Border variety	Protein content (%)							
	0 kg/ha N plot				120 kg/ha N plot			
	Row 1	Row 2	Row 3	Center ^a	Row 1	Row 2	Row 3	Center ^a
					<i>IR8</i>			
IR127-80-1-10	7.2	7.3	7.3		7.9	7.7	7.7	
Peta				7.6	8.5**	8.6**	8.1	7.7
					<i>IR127-80-1-10</i>			
IR8	6.5	6.6	6.8		6.7*	6.9	7.1	
Peta				7.0	7.4**	7.4**	7.2	7.0
					<i>Peta</i>			
IR8	6.1**	6.3**	6.5**		6.6**	6.9**	7.9	
IR127-80-1-10	6.1**	6.4**	6.4**	6.8	6.7**	7.1**	7.4	7.7

^aAverage of four center rows. **Significantly different from the center at the 1% level. *Significantly different from the center at the 5% level.

Consultation and computational services

Consultation. Three major types of consultation services were rendered during 1970: Designing of experiments, interpretation of experimental data, and sampling for rice characters in replicated trials. Several complex designs (fractional factorial, split-plot with control in every main plot, and some lattices) were employed and found useful in agronomic experiments. The increased use of more complex designs created a greater demand for assistance in the interpretation of experimental results. Many problems

on sampling plants for yield components and protein content were tackled in cooperation with the researchers concerned.

Computation. Statistical analyses of 195 experiments and 16 surveys were made. There was an increasing number of requests for analysis of variance for characters used to supplement grain yield. In addition, correlation and regression analyses were frequently employed to examine the inter-relationship among different rice characters. The group-and-trend comparison technique to investigate the nature of treatment differences was also widely accepted.

Plant Pathology

Extensive data were obtained to confirm that rice varieties that have a broad spectrum of resistance to blast have stable resistance. New systemic fungicides tested for controlling blast gave promising results. Some studies on the epidemiology and biochemistry of blast were made.

A simple and efficient method for testing sheath blight resistance was developed. Studies showed that the nutrition of the fungus affects its pathogenicity and sclerotial morphology.

Ecological studies on the bacterial blight disease revealed significant interactions between the bacterium and the phages in the field. The fluorescein-antibody technique may be used for detecting bacterial cells. Studies on the survival of the bacterium on leaves with or without lesions and the effect of saprophytic bacteria on infection were begun. Attempts were made to develop media for the growth of single cells and to develop a selective medium for *Xanthomonas oryzae*.

A new strain of tungro virus, which incites narrow leaves on the infected plant, was found. Other studies of tungro disease were carried out on: determining the effect of temperature on disease transmission, investigating the effect of chemicals on the infectivity of the viruliferous insect, and examining the adaptability of the vector to insect-resistant varieties.

The resistant line of *Oryza nivara* remained the most resistant to grassy stunt disease. Other studies included various aspects of host, vector, and disease agent.

A study on the inheritance of resistance to grassy stunt suggested that the resistance is essentially governed by a single pair of genes.

Resistance to blast

The international blast nurseries. During the past 7 years, two sets of several hundred rice varieties have been tested for blast reaction in 25 countries. In more than 200 trials at these localities at different times, some varieties consistently showed a broad spectrum of resistance to blast. These varieties are the best sources of resistance for a breeding program (Table 1).

New races of *Pyricularia oryzae*. From the several hundred artificial inoculations made during the year, 48 new races were identified by the Philippine differentials (Table 2), bringing the total number of races identified in the Philippines to 198. Twenty-two new races were differentiated by the international set of differential varieties: IA-33, -37, -38, -42, -49, -69, -72, -86, -87, -103, -104, -120, -127, IB-15, -42, -46, -47, -62, IC-8, -14, ID-6, and IE-8, according to the international standardized race numbers.

Stable resistance of Tetep and Carreon. Preliminary results (1969 Annual Report) showed that varieties such as Tetep and Carreon that have a broad spectrum of blast resistance remain stable in resistance to blast. Only a few lesions were produced even when the fungus races isolated from these varieties were inoculated back to the varieties in the greenhouse or in the blast nursery. The reason is that the fungus changes into many new races as it multiplies and the varieties possessing a broad spectrum of resistance are resistant to most of the new races. Since only a small portion of the conidial population is pathogenic few lesions are formed.

Six isolates from Tetep and one from Carreon were tested. Forty-five to 189 single conidial subcultures from each of the seven isolates were inoculated to Tetep and Carreon as well as to the 18 race differential varieties. Variety Khao tah haeng 17 (KTH) served as a susceptible control. Each of the isolates separated into many new races with different pathogenicities

Table 1. The most resistant varieties selected from the International Blast Nurseries. 1964 to 1970.

Variety	Tests (no.)									
	1964-1965		1966-1967		1968-1969		1970		1964-1970	
	Total	Susceptible	Total	Susceptible	Total	Susceptible	Total	Susceptible	Total	Susceptible
	<i>Group I^a</i>									
Tetep	22	2	59	0	62	2	23	1	199	5
Nang chet cuc	39	2	49	2	63	3	23	0	176	7
Tadukan	56	3	57	2	63	5	23	0	201	10
R 67	51	4	51	2	63	1	21	3	188	10
C46-15	56	2	60	3	63	4	22	4	203	13
CI 7787	50	4	59	2	63	4	20	2	194	12
Pah Leuad 29-8-11	47	4	59	4	59	4	20	2	187	14
D 25-4	31	3	60	6	64	3	23	2	180	14
Trang Cut L. 11	27	4	50	5	64	2	23	0	166	11
Pah Leuad 111	18	2	55	5	63	3	22	2	160	13
	<i>Group II^a</i>									
Mamoriaka	—	—	32	0	63	0	22	1	117	1
Huan-sen-goo	—	—	32	1	63	1	21	0	116	2
Dissi Hatif (DH2)	—	—	32	0	63	1	22	2	117	3
Carreon	—	—	31	0	62	3	22	0	115	3
Pah Leuad 29-8-11	—	—	31	1	61	0	22	2	114	3
Ram Tulasi	—	—	32	0	60	1	22	2	114	3
C46-15	—	—	30	1	61	1	23	1	112	3
Ram Tulasi sel	—	—	33	0	60	2	19	1	112	3
Ca 435/B/5/1	—	—	31	1	62	2	22	1	115	4
DNJ60	—	—	29	1	62	1	22	2	113	4

^a The 258 varieties in Group I consisted of 38 race differentials and leading commercial varieties of various countries. The Group II consisted of 332 varieties selected from 8,230 varieties tested at IRRI.

Table 2. Reactions of Philippine differential varieties to new pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* (●=resistant; S=susceptible).

Philippine differential variety	Reaction to															
	P-151	P-152	P-153	P-154	P-155	P-156	P-157	P-158	P-159	P-160	P-161	P-162	P-163	P-164	P-165	P-166
Kataktara	S	S	●	●	S	S	●	●	S	●	●	S	S	●	S	S
CI 5309	S	S	●	●	S	S	●	●	S	●	●	S	●	●	S	S
Chokoto	S	S	●	●	S	●	●	●	●	S	S	●	●	S	S	S
Co 25	S	S	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S
Wagwag	S	●	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	●	●	S	●	●	●	●
Pai-kan-tao	●	●	●	S	●	●	●	S	●	●	●	S	●	S	●	●
Peta	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Raminad Str. 3	●	S	S	S	●	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	S
Taichung TCWC	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	●	●	S
Lacrosse	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	●	S	●	S	S	●	●
Sha-tiao-tsao(s)	●	●	●	S	●	S	●	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	●	S
Khao tah haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

Philippine differential variety	Reaction to															
	P-167	P-168	P-169	P-170	P-171	P-172	P-173	P-174	P-175	P-176	P-177	P-178	P-179	P-180	P-181	P-182
Kataktara	S	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S
CI 5309	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	●
Chokoto	S	●	S	S	●	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	●	●
Co 25	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	●	S
Wagwag	●	●	●	●	S	●	●	●	S	●	●	S	S	●	●	S
Pai-kan-tao	●	●	●	●	S	●	●	S	●	S	●	●	●	●	●	●
Peta	●	●	S	●	S	S	●	S	●	S	S	S	S	●	●	S
Raminad Str. 3	S	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	●	S
Taichung TCWC	●	●	●	●	S	S	S	S	●	S	●	●	S	●	S	S
Lacrosse	●	●	●	●	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	●	S
Sha-tiao-tsao(s)	●	●	●	●	S	●	S	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S
Khao tah haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S

Philippine differential variety	Reaction to															
	P-183	P-184	P-185	P-186	P-187	P-188	P-189	P-190	P-191	P-192	P-193	P-194	P-195	P-196	P-197	P-198
Kataktara	S	●	S	S	S	●	●	●	●	●	S	●	●	●	●	●
CI 5309	●	●	●	S	S	●	●	S	●	S	S	S	●	●	●	●
Chokoto	●	S	●	S	S	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Co 25	●	●	●	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	●
Wagwag	●	S	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	S	S	S	S
Pai-kan-tao	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Peta	S	●	S	●	●	S	S	●	●	S	S	●	S	●	●	S
Raminad Str. 3	●	●	●	●	●	S	●	S	S	S	●	●	S	●	●	●
Taichung TCWC	●	●	●	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	S	S	●
Lacrosse	●	●	●	●	S	S	●	S	S	S	S	S	●	S	S	●
Sha-tiao-tsao(s)	S	●	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Khao tah haeng 17	S	S	S	S	S	●	●	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

(Table 3). The number of lesions, number of pathogenic races, and number of pathogenic subcultures produced on Tetep, Carreon, and KTH by the subcultures of the seven isolates are shown in Table 4.

Significantly fewer lesions were produced on Tetep and Carreon than on KTH. Since the fungus continues to change, no special race is able to build up its population, and the resistant varieties remain resistant even though a few

lesions may appear. This is a new type of host-parasite relationship which promises stable resistance to blast.

Spore release of *Pyricularia oryzae*

Experiments were conducted to obtain information on the dispersal of the conidia of *Pyricularia oryzae* and its relationship to time

Table 3. Pathogenic races of *P. oryzae* derived from isolates FR-1, FR-1-138, FR-13, FR-78, FR-78-16, FR-79, and FR-80 grouped by number of Philippine differential varieties infected.

Differential varieties infected (no.)	FR-1		FR-1-138		FR-78		FR-78-16		FR-79		FR-80		FR-13	
	Races (no.)	Subc. (no.)												
1	—	—	—	—	—	—	1	1	—	—	—	—	—	—
2	1	1	—	—	—	—	1	1	—	—	—	—	2	11
3	1	1	—	—	—	—	6	6	—	—	—	—	6	68
4	4	4	—	—	—	—	7	9	5	12	—	—	7	45
5	7	15	2	2	—	—	5	7	1	1	—	—	9	31
6	5	22	5	11	—	—	7	10	5	17	2	3	8	12
7	1	61	1	19	—	—	6	12	2	11	1	37	6	14
8	3	34	3	12	2	3	6	13	2	2	2	3	4	7
9	3	17	1	4	3	6	7	11	3	5	2	2	1	1
10	—	—	—	—	1	33	3	17	1	4	—	—	—	—
11	2	3	—	—	2	3	2	13	—	—	—	—	—	—
12	1	2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Total	28	160	12	48	8	45	51	100	19	52	7	45	43	189

Table 4. Qualitative (pathogenic races) and quantitative (no. susceptible lesions) pathogenicity of monoconidial subcultures of *P. oryzae* isolates FR-1, FR-1-138, FR-78, FR-78-16, FR-79, and FR-80, from Tetep, and FR-13 from Carreon, on Tetep (T), Carreon (C), and Khao tah haeng 17 (KTH).

Isolate	Races (no.)			Subcultures (no.)			Lesions (no./plant) caused by							
	Total	Pathogenic to		Total	Pathogenic to		All subcultures			Pathogenic subcultures				
		C	T		KTH	C	T	KTH	C	T	KTH	C	T	KTH
FR-1	28	11	5	28	160	60	19	160	0.3	0.1	33.9	1.1	1.4	33.9
FR-1-138	12	6	1	12	48	15	3	48	0.8	0.1	56.6	2.8	6.2	56.6
FR-78	8	—	7	8	45	—	44	45	—	5.2	22.6	—	6.1	22.6
FR-78-16	51	1	17	48	100	1	43	97	0.1	3.6	17.4	8.7	8.9	18.0
FR-79	19	1	11	19	52	1	17	52	0.01	0.7	46.3	0.5	2.5	46.3
FR-80	7	3	1	7	45	7	1	45	0.6	0.2	47.9	4.1	7.9	47.9
FR-13	43	0	17	43	189	0	43	189	0.0	0.1	50.3	0.0	0.8	50.3

and weather conditions. The conidia in the air over our blast nursery were collected with a Kramer-Collins spore sampler every other day for 17 days in March and April during the dry season, and for 19 days in July and August during the wet season.

A distinct daytime and nighttime periodicity in the dispersal of spores occurred in the dry season. Conidia began to be released into air about 8 PM and stopped about 6 AM the next day. The peak release occurred from 1 to 3 AM (fig. 1). Release of spores began with the start of the dew period. The earlier the dew formed in the evening, the earlier the release of conidia began. An occasional drizzle in the afternoon caused a second peak release (fig. 2). The highest hourly conidial concentration in the air was 414/liter and the highest daily conidial concentration, 2,891/liter.

During the wet season, rain showers disturbed the periodicity of spore release. A peak release occurred immediately after a rain. Usually one or two peaks of different magnitudes occurred in the afternoon. The average spore release during a 24-hour period in the dry and wet seasons is shown in figure 3. There were more conidia in the air in the wet season than in the dry season: the highest hourly collection in the wet season was 536 conidia/liter and the highest daily collection, 3,174/liter.

Evidently, the presence of free water in the form of dew or rain is necessary for the release of spores.

During the 1-month period of blast nursery, the conidia release was greatest about 3 weeks after germination. Spore release decreased gradually during the last week because the

susceptible host plants died and little plant tissue was available for further infection.

Biochemistry of blast lesions

Preliminary tests were made to find out what biochemical processes are involved in the formation of blast lesions. On resistant varieties the fungus causes small brown spots, while on susceptible varieties, it causes large lesions. Even in susceptible varieties the lesions stop enlarging after the brown margin appears. The brown discoloration seems to limit the growth of the fungus in the leaf tissue. The speed with which the brown color forms in different varieties might determine the degree of resistance: the faster or sooner it appears on a variety, the more resistant that variety is.

Several phenolic compounds present in the rice plant are toxic to the fungus as shown by spore germination test (Table 5). The oxidized forms of the phenolic compounds, the quinones, are more toxic to the fungus and promote the brown discoloration. The phenolic compounds are oxidized by polyphenol oxidase and polyphenol peroxidase. Since polyphenol oxidase is not known to be present in the rice plant, peroxidase in the tissue possibly plays an important role in oxidizing the phenols. The polyphenols that play a major role in the defense mechanism are therefore present in rice plants. But the amount of phenols present in each variety and the speed of post-infection changes in each variety may differ and result in different degrees of resistance among varieties.

On the other hand, another important system is also involved in the formation of lesions, in which the reducing agents present in rice plant, such as ascorbic acid and glutathione, play a role. We found that these reducing agents decrease the toxicity of the polyphenols. Adding ascorbic acid and glutathione to chlorogenic acid, one of the polyphenols present in rice plant, greatly reduced the toxicity to spore germination (fig. 4). The more reducing agents present in the tissue of a variety, the higher the susceptibility of that variety.

Several polyphenols and quinones, particularly catechol, chlorogenic acid, pyrogallol, and

1. Diurnal periodicity of conidia release of *Pyricularia oryzae*, showing peaks at 1 to 3 AM for each of 3 sample days during dry season.

2. Diurnal periodicity of conidia release of *P. oryzae* on March 4 and March 5 during the dry season showing the peak at 2 AM and a second peak at about noon due to a drizzle.

β -quinone, when added to typical lesions on detached leaves, intensified the brown discoloration. When ascorbic acid was added to lesions whose browning had been artificially enhanced by β -quinone, the brown color more or less disappeared. This supports previous findings that the two systems mentioned above are involved in the browning of lesions.

Healthy tissue has a low concentration of both polyphenols and peroxidase. When the fungus invades the tissue, it stimulates the production of polyphenol and peroxidase and the oxidation processes bring about a brown discoloration. The speed of the process depends on the interaction between the host variety and the fungus race involved. Changes in the peroxidase activity of both healthy and inoculated susceptible plants (Tjeremas) at different periods after inoculation revealed an increased

3. Diurnal periodicity of conidia release of *P. oryzae* during the dry season (17-day average) and the wet season (19-day average).

Table 5. Toxicity of phenolic compounds at different concentrations to germinating spores of *P. oryzae*.

Phenol	Spore germination (%)		
	$2 \times 10^{-4}M$	$5 \times 10^{-4}M$	$1 \times 10^{-3}M$
Catechol	10.2	4.0	0.0
Hydroquinone	14.9	3.6	2.7
p-quinone	28.6	16.9	0.0
Phloroglucinol	38.2	26.2	21.1
Pyrogallol	28.4	21.1	15.6
Vanillic acid ^a	26.6	18.8	10.7
Salicylic acid ^b	26.8	19.4	6.8
Protocatecheic acid ^a	29.7	27.0	25.5
p-coumaric acid ^a	45.5	35.3	24.3
Caffeic acid	20.3	15.3	7.7
Ferulic acid ^b	32.1	29.7	26.4
Chlorogenic acid ^b	39.5	28.3	23.1
Control ^c	79.9	—	—

^aKnown to be present in the rice plant in relatively small amounts. ^bKnown to be present in the rice plant in relatively large amounts. ^cDistilled water.

enzyme activity in the inoculated leaves (fig. 5) when the lesions were forming. The peroxidase oxidized the phenolic compounds, forming a brown melanin-like pigment.

The fungus also secreted enzymes which oxidized the polyphenols. The chlorogenic acid solution used for spore germination turned brown because the germinating spores secreted phenolase which oxidized the chlorogenic acid. The absorption spectrum of this oxidized solution and of pure chlorogenic acid differed completely (fig. 6).

Chemical control of blast

While varietal resistance is the most effective answer to blast, chemical control can reduce losses in fields where blast has occurred.

Several chemicals were tested as seed treatments, as soil treatments, and as foliar sprays. Two new systemic compounds, NF-35 and NF-44, gave promising results.

Seed treatment for seedling blast. Seeds of Tjeremas were treated with chemicals at different rates. Two-week-old seedlings were exposed to the blast nursery. Readings were taken 1 week after exposure and every week thereafter. The two new compounds, NF-35 and NF-44, give as good systemic action as Benlate although a slightly higher rate may be used (Table 6).

New chemicals for soil treatment. Two-week-old Tjeremas seedlings in a seedbox received a soil treatment with three systemic fungicides and were exposed to the blast nursery. NF-35 and NF-44 showed good systemic action. NF-44 was comparable to Benlate but a higher rate of application may be needed (Table 7).

Other experiments showed that the effectiveness of Benlate as a soil treatment is not affected by four different soil types: Casiguran, Luisiana, Maahas, and Pila. A preliminary test also showed that NF-35 and NF-44, like Benlate, remain effective in the soil for more than 4 months.

Kitazin soil treatment. Benlate as a soil treatment controls blast effectively, but it is costly. Although slightly less effective than Benlate, Kitazin costs less so it may be practical to use.

4. Effect of ascorbic acid and glutathione on germination of *P. oryzae* spores in chlorogenic acid.

5. Changes in the peroxidase activity of blast-susceptible Tjeremas 1 to 20 days after inoculation with *P. oryzae* as measured by optical density of the oxidized pyrogallol.

6. Absorption spectra of chlorogenic acid and of the oxidation product of chlorogenic acid.

Two field experiments, one at San Pablo and another at Bay, Laguna, Philippines were conducted to evaluate the usefulness of Kitazin as soil treatment in fields. Both fields were severely infected with leaf blast. Kitazin in granular form was applied to plots 4 sq m in size a few days before flowering to control panicle blast. Ten replications were used at San Pablo and eight at Bay. The results showed (Table 8) that Kitazin soil treatments may increase yield by about 1 t/ha where the blast infection is severe.

Spray treatment for panicle blast. Several chemicals were tested for control of panicle blast in two farmers' fields which were severely infected with leaf blast. Two sprays at the same rate were made for each treatment, the first at the start of flowering and the second, 1 week later. Plots 4 sq m in size were used in each treatment and each treatment was replicated four times. Most of the treatments increased yield considerably (Table 9). The amount of increase,

however, depended on the degree of infection at the time of spraying and on the later development of the disease, both of which varied from season to season. Thus the results can only serve as a general guide.

Separate experiments were conducted to determine whether more frequent spraying would further decrease the damage from panicle blast. Benlate and Hinosan were sprayed one, two, and three times at weekly intervals from the start of flowering. Three sprayings did not seem to increase the yield significantly over two sprayings or even one spraying.

Sheath blight

Methods of evaluating varietal resistance. The conventional method for testing varietal reaction to sheath blight (*Corticium sasakii*) takes an entire crop season. We devised several other methods of inoculation and have compared them to find a method which requires less time and space. Inoculation tests in the seedbox (1966 Annual Report), in the seedbed (similar to

Table 6. Effect of seed treatment for controlling seedling blast with systemic fungicides 1, 2, and 3 weeks after the seedlings were exposed to infection.

Chemical	Rate (g/kg seed)	Lesions (no./seedling)		
		1st reading	2nd reading	3rd reading
Benlate	8	0.0	0.0	0.1
NF-35	4	1.8	7.1	22.9
NF-35	6	0.4	1.5	2.2
NF-35	12	0.9	2.7	1.8
NF-44	4	0.4	1.6	3.2
NF-44	6	0.1	1.8	3.0
NF-44	12	0.0	0.2	0.2
Control	—	32.2	85.0	86.9

Table 7. Effect of soil treatment with chemicals for controlling leaf blast 1, 2, and 3 weeks after treatment.

Chemical	Rate (g/sq m)	Lesions (no./seedling)		
		1st reading	2nd reading	3rd reading
Benlate	4	0	0	0
NF-35	16	0.2	0.4	0.5
NF-35	32	0.2	0.2	0.3
NF-44	16	0	0	0
NF-44	32	0	0	0
Kitazin	20	6.9	10.4	45.0
Kitazin	40	2.2	2.5	40.7
Control	0	60.0	79.5	111.1

Table 8. Results of controlling blast with Kitazin soil treatment at two locations in Laguna, Philippines.

Chemical	Rate (kg/ha)	San Pablo		Bay	
		Neck rot (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Neck rot (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Kitazin	30	47.1**	5.71**	31.3**	4.75**
Kitazin	60	26.7**	6.00**	30.2**	4.75**
Kitazin	120	20.0**	6.08**	10.0**	5.00**
Control	0	61.9	5.00	71.9	3.75

**Significantly different from the control at the 1% level.

Table 9. Control of panicle blast by spraying chemicals at two locations in Laguna, Philippines.

Chemical ^a	Rate/ha	Bay		San Pablo	
		Neck rot (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Neck rot (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Benlate ^b	0.5 kg	51.6**	4.25 ^{ns}	63.7*	3.95*
Benlate	0.9 kg	50.6**	4.75**	65.5*	4.00*
Benlate	1.5 kg	40.2**	5.00**	—	—
Kitazin E.C.	1 liter	58.9*	4.00 ^{ns}	65.1*	4.25**
NF-35 p.	2 kg	50.0**	3.75 ^{ns}	37.8**	4.45**
Hinosan E.C.	1 liter	29.4**	5.00**	29.5**	4.57**
Tecto 60 wp	2 kg	59.7 ^{ns}	3.75 ^{ns}	38.8**	4.37**
NF-44 p	2 kg	34.9**	5.25**	26.1**	4.37**
Control	—	75.4	3.05	86.2	3.20

**Significantly different from the control at the 1% level. *Significantly different from the control at the 5% level. ^{ns}Not significant. ^aEC=emulsifiable conc., p=powder, wp=wettable powder. ^bPlus surfactant.

blast nursery), and in the field at the booting and flowering stages gave similar results for the 60 varieties tested. The seedbox and seedbed methods saved much time and space.

Several types of inoculum also were compared. Placing the fungus culture on sterilized rice stems, 5 cm to 7 cm long, on the soil surface near the seedling as inoculum, was the most convenient.

Thermal differentiation of isolates. Thirteen isolates responded differently to temperature. They differed in rate of growth in culture as well as in response to higher temperatures. Some isolates grew very slowly at 36 C while others grew well (fig. 7).

Nutrition and morphology. Both carbon and nitrogen sources in the media affect the cultural morphology of the fungus, particularly the morphology of the sclerotia which are used for identifying related species (fig. 8). A given nitrogen source in the media gives rise to a

certain size, shape, and number of sclerotia, irrespective of the six isolates studied.

Nutrition and pathogenicity. The 13 isolates studied differed in their pathogenicity to seven selected rice varieties. Their pathogenicity, however, was affected by nitrogen and carbon sources. Generally, sources of nitrogen and carbon that gave good growth produced more virulent cultures. Increased concentration also increased virulence within the range of concentration used.

Ecological studies on bacterial blight

Fluorescin-antibody method for ecological studies. In the absence of a selective medium for detecting the presence and population of *Xanthomonas oryzae* in natural substrates such as soil, irrigation water, and plant parts, the fluorescin-antibody (FA) method was tried.

We found that a single antiserum obtained by injecting isolate B20-6 into rabbit would react to most of the 135 other isolates in agglutination tests *in vitro*, at an antiserum dilution of 800 times or more. This indicates that a single antiserum could detect most of the isolates found in nature.

7. Effects of different temperatures on the mycelial growth (radius of colonies) of various isolates of *Corticium sasakii*.

Hardly any saprophytic bacteria shared the antibody reaction with *X. oryzae*. Small clay particles in irrigation water which produced strong white auto-fluorescence may have interfered with the observation. There were some other bacterial cells in the weak auto-fluorescence but they were easily distinguished from *X. oryzae* by their shape, size, and fluorescence intensity.

When tested with a known population in suspension, the FA method could only detect the bacterial population above 10^4 /ml; at or below this concentration, the bacterium could not be detected by either the FA or the phage method.

Tests to find the population of the bacterial cells in the irrigation water of diseased plots during the tillering stage showed that the population never exceeded 10^6 /ml, regardless of the intensity of the disease. This supports earlier findings that *X. oryzae* does not multiply successfully in irrigation water.

Evidence was obtained that phage-bacterium interaction takes place on the plant surface. Bacterial cells and phages were abundant on

each leaf of the young plants. The irrigation water samples collected at the base of the plant hills contained many more phages than samples from between hills. Under natural conditions, the bacteria apparently move to the paddy field through the irrigation water. When they reach the lower leaf sheath they multiply on the surface to form microcolonies, and then move to the inner surface of the sheath from which they spread to the newly developing leaves.

Phage population in the rice field. The phage population was estimated both on the plants (10 leaves each sample, every other day) and in the irrigation water (1 ml, daily) for 71 days before harvest in field plots with different degrees of disease intensity, i.e. two leaves inoculated per hill, five leaves inoculated per hill, and uninoculated, to observe the change of the population and to evaluate the usefulness of the phage method to indicate disease intensity.

In general, the phage population was high in heavily inoculated plots, moderate in lightly inoculated plots, and low in plots without inoculation, both on the plants and in the irrigation water (fig. 9). The population declined as the plants became mature. The day-to-day fluctuation was large however, particularly on plants. The population was greatly affected by rain, sunlight, and other environmental conditions. Samples taken for a particular day may not have represented the population of the period the sample day was supposed to represent.

Survival of *X. oryzae* on and in plants. We attempted to recover *X. oryzae* from rice leaves which had no visible lesions after having been sprayed with a streptomycin-resistant strain. We were unable to recover the bacterium after 3 to 5 days from two susceptible varieties, IR8 and JC-70, in the greenhouse or the field. Nevertheless we were able to reisolate the bacterium after 3 hours, after 15 hours, and every day thereafter until the third day in some cases and until the fifth day in others. *Xanthomonas oryzae* does not seem to live long on these leaves. Competition among microorganisms on the leaves may have affected its survival.

In experiments to determine the survival of the organism in different parts of infected leaf

8. Effect of nitrogen sources in media on the sclerotial morphology of *C. sasakii*.

Table 10. Number of colonies isolated from different parts of bacterial blight lesions.

Variety	Inoculation point	1-cm from inoculation point	Middle of lesion	Advancing tip of lesion
<i>7 days after inoculation^a</i>				
JC-70	0	5	35	477
IR8	57	—	—	292
Zenith	220	—	—	27
<i>11 days after inoculation</i>				
JC-70	0	0	370	212
IR8	30	44	790	908
Zenith	41	—	—	801
<i>17 days after inoculation</i>				
JC-70	0	6	22	662
IR8	0	6	57	466
Zenith	4	100	130	938
<i>23 days after inoculation^b</i>				
JC-70	0	0	0	2
IR8	0	0	4	313
Zenith	0	0	2	28

^aThe lesions on Zenith and IR8 were very small. ^bThe leaves of JC-70 were dead.

tissues, the leaves of two susceptible varieties, IR8 and JC-70, and one resistant variety, Zenith, were inoculated by needle. The bacteria were isolated and the population estimated during different stages of lesion development at the inoculation points, at 1 cm from the inoculation points, in the middle of the lesions,

and at advancing tips of the lesions. The advancing tips of the lesions produced the most bacterial colonies (Table 10). There were few or no living bacteria in 1-week-old or 2-week-old lesions.

Influence of saprophytic Xanthomonads on infection. There are many saprophytic bacteria on rice leaves, including *Xanthomonas* spp. Tests were made to examine the influence of a saprophytic *Xanthomonas* mixed with *X. oryzae* in the inoculum on the pathogenicity of the latter. Both bacteria were suspended in water at about 4×10^8 /ml, mixed in various proportions, and inoculated to 18 seedlings by needle. The results (Table 11) showed that the mixture of saprophytic *Xanthomonas* reduced the infection particularly at above a 1:1 proportion.

Host influence on virulence of *Xanthomonas oryzae*

Experiments were made to find out whether resistant and susceptible host varieties affect the changes in pathogenicity of *X. oryzae*. B15-37-109-80, a highly virulent strain, and B23-77-89, a weak strain, were inoculated to Zenith (resistant) and JC-70 (susceptible). The

9. Bacteriophage population (plaques) detected in irrigation water and on rice leaves during the growing period in field plots with different disease intensity.

10. Reactions of two rice varieties to two strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* after three passages on the resistant and susceptible host varieties as compared with the original cultures.

Table 11. Influence of saprophytic *Xanthomonas* on the infectivity of *X. oryzae* at 12, 16, and 20 days after inoculation.

Proportion of mixture	Infected seedlings (%)			
	<i>X. oryzae</i> /saprophyte			<i>X. oryzae</i> /water
	12 days	16 days	20 days	12 days
10:0	100	100	100	100
9:1	61	69	100	100
8:2	50	76	100	100
7:3	19	44	100	100
6:4	6	39	89	100
5:5	0	0	74	100
4:6	0	0	39	100
3:7	0	0	31	100
2:8	0	0	30	94
1:9	0	0	0	100
0:10	0	0	0	0

strains were reisolated and reinoculated. After three passages through the two varieties, 100 colonies from each strain were multiplied and inoculated to the two varieties. Twenty seedlings were used for each single-colony culture.

The virulence of the original cultures increased when both passed through the resistant host (fig. 10). It also increased when the cultures passed through the susceptible host. The virulence after the isolates passed through the susceptible host was not significantly different from the virulence of the original cultures. No change was observed in the virulent isolate on the resistant host. We assume that the resistance or susceptibility of host varieties does not have great selective influence on virulence. The

bacterium may change in virulence, however (1969 Annual Report). The variation we observed may have been due to the particular colonies selected for the reisolation process.

Media for *Xanthomonas oryzae*

Although *X. oryzae* is able to grow in many kinds of substrates, no good media for single-cell growth has been found. We tried several known media for single cells and had poor results: few or no colonies developed.

In addition, a selective medium which permits *X. oryzae* to grow but suppresses the growth of other microorganisms is needed to detect *X. oryzae* in the soil, in field water, or on the leaf surface. The lack of such a medium has hampered many ecological studies. Recent findings have shown that the use of phages to indicate the presence and population of *X. oryzae* in natural conditions has many drawbacks. We therefore attempted to find both types of media.

The addition of a small amount of ferrous sulfate to Wakimoto's medium greatly helped colonies develop from a bacterial suspension. Wakimoto's medium without potato further improved colony development. Other salts, such as $MgSO_4$, did not improve the media. The iron in ferrous sulfate was found responsible for the increased growth. A better medium for single cell growth consists of: 0.5 g $Ca(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, 2.0 g $Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 12H_2O$, 5.0 g peptone (Bacto), 20.0 g Sucrose, 0.5 g $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, and 1 liter water, PH 6.8-7. The relative growth of the bacterium on various media is shown in figure 11.

For developing the selective medium, different sources of carbon and nitrogen were tried without success. Eighteen kinds of antibiotics and anti-fungal compounds were also tried. Five of them permitted the growth of *X. oryzae*. They may be used to develop the selective medium.

Chemical control of bacterial blight

A new systemic compound, TF-130, was tried for controlling bacterial blight. Preliminary

results showed that it is effective as a soil treatment (Table 12). It prevented lesions from developing at all the rates tried. When used as a spray at the recommended dosage the chemical seemed less effective but still gave fairly good control within the test period (Table 13). The test on flag leaves indicated similar results (Table 14). Inoculations were made by needle on the three youngest expanded leaves. First readings were made 2 weeks after inoculation, the second and third, at weekly intervals.

Varietal resistance to tungro

Testing of rice varieties for their reaction to tungro disease was continued. Eleven- to 13-day-old seedlings were tested by mass screening. A total of 3,604 entries, consisting of 91 varieties,

11. Growth of *X. oryzae* on different kinds of media by the dilution plate method (above) and streak method (below) of inoculation.

Table 12. Results of soil treatment with TF-130 powder for controlling bacterial blight.

Date of application	Rate (g/pot)	Lesion size ^a (sq cm),	
		10 days after inoculation	20 days after inoculation
1 day before inoculation	0.01	0.11	0.61
	0.02	0.02	0.04
	0.04	0.01	0.01
	0.08	0.01	0.02
5 days before inoculation	0.01	0.21	0.23 ^b
	0.02	0.02	0.07 ^c
	0.04	0.01	0.11
	0.08	0.01	0.02
1 day after inoculation	0.01	0.18	0.27
	0.02	0.01	0.02
	0.04	0.01	0.02
	0.08	0.02	0.03
Control	—	1.43	7.89 ^c

^aAverage from 20 leaves. ^bSome inoculated leaves showed large areas of yellowing or wilting although definite lesions had not formed. ^c38.1% of the seedlings died from kresek symptoms.

2,078 selections of IRRI crosses, four Thai selections, 137 entries of genetical materials, and 1,294 entries of duplicates, were tested in 1970. Pankhari 203 remained the most resistant variety; several crosses had a high percentage of selections in the resistant group (Table 15).

New strain of tungro virus

Two strains of tungro virus were identified in the Philippines several years ago (1966 Annual Report). They can be distinguished by the symptoms they produce on differential varieties such as FK 135, Acheh, and Pacita. The "S" strain causes the interveinal yellow stripes on the leaves of differential varieties; the "M" strain produces only mild diffused mottling or slight discoloration. On other varieties tested, however, the leaf symptoms produced by the strains are not distinguishable. The "S" strain appears to be more common than the "M" strain in the Philippines.

Recently, a third strain of tungro virus (fig. 12) was isolated from infected rice plants in the field at the Mountain Agricultural College in La Trinidad, Benguet. It was designated as the "T" strain. The new strain produces narrow

leaves, apart from stunting and yellowing, on Taichung Native 1, IR5, IR8, and IR22. The width of the leaf blade of Taichung Native 1 plants infected with the "T" strain was 0.96 cm, of plants infected with the "S" strain, 1.11 cm, and of plants infected with the "M" strain, 1.24 cm. The growth of rice plants infected with the new strain was less retarded than that of plants infected with the "M" strain, and much less than that of plants infected with the "S" strain. However, the new strain incited interveinal stripes on FK 135 which closely resembled the stripes caused by the "S" strain.

The new strain is also transmitted by *Nephotettix impicticeps*. The virus-vector interaction of the "T" strain is fundamentally identical to that of the two other strains: there was no demonstrable incubation period in the vector, the infective insects gradually lost their infectivity after the acquisition feeding period, and the longest retention period was 4 days.

The reactions of rice varieties to the three strains seemed similar. Pankhari 203, Peta, Bengawan, and Tjeremas were resistant to all three strains while Taichung Native 1 and FK 135 were susceptible to all of them.

Table 13. Results of spraying TF-130 (2:1000) on seedlings for controlling bacterial blight.

Time of application	Lesion size ^a (sq cm)		
	1st reading	2nd reading	3rd reading
1 day before inoculation	0.02	0.27	4.93
3 days before inoculation	0.03	0.82	10.19
1 day after inoculation	0.02	0.35	9.93
3 days after inoculation	0.02	1.18	8.50
Control	9.17	16.8	^b

^aAverage of 10 seedlings. ^b90% of plants died from kresek.

Table 14. Results of spraying TF-130 (2:1000) on flag leaves for controlling bacterial blight.

Date of application	Lesion size ^a (sq cm)	Reading date
		(days after spraying)
1 day before inoculation	0.12	20
5 days before inoculation	0.14	24
10 days before inoculation	0.10	29
1 day after inoculation	0.02	18
5 days after inoculation	0.85	14
10 days after inoculation	10.64	9
Control	11.17	—

^aAverage of 10 seedlings.

Infectivity of *N. impicticeps*

Nymphs. In last year's annual report, we showed that all five nymphal instars of *N. impicticeps* could transmit tungro virus after acquisition feeding. We assumed that the stylet of the first-instar nymph could reach to the vascular bundle of the leaf blade. This assumption was verified by examining the termination of the feeding tracks of the first-instar nymphs in the cross-sections of the leaf blade (fig. 13). Of the 102 feeding tracks examined, 84 terminated at the vascular bundles. Since the feeding behavior of the nymphs does not differ from the feeding behavior of the adult (1967 Annual Report), the nymph and the adult may inoculate the plant at the same site.

Molting. Infective nymphs of *N. impicticeps* lose their infectivity after molting or ecdysis, but the insects can regain their infectivity by renewed feeding on diseased plants (1965 Annual Report). The phenomenon of loss of infectivity after molting is a critical criterion for determining the nonpersistence of tungro virus in its vector, yet the real mechanism involved in the loss of infectivity during the molting process is not clear.

During molting a new epidermis forms under the old skin. Then the old skin ruptures allowing the insect to emerge. The cleft forms along the dorsal median line of the head and thorax. When the exuviae or cast skin is shed, not only the general cuticle enclosing the body and append-

12. Growth retardation caused by strains of the tungro virus. From left: healthy check, "M" strain, "T" strain (discovered 1970), and "S" strain.

13. Cross section of rice leaf showing the feeding track of the first-instar nymph of *Nephotettix impicticeps* terminating at the vascular bundle.

Table 15. Reaction to tungro disease of IRRI crosses tested by the mass screening method.

Cross no.	Parents	No. of selections showing infection range of		
		0-30%	31-60%	61-100%
IR665	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	9	10	6
IR789	IR8 x Muey Nahng 62M	6	0	12
IR822	IR8/2 x Pankhari 203	14	91	50
IR825	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x (Peta/6 x TN1)	16	102	35
IR848	IR262-43-8 x [(CP231-SLO-17) x Gam Pai]	6	4	0
IR854	(IR8 x Pankhari 203) x IR262-43-8	36	21	6
IR879	IR8/2 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)	4	10	1
IR887	IR8/2 x Muey Nahng 62M	5	2	4
IR932	IR8/3 x Pankhari 203	6	31	2
IR1364	IR262-43-8 x HR21	9	19	31
IR1366	(Sigadis/2 x TN1) x IR127-80-1	17	211	200
IR1529	IR305-3-17 x IR661-1-140-3	4	111	43
Other 135 crosses		28	329	587
Total (147 crosses, 2078 selections, 3243 entries)		160	941	977

ages but also the lining or intima of most of the tracheal tubes and the stomodaeal and proctodaeal parts of the alimentary canal are cast off.

An examination of the exuviae of *N. impicticeps* under a microscope revealed that the mouth portion consists of the external structure of labium, labrum, and stylets, including both mandibles and maxillae (fig. 14). Consequently, the old stylets are cast off when the insect molts. In fact, when the exuviae hang on leaves, the portions sticking to the leaf are the old stylets which are still inserted into the leaf tissues.

An examination of the stylets of the insect early in the molting stage revealed that the new stylets were inside the old ones (fig. 15). When an insect feeds on a diseased plant, the stylets and alimentary canal undoubtedly are contaminated with the virus. If the virus particles are distributed only on the surface of the stylets and on the lining of the alimentary canal, but have not penetrated into tissues under the epidermal layer, the virus particles must be cast off with the exuviae during molting, thus freeing the insect of

the virus. An insect having no virus cannot be infective. This seems to be the reason why infectivity is lost after molting.

Temperature. Since temperature may directly or indirectly affect the insect's transmission of the tungro virus, daily serial transmissions of viruliferous adult *N. impicticeps* were carried out by confining the insects and seedlings in incubators set from 8 to 38 C at intervals of 6 C. Within 5 days, the average life span of the insects was 3.5 days at 8 C, 4.4 days at 14 C, 4.1 days at 20 C, 4.0 days at 26 C, 3.8 days at 32 C, and 1.6 days at 38 C (LSD [5%] 0.8). Hence, the life span of the insect was significantly shorter at 38 C than at any other temperature tested.

The average percentage of infective insects did not differ significantly at 26 C from the average at 20 to 38 C. The number of disease-transmitting days of the insects at 20 C differed significantly from the number at all other temperatures tested except 26 C (fig. 16).

Apparently, the insect had the longest life

14. Mouth portion of exuviae of *N. impicticeps*, left, and after the removal of labium, right. The presence of stylets indicates that they are cast off together with the general cuticle during molting.

span at 14 C, the highest percentage of infective insects at 26 C, and the highest number of disease-transmitting days at 20 C. Consequently, the temperature that favored the life span of the insect did not favor the transmission of the disease. The effect of temperature on the percentage of infective insects did not coincide with the effect of temperature on the number of disease-transmitting days. However, the transmissive ability of the insects decreased at 14 C or below, and the number of disease-transmitting days decreased at 32 C or above.

Amino acids. Analytical data obtained by chemists in the Institute indicated that IR8 and Pankhari 203, two varieties that are resistant to green leafhoppers, have a high amount of histidine in the amino acid composition. We

15. New maxilla (left) and mandible (right) produced inside the old ones during the molting of *N. impicticeps*.

attempted therefore to determine whether histidine plays a major role in the mechanism of leafhopper resistance. The effect of histidine on the life span of the viruliferous adults of *N. impicticeps* was tested by the "solution feeding method."

About 1.5 ml of solution was placed on the outside of the base of a 400-ml beaker and covered with a piece of stretched Parafilm. A plastic cover with openings for ventilation and entrance of insects was placed over the membrane. Then using an aspirator, we put 40 insects on the membrane under the cover. Every morning the solution and the membrane were changed and the dead insects were counted. This method is widely used for testing the effect of chemical compounds on the life span of the insects.

The method is also used to test the effect of chemicals on the infectivity of viruliferous insects. The viruliferous insects are usually confined on the solution for 6 hours. After they have fed on the solution, the insects are transferred individually to Taichung Native 1 seedlings and left there for 16 hours. The infectivity of the insect is determined by the infection of the seedlings. The percentage of infection is

16. Effect of temperature on transmissive ability of tungro viruliferous *N. impicticeps*.

17. Effect of various concentrations of histidine monohydrochloride on the life span of tungro viruliferous *N. impicticeps*.

used to express the effect of the compound on the infectivity of the insect.

The higher the histidine concentration, the shorter was the insects' life span (fig. 17). But even a 1 mg/ml concentration of histidine reduced the insects' life span by less than 50 percent. Histidine cannot be the only reason for varietal resistance to the insect because it did not have as great an effect as Pankhari 203 seedlings on the life span of the insect (1967 Annual Report).

Three other amino acids, asparagine, aspartic acid, and alanine, also were tested. Their effects on the life span of viruliferous *N. impicticeps* were not striking.

The effect of histidine on the infectivity of viruliferous *N. impicticeps* was also tested by the solution feeding method. The percentage of infective insects was reduced slightly with increased concentration of histidine in the solution. But even at a concentration of 1 mg/ml, the percentage of infective insects was reduced only by about 15 percent.

pH value. The effects of pH on viruses depend on temperature, ionic concentration, and the presence of other substances. Using the solution feeding method, no striking differences in the percentage of infective insects of *N. impicticeps* were found when the pH was increased from 4 to 10 at intervals of 0.5 regardless of the growth stage of the insect or of the pH of the solutions regulated with or without buffer. But with a feeding solution at pH 3, none of the viruliferous insects that were fed on the solution for 6 hours transmitted the disease.

To confirm the effect of pH 3 on the infectivity of the viruliferous insects, pH values from 3 to 4 at intervals of 0.2 were regulated with a citrate buffer (0.01M citric acid and 0.01M sodium citrate) and with a citrate-phosphate buffer (0.01M citric acid and 0.01M Na_2HPO_4). Measured by the average percentage of infective insects in different treatments, the number of insects transmitting the disease decreased when the pH value of the feeding solution was decreased from 4 to 3 (fig. 18).

In last year's annual report, we stated that feeding solutions that have a pH lower than 4 or higher than 8.5 reduce the life span of *N. impicticeps*. Hence, the reduction in the percentage of infective insects after the viruliferous insects fed on a solution with a low pH could be due to either the effect of pH on the activity of the insect or the effect of pH on the virus. If the insects were no longer able to feed on seedlings after feeding on a low pH solution, the disease would not be transmitted and the percentage of infective insects would be reduced.

The presence of feeding punctures on leaves exposed to the insects revealed, however, that the insects could feed on the leaves immediately after they had fed for 6 hours on a solution at pH 3. Furthermore, the insects feeding on Taichung Native 1 seedlings after they had fed on solutions at pH 3, 4, and 6 for 6 hours had similar life spans. Consequently, the reduction in percentage of infective insects may not have been caused by the inability of treated insects to feed on seedlings. In other words, the low-pH solution could inactivate the virus in the insects.

Buffer solution. Three buffer solutions with different levels of concentration at pH 4, 5, and

6 were used to determine the effect of the buffer solutions on the infectivity of viruliferous *N. impicticeps*. Sixty-four percent of the insects on citrate buffer were infective, 73 percent on succinate buffer, and 78 percent on tris-maleate buffer. At concentrations of 0.005M and 0.01M, 74 percent were infective, and at 0.02M, 67 percent were infective. At pH 4, 67 percent were infective; at pH 5, 73 percent; and at pH 6, 76 percent. The differences were not statistically significant. Hence, the tested combinations of buffer, concentration, and pH had no important effects on the infectivity of the viruliferous insect.

Chemicals. The effect of 28 chemical compounds on the infectivity of viruliferous *N. impicticeps* was tested by the method described above. Each compound was prepared at four concentrations (0.5, 1.0, 3.0, and 5.0mM) in 0.01M citrate buffer solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5 to 5.8. Viruliferous insects were allowed to feed on the solution for 6 hours.

Based on the infectivity of the insects after treatment, the compounds were divided into two groups, since no single compound increased infectivity of the insects,

The compounds of the first group did not reduce the infectivity of the insects. The insects that fed on the solutions of the compounds of the first group even at the concentration of 5mM, remained as infective as the insects which fed on citrate buffer solution, which served as control. This group consisted of benzoic acid, cinnamic acid, *m*-coumaric acid, *p*-coumaric acid, ferulic acid, gibberellic acid, *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 3-indoleacetic acid, 3-indolepropionic acid, phenol, phloroglucinol, protocatechuic acid, resorcinol, salicylic acid, sinapinic acid, and vanillin. Among these compounds, hydroxylamine is an effective mutagen for DNA *in vitro*. It inactivates RNA of tobacco mosaic virus and also produces mutants, but apparently not on intact virus.

The compounds in the second group decreased the infectivity of the insects. In this group were caffeic acid, catechol, chlorogenic acid, 3-indolebutyric acid, and quinone (figs. 19 and 20). The other six compounds tested might also be in this group but the results need to be reconfirmed.

The reduction of infectivity depended on the concentration of the compound in the solution. Generally, the higher the concentration, the lower the percentage of infective insects. The rate of reduction varied among the compounds however. None of the tested compounds inactivated the virus completely even at a concentration of 5mM.

The effect of chlorogenic acid on the infectivity of the insects varied remarkably among the preparations (fig. 20). Chlorogenic acid prepared in water reduced the percentage of infective insects more than did the compound prepared in a citrate buffer solution at pH 5.6. The main reason for the difference may be the pH value of the preparation because the solution of chlorogenic acid without titration was about pH 3. As mentioned before, a pH lower than 4 could reduce the infectivity of the insects. However, a comparison of 0.5 and 2.0mM chlorogenic acid at pH values from 3.5 to 8.5 at

18. Effect of pH of feeding solution on the infectivity of tungro viruliferous *N. impicticeps*.

intervals of 0.5 indicated that the percentage of infective insects among the viruliferous insects that fed on 2.0mM solution was always lower than that on 0.5mM. Therefore, the higher concentration of chlorogenic acid reduces the percentage of infective insects more than does the lower concentration at all the pH values tested.

The effect of chlorogenic acid on the number of disease-transmitting days was determined by daily serial transmission after treatment. Although the concentration of chlorogenic acid varied from 0 to 1.0mM, the number of disease-transmitting days varied only between 1.25 to 1.33. Consequently, chlorogenic acid may not affect the number of days that the insect transmits the disease.

The effect of chlorogenic acid on the ability of *N. impicticeps* to acquire the tungro virus was determined by the percentage of infective insects that acquired tungro virus at various

lengths of time immediately after the insects had fed on the chlorogenic acid solution for 24 hours. As indicated by the differences in percentages of infective insects between treatments (fig. 21), the compound seemed to affect the ability of the insect to acquire the virus. The effect, however, was temporary and limited to the period immediately after treatment; it was not noticeable when the acquisition feeding period was longer than 16 hours.

To retest the temporary effect of chlorogenic acid, the insects were allowed to feed on the solution for treatment, on the diseased plants to acquire the virus, and on the healthy seedlings for testing. Previous results were verified. Regardless of the age of the insects treated, the percentage of infective insects decreased when the viruliferous insects were tested immediately after feeding on the solution, but the insects that previously fed on the solution regained their infectivity after acquisition feeding.

19. Effect of compounds (in citrate buffer at pH 5.6) on the infectivity of tungro viruliferous *N. impicticeps*.

20. Effect of chlorogenic acid on the infectivity of tungro viruliferous *N. impicticeps*.

Tungro: vector variability

Adaptability of green leafhopper to Pankhari 203.

When reared continuously on Pankhari 203 seedlings, *N. impicticeps* becomes adapted to the variety: its life span gradually increases and more insects reach the adult stage (1969 Annual Report). Studies this year showed that the life span of the 15th to 20th generations of the P203 colony on Pankhari 203 seedlings at the three-leaf stage remained the same as the life span of insects of the 10th generation. Nevertheless, their life span was still slightly shorter than that of insects of either the P203 colony or of the TN1 colony allowed to feed on Taichung Native 1 seedlings. A female of the 20th generation of the P203 colony produced about the same number of progeny on Pankhari 203 as a female of the 10th generation. The insects of the P203 colony however, consistently produced more insects that reached adult stage than insects of the TN1 colony on Pankhari 203. Insects of either colony produced more progeny on Taichung Native 1 seedlings.

To determine whether the adaptability of *N. impicticeps* to Pankhari 203 could be reproduced if the insects were reared on a mixed population of rice varieties, pairs of the insects were used to start four colonies. They were reared on Pankhari 203 alone, on a mixed population of Pankhari 203 and Taichung Native 1 at a ratio of 19 to 1, on a mixed population of these two varieties at a reversed ratio, and on Taichung Native 1 alone. After a few generations, the insects developed their adaptability to Pankhari 203, depending upon the proportion of Pankhari 203 seedlings in the feeding material. Generally, when the insects were tested on Pankhari 203 seedlings, the insects reared on Pankhari 203 had the longest life spans, followed by the insects reared on a mixture of 95 percent Pankhari 203 and 5 percent Taichung Native 1. The insects reared on a mixture of 5 percent Pankhari 203 and 95 percent Taichung Native 1 had only slightly longer life spans than the insects reared on Taichung Native 1 alone.

In the first two generations, the insects reared on Pankhari 203 alone produced fewer insects that reached adult stage than the insects reared

21. Effect of chlorogenic acid on the ability of *N. impicticeps* to acquire tungro virus. (A—Insects fed on 1% sugar solution for 24 hr immediately before acquisition feeding; B—Insects fed on 5mM chlorogenic acid in 1% sugar solution for 24 hr immediately before acquisition feeding).

on Pankhari 203 mixed with 5 percent Taichung Native 1. But the difference became negligible in the fourth and fifth generations. Within five generations, the insects reared on Taichung Native 1 mixed with 5 percent Pankhari 203 produced about the same number of progeny as the insects reared on Taichung Native 1 alone. However, the insects consistently produced more progeny on 100 or 95 percent Taichung Native 1 than on 100 or 95 percent Pankhari 203.

The transmission study did not reveal any distinct difference among the insects reared on various combinations of Taichung Native 1 and Pankhari 203 plants.

Field *N. impicticeps* versus IRRI colony. Since *N. impicticeps* can become adapted to a resistant variety in the laboratory, we attempted to determine whether such adaptability of the insect to IR8 (a resistant variety that has been cultivated extensively since 1964), occurs under natural conditions. Although several factors were unknown, such as the insect's history, availability, age, and original feeding material,

Table 16. Life span of adult *Nephotettix impicticeps* from different localities (Philippines) on seedlings of four rice varieties.

Source of insects	Tests (no.)	Total insects (no.)	Life span (days)	
			Average	Longest
<i>Taichung Native 1</i>				
IRRI colony	5	85	13.8	21-39
IRRI farm	11	168	15.5	21-44
Pila, Laguna	3	40	11.8	32-36
La Trinidad, Benguet	2	30	14.6	26-33
<i>IR8</i>				
IRRI colony	8	105	4.3	2-13
IRRI farm	11	215	15.3	17-42
Pila, Laguna	3	50	15.2	28-35
La Trinidad, Benguet	2	30	15.4	32-37
<i>Pankhari 203</i>				
IRRI colony	6	70	5.2	5-21
IRRI farm	6	109	5.3	8-20
Pila, Laguna	1	15	2.3	3
La Trinidad, Benguet	1	15	6.3	11
<i>ASD 7</i>				
IRRI colony	1	20	3.6	6
IRRI farm	1	20	3.2	10
La Trinidad, Benguet	1	15	4.1	7

etc., the insect's life span on seedlings of rice varieties was determined after the insects were collected from the field at three locations. Insects that had been reared on Taichung Native 1 seedlings at the Institute for the last several years, designated as the "IRRI colony," were used for comparison.

Insects of the IRRI colony consistently had a shorter life span on IR8 than on Taichung Native 1 (Table 16). The insects collected from the field, regardless of locality, had a similar life span on IR8 and Taichung Native 1. All the insects, however, had a shorter life span on Pankhari 203 and ASD 7 than on Taichung Native 1. This suggests a difference in the adaptability of the insect to IR8. The difference between the insects of the IRRI colony and those from the IRRI farm may have been caused by change in the adaptability to IR8 because the insects of the IRRI colony were originally collected from the IRRI farm. Either the insects of the IRRI farm increased their adaptability to IR8 or the insects of the IRRI colony decreased their adaptability to IR8. The difference between insects of the IRRI colony and insects from fields other than the IRRI farm could be due to the development of adaptability to IR8 or to the existence of ecotypes or biological strains of the insect. Since the original adaptability of the

insect to IR8 before IR8 was cultivated cannot be determined, the reason for the difference is uncertain.

Results of a transmission study indicated that the virus-vector interaction of the insects of the IRRI colony, from the IRRI farm, and from La Trinidad was fundamentally the same. Their transmissible ability seemed similar, too.

Tungro in Cotabato

Tungro was one of the major rice diseases in the Philippines before 1966. Since then it has become less important. This year, however, the disease broke out in several areas in the Philippines: Cotabato, Bicol (Camarines Norte and Camarines Sur), and Nueva Ecija.

Cotabato had the highest incidence of the disease in terms of both percentage of infected plants in a field and total affected areas. All rice varieties, and especially IR22, were infected. Two fields of IR20 surrounded by diseased fields remained apparently normal. The population of both *N. impicticeps* and *N. apicalis* was high in almost all the fields observed, even in seedbeds. Some seedlings in seedbeds had the typical yellowing and stunting symptoms of the disease before transplanting.

The virus. The tungro virus recovered by insects from diseased plants from Cotabato was inoculated to seedlings of Taichung Native 1 and FK 135. After an incubation period the inoculated seedlings showed typical symptoms of the disease. In particular, the chlorotic stripes on the leaves of FK 135 were similar to the symptoms caused by the "S" strain of the virus.

Life span of the vector. The progeny of the first two generations of the insects from Cotabato that were reared on Taichung Native 1 seedlings were designated the "Cotabato colony." For purposes of comparison, insects of the same species reared in the Institute for the last several years, designated as the "IRRI colony," were used as checks.

The life spans of adult *N. impicticeps* of these colonies on seedlings of several rice varieties

were compared. The insects of both colonies survived longer on Taichung Native 1 than on Pankhari 203 (fig. 22) indicating that Pankhari 203 is resistant to both colonies. However, the life span of the insects of the Cotabato colony on seedlings of resistant varieties such as ASD 7, IR8, and Pankhari 203 seemed slightly longer than the life span of insects of the IRRI colony. The life span of the insects of the Cotabato colony on IRRI varieties was also generally longer than that of the IRRI colony. Whether this means that biological strains or ecotypes of *N. impicticeps* exist in different geographic regions remains uncertain.

The life span of adult *N. apicalis* of the Cotabato colony was slightly longer than that of the IRRI colony on seedlings of ASD 7, FK 135, IR5, IR8, IR20, IR22, Pankhari 203, and Taichung Native 1.

Transmissive ability. The insects of the Cotabato colony were able to transmit tungro virus to all four IRRI varieties. A comparison of daily serial transmission between the two colonies indicated that incubation period, retention period, and loss of infectivity with time after acquisition feeding of the Cotabato colony and the IRRI colony were similar. In other words, the virus-vector interaction of both colonies was fundamentally the same (fig. 23). The IRRI colony however, had 86.6 percent infective insects while the Cotabato colony had 88.6 percent. The IRRI colony had 1.47 disease-transmitting days and the Cotabato colony, 1.74, but the difference was not statistically significant. The transmissive ability of the Cotabato colony therefore was similar to that of the IRRI colony.

N. apicalis collected from Cotabato was able to transmit tungro virus after acquisition feeding, but the virus did not persist in the vector (fig. 24). Only 20.6 percent of the insects were infective and the number of disease-transmitting days was 1.14. These data were lower than those for *N. impicticeps* of either the IRRI or the Cotabato colony. These data and the retention period (fig. 24) show that *N. apicalis* of Cotabato transmitted the virus less efficiently than *N. impicticeps*. Similar results were obtained

previously for *N. apicalis* collected in Laguna (1968 Annual Report).

Bawden stated that viruses spread in a crop if a source of the virus is present, a vector is present, and the vector moves. Furthermore, he attributed regional and seasonal differences in the severity of individual virus diseases partly to changes in the number of virus sources, but mainly to changes in the number and activity of vectors. Susceptibility of the host and transmissive ability of the vector may also be essential for the spread of a virus disease. The perpetuation cycle of tungro virus under natural conditions remains obscure, nevertheless volunteer plants of a previously infected crop and infected plants under an overlapping cropping system can serve as sources of the virus. Since *N. impicticeps* and *N. apicalis* in Cotabato did not differ greatly in transmissive ability from the IRRI colonies, the transmissive ability of these vectors could not be considered the major factor in the outbreaks of the disease in Cotabato.

Because the disease is transmitted by the insects, the insect population in Cotabato cannot be ruled out among the causes for the outbreak of the disease. Whether favorable environmental conditions, or adaptability of the vectors to IRRI varieties, particularly IR8, caused the high population of the insects is not clear.

Varietal resistance to grassy stunt

Testing of rice varieties for their reaction to grassy stunt disease by mass screening (1968 Annual Report) was continued. A total of 3,373 entries, consisting of 277 entries of *Oryza* spp. other than rice, 1,198 rice varieties, 246 selections of IRRI crosses, 958 entries of genetical materials, and 694 entries of duplicates, were tested in 1970. Except for a line of *O. nivara*, a wild *Oryza* species, no entry consistently showed less than 30 percent infection.

O. nivara. *O. nivara* remained the best source of resistance to grassy stunt. To confirm its resistance, seedlings of *O. nivara* and Taichung Native 1 were inoculated by four methods: mass screening; inoculating individual seedlings with one viruliferous *Nilaparvata lugens* for 1 to

22. Life span of adult *N. impicticeps* of the IRRI and Cotabato colonies allowed to feed on seedlings of seven rice varieties.

6 days; inoculating seedlings with 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, and 64 viruliferous insects per seedling for 1 day; and inoculating seedlings alternatively every other day with 1 to 8 infective insects per seedling. Regardless of inoculation method used, *O. nivara* consistently had a substantially

lower percentage of infected seedlings than Taichung Native 1.

O. nivara was not immune to grassy stunt. Once infected, it was stunted and had profuse tillering and it served as a virus source. When the insects acquired the virus from diseased *O. nivara* plants, 26.5 percent were infective. The incubation period of these infective insects was 8 to 23 days (average 11.4 days). The insects had 0.14 to 0.69 disease-transmitting days (average 0.48 days) from 5 days after acquisition feeding to the death of insect.

But if seedlings were not infected after inoculation they grew like seedlings infested by virus-free insects (fig. 25). Four weeks after treatment, seedlings infested with nonviruliferous insects had 4.0 tillers per seedling, uninfected seedlings infested by viruliferous insects had 4.2, and seedlings without insect infestation had 4.7. Uninfected *O. nivara* plants remained symptomless even after ratooning and they did not act as a virus source. In fact, when 80 insects

23. Daily serial transmission of rice tungro virus by *N. impicticeps* of the IRRI and Cotabato colonies.

were used to recover the virus from inoculated *O. nivara* which showed no symptoms, none of the insects became infective after incubation.

O. nivara did not alter the infectivity of viruliferous *N. lugens*. When viruliferous insects were confined on seedlings of *O. nivara* for 1 to 16 days before the inoculation test, 27.9 percent were infective and when they were confined on seedlings of Taichung Native 1 for a similar period, 29.3 percent were infective.

To confirm the susceptibility of *O. nivara* to the brown planthopper, the vector of grassy stunt, the life span and the number of insects produced by female brown planthoppers on seedlings of rice varieties were determined. The evidence obtained (Table 17) indicates that *O. nivara* should be considered susceptible. It was not as resistant to the brown planthopper as was ASD 7 or Mudgo.

Inheritance of resistance. A strain of *Oryza nivara* resistant to grassy stunt virus was crossed with IR8, IR20, IR661-1-140-3-2, and IR773A1-36-2 in six combinations to transfer the resistance of *O. nivara* to these varieties. Readings were taken 45 days after inoculation. All the data indicated that resistance is essentially governed by a single pair of genes (Table 18). The F₁ individuals were as resistant as *O. nivara*. The F₂ populations segregated into healthy and diseased plants at a 3:1 ratio. When the resistant F₁ plants were crossed with the susceptible parents, the progeny segregated in a 1:1 ratio. The second backcrosses also showed a 1:1 ratio in the progeny. Statistical analysis showed that all have a good fit to the ratios.

Grassy stunt: vector-plant interactions

Damage to plant. Last year we showed that the vector of tungro virus, *N. impicticeps*, could retard plant growth, even if the vector was virus-free. The damaged plants gradually recover although severely damaged plants take longer. Since grassy stunt is also transmitted by an insect, an investigation was made to distinguish damage caused by the brown planthopper, *N. lugens*, itself from damage caused by the insect plus the disease agent.

24. Daily serial transmission of rice tungro virus by *Nephotettix apicalis* collected from Cotabato.

We found that the brown planthopper is capable of retarding the growth of seedlings of ASD 7, Mudgo, IR20 (Tables 19 and 20), and Taichung Native 1 (fig. 26). The degree of retardation was often proportional to the number of insects or to the number of days the insects were allowed to feed. Growth retardation generally became obvious about 1 to 2 weeks

Table 17. Life span and number of insects produced by grassy stunt viruliferous *Nilaparvata lugens* on different rice varieties in two experiments.

Variety	Average life span (days)		Insects produced by a female (no.)	
	Expt. I	Expt. II	Expt. I	Expt. II
ASD 7	2.9	3.5	7	6
IR20	—	7.5	—	192
Mudgo	3.4	—	31	—
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	9.4	7.7	83	98
Taichung Native 1	9.7	8.1	112	131

Table 18. Numbers of healthy and grassy stunt-infected plants in crosses between *Oryza nivara* and IR8, IR773A1-36-2, and IR661-1-140-3-2 in F₁, F₂, backcross I, and backcross II, and in the parents.

Cross and parents	Plants (no.)							
	F ₁ ^a		F ₂ ^a		Backcross I ^a		Backcross II ^a	
	Infected	Healthy	Infected	Healthy	Infected	Healthy	Infected	Healthy
	<i>Progeny</i>							
IR773A1-36-2 x <i>O. nivara</i>	5	88	91	243	42	42	515	495
IR20 x <i>O. nivara</i>	0	16	84	174	12	19	68	54
<i>O. nivara</i> x IR20	0	3	11	40	—	—	—	—
IR661-1-140-3-2 x <i>O. nivara</i>	8	62	96	272	29	32	187	169
IR8 x <i>O. nivara</i>	0	33	56	160	30	37	113	113
<i>O. nivara</i> x IR8	0	6	78	265	2	3	36	30
	<i>Parents</i>							
IR773A1-36-2	24	5	410	3	140	3	34	1
IR20	409	173	94	3	94	3	22	3
IR661-1-140-3-2	62	10	136	1	136	1	26	1
IR8	255	4	126	1	126	1	23	2
<i>O. nivara</i>	25	472	1	41	1	42	0	55

^a Values for parents are from tests of plants grown at the same time as the progeny.

after insect infestation. Thereafter, the damage gradually became unnoticeable, although plants damaged by a greater number of insects (Table 19) or by a longer insect-feeding duration (Table 20) took longer to recover. Growth was retarded not only on varieties susceptible to the insect but also on resistant varieties, such as ASD 7 and Mudgo. The brown planthopper, *N. lugens*, did not generally retard plant growth as severely as the green leafhopper, *N. impicticeps*, when infestation took place at the seedling stage.

The disease agent retarded growth more than did the vector. This difference became noticeable

about 2 weeks after treatment and gradually became more striking because the infected plants were all stunted (fig. 26, Tables 19 and 20).

Except when insect damage was heavy, there were no striking differences in number of tillers per seedling among seedlings infested by various numbers of insects or among seedlings on which the insects fed for different numbers of days. When seedlings were infected with the disease agent, however, the number of tillers increased significantly. At 4 weeks after treatment, seedlings of the four tested varieties without insect infestation had 4.7 tillers per seedling, seedlings with infestation had 4.1, and seedlings infected with the disease agent had 8.7.

Table 19. Effect of number of insects (*Nilaparvata lugens*) and of insects plus grassy stunt on the growth of IR20 seedlings.

Kind of insect	Insects feeding in 1 day (no.)	Average plant height (cm)					
		Before treatment	Weeks after treatment				
			1	2	4	8	
Control	0	13.4	26.1	37.8	60.6	69.0	
Virus-free	1	13.4	22.5	34.4	56.8	68.7	
	2	13.6	21.2	33.9	59.2	72.7	
	4	13.4	20.2	33.0	57.0	73.1	
	8	13.1	20.1	34.0	59.4	76.0	
	16	12.9	17.6	32.3	57.4	72.6	
	32	12.5	16.6	29.1	53.7	71.8	
Viruliferous ^a	1	14.3	23.0	30.5	36.0	39.5	
	2	10.4	17.3	28.0	37.5	36.5	
	4	13.7	21.5	30.8	40.7	43.4	
	8	13.1	21.4	33.0	41.3	41.4	
	16	12.1	18.1	30.2	40.5	40.7	
	32	12.8	14.8	27.3	34.3	39.3	

^a Seedlings were infected with grassy stunt after feeding.

Plant age and infection. To confirm the finding that rice plants become less susceptible to grassy stunt at later stages of growth, eight rice varieties were inoculated under the same conditions at different dates after sowing. Regardless of variety, the percentage of diseased seedlings was always lower when seedlings were inoculated at an older age (Table 21). The degree of decrease with increasing age of the plant differed among rice varieties, however.

The plants inoculated at an old age which did not become diseased usually remained symptomless until harvest. To find out if these symptomless plants were really free from infection, rice seedlings were inoculated at 30 and 40 days

after sowing. After the plants produced panicles, they were ratooned. Except for *O. nivara*, all the surviving plants showed symptoms after ratooning, indicating that they were actually infected but did not show symptoms before harvest (Table 22).

To determine whether rice plants with no symptoms of grassy stunt disease occur under natural conditions, 48 hills of apparently healthy IR20 were selected at harvesting stage from an experimental plot of the entomology department where disease incidence was high and where about 50 percent of the IR20 hills were diseased. The selected hills were transplanted in pots and ratooned. Two months later, only two hills remained healthy, 11 hills showed typical symptoms of grassy stunt, and the rest consisted of diseased and healthy plants in various proportions since the hills were not originally from a single seedling. Obviously, symptomless rice plants that were actually infected with grassy stunt disease occurred in the field.

Rice plants that are symptomless might be a source of the disease agent for the insect. Insects were used to recover the disease agent from IR20 plants that were apparently healthy at harvesting stage. None of the 145 insects that fed on two plants that remained healthy after ratooning

Table 20. Effect of number of feeding days of insects (*Nilaparvata lugens*) and of insects plus grassy stunt on the growth of IR20 seedlings.

Kind of insect	Feeding days (no.) ^a	Average plant height (cm)			
		Before treatment	Weeks after treatment		
			2	4	8
Control	0	15.3	34.5	60.4	69.5
Virus-free	1	15.3	36.5	60.9	68.5
	2	15.1	34.2	57.4	67.7
	4	16.1	31.1	56.7	64.2
	8	15.3	18.0	46.8	69.0
Viruliferous ^b	1	20.5	41.0	45.5	38.5
	2	15.1	31.7	42.0	37.5
	4	15.2	27.2	34.2	38.1
	8	16.4	23.9	31.2	34.3

^aTwo insects per seedling. ^bSeedlings were infected with grassy stunt after feeding.

became infective. On the other hand, three of 67, three of 79, and none of 79 insects that fed on three different plants that showed symptoms after ratooning became infective. Apparently, the insects could acquire the disease agent from plants symptomless before ratooning, but only a small percentage of the insects became infective.

Vector in different localities. The transmissive ability of *N. lugens* of San Pablo City; Pototan, Iloilo; and Valencia, BuSidnon, was compared with the transmissive ability of the insects of the

25. Growth of *Oryza nivara* seedlings infested by various numbers of virus-free and grassy stunt viruliferous *Nilaparvata lugens*.

26. Effect of insects (*Nilaparvata lugens*) and of insects plus grassy stunt virus on the growth of Taichung Native 1 seedlings.

Table 21. Percentages of diseased seedlings of rice varieties inoculated with grassy stunt at various plant ages.

Variety	Diseased seedlings (%)			
	Age at inoculation (days)			
	10	20	30	40
BPI-76	100	70	49	27
C4-63	100	45	34	26
IR5	99	73	63	39
IR8	100	81	60	47
IR20	98	61	34	18
IR22	99	78	61	29
Mudgo	100	61	20	12
Taichung Native 1	100	80	77	50

IRRI colony on the basis of active transmitters, length of incubation period of infective insects, number of disease-transmitting days, and length of retention period. The results showed no striking differences between the transmissible abilities of these insects.

Adaptability to Mudgo. The brown planthopper is able to gradually develop its adaptability to Mudgo if the insect is reared continuously on Mudgo (1969 Annual Report). To evaluate further the adaptability of the insect to Mudgo, rearing of the insect on Mudgo was continued. The life spans of insects of the 14th and 19th generation on Taichung Native 1 and on Mudgo were very similar with the life span of the insects of the 10th generation.

Studies on the adaptability of *N. lugens* reared over several generations on Mudgo plants mixed in various proportions with plants of Taichung Native 1 indicated that insects reared on mixed

Table 22. Expression of symptoms of grassy stunt disease on regenerated growth of rice varieties inoculated at different plant ages.

Variety	Seedlings of original crop (no.)		Surviving ratoon plants (no.)	
	Total inoculated	With symptoms	Total ^a	With symptoms
<i>Inoculated at 30 days</i>				
ASD 7	40	22	14	14
IR20	38	20	16	16
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	38	0	38	0
Taichung Native 1	40	29	10	10
<i>Inoculated at 40 days</i>				
ASD 7	40	7	29	29
IR20	40	5	32	32
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	39	0	39	0
Taichung Native 1	40	19	17	17

^aExcluding those showing symptoms before ratooning.

plants of 95 percent Mudgo and 5 percent Taichung Native 1 had significantly longer life spans on Mudgo than insects reared on Taichung Native 1 alone. But the life span of insects reared on a mixture of 5 percent Mudgo and 95 percent Taichung Native 1 remained short on Mudgo. Consequently, the insects built up their adaptability to Mudgo only when Mudgo made up a high proportion of the feeding materials.

The results of a study of transmission of grassy stunt disease by insects of the 14th and 19th generations indicated that the percentage of active transmitters of these insects did not differ from that of the field population. Similar results were obtained from the insects reared on mixed population of Mudgo and Taichung Native 1.

Soil Chemistry

The main areas of research were zinc deficiency in lowland rice, amelioration of problem soils, water regime in rice soils, varietal differences in resistance to adverse soil conditions, and the thermodynamics of flooded soils.

Zinc deficiency was found to be a widespread nutritional disorder of rice on soils with a high pH or a high watertable. Incorporation of organic matter depressed the concentration of zinc in the solutions of flooded soils and zinc uptake by the rice plant. Drying the soil may be as good a remedy for zinc deficiency on permanently wet soils as applying zinc chloride, zinc sulfate, or zinc oxide.

A combination of leaching and liming gave the highest yield of rice on an acid sulfate soil from Thailand. Liming of acid soils was found to be unnecessary if iron toxicity was not a problem. Delaying submergence until 1 week before initiation of the panicle primordia markedly increased the yield of rice on a cold acid soil.

The low yield of grain in soils at field capacity was due to aluminum and manganese toxicity in strongly acid soils and to iron deficiency in neutral and calcareous soils.

Varieties differed markedly in their resistance to injury caused by too much or too little iron, phosphorus deficiency, excess manganese, and excess reduction products.

The solubility of zinc in flooded soils appeared to be governed by ionic equilibria involving zinc phosphate, zinc ammonium phosphate, zinc sulfide, and zinc silicate. The redox potentials of most flooded soils are determined by the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3\text{—Fe}^{2+}$ system.

The reducing properties of the solutions of flooded soils are due partly to the presence of ferulic and sinapic acids.

Zinc deficiency

Although zinc deficiency was one of the first micronutrient deficiencies recognized in upland crops, the first report of a disorder of rice which was corrected by the application of a zinc salt occurred only in 1966. Field surveys and laboratory and greenhouse studies by IRRI physiologists in recent years showed that zinc deficiency in lowland rice, as in upland crops, was invariably associated with a high soil pH. Now we have evidence that zinc deficiency may occur in flooded soils with air-dry pH values as low as 4.8 if kept continuously submerged and that zinc deficiency may retard the growth of rice on many soils where the moisture regime favors the accumulation of organic matter. Because zinc deficiency appeared to be a widespread disorder of lowland rice, considerable time was devoted to the study of the availability of zinc in flooded soils and practical methods of correcting zinc deficiency.

Availability of zinc in flooded soils. Zinc deficiency in upland crops is associated with high pH, high content of organic matter, or high phosphorus availability. To ascertain to what extent these factors influence the availability of zinc in flooded soils, we grew IR22 on 15 soils varying in pH, organic matter content, and phosphorus

availability. We also followed the kinetics of water-soluble zinc and the uptake of zinc by the plant.

The pH, organic matter content, and phosphorus availability, and the content of either total or available zinc in the soils were not correlated (Table 1). But the kinetics of water-soluble and available zinc (Table 2) appear to reflect the influence of pH, the organic matter content, or the level of phosphorus of the soils.

In all soils, the concentration of zinc in the soil solution declined with duration of submergence: after 10 weeks, it was less than 0.1 ppm except in the three strongly acid soils (acid sulfate clay, Philippines; acid sulfate clay, Vietnam, and Louisiana clay). The decrease in concentration was most rapid in the neutral and calcareous soils and least in the strongly acid soils, although the pH values of all soils (except the two acid sulfate soils) were between 6.5 and 6.7 after 4 weeks' submergence. By and large, soils with a high content of available and water-soluble phosphorus had low concentrations of water-soluble zinc, regardless of pH or the content of total or available zinc. And, barring the two acid sulfate soils, soils high in organic matter tended to have low zinc concentrations after 2 weeks of flooding.

The zinc content of the plant reflected the operation of these factors, as the following regression indicates:

Table 1. Influence of soil properties on the content of total and available zinc.

Soil	pH	Organic matter (%)	P ^a (ppm)	Zinc (ppm)	
				Total ^b	Available ^c
Acid sulfate clay (Philippines)	3.7	4.4	92	77	6.1
Acid sulfate clay (Vietnam)	3.8	7.2	4	42	5.1
Louisiana clay	4.9	2.9	22	114	19.5
Kalayaan ^d clay loam	5.6	16.0	76	93	21.3
Antipolo clay	6.0	2.6	18	73	11.7
Butuan clay	6.8	5.0	78	73	21.9
Maahas clay	7.1	2.4	20	104	35.9
Pila clay loam	7.1	4.0	134	135	31.9
Parayao ^d clay	7.2	1.7	16	96	15.6
Luna ^d clay	7.3	1.9	24	92	12.0
San Pablo ^d clay	7.4	4.7	44	75	16.7
San Roque ^d sandy loam	7.6	3.3	32	75	19.5
Aggaie ^d loam	7.8	1.5	12	36	5.2
Magalang ^d loam	8.0	2.9	38	72	12.7

^a0.5 M NaHCO₃ extraction. ^b0.1 N HCl extraction. ^cQuadruple acid digestion. ^dName of place where sample was taken.

$$X_1 = 119.3 - 14.56 X_2 - 0.746 X_3 - 1.197 X_4 + 27.01 X_5 + 0.174 (X_2 X_4) - 1.181 (X_2 X_5) - (1.98^{ns}) - (0.73^{ns}) - (2.73^*) - (0.35^{ns}) - (2.39^*) - (-0.067^{ns})$$

where:

- X₁ = Zinc content of the straw at harvest (ppm).
- X₂ = pH of the air-dry soil.
- X₃ = Percentage of organic matter in the soil.
- X₄ = Available P content of the soil (ppm).
- X₅ = Concentration of zinc (ppm) in the soil solution just after submergence.

This equation reveals that as the available P content of the soil increased, the zinc content of the straw decreased and that the interaction between available P and pH influenced the zinc content of the straw. The high P:Zn ratio in the straw of zinc-deficient plants reflects this interaction (Table 3).

Table 3. Some morphological traits of parents, F₁, and BC₁ generations in the breeding program for resistance to grassy stunt.

Generation	Height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Awns ^a	Sterility (%)	Fragility ^b	Flagleaf angle ^c	Pericarp color
IR661-1-140-3 (P ₁)	86	34	0	14	1	E	Brown
<i>O. nivara</i> (P ₂)	72	15	4	36	4	D	Red
F ₁	115	41	3	13	3	I	Red
5256-1 (BC ₁)	78	28	1	49	1	E	Brown
2	95	38	2	15	2	E	Brown
3	94	40	2	18	2	D	Red
4	85	22	2	29	2	E	Brown
5	109	29	0	37	3	E	Brown
6	106	37	0	8	3	E	Red
7	94	31	3	27	2	E	Brown
8	107	51	3	18	3	E	Red
9	135	26	1	44	1	E	Brown
10	133	60	2	31	2	E	Red
11	94	45	3	24	3	D	Red
12	102	53	2	13	2	D	Brown
5329-1	95	23	0	40	3	D	Red
2	88	40	0	43	2	E	Brown
3	83	20	1	16	2	E	Red
4	87	45	0	28	2	E	Brown
5	80	39	1	5	1	E	Red

^a0=No awns, 1=very small awns, 2=awns half the length of P₂, 3=awns $\frac{1}{2}$ the length of P₂, 4=awns 6-7 cm long like those of *O. nivara*. ^b1=non-fragile, 2=slightly fragile, 3=moderately fragile, 4=highly fragile. ^cE=erect, D=droopy, I=intermediate.

and Institute breeding lines for sources of resistance. At present IR8 is among the more resistant types to sheath blight.

Brown planthoppers. Selections from the IR532-1-33 x Mudgo cross that are resistant to brown planthoppers were evaluated. Most have weak stems and are susceptible to several diseases. Resistant lines with good plant type and sturdy stems have been identified from IR8/2 x Mudgo but most of them have poor grains. Lines resistant to brown planthoppers from (Luang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263 have good grains and in addition possess resistance to several diseases and to green leafhoppers.

An F₄ line resistant to brown planthoppers from IR8 x Mudgo was crossed with IR661-1-140-3. Many F₃ lines from this cross with good plant type and grain quality and resistance to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers were identified. Several are resistant to bacterial leaf streak and tungro virus.

IR747B2-6-3, a selection that is resistant to brown planthoppers and which has short growth duration but weak stems, was crossed with IR579-48-1, an early maturing selection that has sturdier stems and long, slender grains. F₃ and F₄ selections of 100 days growth duration

from this cross have been selected which are resistant to brown planthoppers and to bacterial diseases.

Green leafhoppers. Since varieties resistant to green leafhoppers, such as IR8, Peta, Sigadis, and Pankhari 203, have been used as parents in many crosses, perhaps a majority of Institute breeding lines are resistant to green leafhoppers. Efforts are now under way to combine resistance to green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers with resistance to important diseases. Several F₆ lines resistant to both insects were identified from (Luang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263. Many F₄ lines from IR8/2 x Mudgo are also resistant to both insects but all of them have poor grains. Another promising cross that has lines resistant to both insects and several diseases is IR661-1-140-3 x (IR8 x Mudgo). Most of the lines of this cross have good grain and excellent plant type.

Gall midge. Forty F₆ selections from (Luang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263 were evaluated for resistance to gall midge in cooperation with Thai entomologists. Twelve of these were highly resistant to gall midge. Several were resistant to green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers. In addition some had resistance to tungro and

either depressed the availability of zinc or hindered its uptake by the rice plant through its effects on soil metabolism.

The incorporation of cellulose markedly depressed the concentration of water-soluble zinc in all soils, but retarded vegetative growth and decreased the yield of grain only on the three soils in which zinc deficiency occurred. It depressed straw yield but not grain yield on the other soils (Table 5).

Figure 1 shows how cellulose affects the kinetics of some factors which may influence the availability of zinc to the rice plant. In Casiguran sandy loam, cellulose depressed pH, had no effect on P_{CO_2} , and brought down the concentration of water-soluble iron. Because these effects favor the uptake of zinc, cellulose had no adverse effect on the grain yield or on the zinc content of the straw on Casiguran sandy loam (Table 5). In Luna and Butuan clays, cellulose depressed pH but increased P_{CO_2} . The high P_{CO_2} probably reduced the availability of zinc in both soils and caused zinc deficiency.

The content of iron, manganese, and zinc in the active center leaf and the straw gave no indication that iron or manganese interfered with uptake of zinc. This agrees with the data in Table 3.

Table 5. Influence of cellulose on the yield of rice, on the zinc content of the straw, and on the mean concentration of zinc in soil solutions of flooded soils.

Soil	pH	Organic matter (%)	Added cellulose (%)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Zn concn. (ppm)		Zn deficiency symptoms ^b
						Straw	Soil solution ^a	
Luisiana clay	4.7	3.2	0	50	35	45	0.30	0
			0.5	38	34	34	0.16	0
Casiguran sandy loam	4.8	4.4	0	76	73	33	0.16	0
			0.5	80	85	32	0.13	0
Sandy loam from Korea	4.8	1.5	0	45	28	62	0.33	0
			0.5	40	21	47	0.15	0
Pulilan fine sandy loam	6.5	2.3	0	53	44	19	0.18	0
			0.5	36	42	18	0.19	1
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	0	63	49	47	0.21	0
			0.5	55	60	28	0.14	0
Pila clay loam	7.6	1.5	0	84	100	30	0.22	0
			0.5	58	99	28	0.12	0
Silo silt loam	8.0	2.0	0	38	54	38	0.13	0
			0.5	22	22	23	0.05	0
Aggaie loam	7.9	1.2	0	46	43	30	0.11	1
			0.5	35	31	34	0.14	2
Butuan clay (Ampayan)	6.8	5.4	0	53	59	17	0.16	4
			0.5	33	38	13	0.16	4
Butuan clay (Luna)	6.5	5.3	0	50	56	22	0.19	4
			0.5	9	5	17	0.13	5

^aMean concentration during the first 12 weeks of submergence. ^bScale: 0=symptoms absent; 5=symptoms most pronounced.

Forms and levels of zinc. The effects of four forms of zinc (chloride, sulfate, oxide, and the metal) at 0, 10, and 20 kg/ha of zinc on the growth and yield of IR22 on Butuan clay (a soil on which zinc deficiency occurs) were studied in the greenhouse in the wet season.

Regardless of form, 10 kg/ha Zn increased the yield of straw and grain, but applying zinc oxide at 20 kg/ha Zn resulted in the largest number of tillers, the highest weight of straw and grain, and the highest content of zinc in the plant.

Because zinc oxide is a harmless, inexpensive, commercial chemical, it may prove a practical remedy for zinc deficiency in flooded rice fields.

Used flashlight batteries as a zinc source. A standard flashlight battery contains 14 g of zinc, some zinc chloride, 6 g of ammonium chloride, 19 g of manganese dioxide, and some copper in the brass cap of the carbon rod. Thousands of these batteries are thrown daily into trash cans. If instead, they are thrown into rice fields, they could alleviate zinc deficiency and provide manganese and copper in soils deficient in these two micronutrients.

In an exploratory greenhouse test, IR22 was grown on four flooded soils with zero, one, and

1. Kinetics of the pH, P_{CO_2} and water-soluble iron of three flooded soils with and without 0.5 percent added cellulose.

Table 6. Influence of used dry cell batteries on the yield and zinc content of IR22 on flooded Butuan clay with and without added cellulose.

Dry cells (no./pot)	Tillers (no.)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Zn (ppm)	
				Flag leaf	Straw
<i>Without added cellulose</i>					
0	45	57	44	19	6
½	69	114	102	21	92
1	60	96	61	47	112
2	45	68	36	71	376
<i>With added cellulose (5%)</i>					
0	14	8	1	20	6
½	30	89	34	33	23
1	36	103	36	36	65
2	21	54	26	66	82

10 sliced batteries per 10 kg of soil. Ten weeks later the plants were harvested.

A single battery greatly improved tiller number and the weight of straw on Butuan clay (a soil on which zinc deficiency occurs). Its effect was moderate in Casiguran sandy loam and Maahas clay. It depressed growth in Malabog sandy loam (pH 6.5; organic matter 2.5%; cation exchange capacity: 13 meq/100 g). Ten batteries were lethal on all soils apparently because of zinc toxicity and the release of too much ammonium chloride into the soil solution.

Although the plants on the zinc deficient soil responded to the presence of a battery, it was not clear whether the increase in yield was due to zinc, nitrogen, manganese dioxide, copper, or all combined.

2. Response of IR22 to the addition of used flashlight batteries on Butuan clay in the presence of 0.5 percent cellulose.

In a second experiment, the response of IR22 to zero, one-half, one, and two standard used dry cells per 10 kg of Butuan clay from Luna (Philippines) with and without 0.5% cellulose (added to intensify zinc deficiency) was studied in the greenhouse along with four forms of zinc (chloride, sulfate, oxide, and the metal) at various rates. Table 6 and figure 2 show the marked benefits of the addition of half a battery, especially in the presence of cellulose. Because zinc deficiency symptoms were eliminated by both the application of zinc by batteries and because the zinc content of the plant increased, it is apparent that used flashlight batteries corrected zinc deficiency of rice on this soil.

A field test in a farmer's field at Luna, Agusan del Norte, Philippines, showed that the growth of rice improved markedly as the number of batteries per square meter was increased from zero to four.

Zinc deficiency on Maahas clay. Maahas clay, which is the dominant soil at the Institute experimental farm, appears to be an ideal soil for lowland rice. It is not a soil on which, a year ago, one would have expected to encounter zinc deficiency. Certain blocks, however, have been cropped the year around for 7 years and therefore have been continuously wet. Now there are signs that the stunted growth and discoloration of leaves of rice plants in these blocks are at least partly due to zinc deficiency. Apparently, the increase in pH from 6.0 to 7.1 by irrigation with alkaline water, coupled with the increase in organic matter content from 2.0 to 2.4 percent during the 7-year period has made zinc less available.

In the greenhouse, when we added zinc chloride at 20 kg/ha Zn to mud from an affected area, the number of tillers and the weight of straw increased but the grain yield did not (Table 7). Air-drying the soil followed by flooding produced a dramatic increase in yield.

Growing two crops of rice a year with an upland crop between them might be a better way of preventing zinc deficiency of lowland rice than applying zinc to the soil.

Zinc deficiency in acid soils. After discovering the widespread occurrence of zinc deficiency

Table 7. Influence of some treatments on the growth and yield of IR22 on Maahas clay from a continuously cropped (continuously wet) area of the Institute farm.

Treatment	Tillers (no.)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Zn in straw (ppm)
Mud	34	79	57	20
Mud + ZnCl ₂	45	97	52	23
Mud + cellulose	19	47	42	16
Dried and kept at field capacity	29	86	34	67
Dried and flooded at planting	71	140	80	47

in rice on the slightly acid, perennially wet soils of Agusan del Norte, we examined rice plants on 20 soils (pH values from 4.6 to 8.1) which had been kept continuously submerged for 3 years in pots (in duplicate) and planted to rice in eight successive seasons after incorporation of stubble and complete fertilizer. We observed typical symptoms of zinc deficiency — interveinal chlorosis of the emerging leaf and reddish-brown spots on the leaves — on rice plants in 10 of the 20 soils. The addition of zinc chloride produced a dramatic response. Only two soils had aerobic pH values exceeding 6.9 at the start of the experiment. Zinc deficiency was visible on one soil which had an initial pH as low as 4.8. Although the pH values of the soils (measured after air-drying) had increased during this period, only one of the soils had a pH value above 6.8 at the time deficiency symptoms were observed. The concentration of zinc in the solutions of the soils on which zinc deficiency was observed was less than 0.1 ppm.

Zinc deficiency may be one cause of the downward trend in yield after the fourth crop (fig. 3) in these continuously submerged soils.

Problem rice soils

In many parts of the tropics, soil problems prevent the new improved varieties from yielding, even with good management, as much as they should. We procured samples of such soils and studied them in the laboratory and the greenhouse. Where possible, field experiments on the spot supplemented studies at the Institute.

A widespread physiological disorder of rice in Agusan del Norte was diagnosed as zinc

deficiency, and a simple means of correcting it was found (see previous section). The growth of rice on an acid sulfate soil from Thailand was improved by a combination of leaching and liming. Severe stunting and reddish-brown discoloration of the leaves on the ferrallitic soils from Taiwan and Colombia were identified as iron toxicity and alleviated by liming. The trouble with the calcareous soil from Aggaie, Nigeria, was zinc deficiency and low nutrient status. Studies of the soils, which were available in sufficient quantity for replicated greenhouse experiments, are reported below.

An acid sulfate soil from Thailand. Acid sulfate soils cover 1.5 million hectares in Thailand. Because some of these soils have been irrigated for decades with alkaline irrigation water and have attained pH values above 4.5 they are not considered problem soils. There are, however, about half a million hectares where acidity may be a retarding factor. Two tons of such a moderately acid soil (an acid sulfate soil of the Ongkharak series) were shipped to the Institute for study.

Earlier work with an acid sulfate soil from Vietnam (1965 Annual Report) showed that liming, application of manganese dioxide, and prolonged submergence were useful amendments, and that leaching might be an additional

3. Mean yield of rice on 20 soils kept continuously submerged.

4. Influence of leaching and liming on the kinetics of specific conductivity, water-soluble iron, and P_{CO_2} in a flooded acid sulfate soil.

benefit. So the factorial combinations of pre-submergence (0 and 4 weeks), lime (0 and 7 t/ha $CaCO_3$), manganese dioxide (0 and 0.5% MnO_2), and no leaching and leaching were studied in the greenhouse with RD1, a new Thai variety, as the test plant.

The best growth of rice was obtained in the treatment combinations that included leaching, liming, or MnO_2 . The treatment that combined leaching, liming, and MnO_2 gave the highest yield of straw (155 g/pot). The single-factor treatments gave a mean yield of 131 g/pot of straw, while the check yielded 135 g/pot. Leaching combined with liming gave the highest grain yield, 48.5 g/pot, compared with 43.5 g for liming, 42.2 g for leaching, and 36.4 g for check. Leaching markedly depressed the concentration of salts, iron, and CO_2 (fig. 4). So it is not clear what additional benefits were derived by liming. The yield of grain for all treatments was unusually low because of the high percentage of sterility (28 to 41%) due to bad weather.

The responses to lime and manganese dioxide were not as marked as in the acid sulfate soil from Vietnam (1965 Annual Report) because 1) the initial pH was not too low; 2) the concentration of water-soluble iron was unusually low at all stages of growth of the crop, apparently because iron was present as a solid more stable than $Fe(OH)_3$; and 3) the Thai variety RD1 is probably adapted to acid sulfate soils.

Even though the soil was not too acid and did not contain too much salt, leaching plus liming increased the yield of rice. Also, in view of claims that acid sulfate soils are deficient in zinc, it is noteworthy that the mean zinc content of the straw for the 16 treatment combinations was 61 ppm. This is three times the threshold value for zinc deficiency in rice.

Acid ferrallitic soils. Previous experiments (1968 Annual Report) showed that some benefits ascribed to liming of acid soils are achieved when the pH of acid soils increases during submergence. But in soils that are low in active iron or in soils that undergo reduction slowly, the increase in pH may not be rapid enough to prevent the build-up of high concentrations of water-soluble iron. Two such soils were compared with Louisiana clay, an acid soil that does

not respond to liming (1968 Annual Report), at two levels (0 and sufficient CaCO_3 to give an aerobic pH of 6.5) and two methods of application (liming and keeping the soil moist at field capacity for 2 weeks before planting and liming just before planting) in factorial combination. All treatments received 0.15 percent of a 1:1 mixture of chopped straw and *Glyricidia sepium* at the start of premoistening, and 100 ppm N, P, K at planting.

The effect of lime on the yield of straw and grain varied with the soil and the method of application (Table 8). On the average, lime depressed the yields of both straw and grain in Luisiana clay, increased both yields in the red soil from Taiwan, but had no significant effect in the silt loam from Korea. Liming and keeping the soil moist for 2 weeks markedly depressed the growth and yield of rice on Luisiana clay. On the two other soils the method of liming made no difference. Some of these results can be explained by chemical kinetics.

Lime, generally, depressed yield in Luisiana clay because of the severe injury in the treatment in which the soil was limed and kept moist for 2 weeks before flooding and planting. The injury was apparently due to nitrate which was present in concentrations exceeding 200 ppm N in the soil solution during the first 2 weeks of submergence and exceeding 25 ppm during the next 4 weeks. The apparent nitrate injury is difficult to understand, for nitrate retarded soil reduction and the build-up of high concentrations of iron, CO_2 , and organic acids in the soil solutions. Chemical analysis of the plant tissues, however, showed a higher, though not excessive, concentration of manganese in the limed, premoistened treatment than in the others (Table 9).

The marked response to lime in the ferrallitic clay from Taiwan was due to the alleviation of iron toxicity. Five weeks after transplanting, the plants in the unlimed pots showed symptoms similar to those of potassium deficiency—brown discoloration of the older leaves along the margins, followed by their death and desiccation. But several observations showed that the disorder was iron toxicity. First, the mean concentrations of potassium in the soil solution during the first 5 weeks were 31 ppm for the

unlimed soils and only 13 ppm for the limed soils. Second, concentrations of water-soluble iron were much higher in the unlimed soils than in the limed soils (fig. 5). Third, the concentration of potassium in the straw was well above the deficiency limit, while that of iron was considerably above the toxicity limit (Table 9). There was no response to lime in the silt loam from Korea apparently because high concentrations of iron were shortlived (fig. 5).

The experiment was repeated in the next season with a sandy soil high in organic matter (Casiguran sandy loam; pH 4.8; organic matter, 4.4%), a sandy soil low in organic matter (Badeggi sandy loam; pH 4.8; organic matter, 1.7%), and another ferrallitic clay from Taiwan (pH 4.8; organic matter, 2.3%). Liming followed by immediate flooding produced no significant increase in yield in any of the soils, but keeping the soil moist for 2 weeks before flooding benefited rice on Casiguran sandy loam.

Only soils that build up high concentrations of iron are likely to benefit from liming. Such soils should be limed just before flooding.

Table 8. Influence of the rate and method of liming of three soils on the yield of IR20 (LSD [5%] lime or method means within a soil: 8.9 for straw and 8.4 for grain).

Soil ^a	Limed ^b	Yield (g/pot)		
		Pre-moistened ^c	Not pre-moistened ^d	Mean
<i>Straw</i>				
Luisiana clay	No	141	154	148
	Yes	100	160	130
	Mean	121	157	—
Ferrallitic clay from Taiwan	No	57	58	57
	Yes	63	84	74
	Mean	60	71	—
Silt loam from Korea	No	74	74	74
	Yes	58	82	70
	Mean	66	78	—
<i>Grain</i>				
Luisiana clay	No	97.2	101.8	99.5
	Yes	71.5	93.2	82.4
	Mean	84.4	97.5	—
Ferrallitic clay from Taiwan	No	26.0	30.2	28.1
	Yes	42.2	41.0	41.6
	Mean	36.1	35.6	—
Silt loam from Korea	No	46.2	42.0	44.1
	Yes	40.0	46.0	43.1
	Mean	43.6	44.1	—

^aLuisiana clay—pH 4.8, organic matter: 3.2%, Fe: 3.3%; ferrallitic clay from Taiwan—pH 4.8, organic matter: 1.5%, Fe: 2.1%; silt loam from Korea—pH 4.8, organic matter: 1.5%, Fe: 0.46%. ^bTo pH 6.5. ^cKept moist for 2 weeks before flooding and planting. ^dFlooded and planted without premoistening.

5. Kinetics of water-soluble iron in three soils.

Cold soils. Last year (1969 Annual Report) we showed that injury to rice plants caused by low temperature of flooded soils was associated with the accumulation of organic acids, carbon dioxide, and water-soluble iron. In greenhouse tests this year we found some water treatments and chemical amendments that counteract the build-up of high concentrations of these harmful substances at 20 C.

The water treatments were providing drainage to remove the toxic substances; midseason soil drying to oxidize reduction products and to let CO₂ escape; late flooding to enable the plants

to grow in a medium virtually free of these substances in the early stages; keeping the soil submerged for 4 weeks before planting to provide an environment low in organic acids, CO₂, and water-soluble iron in the later stages; and maintaining the soil at field capacity. Lime and manganese dioxide were used to depress the concentration of water-soluble iron. The soil was Louisiana clay (pH 4.7, organic matter 3.2%). It was treated with 0.15 percent of 1:1 mixture of chopped straw and *Glyricidia sepium* and 75 ppm each of N, P, and K.

Late flooding gave the highest yield of straw

Table 9. Influence of two rates of liming and two methods of water management on the yield of IR20, and the mineral composition of the leaves and straw.

Limed ^a	Premoistened ^b	Tillers (no.)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	In straw				In leaf ^c	
					P(%)	K(%)	Fe(ppm)	Mn(ppm)	Fe(ppm)	Mn(ppm)
<i>Louisiana clay</i>										
No	No	62	141	97	0.07	2.72	168	1260	150	807
No	Yes	72	155	102	0.06	2.94	161	1161	165	784
Yes	No	45	101	72	0.07	2.87	144	738	129	1076
Yes	Yes	69	160	93	0.07	3.26	154	808	124	759
<i>Ferrallitic clay from Taiwan</i>										
No	No	52	57	26	0.11	3.24	377	864	1177	624
No	Yes	50	58	30	0.10	3.64	325	869	901	673
Yes	No	35	63	42	0.07	3.53	117	1167	149	730
Yes	Yes	41	84	41	0.08	4.10	100	1008	132	725
<i>Silt loam from Korea</i>										
No	No	46	74	46	0.21	3.41	340	343	150	103
No	Yes	46	74	42	0.19	3.17	252	458	131	124
Yes	No	33	58	40	0.18	3.53	204	157	161	405
Yes	Yes	43	82	46	0.16	3.51	224	100	148	200

^aTo pH 6.5. ^bKept moist for 2 weeks before flooding and planting. ^cActive center leaf at panicle primordia initiation.

Table 10. Influence of six water treatments and two chemical amendments on the yield of IR20 and kinetics of reducing substances in Louisiana clay at 20 C in the greenhouse.

Treatment	Tillers (no.)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Sterility (%)	In straw (ppm)		Reducing substances (meq/liter)						
							Weeks submerged						
					Fe	Mn	0	2	4	6	8	12	16
Submerged throughout	38	74	60	14	297	1230	10.4	18.7	25.1	27.2	26.1	25.6	12.6
Presubmerged 4 weeks	32	62	51	14	254	1290	23.4	16.8	19.7	23.7	19.5	15.2	8.5
Submerged +1 cm/day drainage	42	83	67	13	272	1490	10.2	2.3	8.3	5.9	4.3	4.3	3.0
Submerged with msd ^a	46	90	63	14	223	1210	10.0	14.2	17.7	19.9	16.8	14.0	10.9
Field capacity	37	73	25	52	86	4920	14.4	20.1	8.6	2.2	1.3	1.0	0.7
Field capacity +late submergence ^b	49	96	73	12	207	1390	18.5	23.7	8.7	1.2	5.7	7.1	12.6
Limed to pH 6.5	34	74	50	22	189	620	13.9	28.7	30.0	33.1	28.8	22.5	16.7
0.4% MnO ₂	38	79	55	14	199	1630	11.4	19.2	18.9	20.5	21.8	22.2	19.1
LSD (5%)		12	12										

^a Watering stopped 9 weeks after planting and soil was allowed to dry until Eh rose to +0.2V, then soil was re-flooded. ^b Submerged 1 week before panicle primordia initiation.

and grain. Drainage and midseason soil drying gave grain yields not significantly different from those resulting from late flooding (Table 10). The grain yield from the field capacity treatment was by far the lowest in spite of adequate vegetative growth. High sterility, which was apparently associated with manganese toxicity, lowered the grain yield.

The chemical kinetics of the soil solutions (fig. 6 and Table 10) indicates that benefits of delaying submergence, percolation, or mid-

season soil drying were associated with low concentrations of iron, carbon dioxide, organic acids, and reducing substances.

This experiment suggests that the injurious effects of low soil temperature on rice can be partly alleviated by delaying submergence, by midseason soil drying, or by providing internal drainage. In Japan, midseason soil drying is always practiced by prize-winning farmers, and a moderate amount of percolation is considered beneficial to rice.

6. Influence of four water treatments on the kinetics of P_{CO_2} , water-soluble iron, and organic acids in Louisiana clay at 20 C as influenced by submerging the soil (A), submerging the soil with mid-season soil drying (B), submerging the soil with 1 cm/day percolation (C), keeping the soil at field capacity until 1 week before panicle initiation then submerging the soil (D).

Table 11. Influence of duration of storage in pots at field capacity before planting (premoistening) on the growth and mineral composition of IR5 on three soils at field capacity.

Weeks premoistened ^a	Days (sowing to flowering)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	In straw (ppm)		
				Fe	Mn	Al
<i>Luisiana clay (pH 4.7, organic matter: 3.2%)</i>						
8	117	71	30	28	3170	27
4	122	95	37	41	2950	28
0	124	149	36	57	2660	17
Flooded	113	133	100	254	979	—
<i>Maahas clay (pH 6.6, organic matter: 2.0%)</i>						
8	112	110	63	40	166	—
4	113	105	65	40	208	—
0	113	105	69	36	252	9
Flooded	104	131	103	98	1350	—
<i>Pila clay loam (pH 7.6, organic matter: 1.5%)</i>						
8	121	36	20	24	24	—
4	120	37	19	24	26	—
0	115	55	36	25	34	—
Flooded	103	134	116	98	1030	—
LSD (5%)		15	18			

^aData for 12 weeks' premoistening were almost the same as for the 8 weeks' treatments.

Water regime in rice soils

The water regime of rice soils profoundly influences the availability of nutrients and the formation of substances that may harm the rice plant. A deeper understanding of these changes may reveal ways to grow rice with less water and to help correct nutritional disorders of rice by water management.

Low yields of rice on non-flooded soils. Previous experiments (1964, 1965, 1966 Annual Reports) showed that rice grows luxuriantly on aerobic soils at field capacity if it is supplied with extra phosphorus, but it suffers a setback in the reproductive phase of the plant's development. We have found that this setback is partly caused by iron deficiency on neutral and calcareous soils and by manganese toxicity on strongly acid soils (1966 Annual Report). But it was not clear whether these problems derived from the state of the soil or the physiological condition of the plant during the reproductive phase. If aerobic soils go through a period of intense biological activity during the first 10 weeks after moistening, followed by a lull that persists (as occurs in flooded soils), the deficiency of iron could be due to reduced availability of iron rather than to a greater demand for iron

or to an impaired ability of the plant to absorb iron.

To study this problem, 10-kg portions of three air-dry soils were treated with 0.15 percent of a 1:1 mixture of chopped straw and *Glyricidia sepium* along with 50 ppm each of N, P, K as ammonium sulfate, concentrated superphosphate, and muriate of potash. The soils were moistened and kept at field capacity for 12, 8, 4, and 0 weeks. A parallel set was similarly treated and kept flooded for comparison. Two IR5 seedlings were planted in each pot on the same day. During the growth of the rice plants the premoistened soils were held at field capacity and the presubmerged soils were kept flooded. All pots received 50 ppm N as urea 8 weeks after transplanting.

Premoistening of the soil depressed vegetative growth markedly in Luisiana clay, moderately in Pila clay loam, and little in Maahas clay, but it did not affect grain yield appreciably on any soil. Presubmergence increased the yield of grain in Luisiana clay and Pila clay loam but not in Maahas clay. The grain yields of the flooded treatments were considerably higher than those at field capacity (Table 11).

As in several previous experiments (1963, 1964, 1965 Annual Reports), plants on Luisiana clay at field capacity with no pretreatment made

7. Kinetics of pH and nitrate in premoistened Louisiana clay at field capacity.

excellent vegetative growth: the yield of 149 g/pot of straw was, in fact, the highest among all treatments, flooded or not. This means that both water and nutrients were adequate, and injurious substances were absent in Louisiana clay at field capacity during the first 8 weeks after the soil was moistened and the rice seedlings were transplanted. Why then was the grain yield so low (35.7 g compared with 100.3 g for the same soil flooded) and no different from the premoistened treatments in which vegetative growth was so poor (Table 11)?

Figures 7 and 8 show that the growth retarding factors in the premoistened soils were low pH

8. Kinetics of water-soluble manganese in Louisiana clay at field capacity and submerged.

and high concentrations of nitrate and manganese. Low pH, brought about by nitrification and preferential absorption of NH_4^+ from fertilizer $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, made aluminum and manganese more soluble relative to iron (Table 12 and fig. 8). The high concentration of nitrate enhanced the uptake of manganese while depressing that of iron (Table 11). These adverse factors came into operation in the non-premoistened soil only after the 10th week. Hence, the yield of grain was low, in spite of prolific vegetative growth.

Although the manganese content of the plants on non-flooded Louisiana clay was high and

Table 12. Influence of duration of premoistening on the concentration of aluminum in Louisiana clay at field capacity 10 weeks after planting.

Weeks premoistened	Water-soluble Al (ppm)	Exchangeable Al in soil (ppm)
12	1.87	598
8	1.60	588
4	1.13	565
0	0.80	551

straw yield was negatively correlated with it (fig. 9), we did not see any signs of manganese toxicity. Instead, we observed that the leaf tips and borders of older leaves dried up and young leaves showed interveinal yellowing and rolling (fig. 10) — symptoms similar to those of aluminum toxicity in corn. The symptoms became more severe and the content of aluminum in the straw increased as the duration of premoistening increased from 0 to 8 weeks (fig. 11 and Table 11). Similar symptoms were observed in varying degrees on 43 of the 52 varieties or lines grown on Louisiana clay under upland conditions in the field, the same season. Surprisingly, the upland varieties showed more marginal leaf scorch than the lowland varieties.

The low yield of grain on Louisiana soil at field capacity appears to be due to a combination

of manganese toxicity, aluminum toxicity, and iron deficiency (fig. 9) brought about by decrease in pH and accumulation of nitrate in the later stages. It is not due to some physiological change affecting the mineral nutrition of the rice plant in the reproductive phase of its development.

On Pila clay loam at field capacity all plants suffered from iron deficiency, and this was more severe on the premoistened soils. No iron was detectable in the solutions of this soil at field capacity from 4 to 14 weeks after planting while large amounts of nitrate were present in the premoistened soils. Flooding eliminated iron deficiency and dramatically increased yield (Table 11).

Premoistening did not affect the growth and yield of rice on Maahas clay at field capacity. The concentration of iron in the soil solution was 0.1 to 0.4 ppm in the soils at field capacity during the first 8 weeks after planting, but dropped to less than 0.01 ppm thereafter. The concentration of iron probably decreased because as the plants grew bigger evapotranspiration increased and anaerobic pockets in the soil were eliminated. The slight chlorosis of the younger leaves observed at this time reflected the low iron availability rather than

9. Correlation between the yield of straw and the content of manganese and iron in the straw in Louisiana clay at field capacity.

a greater need for iron or an impaired ability of the rice plant to absorb iron at this stage of its development.

Excess manganese and aluminum in acid soils and insufficient available iron in neutral and calcareous soils are the main causes of poor yield of rice on aerobic soils in the absence of water stress.

Chemical benefits of flooding. Most studies of rice on non-flooded soils, both in the greenhouse and in the field, emphasize the harm done by water stress. But we have consistently found that, although rice grows luxuriantly on acid soils at field capacity, the yield of grain is only a fraction of that on the same soil, flooded. Physiologists have attributed this to the elimination of water stress, rather than to the chemical consequences of the absence of molecular oxygen in flooded soils.

It is difficult to devise an experiment in which the direct effect of flooding — elimination of water stress — can be separated from the secondary effects of soil saturation — anaerobic soil metabolism and its chemical consequences. In spite of this limitation, one experiment indicated that the absence of oxygen, even without flooding, benefited rice (1964 Annual Report).

To clarify this point further, we compared the effects of an abundance of water while the soil was aerobic with those of submergence. We subjected two soils to three treatments in the greenhouse: submergence, field capacity, and field capacity plus a continuous drip of water during the day, with recycling of the drainage water.

In spite of the elimination of water stress by a continuous drip of water, the yield of both grain and straw was much lower in the aerobic soils than in the submerged soils (Table 13). Chemical analyses revealed that plants on the flooded soil had a much higher concentration of iron than plants on the non-flooded soils, but no great difference between the two non-flooded treatments existed.

The benefits of flooding were chemical: the increase in availability of iron in both soils and the decrease in uptake of manganese in the acid soil.

10. Aluminum toxicity of rice on non-flooded Louisiana clay. Leaves 1 to 6: youngest to oldest leaves from one plant. Extreme right: healthy leaf.

11. Severity of Al toxicity increased with duration of premoistening from 0 to 8 weeks.

Delaying flooding. In Agusan del Norte and Agusan del Sur (Philippines) about 80,000 hectares of low-lying alluvial soils are almost

Table 13. Influence of three water regimes on the yield of IR20 and its mineral content on two soils.

Water regime	Tillers (no.)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	In straw (ppm)		
				Fe	Mn	Zn
<i>Luisiana clay (pH 4.6, organic matter: 3.2%)</i>						
Submerged	50	130	69	338	1480	67
Field capacity	40	76	13	55	3070	159
Field capacity + water drip	42	96	23	55	4320	174
<i>Maahas clay (pH 6.6, organic matter: 2.0%)</i>						
Submerged	52	182	68	156	680	56
Field capacity	41	103	28	39	214	53
Field capacity + water drip	39	106	30	48	149	48

Table 14. Influence of two water treatments in the presence and absence of added organic matter (weeds) on the yield of IR20 on Butuan clay loam (pH 6.4, organic matter: 5.3%). Butuan, Philippines, 1970.

Water treatment	Weeds (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)	
		Straw	Grain
Continuously flooded	0	6.2	6.0
	20	6.3	5.8
Flooded 1 week before panicle primordia initiation ^a	0	7.2	7.0
	20	7.3	7.1

^aField capacity until panicle primordia initiation.

Table 15. Grain yield of rice varieties grown in pots on three non-flooded soils and flooded Tungshan silt loam.

Variety or line	Grain yield (g/pot)				
	Aerobic			Flooded	
	Luisiana clay ^a	Maahas clay ^b	Pila clay ^c	Mean	Tungshan silt loam ^d
IR5	26	18	19	21.0	39
IR8	6	12	23	14.0	36
IR20	18	16	15	16.3	39
IR305	23	26	24	24.7	17
IR661-170-1	6	4	11	7.2	32
IR332-2-10	12	29	24	21.6	40
IR408-2-1	17	39	15	23.5	55
Bluebonnet 50	18	26	8	17.4	4
Peta	9	12	17	12.6	60
Dinalaga	17	20	19	18.8	2
Azucena	20	29	20	23.0	2
Palawan	32	28	29	29.5	10
Aznil 26	26	1 ^e	17	21.3	1
Taichung Native 1	25	33	26	28.0	43

^apH 4.6; organic matter: 3.2%. ^bpH 6.6; organic matter: 2.0%. ^cpH 7.6; organic matter: 1.5%. ^dpH 5.8; organic matter: 3.4%, a problem soil from Taiwan. ^eDamaged by rats, not included in mean.

perennially wet. When these fields are not under rice they carry a luxuriant growth of marsh plants, chiefly *Cyperus imbricatus*. Farmers plow in about 30 t/ha of these weeds before they plant rice in the flooded fields. Therefore, we attributed a widespread physiological disorder of rice in Agusan to the toxicity of the products of the anaerobic decomposition of organic matter.

To ascertain the role of organic matter, we conducted an experiment in cooperation with the Northern Mindanao National Agricultural College at Butuan, Agusan.

Delaying submergence until a week before initiation of panicle primordia increased the grain yield by a ton (Table 14). Older leaves of the plants in the continuously flooded soil showed a brown discoloration about 40 days after transplanting while plants in the unflooded soil were green and healthy. This disorder was later diagnosed as zinc deficiency.

Growing an upland crop between the rice crops may be the simplest remedy for zinc deficiency of rice on soils high in organic matter.

Fallow methods. For centuries, farmers in China and Japan have kept their rice fields under water in winter because they believed this increased the fertility of the soil. In the course of a 4-year study (1969 Annual Report), we found that flood fallowing produced a chemical environment favorable to rice roots and led to a substantial saving and accretion of soil nitrogen. But last year in the 10th successive crop, we observed growth retardation in a nearly neutral soil (Maahas clay) and in a calcareous soil (Pila clay loam) which had been kept continuously submerged. On these two soils, rice plants showed signs of mild zinc deficiency. The use of alkaline irrigation water had raised the pH of Maahas clay to 7.1, while continuous submergence had increased the organic matter and nitrogen content of the soils (1969 Annual Report). Although last year we recommended continuous submergence of the soil if rice is the only crop, we now advise occasionally drying the soil (with measures to minimize denitrification losses) to avoid zinc deficiency, or applying zinc oxide or zinc chloride to the continuously flooded soil.

Varietal resistance to soil problems

In our search for criteria for selecting rice varieties suited to aerobic soils not subject to water stress, we observed that four Philippine upland varieties did not show symptoms of iron deficiency on a calcareous soil or of manganese toxicity on a strongly acid soil (symptoms shown in varying degrees by the varieties commonly grown on flooded soils), but they succumbed to the toxins in soil on which a physiological disorder called suffocation disease occurs (1969 Annual Report).

In studies this year, the upland varieties Dinalaga, Azucena, Palawan, and Azmil 26 produced more grain, uniformly, on the three aerobic soils than other varieties, while yielding practically nothing on a flooded problem soil (Table 15). Three lowland rices, Taichung Native 1, IR5, and IR408-2-1 yielded relatively well on both the aerobic soils and the flooded problem soil, however. It is remarkable that Peta, which gave the highest yield on the flooded problem soil (apparently because it was resistant to the toxins in this reduced soil), gave the lowest average yield for the aerobic soils.

Although distinct foliar symptoms of iron deficiency and manganese toxicity were observed mostly in the lowland varieties, chemical analysis revealed no consistent differences in the plant content of iron or manganese between the upland and lowland varieties. The content of iron, however, was generally lower in the upland varieties, both on flooded and non-flooded soils, than in the lowland varieties. The upland varieties accumulated large amounts of manganese but showed no symptoms of toxicity (Table 16). The zinc uptake by the upland varieties when grown on flooded soils was also remarkably low.

The discovery of varietal differences in resistance to adverse soil conditions prompted us to test a few varieties of rice on Luisiana clay which is a ferrallitic soil deficient in phosphorus and on a red ferrallitic soil from Taiwan which when flooded builds up high concentrations of water-soluble iron.

IR8 was severely injured both by phosphorus deficiency and by iron toxicity (Table 17). Iron toxicity (which can occur only on flooded soils)

severely injured the two upland varieties, Azucena and Azmil, while phosphorus deficiency depressed the yield of grain only slightly. H4 and IR5 were affected least by phosphorus deficiency and iron toxicity.

These observations are based on unreplicated experiments in pots, in the greenhouse, with varieties with different plant types. Therefore, they may not reveal too much about the performance of these plants in the field. But they do suggest that physiological differences exist among varieties that can be exploited for breeding varieties resistant to adverse soil conditions.

Thermodynamics of flooded soils

Thermodynamics is useful in the study of the chemical changes that affect the availability of nutrients or the accumulation of toxins in flooded soils. For example, given the pH of a

Table 16. Mineral content of two varieties of rice grown on three flooded and non-flooded soils.

Soil	Treatment	IR5			Palawan		
		Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Zn (ppm)
Luisiana clay ^a	Flooded	365	735	53	260	460	21
	Non-flooded	80	2765	202	55	4238	247
Maahas clay ^b	Flooded	245	2090	64	130	665	28
	Non-flooded	70	1415	91	60	4163	93
Pila clay loam ^c	Flooded	200	745	56	100	315	20
	Non-flooded	60	50	44	60	48	51

^apH 4.7; organic matter: 3.2%; Mn: 0.05%. ^bpH 6.6; organic matter: 2.0%; Mn: 0.31%. ^cpH 7.2; organic matter: 4.0%; Mn: 0.06%.

Table 17. Growth and yield of rice varieties on two flooded problem soils.

Variety	Luisiana clay ^a			Ferrallitic clay ^b		
	Tillers (no./pot)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)	Tillers (no./pot)	Straw (g/pot)	Grain (g/pot)
IR5	24	70	57	32	42	11
IR8	9	29	13	8	16	0
IR20	22	48	46	15	19	10
IR22	23	57	46	28	28	13
C4-63G	26	65	24	26	29	0.5
H4	25	103	67	30	59	12
TN1	33	45	40	27	33	9
PI 215936	14	56	47	30	32	9
Azucena	12	67	37	14	35	1
Azmil 26	8	58	33	5	10	0

^aDeficient in phosphorus. ^bIron toxicity.

flooded ferrallitic soil, thermodynamics allows the calculation of the redox potential (Eh), the concentration of water-soluble iron, the P_{CO_2} (1966 Annual Report), and even the specific conductance of the soil. Thus a single rapid and accurate electrometric measurement tells us whether the solution bathing the roots of the rice plant has too little or too much iron or too much carbon dioxide or excess salts.

Because thermodynamics proved so useful in understanding the changes in pH, Eh, and transformations of iron and manganese (1964-1968 Annual Reports) in flooded soils and made possible the formulation of remedies for some soil problems (1964, 1965 Annual Reports), equilibrium concepts were applied to the study of zinc in flooded soils. Also, a problem in the measurement of redox potential of flooded soils was re-investigated.

Zinc equilibria. The concentration of water-soluble zinc in flooded soils influences the uptake of zinc by the rice plant. Therefore, an understanding of the factors that affect its solubility may be useful in correcting zinc deficiency.

If the bulk of the zinc in the solution of a flooded soil is in the form of Zn^{2+} , the following equilibria (pK_s denotes activity product; L stands for an organic ligand) may influence its concentration:

If zinc phosphate controls the solubility of zinc in flooded soils, the value of the expression, $3 pZn^{2+} + 2 pPO_4^{3-}$, should be constant and tend to 32.0, in spite of variations in the activity of Zn^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} (pZn^{2+} and pPO_4^{3-} stand for the negative logarithm of the activities of Zn^{2+} and PO_4^{3-}). Table 18 shows that zinc phosphate was probably present transitorily in the soils with peak pH values exceeding 6.6. In acid soils, the value of the expression deviated markedly from 32.0. Apparently zinc phosphate is not precipitated in acid solutions because the concentration of the PO_4^{3-} ion is too low.

Soil solutions contain Zn^{2+} , NH_4^+ , and PO_4^{3-} ions. If the solubility product of zinc

ammonium phosphate is exceeded, $ZnNH_4PO_4$ should precipitate:

If zinc ammonium phosphate is present in flooded soils, the value of the expression, $pZn^{2+} + pNH_4^+ + pPO_4^{3-}$, should be constant and tend to 16.0, in spite of variations in the activities of the participating ions. Table 18 shows that zinc ammonium phosphate may be present transitorily in the soils whose solution pH values exceed 6.5.

Finely divided quartz is present in all soils. Besides, silica brought in by irrigation water may crystallize slowly giving fine quartz crystals. Zinc ions in the soil solution may react with quartz and attain the equilibrium:

$$\log Zn^{2+} + 2 pH = 6.97$$

Applying the criterion, $2 pH - pZn^{2+} = 7.0 \pm 0.3$, to the solutions of the flooded soils, we found that zinc silicate was probably present in all soils, at some stage, except for the two acid sulfate soils. In Maahas clay irrigated with water high in silica, the solubility of zinc appears to be determined by zinc silicate.

We found no thermodynamic evidence for the presence of $Zn_3(PO_4)_2$, $ZnNH_4PO_4$, or $ZnSiO_3$ in the two acid sulfate soils. Since these soils produce much H_2S when kept submerged, we suspected that zinc sulfide might be involved:

But because we could not measure the infinitesimal concentrations of S^{2-} at the low pH value of these soils, we tried an indirect method:

If the systems

are in equilibrium, then

$$\frac{(Zn^{2+})(S^{2-})}{(Fe^{2+})(S^{2-})} = \frac{10^{-22.80}}{10^{-18.40}}$$

or

$$-\log (Zn^{2+})/(Fe^{2+}) = 4.40$$

or

$$pZn^{2+} + pFe^{2+} = 4.40$$

Table 18. Influence of soil properties on the residence time of zinc phosphate, zinc ammonium phosphate, and zinc silicate in flooded soils.

Soil	Peak value in soil solution			Residence time after submergence (weeks)		
	pH	P (ppm)	NH ₄ ⁺ (mmole/liter)	Zn ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ ^a	ZnNH ₄ PO ₄ ^a	ZnSiO ₃ ^a
Acid sulfate clay (Philippines)	6.20	2.85	7.33	—	—	0
Acid sulfate clay (Vietnam)	4.63	0.18	4.90	—	—	—
Louisiana clay	6.51	0.07	1.28	—	—	8 to 10
Kalayaan clay	6.64	2.36	4.70	3 to 8	2	10
Antipolo clay	6.82	0.07	1.02	—	—	1
Butuan clay	6.71	1.10	1.60	0	—	1 to 10
Maahas clay	6.61	0.39	1.11	—	3 to 5	0 to 10
Pila clay loam	6.71	6.63	1.61	1 to 3	—	2 to 10
Luna clay	6.86	0.27	2.69	—	0 to 2	4 to 10
San Pablo clay loam	6.76	2.10	1.60	0 to 4	2 to 6	1 to 10
Aggaie loam	6.75	0.39	6.11	0 to 4	1 and 4	8 to 10
Magalang loam	6.89	0.43	0.82	4	0 to 1	10

^aCriteria used for the presence of the solids—Zn₃(PO₄)₂: pK_s=32.0±0.3; ZnNH₄PO₄: pK_s=16.0±0.3; ZnSiO₃: log Zn+2 pH=7.0±0.3.

If $pZn^{2+} + pFe^{2+}$ is relatively constant and nearly equal to 4.4 in spite of variations in the activities of Zn^{2+} and Fe^{2+} , zinc sulfide is likely to be present. The only soil which gave 4.4 for the value of this expression was the acid sulfate soil (Philippines). Table 19 shows that zinc sulfide controlled the concentration of zinc in this soil from 2 weeks of submergence onwards.

The thermodynamics of zinc in flooded soil suggests that neutral and alkaline soils high in phosphate tend to have low concentrations of water-soluble zinc. Ammonium fertilizers may depress the concentration further.

Redox equilibria in soils. A reliable measure of the oxidation-reduction level of a soil is necessary for the quantitative study of redox equilibria. Numerous workers have used the potential of a platinum electrode inserted in the soil as a measure of its oxidation-reduction level. But we have pointed out (1964, 1966 Annual Reports) that such potentials are highly variable, differ by several hundred millivolts from the solution potential, are far too low, and are unreliable as a quantitative measure of redox equilibria in a soil. We gave reasons for believing that the soil solution is the thermodynamically meaningful phase and used soil solution potentials to prove the presence of the $Fe(OH)_3 - Fe^{2+}$, $Fe(OH)_3 - Fe_3(OH)_8$, and $Fe_3(OH)_8 - Fe^{2+}$ systems in many flooded soils (1964, 1965, 1966 Annual Reports).

Recently the validity of potential measurements in natural systems (including solutions) has been questioned on the grounds that redox systems in nature are not electroactive at a platinum electrode, that the potentials measured are mixed potentials, and that the apparent conformity of the potentials of flooded soils to those of the iron systems may be due to an experimental error.

We have examined these objections theoretically and experimentally and have reached the following conclusions. First, the oxidized and reduced forms of iron and manganese are not electroactive at a bright platinum electrode only if their concentrations are exceedingly low, as in oxygenated surface media with a neutral or alkaline reaction. Second, the mixed potentials proposed for soils are an attempt to explain the failure of one researcher to obtain acceptable quantitative relationships when soil potentials

Table 19. Influence of the kinetics of water-soluble zinc and iron on the value of $-\log Zn^{2+}/Fe^{2+}$ in a flooded acid sulfate clay.

Weeks submerged	Zn ²⁺ (10 ⁻⁶ mole/liter)	Fe ²⁺ (10 ⁻⁶ mole/liter)	$-\log Zn^{2+}/Fe^{2+}$
0	7.80	0.07	1.96
1	6.58	3.73	3.75
2	2.60	4.21	4.21
3	3.20	5.49	4.23
4	3.20	5.19	4.21
6	1.68	5.19	4.48
8	1.53	4.51	4.47
10	1.83	4.34	4.38

12. Kinetics of soil and solution Eh in flooded Louisiana clay in pots.

were used as a measure of the level of oxidation-reduction. Third, the experimental error criticism is based on the results of a single experiment, where suction was used to draw out the soil solution.

Figure 12 shows the wide gap between potentials, measured in the soil and in the solution in porous cups sitting in the soil, and its inversion after 2 weeks. Figure 13 shows how the application of suction to draw solution out of the porous cups depressed the partial pressure of CO_2 , increased the pH, and therefore lowered Eh. The effect of suction on pH and Eh were more marked after 6 weeks' submergence, when the $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{CO}_2$ system came into operation and determined the pH of the reduced soil (1964, 1967 Annual Reports). The lower

potentials of the solutions extracted by suction are due to loss of CO_2 and not to the operation of the $\text{FeOOH} \cdot \text{Fe}^{2+}$ system as one researcher has suggested. Further proof that the conformity of change in activity of pH, Eh, and Fe^{2+} to those of the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot \text{Fe}^{2+}$ system is not an experimental error is given in Table 20. In a wide variety of lowland rice soils, over submergence periods that varied from 1 to 25 weeks, over Fe^{2+} concentrations that ranged from 2.7 to 500 ppm, and over Eh and pH values that varied from 34 mv to 187 mv and pH 5.87 to 6.83, the value of the expression, $\text{Eh} + 0.059 \log \text{Fe}^{2+} + 0.177 \text{pH}$, was approximately 1.06 v. Appreciable deviations were observed only in the two acid sulfate soils and Keelung silt loam.

The relationship holds even at Fe^{2+} concentrations as low as 0.2 ppm and at pH values that are considerably lower and Eh values that are considerably higher than those that occur in submerged soils (Table 21). This means that the specific exchange current at the platinum electrode is high enough to give a reversible Nernst potential for the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3 - \text{Fe}^{2+}$ system at concentrations of Fe^{2+} as low as 0.2 ppm.

Reducing substances

The solutions of flooded soils contain substances that can reduce KMnO_4 under mild conditions. These substances compete with rice roots for

13. Effects of two methods of draining the solution from flooded Louisiana clay on its P_{CO_2} , pH, and Eh.

Table 20. Influence of soil properties on the value of the expression, $Eh + 0.059 \log (Fe^{2+}) + 0.177 pH = Eo$, based on Eh, Fe^{2+} activity, and pH in the soil solution at the peak of water-soluble iron for each soil kept submerged in pots.

Soil	pH	Organic matter (%)	Active Fe (%)	Weeks submerged	After submergence				
					Eh (v)	pH	Fe^{2+} (ppm)	$\gamma_{Fe^{2+}}$	Eo (v)
Luisiana clay	4.7	3.2	2.9	4	0.057	6.42	500	0.565	1.058
Maahas clay	6.6	2.0	1.6	6	0.034	6.83	46	0.624	1.049
Casiguran sandy loam	4.8	2.0	0.2	1	0.095	6.36	146	0.564	1.054
Pila clay loam	7.6	1.5	0.3	4	0.088	6.72	18	0.554	1.056
Acid sulfate soil (Vietnam)	3.6	7.2	0.1	12	0.255	4.14	785	0.534	0.863
Acid sulfate soil (0.4% $CaCO_3$)	4.7	7.2	0.1	8	0.235	5.29	520	0.495	1.033
Acid sulfate soil (9.8% $CaCO_3$)	5.4	7.2	0.1	4	0.187	5.87	152	0.487	1.056
Keelung silt loam	7.9	6.9	2.3	7	-0.025	6.91	77	0.546	1.014
Korean sandy loam	4.8	1.5	0.4	2	0.111	6.13	244	0.580	1.028
Aggaie loam	8.0	1.2	0.5	4	0.091	6.59	23	0.628	1.046
Antipolo clay	5.5	2.6	3.0	3	0.046	6.68	95	0.597	1.052
Luna clay	7.0	1.9	1.8	4	0.174	6.57	3	0.552	1.068
San Pablo clay	7.4	4.7	—	4	0.056	6.66	24	0.574	1.022
Acid sulfate clay (Philippines)	3.8	4.4	1.9	3	-0.008	6.07	3067	0.452	0.972

oxygen, and, if present in excess, may deprive them of the oxygen vital for respiration and nutrient uptake.

Water-soluble Fe^{2+} accounts for about 25 percent of the reducing substances, while the other inorganic substances are present only in very small amounts. It was assumed, therefore, that the bulk of the reducing substances was organic. But careful tests showed that such substances as alcohols, reducing sugars, aldehydes and ketones, aliphatic hydroxy and unsaturated acids, and mercaptans and organic sulfides were present only in traces (1965 Annual Report). So we suspected that phenolic substances might be responsible for the reduction of $KMnO_4$. Two such compounds — ferulic

acid (3-methoxy-4-hydroxycinnamic acid) and sinapic acid (3, 5-dimethoxy-4-hydroxy-cinnamic acid) — were detected by thin layer chromatography of ether-ethyl acetate extracts of the solutions of flooded soils.

Table 21. Influence of low Fe^{2+} concentrations on the value of the expression, $Eh + 0.059 \log Fe^{2+} + 0.177 pH = Eo$, based on Eh, Fe^{2+} activity, and pH of the soil solution.

Weeks at field capacity	Eh (v)	pH	Fe^{2+} (ppm)	$\gamma_{Fe^{2+}}$	Eo (v)
0	0.457	5.18	0.20	0.719	1.044
2	0.410	5.38	0.20	0.737	1.033
4	0.371	5.26	2.77	0.745	1.041
6	0.326	5.60	4.72	0.758	1.070
8	0.352	5.42	1.06	0.812	1.027
10	0.322	5.55	1.42	0.785	1.027

Agronomy

Among the significant results in 1970 agronomy research was the improvement of rice quality with cultural practices. Topdressing of nitrogen at heading apparently increases the percentage of head rice of IR8.

Application of simetryne at 0.5 kg/ha of active ingredient significantly increased the protein content and protein yield of IR22 rice without decreasing grain yield. IR480-5-9, which has high yield potential with good grain quality, also showed that it has high protein content. It may prove to be an excellent material for developing high yielding rice with high protein content.

To obtain high grain yields, cultural practices, such as land preparation and water management which are optimum for transplanted rice, also appeared to be optimum for broadcast-seeded flooded rice. For weed control in broadcast-seeded flooded rice, the granular herbicides benthocarb and CP 53619, when applied between 6 and 8 days after seeding, were remarkably effective and did not cause injury to high yielding varieties.

Chemical weed control in upland rice looked promising under tropical monsoon conditions. Weed control with NTN 5006 or CP 53619 was as good as hand weeding twice and they gave much better control than propanil. For upland rice, the high yielding variety IR5 produced up to 7 t/ha in a cooperative experiment in Central Luzon in the Philippines. The local upland variety M1-48 produced up to 4.8 t/ha.

Experiments on the effects of water stress at different physiological growth stages of lowland rice were conducted. With improved varieties, the duration of the moisture stress was more important in determining the amount of yield reduction than was the growth stage at which the stress occurred. Differences were found in the growth response of upland and lowland varieties to moisture stress.

Continuous cropping

The continuous-cropping experiment tests the annual production of early-maturing varieties or promising lines.

In four crops in 365 days (including 1 day for land preparation before each crop), an improved line, IR579-48-2, which was developed from the same cross as IR22 and which has excellent plant type, produced 22.2 t/ha (Table 1). The line, however, matured in 105 to 110 days as compared with IR22 which matured in 107 to 126 days (IR22 is weakly photoperiod sensitive). The production per day for the IR579 line was 61 kg.

In the same experiment, another line, IR773A1-36-2, produced 20 t/ha in 360 days, or 58 kg/day. Both the IR579 line and the IR773 line do not have resistance to green leafhoppers or brown planthoppers. The IR579 line is also susceptible to blast, but resistant to bacterial leaf blight. On the other hand, the IR773 line is susceptible to bacterial leaf blight, but moderately resistant to blast. Susceptibility to either blast or bacterial leaf blight is undesirable for stable high yields.

Date-of-planting experiment

The date-of-planting experiment, in which crops are planted in every month, was continued. Figure 1 shows the nitrogen response of IR8,

IR22, IR661-1-140-3-2, and H-4. For the crops harvested in November and December, IR661-1-140-3-117 was used instead of IR661-1-140-3-2. Solar radiation during the last 45 days for the May harvest was much lower than usual. This is because the solar energy during the last week of March and the first week of April was considerably lower in 1970 than in previous years.

In most harvest months, the IR661 line produced high grain yields. Yields of all varieties harvested in November and December were low because of severe lodging due to typhoons, low solar energy during the ripening period, and severe incidence of bacterial leaf blight, particularly in IR8.

Nitrogen response

Experiments were conducted at IRRI farm, in farmers' field, and at various experiment stations in the Philippines to study the nitrogen response and growth characteristics of varieties or lines developed by IRRI or by breeders in several countries.

International varieties. Among the 12 varieties or promising lines tested in an experiment at the IRRI farm in the dry season, the highest grain yield, 8.3 t/ha, was obtained from IR661-1-140-3-2. The Indian variety, Jaya, and an IRRI line, IR844-86-1, yielded almost as well as the IR661 line (Table 2).

In the wet season the highest grain yield, 6.4 t/ha, was obtained with Jaya at 60 kg/ha N despite an outbreak of bacterial leaf blight after flowering (Table 3). IR8 also had bacterial leaf blight. It produced slightly lower grain yields than Jaya. Blast reduced the yield of IR22. In contrast with the dry season, the growth duration of IR22 was similar to that of IR8, reflecting the photoperiod sensitivity of IR22.

Figures 2, 3, and 4 show the relationship between the leaf area index (LAI) values at flowering and the grain yield of several rice varieties. The data for IR22, Jaya, Padma, and RD3 suggest that grain yields of varieties might be higher at higher LAI values (fig. 2). The varieties IR5, C4-63, CR36-148, Taichung Native 1, and Peta showed an optimum LAI

Table 1. Yields of two promising lines in a continuous-cropping experiment. IRRI, 1970.

Crop number	Seedling age (days)	Field duration ^a (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>IR579-48-2</i>			
1 (Nov. 24 [1969] to Feb. 18)	18	87	6.0
2 (Feb. 20 to May 19)	21	89	7.4
3 (May 21 to Aug. 20)	19	92	5.5
4 (Aug. 22 to Nov. 22)	18	93	3.3
Total		361	22.2
<i>IR773A1-36-2</i>			
1 (Nov. 15 [1969] to Feb. 11)	21	89	5.1
2 (Feb. 13 to May 14)	18	90	7.0
3 (May 16 to Aug. 13)	25	90	4.6
4 (Aug. 15 to Nov. 9)	18	87	3.4
Total		356	20.1

^aLand preparation took 1 day per crop.

Table 2. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the grain yield of rice (International Variety Trial). IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)						Growth duration (days)
	Nitrogen applied ^b (kg/ha)						
	0	50	80	110	140	Mean	
IR8	4.9	6.0	7.0	7.3	7.3	6.5	129
IR22	4.7	5.8	7.2	7.4	7.8	6.5	109
IR844-86-1	4.4	6.4	7.8	7.8	8.2	6.9	129
IR661-140-3-2	4.6	6.5	7.6	8.1	8.3	7.0	129
IR790-28-6	6.0	7.0	7.5	8.0	7.5	7.2	129
RD1	4.5	6.2	7.6	7.7	7.6	6.7	129
RD3	4.3	6.3	6.9	7.3	7.0	6.4	126
Jaya	4.9	6.4	7.6	7.9	8.2	7.0	122
Padma	4.0	5.2	6.0	6.0	6.3	5.5	109
Taichung Native 1	4.3	6.6	6.9	6.8	6.9	6.3	122
C4-63	3.6	6.4	6.8	6.7	6.6	6.0	126
Peta	4.6	4.6	3.3	3.9	2.4	3.8	137

^aAverage of three replications. ^bIncludes 20 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation.

Table 3. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the grain yield of rice (International Variety Trial). IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Variety or line	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)						Growth duration (days)
	Nitrogen applied ^b (kg/ha)						
	0	30	60	90	120	Mean	
IR8	4.9	5.2	6.0	5.6	5.5	5.4	125
IR20	4.6	5.1	5.9	5.9	5.7	5.4	125
IR22	3.6	4.4	4.8	4.6	4.8	4.4	125
IR5	4.9	5.5	5.2	4.8	4.5	5.0	134
Padma	4.1	4.5	5.3	4.7	5.1	4.8	119
Jaya	5.2	5.3	6.4	6.2	6.2	5.9	125
CR36-148	4.0	5.1	5.2	4.8	5.0	4.8	119
RD1	4.6	5.2	5.7	4.3	4.6	4.9	126
RD3	4.0	5.2	5.3	4.9	5.2	4.9	126
Taichung Native 1	4.1	3.8	4.8	4.9	4.5	4.4	119
C4-63	3.8	4.0	4.0	3.8	3.2	3.8	126
Peta	2.8	1.5	1.3	0.9	0.9	1.5	134

^aAverage of three replications. ^bIncludes 20 kg/ha N topdressed at panicle initiation.

1. Nitrogen response of IR8, IR22, IR661-1-140-3-2 (IR661-1-140-3-117 for November and December harvests), and H-4 by harvest month plotted with solar radiation total (IRRI pyrheliometer) for 45 days before harvest. Date-of-planting experiment, IRRI, 1970.

value beyond which the grain yields were reduced (fig. 3). The decrease in grain yields was associated with increased lodging at higher

LAI values for IR5, C4-63, and Peta. Taichung Native 1 and CR36-148 had more severe bacterial leaf blight at high nitrogen levels which

2. Rice varieties showing an increase in yield with an increase in leaf area index at flowering. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

3. Rice varieties showing decrease in grain yield at high leaf area index values at flowering. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

reduced grain yields. IR8, IR20, and RD1 showed no optimum LAI values for high grain yields (fig. 4). These results indicate that the relationship between LAI at flowering and grain yield is determined by the lodging and disease resistance of the improved varieties in addition to their short stature and erect leaves.

Farmers' fields. Each year experiments are conducted in farmers' fields to study varietal reaction to nitrogen fertilization under management conditions which are within reach of most Asian farmers.

In the dry season, the highest grain yield, 9.5 t/ha, was obtained with IR8 (fig. 5). The maximum grain yield of C4-63 was lower than the maximum grain yields of all the IRR1 varieties.

In the wet season, IR5 yielded more than IR8, primarily because it had less bacterial leaf blight. The growth duration of IR8 was 126 days and of IR5, 133 days. IR20 and IR22 produced similar grain yields and matured in 126 days.

Cooperative fertility experiment. Field experiments were conducted at two locations in the Philippines to study varietal reactions to nitrogen levels in cooperation with the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and the Visayas Rice Experiment Station (Table 4).

In these experiments, the differences in grain yields between the improved varieties were primarily due to the differences in resistance to bacterial leaf blight. The incidence of bacterial blight was particularly serious at the Visayas station. IR20 and IR22 showed the most resistance to bacterial leaf blight and IR8, the least. The improved line IR661-1-140-3-2 showed almost as low field resistance to bacterial leaf blight as IR8. The consistently low grain yields of IR8 at Visayas demonstrate that field resistance to bacterial leaf blight is highly desirable for stable high yields.

Other soil fertility studies

The twelfth and thirteenth crop in the long-term fertility experiment were grown in 1970. In both

the dry and wet seasons this year, none of the three rice varieties (or lines) showed significant response to phosphorus or potassium (Tables 5 and 6).

In the dry season, IR22 matured 19 days earlier than IR8. In the wet season, however, both varieties matured in the same period. The differences in growth durations between IR8 and IR22 were primarily due to the photoperiod sensitivity of IR22.

IR773A1-36-2, which is shorter than both IR8

4. Rice varieties showing no optimum leaf area index at flowering. IRR1, 1970 wet season.

Table 4. Grain yields of seven varieties (or lines) at various nitrogen levels grown at two locations in the Philippines — Maligaya (M) and Visayas (V). IRRI-BPI Cooperative nitrogen response experiments, 1970 wet season.

Nitrogen applied ^a (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)													
	IR8		IR20		IR22		IR579-48-2		IR661-1-140-3-2		IR790-28-6		Peta	
	M	V	M	V	M	V	M ^c	V	M	V	M	V	M	V
0	4.0	2.2	4.3	3.5	4.9	3.0	2.9	3.5	5.4	3.0	5.2	3.4	2.8	3.4
30	5.5	2.1	5.2	4.3	6.0	4.4	3.8	3.5	5.8	3.5	5.5	4.3	2.8	2.7
60	5.0	2.4	5.6	5.2	6.2	5.4	4.5	3.9	5.7	4.4	5.7	4.9	1.9	3.2
90	4.5	2.2	6.2	6.2	6.4	5.6	5.4	4.8	6.0	4.4	5.7	5.5	1.6	2.4
120	4.3	2.2	5.0	4.9	5.5	5.6	5.4	5.7	5.3	4.0	5.8	4.6	1.1	1.9
150	3.7	2.6	4.8	2.5	5.3	5.0	5.0	6.1	4.5	2.9	4.7	5.6	1.1	2.1
Duration (days)	126	121	124	121	126	111	120	111	120	121	126	121	142	131

^aBasal application plus 20 kg/ha N at panicle initiation. ^bAverage of three replications. ^cCrop partially damaged by birds.

Table 5. Effect of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of IR8, IR22, and IR773A1-36-2. IRRI, 1970 dry season (Long-term fertility experiment, 12th crop).

Fertilizer treatment ^a (kg/ha)			Grain yield ^b (t/ha)			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	IR22	IR773A1-36-2	Mean ^c
0	0	0	4.1	3.7	3.3	3.7
140	0	0	7.9	7.5	6.6	7.3
0	30	0	4.2	4.0	3.3	3.8
0	0	30	4.0	3.6	3.4	3.6
140	30	0	8.1	7.6	6.9	7.5
140	0	30	8.1	7.5	6.6	7.4
140	30	30	7.9	7.7	6.7	7.4
140 ^d	30	30	7.2	7.1	6.5	7.0
Mean ^e			6.4	6.1	5.4	
Duration (days)			130	111	115	

^aIncludes 40 kg/ha N applied at panicle initiation. ^bAverage of four replications. ^cLSD (5%)=0.3. ^dCompost plus inorganic. ^eLSD (5%)=0.2.

Table 6. Effects of NPK fertilization on the grain yield of IR8, IR22, and IR773A1-36-2. IRRI, 1970 wet season (Long-term fertility experiment, 13th crop).

Fertilizer treatment ^a (kg/ha)			Grain yield ^b (t/ha)			
N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	IR8	IR22	IR773A1-36-2	Mean ^c
0	0	0	4.8	4.0	3.7	4.2
60	0	0	5.5	4.8	3.9	4.7
0	30	0	5.1	4.4	3.7	4.4
0	0	30	4.9	3.8	3.5	4.1
60	30	0	5.4	4.6	4.3	4.7
60	0	30	5.5	4.8	4.4	4.9
60	30	30	5.4	4.4	4.5	4.8
60 ^d	30	30	5.4	4.4	4.0	4.6
Mean ^e			5.2	4.4	4.0	
Duration (days)			128	128	116	

^aBasal. ^bAverage of four replications. ^cLSD (5%)=0.3. ^dCompost plus inorganic. ^eLSD (5%)=0.2.

and IR22, was highly resistant to lodging. The IR773 line is early maturing and has good grain quality. The yields of the IR773 line were, however, lower than those of IR8 in these experiments (Tables 5 and 6).

Growth characteristics and yield. In monsoon Asia, high-tillering varieties are desirable for growing transplanted or direct-seeded rice. Varieties with improved plant type and high-tillering capacity can be planted at a wide range of spacings and still produce an adequate number of tillers per unit area. The total leaf area of a rice population is also closely related to grain production.

In field experiments on the effects of plant density and nitrogen levels on growth characteristics and grain yield, IR20, at flowering, produced the most tillers per plant (a maximum of 105 to 108 tillers per plant) and an IR127 line produced the least (25 to 28 tillers). Application of nitrogen markedly raised the tillering capacity of all the varieties and lines (fig. 6).

Under farm conditions, transplanting at a planting density closer than 20 x 20 cm is impractical. At 20 x 20 cm, however, high LAI values are difficult to obtain even with medium- and high-tillering varieties, such as IR8 or IR305-4-12, grown at optimum nitrogen levels for maximum grain yield. Therefore studies were conducted to compare broadcast seeding with transplanting at various plant densities. In the 1970 dry season, the highest grain yield of the IR305 line was obtained at an LAI value of 11.7,

5. Effect of nitrogen level on grain yields of rice varieties in farmer's fields. Laguna, Philippines, 1970.

while that of Peta occurred at an LAI value of 7 (fig. 7). The highest LAI value, 12.6, for IR8 was obtained with broadcast seeding but the grain yield was highest at an LAI value of 7.2, with transplanting because broadcast IR8 lodged 7 days before harvest, which reduced grain yield.

The varieties IR20 and IR22 demonstrated the importance of lodging resistance in determining the relationship between the leaf area index value at flowering and the grain yield of rice (fig. 8). IR20 which has longer leaves and slightly longer culms had higher LAI values than IR22 under broadcast seeding at 150 kg/ha N.

By analyzing the nitrogen content in plants in this experiment, it was observed that for every increase of 1 g/sq m in nitrogen absorbed by an IR8 plant, there was a corresponding

increase of 0.6 unit of LAI. This value was 0.5 for the IR127 and the IR305 lines, 0.4 for IR20 and Peta, and 0.3 for IR22. At the same level of absorbed nitrogen, IR20 had slightly higher LAI values than IR22 but lower lodging resistance. Despite the difference in the LAI values with broadcast seeding, the maximum grain yields obtained with IR20 and IR22 were similar (fig. 8). IR8 utilized absorbed nitrogen more efficiently for the development of leaf area than the other varieties studied.

The data also indicated that the nitrogen absorbed at flowering was closely related to the grain yield of the improved varieties except for Peta which lodged before flowering (fig. 9).

Temperature and growth. A greenhouse experiment was conducted to determine the effects of soil and water temperature regimes (15, 25, and 35 C) on growth and nutrition of IR22 rice.

6. Effect of nitrogen level on the tillering capacity of rice varieties at flowering (100 x 100 cm spacing). IRRI, 1970.

Plants grown at greenhouse temperature were used as the control.

Low temperatures at the early vegetative stage retarded the growth of shoots and roots (fig. 10). A temperature of 15 C delayed panicle initiation by 17 days and extended the time required for complete heading. Crop maturity was proportionately delayed. Soil temperature during the early vegetative stage had little effect on the concentration of N, P, and Si in the plant tissues.

The plants were highly sensitive to cool soil and water temperatures during panicle development (fig. 11). Low temperatures killed the lower leaves, caused chlorosis of the upper leaves, and retarded vegetative growth and production of dry matter. Heading was delayed and it took longer for all the panicles to emerge at the low temperature. Furthermore, fewer spikelets were formed and some were injured.

Plant growth was least affected by low soil and water temperatures during the period from heading to crop maturity.

7. Relationship between leaf area index at flowering and grain yield of rice at 150 kg/ha N. IRR1, 1970 dry season.

8. Relationship between leaf area index at flowering and grain yields of IR20 and IR22 at 150 kg/ha N. IRR1, 1970 dry season.

Milling quality. As new varieties with better grain qualities are introduced, cultural requirements such as time of nitrogen application and optimum time of harvest should be known.

An experiment conducted in the 1970 dry season indicated that, compared with making a single basal application of nitrogen, applying half the nitrogen at heading significantly increased the head rice yield of IR20 and RD1 by 4 to 5 percentage points (Table 7). These two varieties are moderately susceptible to lodging. The split application of nitrogen reduced the amount of lodging and thus raised the percentage of head rice. IR22, which has good straw strength, did not show any significant difference in the percentage of head rice between the two treatments. IR8, a chalky variety which has good straw strength, showed a large increase in the percentage of head rice. Split application, however, did not decrease the proportion of

chalky kernels so that the increase in percentage of head rice of IR8 apparently must be attributed to increased resistance of the grain to breakage during milling.

In this experiment, IR8 had a slightly higher grain yield than IR20 and IR22, but it had a slightly lower percentage of head rice so the total head rice yield was about the same for the three varieties (fig. 12). Since the head rice yield is the same, IR20 and IR22 would bring the farmer a greater return than IR8, because IR20 and IR22 have better grain quality and sell at a higher price than IR8.

The varieties IR8 and IR20 recorded the highest head rice yield when harvested at 32 days after heading. With IR22, the maximum head rice yield was obtained when harvested at 30 days after heading (fig. 12). The growth duration of IR22 was also shorter than the growth duration of IR8 and IR20 in the dry season, which may explain the differences in the optimum times of harvest of these varieties.

Data from the same experiment showed that for maximum grain yield, head rice yield, germination percentage, and high protein content, the optimum time of harvesting for the three varieties was 28 to 34 days after heading. During this period, the moisture content of the grain ranged from 18 to 21 percent.

Studies on high protein rice

A series of experiments were conducted to study the varietal differences in protein content in rice grain and to determine proper cultural practices for high protein rices.

10. Vegetative and root growth of IR22 were retarded by low temperatures at the early vegetative stage.

9. Relationship between nitrogen absorbed at flowering and grain yield of rices. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Varietal differences in protein content. In field experiments during the 1969 wet season at IRRI and at three experiment stations of the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry, an improved line, IR480-5-9, developed from a cross between Nahng Mon S-4/2 and Taichung Native 1 had

Table 7. Effects of applying 150 kg/ha N at different times on the percentages of head rice and chalky kernels in four varieties (average of 15 times of harvest). IRR1, 1970 dry season.

Variety	Head rice (%)				Chalky kernels (%)			
	Application time ^a				Application time ^a			
	B	B+PI	B+H	Mean	B	B+PI	B+H	Mean
IR8	53	56	60	56	9	10	9	9
IR20	60	60	65	61	8	8	7	8
IR22	66	65	65	65	5	3	3	4
RD1	59	61	63	61	5	5	3	5
Mean	60	61	63	—	7	6	6	—

^aB=basal; B+PI=50% basal and 50% at panicle initiation; B+H=50% basal and 50% at heading.

between 9.5 and 10.2 percent protein in the brown rice without fertilizer nitrogen. The highest protein content of the IR480 line was about 12.5 percent while IR8 had a maximum of 9.8 percent (fig. 13).

In these experiments, the grain yields of the IR480 line varied from 3.4 to 3.8 t/ha without fertilizer. The maximum grain yield in these experiments was about 5.8 t/ha, a normal grain yield for a wet-season crop.

Table 8. Effect of applying 60 kg/ha N at different times on the percentages of protein of brown rice in four varieties (average of 15 times of harvest). IRR1, 1969 wet season.

Variety	Protein content (%)			Mean ^b
	Application time ^a			
	B	B+PI	B+H	
IR8	8.8	8.6	9.0	8.8
IR20	9.2	9.6	9.5	9.4
C4-63	9.6	10.2	10.1	9.9
RD1	9.9	9.6	10.2	9.9
Mean ^c	9.4	9.5	9.7	—

^aB=basal; B+PI=50% basal and 50% at panicle initiation. B+H=50% basal and 50% at heading. ^bLSD (5%)=0.4. ^cNo significant difference.

Since the IR480 line has good grain quality and has high protein content with high yield potential, it may serve as an excellent material for developing high protein rices.

Cultural practices for high protein rice. In the wet season, the protein content of brown rice in IR20, C4-63, and RD1 was significantly higher than that in IR8 and the time of nitrogen application did not significantly affect the protein content (Table 8).

In the dry season, the protein content of IR20, IR22, and RD1 was significantly higher than that of IR8. When 150 kg/ha nitrogen was applied in split doses at planting and panicle initiation or at planting and heading, the protein contents were significantly higher than when the entire amount was applied during planting (Table 9). Top-dressing at heading gave significantly higher protein content than at panicle initiation.

At the normal time of harvest, which is about a month after heading, the protein content of rice varieties does not vary significantly. The protein contents of IR20, IR22, and RD1 were higher than that of IR8 at all harvest times.

In studies on plant density we found that the protein content of IR8 brown rice was higher at wider spacings but grain yields were decreased (fig. 14). Obviously, at wider spacings more nitrogen is available to the plants. Therefore, the protein content in rice grain was increased. But the grain yields were lower at wider spacings because of fewer panicles per unit area.

Last year, studies by the plant physiology department (1969 Annual Report) indicated that

11. The development of panicles of IR22 was restricted when the plants were subjected to 15 C for 13 days following panicle initiation.

application of simazine at flowering increased protein content of rice but reduced the grain yield. In 1970, we screened several triazines and substituted urea (Table 10) for their possible effects on the protein content of the rice grain.

In the dry season, simetryne at 0.5 kg/ha active ingredient, applied at complete heading, significantly increased the protein content and protein yield of IR22 rice compared with the fertilizer control (Table 11). The grain yield and yield components were not affected by the simetryne treatment.

In the wet season simetryne, at 0.5 kg/ha active ingredient, again increased the protein content of rice grain without decreasing the grain yield over the fertilizer control (Table 12). But simetryne in this season was effective when applied at panicle initiation rather than at complete heading.

Table 9. Effect of applying 150 kg/ha N at different times on the percentages of protein of brown rice in four varieties (average of 15 times of harvest). IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Variety	Protein content (%)			
	Application time ^a			Mean ^b
	B	B+PI	B+H	
IR8	8.3	8.6	8.9	8.6
IR20	8.9	9.2	9.9	9.3
IR22	8.8	8.8	9.7	9.1
RD1	8.3	9.2	9.8	9.1
Mean ^b	8.6	9.0	9.6	—

^aB=basal; B+PI=50% basal and 50% at panicle initiation; B+H=50% basal and 50% at heading. ^bLSD (5%)=0.3.

Other chemicals which increased the protein content without reducing the grain yields, were Benzomarc, Tenoran, and CP 17029. The grain yield differences between these treatments and

12. Effect of time of harvest on the grain yield and head rice yield of IR8, IR20, and IR22 (average of three nitrogen treatments). IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Table 10. Common or trade names and chemical formulas of herbicides tested for increasing protein content in IR22 rice. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Common or trade name	Chemical name
Simazine	2-chloro-4,6, bis (ethyl amino)-S-triazine
Simetryne	2,4-bis (ethyl amino)-6-(methyl thio)-S-triazine
Tenoran	N'-4(4-chlorophenoxy) phenyl-N,N-dimethylurea
CP 17029	2,4 bis (3 methoxy-propyl amino)-6-(methyl thio)-S-triazine
Diuron	3-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)1,1-dimethyl urea
Monuron	3(p-chlorophenyl)-1,1-dimethyl urea
Benzomarc	N-benzoyl-N-dichloro-3,4-phenyl N'-N'-dimethyl urea

the fertilizer control were, however, not significant.

Monuron and diuron significantly increased the protein contents but substantially reduced the grain yields, primarily due to higher percentage of unfilled grains and lower 100-grain weight over the fertilizer control (Table 12).

Future high yielding rice varieties should have higher protein contents without a decrease in grain yields. Our results indicate that protein content of rice grain may be further increased by applying certain chemicals.

Table 11. Protein content of rice grain and grain yield of IR22 as affected by liquid formulations of simazine and simetryne. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Chemical	Application		No. of spikelets (10 ³ /sqm)	100-grain wt. (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein		
	Rate (kg/ha)	Time ^a					Content (%)	Yield (kg/ha)	Relative yield ^b
Simazine	0.5	B	31	2.4	17	6.7	11.5	607	103
		CH	40	2.5	8	5.8	12.0	536	91
	1.0	B	34	2.4	14	5.2	13.3	545	92
		CH	30	2.4	20	4.1	13.4	422	71
Simetryne	0.5	B	38	2.4	13	6.3	11.6	574	97
		CH	43	2.4	6	6.6	13.6	706	119
	1.0	B	43	2.5	8	6.3	11.5	564	95
		CH	43	2.5	11	6.3	12.0	590	100
N fertilizer	150	^c	47	2.5	4	7.0	10.6	591	100
LSD(5%) ^d			<i>ns</i>	<i>ns</i>	9	1.5	2.2	156	
CV(%)			19	3	42	12	8	13	

^aB=booting; CH=complete heading. ^bProtein yield with 150 kg/ha N=100. ^c100 kg/ha during land preparation and 50 kg/ha at panicle initiation. ^d*ns*=not significant.

Table 12. Protein content of rice grain, grain yield, and yield components of IR22 as affected by some granular chemicals. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Chemical	Application		Toxicity rating ^b	No. of spikelets (10 ³ /sqm)	100-grain wt. (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Brown rice protein		
	Rate (kg/ha)	Time ^a						Content (%)	Yield (kg/ha)	Relative yield ^c
Simazine	0.5	PI	0	23	2.2	7	4.4	9.8	348	113
Simazine	1.0	CH	4	21	2.1	35	2.6	10.9	214	70
Simetryne	0.5	PI	0	23	2.3	10	4.4	10.3	358	117
Simetryne	1.0	CH	2	23	2.2	15	3.8	10.1	296	96
Tenoran	1.0	PI	0	20	2.3	6	4.5	9.2	331	108
CP 17029	0.5	B	0	23	2.3	9	4.5	9.2	324	106
Diuron	1.0	B	7	16	2.0	62	1.1	13.8	111	36
Monuron	1.0	B	9	16	1.9	84	0.4	14.8	51	17
Benzomarc	0.5	CH	0	21	2.3	9	4.5	9.5	340	111
N fertilizer	0	—	—	18	2.3	7	3.5	7.9	212	69
N fertilizer	80	^d	—	24	2.3	6	4.4	8.8	307	100
LSD(5%)				4	0.1	14	0.5	1	46	
CV(%)				13	4	18	10	6	11	

^aPI=panicle initiation; B=booting; CH=complete heading. ^bScale: 0=no toxicity; 10=complete kill. ^cProtein yield with 80 kg/ha N=100. ^d60 kg/ha N during land preparation and 20 kg/ha N at panicle initiation.

Broadcast-seeded flooded rice

Under farm conditions in Asia, cultural practices such as land preparation, water management, weed control, and fertilizer application are often less than optimum for successfully growing broadcast-seeded flooded rice. With the recent developments in chemical weed control, the prospects of using broadcast-seeded flooded rice in the tropics has improved.

A series of experiments was conducted during 1970 to study cultural requirements for broadcast-seeded flooded rice under tropical conditions.

Land preparation. In the dry season, grain yields with one plowing and two harrowings were significantly higher than when chemicals were used in place of land preparation (Table 13). When chemical treatments were followed by one plowing, the grain yields for broadcast-seeded rice were significantly lower than with one plowing and two harrowings. With chemical land preparation alone or with chemical land preparation followed by one plowing, transplanted rice performed better than the broadcast-seeded rice. Under optimum land preparation (one plowing and two harrowings), however, broadcast-seeded rice significantly outyielded transplanted rice.

In the wet season, one plowing and two harrowings also produced the highest grain yields of broadcast-seeded and transplanted rice. With both methods of planting, the effects of weeding was highly significant compared with the unweeded plots (Table 14).

These results show that the normal practice for transplanted rice, one plowing and two harrowings, is also adequate for broadcast-seeded flooded rice.

Water management. In the dry season, plants lodged earlier in the water-seeded rice than in rice seeded on mud. The lodging was more severe when rice was seeded into 20-cm-deep water than rice seeded into shallower water or onto mud. Figure 15 shows that rainfed IR22 was erect and standing, while it lodged when it was grown under continuous flooding with 20 cm of water. Because of severe lodging, the

13. Effect of nitrogen level on grain yield and protein content (brown rice) at IRRRI and at other locations (average of three Bureau of Plant Industry stations). 1969 wet season.

14. Effect of plant density (B = broadcast; other spacings are transplanted) on grain yield and protein content of brown rice without fertilizer nitrogen (variety IR8). IRRRI, 1969.

grain yield was lowest when rice was seeded into 20-cm-deep water (Table 15). Drainage for 7 days at maximum tillering, panicle initiation, or heading reduced lodging compared with seeding into a field continuously flooded 5 cm deep.

In the wet season, the yield of rainfed rice was as high as that of the best-managed irrigated plot (Table 15). More rain fell during the 1970 wet season than in any wet season since 1966. Nevertheless, the grain yields were normal.

Table 13. Effects of level of land preparation with or without chemicals on the grain yields of broadcast-seeded and transplanted rices (average of IR8 and IR22). IIRRI, 1970 dry season.

Chemical ^a	Tillage	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Broadcast	Transplanted
Dalapon/2,4-D NH ₂ none fb Paraquat		5.3	5.8
Dalapon/2,4-D NH ₂ 1 plowing fb Paraquat		5.6	6.2
PCP/oil	1 plowing	5.7	5.9
Paraquat	1 plowing	5.6	5.9
None	1 plowing, 2 harrowings	6.8	6.4
None	1 plowing, 4 harrowings	6.9	6.4
LSD(5%)		0.4	
CV(%) = 7			

^afb=followed by.

Table 14. Effects of level of land preparation with or without chemicals on the grain yields of broadcast-seeded and transplanted rices (average of IR8 and IR22). IIRRI, 1970 wet season.

Chemical ^a	Tillage	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Broadcast	Transplanted
Dalapon/2,4-D Na fb Paraquat	none	3.4	3.9
Dalapon/2,4-D Na fb Paraquat	1 plowing	3.9	4.6
PCP/oil	1 plowing	3.7	4.2
Paraquat	1 plowing	3.6	4.2
None	1 plowing, 2 harrowings, 1 hand weeding	4.6	5.0
None	1 plowing, 2 harrowings, unweeded	3.5	4.1
LSD(5%)		0.15	
CV(%) = 5			

^afb=followed by.

Thus water management requirements for broadcast-seeded rice are the same as for transplanted rice. However, the stand of rice will be reduced if the seeds are moved around by heavy rains. Under rainfed conditions, the fields become drained from time to time, which undoubtedly helps minimize lodging with broadcast-seeded flooded rice.

Seeding rate and nitrogen level. An experiment was conducted to determine the effects of plant density and nitrogen level on the plant and root characteristics, yield components, and grain yields of broadcast-seeded rice. Rice was broadcast at 50 to 150 kg/ha in 25-kg increments. The control was transplanted 21-day-old seedlings planted at 20 x 20 cm. The nitrogen levels were 0, 60, and 120 kg/ha. The fertilizer was applied in three equal parts, one basally, one 30 days after seeding, and one at panicle initiation.

The number of roots and weight of roots were studied from samples collected at 40 days and 70 days after seeding. For root measurement, eight samples were collected from each plot from broadcast-seeding treatments and five samples per plot were collected from transplanted control. Each sample was collected by digging soil from 10-cm radius from the base of the plant and 20 cm deep and making a mud ball to include as many intact roots as possible.

Without added nitrogen, IR22 gave significantly lower grain yield when transplanted than when broadcast, primarily because the broadcast plots had more panicles per unit area. The grain yields obtained with seeding rate from 50 to 150 kg/ha were not significantly different (fig. 16).

With increased plant density, the number of panicles per unit area increased, but a corresponding decrease in the number of spikelets per panicle and panicle weight also occurred (fig. 16). The length of panicles and the number of filled grains also decreased with increased plant density. These yield components explain why IR22 gave almost the same grain yields at varying seed rates (fig. 16). This further demonstrates that the medium- or high-tillering varieties, such as IR22, are able to produce high grain yields with broadcast seeding at low seeding rates, because they are able to put out additional tillers provided nitrogen is not limiting.

15. Rainfed IR22 was erect and standing (left), but IR22 lodged when it was grown under continuous flooding with 20 cm of water.

The differences in number and dry weight of roots per plant between transplanting and broadcast seeding at varying seed rates were more pronounced at 70 days after seeding than at 40 days after seeding (fig. 17). At maturity, broadcast-seeded plants had lower straw strength despite having fewer tillers, less dry matter per plant, and shorter plant height than transplanted plants (Table 16). These data explain why broadcast seeding results in more lodging than transplanting.

Time of nitrogen application. Two nitrogen levels, 60 and 120 kg/ha, were applied in a single dose or in split doses at different growth stages of IR8 and IR661-1-140-3.

Nitrogen application at active tillering gave significantly more grain yield than a single application at any other time (Table 17). The highest grain yield was obtained when nitrogen was applied half at planting and half at panicle initiation. Applying nitrogen in a single dose later than active tillering resulted in a gradual decrease in grain yield, primarily because the number of panicles decreased.

The nitrogen applied at maximum tillering remarkably increased the spikelet number per panicle but reduced the 100-grain weight. IR661-1-140-3 had a significantly higher spikelet number per panicle and lower 100-grain weight than IR8 (fig. 18). These two yield components compensated for each other and the grain yields

of IR8 and the IR661 line were similar. The filled-grain percentage was almost constant except that nitrogen was applied at heading in a single dose or at land preparation and heading

Table 15. Effects of water depth and drainage (for 7 days) on grain yield of broadcast-seeded rice. IIRI, 1970.

Water depth (cm)	Water management	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)
<i>Dry season</i>		
2.5	continuously flooded	6.4 bc
5	continuously flooded	6.5 abc
10	continuously flooded	6.3 c
20	continuously flooded	5.8 d
2.5 ^b	drained 1 week then continuously flooded	6.7 abc
5	drained at maximum tillering	6.9 ab
5	drained at panicle initiation	7.0 a
5	drained at heading	6.4 bc
5	drained 2 weeks after heading	6.2 cd
5	drained 3 weeks after heading	6.2 cd
<i>Wet season</i>		
5	continuously flooded	5.2 a
10	continuously flooded	4.9 ab
20	continuously flooded	4.0 c
10	reduced to 5 cm 21 DAS ^c	5.0 a
20	reduced to 5 cm 21 DAS ^c	4.6 b
5	drained from maximum tillering to panicle initiation	5.0 a
5	drained from panicle initiation to heading	5.0 a
5	drained from panicle initiation to harvest	5.1 a
5	drained from heading to harvest	5.0 a
—	rainfed	5.2 a

^aAverage of IR8 and IR22; any two means in one season followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bSeed broadcast on mud, field flooded to 2.5 cm 1 week after sowing. ^cDAS—days after seeding.

16. Effect of nitrogen level (average of all plant densities) and plant density on grain yield and yield components of broadcast-seeded and transplanted IR22. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Table 16. Plant height, culm length, and straw strength of broadcast-seeded and transplanted IR22 as affected by nitrogen level and plant density. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Planting method	Seeding density or rate	Plant height (cm)	Culm length (cm)	Relative straw strength	
				Leaf sheath included	Leaf sheath removed
<i>Without fertilizer</i>					
Transplanted	20 x 20 cm	81	59	80	26
Broadcast	50 kg/ha	74	53	49	10
Broadcast	100 kg/ha	70	52	45	8
Broadcast	150 kg/ha	69	50	26	4
<i>120 kg/ha N</i>					
Transplanted	20 x 20 cm	89	68	60	18
Broadcast	50 kg/ha	87	66	53	10
Broadcast	100 kg/ha	83	62	29	5
Broadcast	150 kg/ha	82	61	17	3

in a split dose slightly increased the filled grain percentage.

Among the yield components of IR8, the panicle and spikelet numbers per unit area increased as leaf area index (LAI) values increased at flowering. At high LAI values, the IR661 line had a higher spikelet number per square meter but lower 100-grain weight than IR8. The filled-grain percentages of both varieties were similar (fig. 18). The results also show that there was no optimum LAI values for maximum grain yields of IR8 and the IR661 line under broadcast seeding (fig. 18).

Weed control

Phenoxy acid herbicides for transplanted rice.

During the 1970 dry season various formulations and derivatives of phenoxy acid herbicides were compared with the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D for controlling annual grasses and other weeds in transplanted tropical rice. The test varieties were IR22, an indica variety, and Chianung 242, a japonica variety (ponlai).

The potassium salt of MCPA, the allyl and the ethyl esters of MCPA and the ethyl ester of 2,4-D caused high initial toxicity in all plots of IR22 (Table 18). IR22, which is a medium-tillering variety, recovered from the initial toxicity caused by these chemicals and produced grain yields which were statistically similar to those from plants treated with chemicals that caused

Table 17. Effects of time of nitrogen application on the grain yields of broadcast-seeded IR8 and IR661-1-140-3. IRR1, 1970 dry season.

Time of application ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean ^b	
	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)					
	60		120			
IR8	IR661-1-140-3	IR8	IR661-1-140-3			
LP	6.1	7.4	6.0	7.0	6.6	cde
AT	6.1	7.4	7.4	8.4	7.4	ab
MT	6.5	7.5	6.6	7.3	7.0	bc
PI	7.0	6.3	6.6	7.5	6.9	bc
B	5.7	6.9	6.3	6.3	6.3	de
H	5.4	6.3	5.8	6.9	6.1	e
LP+AT ^c	6.7	6.6	6.7	7.9	7.0	bc
LP+MT ^c	6.5	7.6	7.3	8.1	7.4	ab
LP+PI ^c	6.6	8.0	7.6	8.7	7.7	a
LP+B ^c	5.8	7.1	7.4	7.1	6.8	bcd
LP+H ^c	6.0	6.0	5.6	7.2	6.2	de
Control	4.5	5.1	4.9	5.8	5.1	f

^aLP=during land preparation; AT=at active tillering (20 days after seeding); MT=at maximum tillering (40 days after seeding); PI=at panicle initiation stage; B=at booting stage; H=at heading stage. ^bTreatment means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cHalf the total application rate at each time.

less toxicity. The liquid formulation of the potassium salt of MCPA caused some toxicity which lasted to the heading stage of IR22 and even longer on Chianung 242.

When comparisons were made between esters and salts of 2,4-D or MCPA, once again the differences in grain yields were not significant. All commonly marketed liquid or granular formulations and derivatives of 2,4-D and MCPA were equally effective in controlling barnyardgrass and other annual weeds in transplanted rice. These low-cost phenoxy acid herbicides provide excellent alternatives to hand-weeding in transplanted tropical rice.

In the Philippines, the granular formulation of 2,4-D or MCPA costs about one-half as much as hiring labor to weed by hand. Although the liquid formulations of 2,4-D or MCPA sell for about half the cost of the granular formulations, liquid herbicides must be applied with sprayers. Furthermore, liquid formulations are sprayed over the rice plants so they are not as safe as the granular formulations when somewhat more than the recommended rate is applied. At the optimum rate of application, the liquid formulation of 2,4-D or MCPA should perform as well as the granular formulation.

17. Plant and root characters of broadcast-seeded and transplanted IR22 as affected by nitrogen level (average of all plant densities) and plant density. IRR1, 1970 dry season.

18. Relationship between leaf area index at flowering and grain yield and yield components of broadcast-seeded IR8 and IR661-1-140-3. IRR1, 1970 dry season.

Table 18. Weed control, crop tolerance, and grain yield of transplanted indica variety, IR22, as affected by granular formulation of phenoxy-acid derivatives applied 4 days after transplanting. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Chemical	Ester	IR22				Chianung 242			
		Toxicity rating ^a		Control rating ^b	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)	Toxicity rating ^a		Control rating ^b	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)
		17 DAT	Heading of rice			17 DAT	Heading of rice		
2,4-D	isopropyl	1	0	8	7.6 a	2	1	8	5.3 ab
2,4-D	butyl	2	0	9	7.8 a	3	0	8	5.7 ab
2,4-D	isobutyl	3	0	8	7.3 a	3	1	8	5.4 ab
2,4-D	ethyl	4	2	9	7.9 a	3	1	9	5.6 ab
2,4-D	ethylhexyl	2	0	8	7.2 a	2	0	8	5.6 ab
2,4-D	dimethylamine ^d	3	1	9	7.9 a	3	1	9	6.2 a
MCPA	allyl	4	2	9	7.6 a	3	3	9	5.9 ab
MCPA	ethyl	5	3	8	7.6 a	4	3	9	5.2 ab
MCPA	isopropyl	3	1	8	7.1 a	2	1	7	5.0 b
MCPA	potassium ^e	5	4	8	7.9 a	3	3	8	4.9 b
Control		0	0	3	2.0 b	0	0	2	2.1 c

^aScale: 0=no toxicity; 10=complete kill. DAT=days after transplanting. ^bAt heading of rice. Scale: 0=no control; 10=complete control. ^cValues followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^dSalt. ^eSalt, water soluble-liquid.

Granular herbicides for transplanted rice. Until recently, the farmers have had to remove grassy weeds from transplanted rice fields by hand. Results from cooperative experiments conducted during 1970 at three locations in the Philippines, demonstrate that the application of granular herbicides before weeds emerge provided excellent weed control in transplanted rice.

In the dry season, a new Japanese chemical, benthocarb, S-(4-chlorobenzyl-N, N-diethyl thiol carbamate), showed that it controls weeds well over a wide range of application time (Table 19). In our experiments EPTC in combination with the isopropyl ester of 2,4-D provided adequate control and resulted in grain yields statistically the same as those of other successful chemicals. This combination could be a low-cost substitute for EPTC/MCPA in the Philippines because it involves a lower rate of EPTC. Testing of TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE was concluded this season. The herbicide is now sold in the Philippine market.

In the wet season, the rate of benthocarb application was reduced to half or one-third the rate applied during the dry season. Nevertheless, it performed remarkably well (Table 20). Another Japanese chemical, NTN 5006, O-Ethyl 0-(2-nitro 4-methylphenyl)N-isopropyl thionophosphoro amidate, in combination with 2,4-D, showed excellent selectivity in controlling barnyardgrass and other weeds in transplanted rice.

Testing of CP 53619 was concluded. It is now sold in the Philippines and soon will be marketed elsewhere in Asia.

In another experiment in the wet season, application of benthocarb or CP 53619 before weeds emerge was compared with application after weeds emerge. When applied before weeds emerge (4 days after transplanting) plots treated with benthocarb yielded 5.4 t/ha and plots treated with CP 53619 yielded 5.5 t/ha. But when applied 8 days after transplanting (when grasses were in the two- to three-leaf stage) plots treated with benthocarb yielded 4.6 t/ha while plots treated with CP 53619 yielded only 3.5 t/ha.

Table 19. Grain yields of transplanted IR22 at three locations in the Philippines as affected by granular herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting. IRRI cooperative weed control experiments, 1970 dry season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)		
		IRRI	Maligaya ^d	Bicol ^d
Benthocarb	3.0	7.3 a	5.5 a	6.7 a
Benthocarb ^e	3.0	7.5 a	5.2 a	6.8 a
CP 53619	1.0	7.2 a	5.9 a	6.4 a
CP 53619/2,4-D BE	1.0/0.5	7.3 a	5.2 a	6.8 a
2,4-D IPE	0.8	7.2 a	4.8 a	6.7 a
2,4-D EE	0.8	7.5 a	5.2 a	6.7 a
EPTC/2,4-D IPE	0.75/0.5	7.4 a	5.1 a	6.6 a
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.75/0.5	7.4 a	5.2 a	6.5 a
Control	—	3.9 b	1.0 b	2.5 b

^aIPE=isopropyl ester; EE=ethyl ester; BE=butyl ester. ^bOf active ingredient. ^cRough rice at 14% moisture; any two means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^dWith Bureau of Plant Industry. ^eApplied at the two- to three-leaf stage of grassy weeds.

Thus the chemicals are equally effective when applied before weeds emerge, but after weeds emerge benthicarb is better.

Broadcast-seeded rice. Weed control in broadcast-seeded rice is difficult because laborers cannot move through the field to weed by hand without pushing under some rice plants. In addition, weeders cannot distinguish between young grassy weeds and young rice.

In recent years, two selective herbicides, propanil and molinate, have been developed to control grassy weeds in broadcast-seeded rice. They are now widely used in Europe, South America, and U.S.A. Although propanil has revolutionized rice culture in many countries, it is not widely used in tropical Asia because of its high cost and its demanding water management requirements. Molinate also is costly for Asian rice growers.

Experiments conducted during 1970 demonstrate that other chemicals are suitable for direct-seeded flooded rice in tropical Asia.

In the dry season, benthicarb showed striking selectivity. Figure 19 shows the remarkable contrast between an untreated plot and a plot treated with benthicarb. Benthicarb, at 1.5 kg/ha active ingredient applied at 6 days after seeding rice (grassy weeds had one to two leaves), completely controlled all weeds in the plots and caused no toxicity to the crop (Table 21). The addition of 2,4,6-trichlorophenyl-4-

Table 20. Grain yields of transplanted IR22 at three locations in the Philippines as affected by granular herbicides applied 4 days after transplanting. IRRI cooperative weed control experiments, 1970 wet season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)		
		IRRI	Iloilo ^d	Maligaya ^d
2,4-D IPE	0.8	5.9 a	5.6 a	6.2 a
CP 53619	1.0	6.1 a	6.0 a	6.6 a
CP 53619/2,4-D BE	1.0/0.5	6.4 a	5.9 a	6.5 a
Benthicarb	1.0	5.9 a	6.0 a	6.6 a
Benthicarb ^e	1.0	5.8 a	5.9 a	6.4 a
Benthicarb	1.5	6.2 a	6.0 a	6.7 a
Benthicarb/MO	1.0/0.85	6.2 a	5.9 a	6.7 a
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.45	6.2 a	6.0 a	6.5 a
EPTC/2,4-D IPE	1.25/0.5	6.2 a	5.6 a	6.2 a
Control	—	4.2 b	2.7 b	5.0 b

^aIPE=isopropyl ester; BE=butyl ester. ^bOf active ingredient. ^cRough rice at 14% moisture; any two means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^dWith Bureau of Plant Industry. ^eApplied at the two- to three-leaf stage of grassy weeds.

Table 21. Effect of granular herbicides applied after weeds emerge on grain yield of broadcast-seeded IR22 and phytotoxicity ratings. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Phytotoxicity ^c		Grain yield ^d (kg/ha)
		(28 DAS)	(56 DAS)	
<i>Applied 6 days after seeding</i>				
CP 53619/2,4-D BE	1.5/0.5	4	1	6.6 a
Nitrofen+2,4-D IPE	2.0+0.5	2	1	6.5 a
Molinate/2,4-D IPE	1.5/0.6	2	1	6.4 a
Nitralin/MCPA-Na	1.2/0.5	2	1	6.4 a
Benthicarb	1.5	1	1	6.3 ab
NTN 5006/MCPA EE	2.0/0.4	1	1	6.2 ab
Benthicarb/CNP	1.4/0.6	1	1	6.0 ab
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	8	2	5.6 ab
Benthicarb/-simetryne	1.75/0.5	8	3	5.0 b
<i>Applied 8 days after seeding</i>				
NTN 5006/MCPA EE	2.0/0.4	1	1	6.4 a
CP 53619/2,4-D BE	1.0/0.5	5	1	6.4 a
Benthicarb	1.5	1	1	6.2 a
Benthicarb/CNP	1.4/0.6	1	1	6.1 a
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	4	1	6.0 a
Nitralin/MCPA-Na	1.2/0.5	1	1	5.9 a
Benthicarb/-simetryne	1.75/0.5	8	2	5.8 a
Control	—	0	0	3.0 b

^aBE=butyl ester; +=chemicals applied in immediate succession; IPE=isopropyl ester; EE=ethyl ester. ^bOf active ingredient. ^cScale: 1=no toxicity; 10=complete kill. Estimates made 28 and 56 days after seeding. ^dAverage of four replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

nitrophenyl ether (CNP) did not further improve the activity of benthicarb. The combination of simetryne and benthicarb, which is used in Japan, showed high initial toxicity to the rice crop. Therefore, this combination of herbicides is undesirable under tropical conditions.

Almost all treatments which included 2,4-D showed "onion leaf" symptoms of injury, particularly when 2,4-D was combined with either TCE-styrene or with CP 53619. Additional tillers produced by IR22 compensated for the initial toxicity observed in plots treated with CP 53619/2,4-D butyl ester 6 days after seeding (Table 21).

Another herbicide showing a high degree of selectivity was the mixture of NTN 5006 with ethyl ester of MCPA.

Most of these chemicals, when applied 8 days after seeding (when grassy weeds had two to three leaves), were as effective as when they were applied 6 days after seeding (when the grassy weeds had one to two leaves).

19. Weeds in direct-seeded IR8 were completely controlled by the granular herbicide benthocarb applied 6 days after seeding.

Experiments conducted during the 1970 wet season indicated that 1.0 kg/ha of CP 53619 was adequate to control weeds in broadcast-seeded flooded IR8 at IRRI and IR22 at the Maligaya station of the Bureau of Plant Industry (Table 22). CP 53619 which is currently marketed in the Philippines for transplanted rice, could be used also for broadcast-seeded flooded rice.

The herbicide TCE-styrene/2,4-D which was effective in controlling weeds in transplanted rice was also found effective in broadcast-seeded rice (Table 22). However, this chemical must be applied at the three- to four-leaf stage of grassy weeds (10 days after seeding) to avoid heavy initial toxicity. Other herbicides such as benthocarb, CP 53619, and NTN 5006/2,4-D can be applied when grassy weeds have one to two leaves.

Although a few chemicals have been found that improve the prospects for chemical weed control in broadcast-seeded flooded rice in the tropics, our efforts to identify chemicals that would cost less or would have a wider latitude in their time of application have continued.

Table 23 presents the results of using a few outstanding herbicides and combinations in a screening trial during the 1970 wet season. The new chemicals, C-285, C-288, C-290, PP 493,

and M-3338, provided excellent weed control without injury to IR22.

Amiben, which looked promising for transplanted rice in a trial conducted by the University of Hawaii, did not perform well for either transplanted or broadcast-seeded flooded rice under our tropical monsoon conditions. Dinoben, a herbicide similar to Amiben, however, performed well when applied in combination with isopropyl ester of 2,4-D for broadcast-seeded flooded rice (Table 23).

Table 22. Grain yields of broadcast-seeded rice at two locations (IR8 at IRRI and IR22 at Maligaya) in the Philippines as affected by granular herbicides applied after weeds emerge. IRRI cooperative weed control experiments. 1970 wet season.

Herbicide ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^c (t/ha)	
		IRRI	Maligaya ^d
CP 53619	1.0	4.7 a	6.1 a
NTN 5006/2,4-D IPE	2.0/0.45	4.4 a	6.0 ab
TCE-styrene/2,4-D IPE	0.6/0.4	5.0 a	5.9 abc
CP 53619/2,4-D BE	1.0/0.5	5.2 a	5.9 abc
Benthocarb	2.0	4.8 a	5.5 bc
Nitralin/MCPA-Na	1.2/0.5	4.5 a	5.4 c
Control	—	0 b	1.2 d

^aIPE=isopropyl ester; BE=butyl ester. ^bOf active ingredient. ^cAny two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^dExperiment station of the Bureau of Plant Industry.

Table 23. Promising granular herbicides (applied at the 1- to 2-leaf stage of grasses) for broadcast-seeded IR22. IRRRI, 1970 wet season.

Chemical ^a	Rate ^b (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weed weight ^c (g/sq m)	Control rating ^d	Toxicity rating ^e
Amiben +2,4-D					
IPE	1.25+0.5	2.9	608	6	0
Amiben	1.25	0.0	700	1	1
Dinoben +2,4-D					
IPE	1.25+0.5	5.3	120	8	0
C-285	1.0	4.8	123	9	1
C-285 ^f	2.0	5.6	80	9	1
C-288	1.0	4.7	50	9	0
C-288 ^f	2.0	5.2	30	9	1
C-290	1.0	5.1	78	8	2
C-290 ^f	2.0	5.8	123	9	2
C-293	1.0	5.0	103	9	0
C-293	2.0	4.9	86	9	4
S-16342 ^g	2.0	5.0	125	8	0
M-3338 ^g	1.0	5.6	49	8	2
M-3338 ^g	2.0	5.1	33	9	0
PP 493 (K-salt)	0.75	5.1	56	7	2
NTN 5006/2,4-D					
IPE	2.0/0.45	5.1	135	8	0
Control	—	0.4	933	0	0

^aIPE=isopropyl ester. ^bOf active ingredient. ^cMeasured at heading stage of grasses. ^dScale: 0=no control, 10=complete control. ^eScale: 0=no toxicity, 10=complete kill. ^fChemical applied at the 2- to 3-leaf stage of grasses. ^gLiquid.

Table 24. Promising liquid herbicides for upland rice (variety IR8). IRRRI, 1970 wet season.

Herbicide	Application		Visual rating ^c		Grain yield ^d (t/ha)
	Rate ^a (kg/ha)	Time ^b	Control	Toxicity	
NTN 5006	2.0	RE	5	1	2.3 abc
NTN 5006	4.0	RE	5	1	2.7 ab
NTN 5006	4.0	1-2 lsg	3	1	2.6 abc
CP 53619	2.0	RE	5	1	3.2 a
CP 53619	4.0	RE	5	2	2.0 abc
Benthiocarb	2.0	RE	3	1	2.4 abc
Benthiocarb	2.0	1-2 lsg	2.5	1	1.6 bc
Benthiocarb	4.0	RE	5	2	2.5 abc
Preforan	4.0	RE	2.5	1.5	1.3 c
Preforan	4.0	1-2 lsg	3	1.5	2.0 abc
S-16342	4.0	2-3 lsg	5	1	2.1 abc
PH 40-51	2.0	2-3 lsg	2.5	1	1.9 bc
PH 40-51	4.0	1-2 lsg	3.5	1	2.6 abc
Nitralin	2.0	1-2 lsg	3	2	2.0 abc
Dicamba	2.0	1-2 lsg	2.5	1.5	2.2 abc
Propanil ^e	3.0	15 DARE	1	1.5	0 d
Propanil ^f	3.0	15 DARE	1	1	0 d
Hand weeding ^g					
twice	—	—	5	1	2.6 abc
Control	—	—	1	1	0 d

^aOf active ingredient. ^bRE=rice emergence; lsg=leaf stage of grasses; DARE=days after rice emergence. ^cTaken at 52 days after emergence of rice. Control scale: 1=no control, 5=complete control. Toxicity scale: 1=no toxicity, 5=complete kill. ^dAverage of two replications. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^eFrom Monsanto Chemical. ^fFrom Rohm and Haas. ^gAt 15 and 30 days after emergence of rice.

Upland rice. The grain yield of upland rice in Asia is low because of problems such as lack of suitable varieties, erratic moisture supply, and poor weed control. Hand-weeding has been the most common method of weed control for upland rice in Asia.

Experiments were conducted at the Institute farm during the 1970 wet season to identify herbicides that would control weeds in upland rice under monsoon conditions. The test variety was IR8.

The major weed species found in the experimental area were grasses such as *Echinochloa colonum*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, and *Eleusine indica*; sedges such as *Cyperus iria*; and broadleaved weeds such as *Ipomoea triloba*.

The natural population of weeds was so heavy that the untreated control did not produce any grain (Table 24). The grain yields were generally low throughout the experiment because two typhoons occurred during flowering.

NTN 5006 sprayed at 2 kg/ha gave the best weed control (Table 24). Another chemical which looked very promising was CP 53619. Both chemicals were effective when sprayed before any weeds had germinated and the rice plants had one to two leaves. Propanil, which is widely used in South America for upland rice, failed to show sustained weed control in our experiment. The regrowth of weeds in the plots treated with propanil was so great that by 52 days after the rice emerged, the plots had as many weeds as the untreated control plots (Table 24). Other chemicals such as benthiocarb, PH40-51, and S-16342, also looked promising in the experiment.

Upland rice

Yield trial. During the 1970 wet season, 70 new lines including a few high yielding lowland varieties were planted in upland plots at three dates of seeding. A new upland variety, M1-48, was included for comparison. Several lines such as IR937-55-3, IR1154-243-1, and IR841-67-1 looked highly promising (Table 25).

The growth durations of crops seeded on July 10 and August 11 were shorter than the

growth duration of the crop seeded on June 9. Most varieties or lines seeded on July 10 and August 11 were at reproductive or ripening stage when two tropical storms occurred which reduced grain yields from these seedings. IR5, which matured later than most other lines tested, was affected by storms at all dates of seeding and the grain yields were not as impressive as in previous years but comparable to those of IR8 and other high-yielding lines tested.

IR22 had blast disease, nevertheless the grain yields were similar to those of the upland variety M1-48.

Varietal response to soil moisture and solar energy. Two field experiments were conducted during the 1970 wet season at the Institute farm and at Maligaya, Philippines, to study the nitrogen response of rice varieties under upland conditions as affected by soil moisture and solar energy level. The experiment at Maligaya was conducted in cooperation with the Bureau of Plant Industry of the Philippines.

At the IRRI farm, the responses of the May 31 and June 15 plantings to nitrogen application were normal and similar to those reported for earlier experiments (fig. 20). High yielding lowland varieties, including IR442-2-58 which was developed for deep-water rice, consistently outyielded the upland variety, M1-48, under upland conditions. Rice seeded on June 30 or July 23 was severely damaged by the two tropical storms which occurred during the reproductive and ripening period of the crops.

Rarely were soil moisture tensions higher than 250 mm Hg (field capacity). Therefore, none of the crops suffered from soil moisture stress. Although more rain fell at both the vegetative and the ripening stages of the crop seeded July 23 than during the comparable stages of the previous three seedings, it received less solar energy during the ripening period than the earlier plantings, which undoubtedly contributed to lower yields (Table 26).

At Maligaya, the high yielding lowland variety, IR5, produced consistently higher grain yields under upland conditions than the upland variety M1-48. Except for the crop seeded July 2, the nitrogen response of IR5 was almost linear

Table 25. Upland rice yield trial (seeded June 9, July 10, August 10). IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Variety or line	Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
		June 9 crop	July 10 crop	August 11 crop	Mean (t/ha)
IR937-55-3	118-127	5.5	3.2	2.9	3.9
IR1154-243-1	110-114	5.2	3.2	3.0	3.8
IR8	118-127	5.5	3.0	2.8	3.8
IR1108-3-5	111-122	5.3	2.8	3.3	3.8
IR788-21-3	110-122	5.3	3.1	2.9	3.8
IR841-67-1	114-120	5.7	3.0	2.6	3.8
IR577-24-1	111-122	5.2	2.8	2.9	3.6
IR879-183-2	118-127	5.1	2.7	3.0	3.6
IR937-76-2	112-122	5.0	2.9	2.6	3.5
IR5	125-135	4.8	2.9	2.7	3.5
IR879-314-2	115-122	4.8	3.0	2.5	3.4
IR854-179-1	118-124	4.0	3.1	3.2	3.4
IR812-76-5	115-127	5.0	2.5	2.7	3.4
IR1133-44-1	110-122	4.4	3.1	2.6	3.4
IR22	112-127	3.4	2.1	2.1	2.5
M1-48	105-112	3.5	2.0	1.4	2.3
Mean	—	4.9	2.8	2.7	—

Table 26. Solar radiation, rainfall, and upland rice grain yield data (average of six varieties and three nitrogen levels) at Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and at IRRI (average of three varieties and two nitrogen levels). 1970 wet season.

Planting time	Vegetative period rainfall (mm)	Reproductive period		Grain yield (t/ha)
		Solar radiation (cal/sq cm)	Rainfall (mm)	
<i>Maligaya</i>				
June 2	683	16,543	393	4.7
June 17	648	16,211	361	4.8
July 2	688	16,200	302	4.6
July 17	617	15,184	256	4.3
<i>IRRI</i>				
May 31	410	16,324	449	3.2
June 15	465	15,892	692	3.1
June 30	575	15,989	616	2.5
July 23	619	13,902	698	2.0

up to 120 kg/ha. On the other hand, for M1-48, positive grain yield response was obtained only up to 60 kg/ha N. The highest grain yield of 7 t/ha was obtained with IR5 seeded on June 17 (fig. 21). This is the highest grain yield obtained in any IRRI experiment on upland rice. The early maturing line IR579-48-2 was intermediate in performance compared with IR5 and M1-48.

Compared with the IRRI farm, solar energy values at Maligaya were slightly higher, the rainfall was lower, and the crop damage due to tropical storms was negligible. Undoubtedly

20. Nitrogen response of IR5, IR22, IR579-48-2, IR442-2-58, M1-48, and IR661-1-140-3-2 under upland conditions at four dates of seeding. IRR, 1970 wet season.

grain yields of IR5 were higher at Maligaya for these reasons.

The crop planted on July 17 received less solar energy and rainfall during the ripening period than the earlier plantings, which may explain why that planting had somewhat lower grain yields (Table 26). However, neither solar energy nor soil moisture was inadequate for high grain yield production at the four planting dates.

Results from the two locations demonstrate that when moisture and solar energy are not limiting and management practices are at optimum levels, high-tillering lowland varieties

with high yield potentials and good plant type, such as IR5, outyield the "upland varieties," such as M1-48, even under upland conditions.

Seeding rate of upland rice. Previous experiments at IRR have shown that seeding rates between 25 and 100 kg/ha produced no significant difference in grain yield when high-tillering, improved varieties such as IR8 are grown under upland conditions. The higher seeding rate is recommended as insurance against poor germination. In the 1970 wet season, three rice varieties were seeded in 25-cm rows at 25, 50,

100, and 150 kg/ha on July 9 and August 9. IR5 and IR22, medium-tillering lowland varieties, were planted along with M1-48, a lower tillering Philippine upland variety.

Even at the lowest seeding rate, the medium-tillering M1-48 produced satisfactory yields. The highest average yield for both dates of seeding was obtained with the improved varieties (Table 27). Lodging near harvest was more severe at the higher seeding rates where both leaf area index and tiller number tended to increase.

Tensiometers were installed at depths of 10, 20, and 30 cm in one replicate from each date of seeding. The data on soil moisture tension showed no consistent difference in soil drying which could be attributed to seeding rate. Rather, differences in the moisture tension in the different plots were associated with small variations in the soil properties.

Water stress effects

Irrigation in response to soil moisture measurements. Where the supply of irrigation water is limited it may be advantageous to irrigate rice

in response to some measurement of the soil moisture status. For upland crops, soil moisture tension is one index of the soil moisture status used to determine when to irrigate.

In the 1970 dry season, an experiment was conducted in which lowland rice was irrigated when the soil moisture tension reached 30 centibars (cb) at 10-cm depth in the soil, 50 cb at 10-cm depth, and 30 cb at 20-cm depth. Plots 5 x 5 m were lined with galvanized metal sheets to a depth of 1 m to reduce seepage between the plots. Two centimeters of water were applied at each irrigation. Plots continually flooded at 5 cm were used as controls. Nitrogen as ammonium sulfate at a rate of 120 kg/ha nitrogen was incorporated into the soil at the final harrowing. For each irrigation treatment 21-day-old IR22 seedlings were transplanted at two spacings (10 x 10 cm and 30 x 30 cm). After transplanting the plots were allowed to dry until the pre-selected soil moisture tension was reached.

At the 10 x 10 cm spacing, the treatment with irrigation at 50 cb at 10 cm showed only a slight drying at 30 cm below the surface, while high moisture tensions developed nearer the soil surface (fig. 22). Irrigation at 30 cb at 10 cm

21. Nitrogen response of three rices under upland conditions at four dates of seeding. IRRI-BPI Cooperative Soil Fertility Experiment, 1970 wet season.

developed quite high tensions at 20 and 30 cm. The difference in soil drying in the two treatments probably resulted from differences in sub-surface seepage into the two plots. The grain yield decreased from 5.47 t/ha in the wetter plot to 4.29 t/ha in the plot that developed high soil moisture tensions at 20 and 30 cm. Without detailed measurement of the soil moisture status throughout the experiment it would be impossible to explain this decrease in yield since the yield is higher in the plot subjected to the irrigation treatment that should have produced the most stress.

Irrigation when 30 cb developed at 20 cm gave a higher yield than irrigation at 30 cb at 10 cm. This was unexpected since a soil dries most

22. Soil moisture tension as a function of depth and time (MT = maximum tillering, PI = panicle initiation, H = heading, and M = maturity) for plots with IR22 planted at 10 x 10 cm and irrigated when 30 centibars (cb) water tension was reached at 10 cm depth (T1), 50 cb was reached at 10 cm (T2), or 30 cb was reached at 20 cm (T3). IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Table 27. The effect of seeding rate on the grain yield of three rice varieties grown under rainfed upland conditions. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)					
	July seeding			August seeding		
	IR5	IR22	M1-48	IR5	IR22	M1-48
25	2.80	2.10	1.69	2.21	1.65	2.02
50	2.56	2.66	1.78	2.27	1.65	1.96
100	1.88	2.59	1.84	1.91	1.62	1.49
150	2.35	2.56	1.53	1.78	1.83	1.65
Mean	2.40	2.48	1.71	2.04	1.69	1.78

^aMean of four replications.

rapidly at the surface. The reason is that the 5-day average of soil moisture tension at all depths never exceeded 30 cb in this treatment (fig. 22). Irrigation in response to soil moisture tensions at 20 cm gave the highest grain yield because only 2 cm of irrigation water was applied which kept the upper layers of the soil moist.

Grain yields were lower for each irrigation treatment at the wide plant spacing (Table 28). At the close spacing, the tiller number was little affected by the irrigation treatment, but the percentage of effective tillers was lower in the nonflooded plots than in the flooded control. At the wide spacing, however, tillering was reduced while the effective tiller percentage was increased on the nonflooded plots. Thus, vegetative growth appears to be affected more by water stress at wide plant spacings than at narrow spacings where competition for nutrients and light becomes important. For example, soil analysis showed the ammonium nitrogen content decreased more rapidly at the higher plant density.

Stress at different growth stages. If the water supply is less than adequate at some time in the growing season, it should be distributed in the most efficient manner possible. Knowledge of the effects on grain yield of water stress at different physiological growth stages would be helpful in deciding the optimum allocation of the limited water.

The experiment was conducted in the greenhouse. IR8, IR5, and H-4 were transplanted at one seedling per hill and four hills per pot in pails containing puddled, water-saturated Maahas clay. The plants were subjected to water

Table 28. Effect of water management and plant spacing (10 x 10 and 30 x 30 cm) on the grain yield and yield components of IR22. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Treatment ^a	Tillers (no./sq m)	Effective tillers (%)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	100-grain wt. (g)	Unfilled grains (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>10 x 10 cm</i>						
CF	510	99	83	2.4	8	7.66
T1	540	86	70	1.9	15	4.29
T2	500	88	92	2.4	9	5.47
T3	475	96	90	2.2	11	5.95
<i>30 x 30 cm</i>						
CF	455	73	112	2.2	10	6.40
T1	351	88	117	2.1	12	3.71
T2	273	87	108	1.8	8	3.65
T3	254	90	103	2.1	9	3.82

^aCF = continuously flooded with 2.5 cm of water; T1 = irrigated when 30 cb was reached at 10 cm below the soil surface; T2 = irrigated when 50 cb was reached at 10 cm; T3 = irrigated when 30 cb was reached at 20 cm.

stress at different growth stages (Table 29). Stress was imposed by allowing the soil in the pots to dry to 50-cb tension at 15 cm before irrigating with 2 cm of water. This procedure was repeated until the stress period was terminated by flooding the soil with 5 cm of water. Continually flooded pots were maintained under 5 cm of water throughout the experiment as controls and to measure the water use under nonstressed conditions.

The grain yield of all varieties was reduced when the plants were subjected to moisture stress at any growth stage (fig. 23). Moisture stress in the vegetative growth stages reduced the grain yield through a reduction in tiller number

and hence in panicle number per hill (Table 29). Stress in the reproductive and ripening stages lowered grain yield by reducing filled-grain number and grain weight. H-4 seemed especially sensitive to moisture stress after panicle initiation. Stress at this time caused a large increase in the percentage of unfilled grains.

The most "critical" time for moisture stress often is assumed to be the period immediately around panicle initiation. Our data suggest that for improved varieties, the length of time the plant is subject to moisture stress, is more important in determining the amount of yield reduction than the particular growth stage at which the stress occurs (fig. 24). For the improved

23. Grain yield of three varieties as affected by moisture stress at various physiological growth stages (T = transplanting, MT = maximum tillering, PI = panicle initiation, H = heading, and M = maturity).

24. Relative grain yield of IR5 and H-4 in the greenhouse as a function of the number of days the soil was not flooded.

variety, IR5, the grain yield shows a linear relationship with the number of days not flooded. Two points fall significantly below the straight line of best fit to the H-4 data. These points are for the treatments where stress was imposed during the grain filling stages, again illustrating the sensitivity of H-4 to moisture stress at this stage.

Figure 25 shows the regression lines for the IR8 data for the greenhouse experiment and for experiments conducted in 1969 in tanks with and without bottoms. The single points are for the treatment of moisture stress from maximum tillering to the panicle initiation. These three points fall significantly above the line of best fit to the other data points, suggesting again that this period is perhaps not a highly critical one for moisture stress. The slopes for the tanks with and without bottoms differ because tanks

Table 29. Yield components of the three rice varieties subjected to moisture stress at different growth stages in the greenhouse.

Stress period ^a	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	100-grain wt. (g)	Unfilled grains (%)
<i>IR8</i>					
None	7.2	7.2	89	2.55	22
T—MT	4.8	4.4	114	2.57	24
T—PI	4.0	3.9	116	2.52	17
T—H	4.1	3.5	91	2.77	17
MT—H	8.2	7.7	76	2.50	18
PI—M	7.3	6.5	67	2.50	20
H—M	7.7	7.4	79	2.40	34
T—M	7.0	5.3	12	1.58	63
<i>IR5</i>					
None	8.6	8.5	112	2.67	10
T—MT	5.5	5.4	128	2.63	10
T—PI	4.7	4.7	101	2.63	16
T—H	5.4	5.4	89	2.61	15
MT—H	9.2	9.2	84	2.53	8
PI—M	9.3	9.0	92	2.55	14
H—M	9.5	8.7	109	2.43	16
T—M	4.7	4.2	21	1.76	74
<i>H-4</i>					
None	8.2	7.6	150	2.57	21
T—MT	4.2	4.1	170	2.73	25
T—PI	4.0	4.0	148	2.60	15
T—H	3.5	3.2	118	2.52	27
MT—H	6.8	6.5	95	2.75	28
PI—M	8.0	7.3	75	2.53	46
H—M	10.9	9.8	69	2.32	53
T—M	3.5	1.4	3	1.50	89

^aT=transplanting, MT=maximum tillering, PI=panicle initiation, H=heading, M=maturity.

without bottoms drain more rapidly than the tanks with bottoms. Thus, plants grown in the tanks without bottoms are subjected to more severe water stress than the plants grown in tanks with bottoms. High temperatures in the greenhouse increase the atmospheric demand for water, causing more severe water stress at the same soil moisture tensions used in the field experiment. This results in the high negative slope for the greenhouse data in figure 25.

Water relations in flooded soil

Data from evaporation pans are often used to estimate consumptive use of plants that are not subjected to water stress. These data are determined not only by the same atmospheric and climatic factors which determine consumptive use, but also by the size, type, and exposure of the evaporation pan. In figure 26 daily evapor-

ation from two different pans is plotted against the solar radiation. One pan is the standard U.S. Weather Bureau Class A pan. The second is a square, 2.45 x 2.45 m pan, which was placed in the field so the water level in the pan was at the same level as the water in the surrounding field. The bottom of the pan was covered with soil. The class A pan gave consistently higher evaporation readings than the square pan. On the average, these readings differed by almost 20 percent. Thus, direct comparisons of evaporation data from different locations should be avoided unless the data are obtained using standardized equipment.

Water use of flooded rice. Water use in continually flooded rice fields increases as the plants grow and transpire more. As the plant canopy develops, less water evaporates from the surface of the water in the field. Figure 27 illustrates

25. Relative grain yield as a function of the number of days soil was not flooded (Yield from treatments with water stress from maximum tillering to heading in tanks with bottoms is shown by point A, in tanks without bottoms by point B, and in the greenhouse by point C).

26. Evaporation from two different evaporation pans as determined by solar radiation. IIRI, 1970 dry season.

this for continually flooded IR8 grown in tanks with bottoms in the 1970 wet season. Total evapotranspiration was measured with a hook gauge and stilling well while the surface evaporation was obtained from a small evaporation pan placed between hills near the center of the plot. The potential water use is calculated from the solar radiation by assuming all of the measured incoming solar energy could be used in evaporation. Thus potential water use (cm/day) equals the solar radiation ($\text{cal cm}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) divided by 590 cal/cm^3 .

The amount of water transpired by the rice can be calculated by taking the difference between the evapotranspiration and the surface evaporation (fig. 27). If water is to be conserved at the field level only, the evaporation component of evapotranspiration can be reduced without significantly reducing grain yield. Figure 27 shows this evaporation loss to be quite a high percentage of the total water use for the first 50 days of the crop. The spreading of evaporation suppressants such as the long-chain alcohols on the water surface at early growth stages may

27. Measured evapotranspiration and surface evaporation and calculated transpiration from IR8 grown in tanks with bottoms. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

be useful in reducing the total water requirement of rice.

Salt movement in flooded soil. Flooding the soil and growing lowland rice is one way to reclaim salt-affected soil. An experiment was conducted

28. Salt concentration in the surface 15 cm of a flooded cropped soil and of a flooded uncropped soil, and in the irrigation water. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

in the 1970 dry season to study salt movement in flooded soil with and without a growing rice crop. IR22 seedlings were transplanted at 20 x 20 cm in the cropped plots. One day before transplanting CaCl_2 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ were incorporated in four plots. Two uncropped plots were kept free of vegetation. All plots were flooded to a depth of 10 cm. Samples of the soil solution were periodically extracted from different depths in the soil with sampling tensiometers. The chloride concentration was determined chemically and used as an index of the total soluble salt concentration.

Without rice, the salt was leached rapidly from the top 15 cm of the soil while under the growing rice crop the salt concentration in the top 15 cm increased with time (fig. 28). Apparently, high evapotranspiration losses from

29. A fan-shaped planting pattern creates a wide range of plant densities within one experimental plot.

the cropped plots tended to increase the salt concentration in the soil solution more rapidly than the salt could be leached from the surface 15 cm. Water extraction by roots also influenced the water movement pattern in these plots and may have affected the amount and pattern of salt leaching. In the uncropped plots, the percolation rate apparently was sufficient to balance the increase in salt concentration from evaporation. The time of transplanting after soil flooding seems to be important in determining the effectiveness of rice cultivation as a reclamation tool. For example, delaying transplanting until 3 weeks after flooding in this experiment would have produced a more favorable salt concentration for rice than transplanting immediately after flooding.

Upland and lowland conditions for rice

Plant density. The effects of plant density on the growth and yield of rice may be quite different when the same varieties are grown under upland and lowland conditions. This difference can result from differences in water supply and stress, nitrogen supply, temperature, or other factors.

We planted two upland varieties, M1-48 and Palawan, and two lowland varieties, IR5 and IR22, under both upland and lowland (continually flooded) conditions. A fan design was used which gave 17 plant spacings from 15 x 15 cm to 60 x 60 cm in one 6 x 10 m plot (fig. 29). Ammonium sulfate at 60 kg/ha N was applied in a split dose to both the upland and lowland crops.

The optimum spacing for both upland and lowland conditions in this experiment was about 25 x 25 cm for IR5 and somewhat wider for M1-48 (fig. 30). IR5 planted under upland conditions outyielded the lowland planting at all densities used. The soil in this area of the farm was moist throughout the experiment and no severe moisture stress occurred in the upland plots. The yield differences in IR5 resulted from increased tillering in the upland field. M1-48, on the other hand, yielded much better under the lowland conditions. The tillering and grain number per panicle were higher for M1-48 under lowland conditions. These limited data suggest

30. Grain yield of IR5 and M1-48 at different plant densities. IRR1, 1970 wet season.

that varietal differences in response to water management do exist.

A severe attack of blast in the vegetative stage influenced the yield of upland IR22. The incidence of blast was closely related to the plant density. The percentage of the leaves affected by blast fell from 38 percent to 13 percent as the spacing increased from 15 x 15 cm to 60 x 60 cm (fig. 31). The difference in infection percentage may have resulted directly from spacing variations which determine the ease of spreading and the most probable spreading direction of the disease in the plots. Plant spacing may also have influenced the amount of infection indirectly through modification of the microclimate or by causing differences in plant vigor.

In the lowland plots, increased availability of nitrogen or more efficient uptake of nitrogen by the plants resulted in higher plant nitrogen concentrations at all densities than in the upland

31. Relation between blast infection and plant spacing in upland IR22 50 days after seeding. IRR, 1970 wet season.

plots (fig. 32). At the highest plant densities, the plants were visibly deficient in nitrogen, especially in the upland plots.

Figure 33 illustrates effects of plant density on the soil moisture tension in an upland field. Water use increased at the higher plant densities and subjected these plants to higher soil moisture tensions.

Morphological characteristics. The rate of development and the morphology of the root system in part determine the ability of a plant to grow under sub-optimal soil moisture conditions.

The lowland variety IR5 and the upland variety Palawan were planted under upland and lowland (continually flooded) conditions in the 1970 wet season. At 2-week intervals, various measurements were made on randomly chosen plants (fig. 34). Soil moisture tensions higher than field capacity developed in these plots from 50 to 70 days after emergence. The varieties showed a quite different response to moisture deficit. In the upland plot, the root development of Palawan continued while the root develop-

32. Nitrogen content of the straw plus leaves of IR5 and Palawan at panicle initiation as affected by plant density in flooded and upland plots. IRR, 1970 wet season.

33. Soil moisture tension in an upland field as affected by plant density (IR5) after a period of low rainfall. IRR, 1970 wet season.

ment of IR5 was retarded. IR5, the lowland variety, continued to tiller during the stress period, but Palawan stopped. The leaf area index of the upland variety increased at a slower rate and did not show the same decrease in the reproductive and ripening stages that the LAI of the lowland variety did. These observations indicate that upland varieties are adapted to perform better than lowland varieties under moisture stress. It may be possible to breed

these characteristics into a variety with improved plant type and increased yield potential.

Double cropping

Abundant rainfall in monsoon Asia makes double cropping feasible if short-season crops can be grown that will do well in very wet soil. The germination and stand establishment of

34. Effects of soil and water management on leaf area index, tiller number, and root development of Palawan, an upland variety, and IR5, a lowland variety. IRR1, 1970 wet season.

four different crops following upland rice was tested in the 1970 wet season. Soybeans (Hsi hsi), corn (Hawaii-68), sorghum (Corsor-2 and Savanna), and upland rice (M1-48) were planted after the straw from the preceding upland rice crop was removed. Three levels of land preparation were used: no tillage, row rototilling of 10-cm-wide bands where the seeds were sown, and complete rototilling of the plots.

Heavy rains during and immediately after

seeding maintained the soil surface in a nearly saturated state for a week after seeding. The corn produced a satisfactory stand under all levels of land preparation. Neither variety of the sorghum germinated well at any level of land preparation. Both the rice and the soybeans produced a much more uniform stand when some rototilling was done in the plots but did poorly when the seeds were just dibbled into holes in the uncultivated plots.

Agricultural Engineering

Four machines are near or in commercial production. A company in Japan is producing an improved power weeder based on our design. Production of six-row and eight-row seeders for pregerminated paddy has begun in the Philippines. Three local companies are setting up production of the table thresher. Another company in the Philippines is fabricating prototype rotary grain cleaners. Several manufacturers in the industrialized countries are interested in some of the designs for their local and export markets. More attention was given during the year to improving the prototype machines submitted by local manufacturers.

Fabrication of the first power-take-off thresher made good progress. The machine is undergoing further development. An experimental heated-sand drier is being developed. Economic research continued on hand-tractor use and ownership patterns.

Field machinery

Rotary power weeder. The three-row and five-row rotary power weeders which we have developed use lightweight, aircooled engines to drive three or five weeding rotors through a shaft and worm-gear transmission. The weeder assembly consists of high-flotation rotors which uproot and bury the weeds between the paddy rows. The three-row weeder weighs 19 kg and the five-row weeder weighs 27 kg. The most important feature of this machine is that the rotor assembly can be lifted off the ground to permit turning at the end of the rows without disturbing the plants.

A weeder based on the IRRI concept has been placed on the market by Ohtake Nouki Seisakusho Co., Aichi, Japan (fig. 1). It weighs 14 kg and is equipped with a sled which supports the weight of the machine during operation. This lighter machine is easier to operate than the original design. It can be set for two-row or three-row operations. Another Japanese manufacturer is developing a similar three-row weeder.

This type of portable equipment has generated interest in Japan not only for weeding but also for cultivation.

Row seeder for pregerminated paddy. Comments from farmers on the eight-row seeder for lowland rice (1969 Annual Report) indicated they wanted a lighter machine to improve handling. The seeder was subsequently redesigned to reduce its weight and permit compact packaging.

A new six-row seeder (fig. 2) weighing 19 kg (compared to 23 kg for the eight-row seeder) was also developed. The reduction in the number of seed tubes has lowered the overall height of the hopper to 115 cm (30 cm lower than the eight-row seeder). The lower center of gravity of the six-row unit has made the seeder easier to handle.

The designs of the six-row and eight-row machines were released to three manufacturers in the Philippines. A few of their seeders were distributed to cooperating institutions and farmers in the Philippines for evaluation. Agencies in Thailand, Nigeria, Peru, India, Indonesia, Ceylon, Pakistan, and Taiwan also received some machines.

The release of these seeders has generated unusual interest from Asian countries. Manufacturing drawings have been sent to companies in India, Japan, West Pakistan, Thailand, Taiwan, Korea, and Ceylon.

1. Japanese power weeder based on the IRRI design.

2. Six-row seeder for pregerminated paddy.

Multi-purpose seeder. The introduction of the six-row and eight-row seeders for pregerminated paddy drew inquiries for row seeders for upland crops. A simpler machine has been designed that has detachable assemblies (fig. 3).

The basic unit consists of a hopper, a seed distributor, and a drive wheel. It can be equipped with furrow openers for row seeding of upland crops or a skid for seeding pregerminated paddy on puddled soils. The machine can be modified to be pulled by hand, by draft animal, or by small tractor. It also can be used as a toolbar attachment on a standard four-wheel tractor. Further development work is underway.

Table thresher. The paddy table thresher (1969 Annual Report) has a flat, circular rotating surface for threshing instead of the conventional cylindrical drum. This arrangement makes more effective use of the threshing surface and permits a lighter design. The latest prototype has spiral baffles on the underside of the cover to improve the radial movement of the straw and a re-designed top cover and air-intake duct for compact packaging. The thresher, complete with an engine, fits in a 1.3-m³ crate. Compact packaging will encourage export marketing.

The thresher weighs 174 kg and is equipped with four handles so it can be carried into the paddy fields. To allow the thresher to be conveniently moved on the roads, fields, and levees, three different wheel configurations are being explored: a simple wheelbarrow-type arrangement, two wheels with a drawbar for hitching to small tractors, and three wheels in a tricycle arrangement.

In tests at the Institute's farm the threshing output was 250 to 400 kg/hr of rice when the thresher was operated by four to five men.

The design was released to three manufacturers in the Philippines. Two of these manufacturers submitted their initial prototype machines for evaluation. The units were tested and modified to improve their performance. A detachable engine mounting was designed so that the 3-hp engine could be quickly removed and used by the farmer for other operations. The manufacturers are incorporating these modifications in their new machines.

We have ordered some threshers from the manufacturers for evaluation in the Philippines and other Asian countries. Some companies located in the developed countries have indicated interest in the thresher. An Australian manu-

3. Multipurpose seeder (a) basic unit, (b) for dryland operation, (c) for wetland operation.

4. Second prototype rotary grain cleaner.

facturer is building two units for testing in the Asian market. A company in Japan is building a prototype for evaluation.

In response to requests, drawings were forwarded to manufacturers in Japan, Taiwan, India, and Pakistan.

Rotary screen grain cleaner. The second prototype of a rotary grain cleaner was fabricated with a centrifugal blower to improve air distribution and control. In the first prototype, the grain hopper and the fan housing were designed as a single unit. Separating these components (fig. 4 and 5) has simplified construction of the machine. When tested at the Institute and at rice mills in Laguna province, the second prototype had an output of up to 3 t/hr of clean grain.

Drawings have been released to two companies in the Philippines that are interested in manufacturing this grain cleaner. One company has nearly completed two prototype cleaners. This company manufactures grain driers and is interested in incorporating the rotary cleaner in its continuous-flow paddy drier.

Inquiries about the grain cleaner were also received from some developed countries. A leading manufacturer of grain cleaning equipment in the United States is exploring the possibility of introducing it as a general-purpose farm cleaner in the American market. This company has placed an order for one cleaner with a Philippine manufacturer. A company in Japan is considering manufacturing it for export to Asian countries.

Paddy stripper harvester. The experimental stripper harvester (1969 Annual Report) was modified to reduce the grain lost due to scattering. Different types of flexible and rigid baffles were installed inside the gathering-chain mechanism to prevent grain from being thrown out of the machine.

PTO-driven thresher. The first prototype unit of a thresher operated from a tractor power-take-off (fig. 6) was completed. Problems were encountered with the axial movement of the

5. Schematic drawing of the rotary grain cleaner.

6. Prototype tractor-PTO thresher.

threshed material through the threshing cylinder and the movement of wet grain in the grain-collecting auger. The axial movement of the material in the threshing cylinder was improved by redesigning the spiral baffles in the cylinder cover. The movement of grain in the auger is a severe problem with wet crops. The wet threshed material sticks to the sloping side walls and does not easily flow into the auger. The auger will be replaced with a belt conveyor which will increase the side wall slope and thus reduce this problem.

Tests with the first prototype machine revealed three additional problems: excessive shredding of straw into small pieces from over-threshing, slow axial movement of the straw in the rotary separator, and reverse draft from the straw thrower.

The shredding of straw into small pieces is a desirable feature in countries where straw is needed for animal feed. But it consumes extra power and is undesirable if the straw is a low-value by-product. The problem of over-threshing was reduced by removing some of the spikes from the cylinder and the concave. The present cylinder has 42 spikes installed in a spiral

arrangement to help axial straw ejection. The concave has 27 spikes arranged in three rows. In countries where finely chopped and bruised straw is required for animal feed, the thresher can be marketed with additional spikes in the cylinder and the concave.

The slow axial movement of the threshed straw in the rotary screen cleaner proved to be more difficult to correct. Ideally, the separating drum should move the threshed straw at a faster speed than the maximum threshing capacity of the cylinder. During tests with wet crops, excess moisture released from the straw increased the tendency of the straw to stick in the separator. Reducing the spikes in the threshing cylinder and concave partially solved this problem.

During the early stages of development, straight sheet metal spirals 10 cm high were used to form an internal auger in the separating cylinder. With these spirals, straw tumbled back into the preceding section and was retained too long in the drum. Using two spirals 20 cm high caused the straw to be forcibly ejected in two to three revolutions of the cleaning cylinder. Slightly bending the inner edge of the spiral so

the concave side was towards the straw thrower also improved the straw movement.

Initially the threshing and separating cylinders rotated in the same direction. The threshed material which was ejected from the threshing cylinder fell against the slower rotating spiral walls in the separating cylinder. This interrupted the smooth movement of the threshed material from the threshing cylinder to the separating cylinder and caused a slight piling and rolling of the straw. A counter rotation of the threshing and separating cylinders with a reverse helix spiral in the separating cylinder was tried. This arrangement permitted a continuous flow of the threshed material from the threshing cylinder to the cleaning cylinder.

A centrally mounted beater helped accelerate the movement of straw in the separating section. A series of fingers installed in the separating cylinder lifted and dropped the straw on the beater. The beater blades which were arranged at an angle to the rotational axis gave the straw an axial movement. At operating speed, the thrower created a reverse draft which pushed some of the chaff back with the clean grain. We are attempting to solve this problem by reducing the surface areas of the straw-thrower paddles

to limit the air movement without affecting the straw-thrower function.

Many Asian visitors who have seen the PTO-driven thresher have commented on the urgency of developing such a machine. This thresher design has been principally oriented towards the needs of large farm holdings and custom threshing operators. Discussions in Central Luzon with operators of custom threshers indicate that a tractor-mounted, PTO-driven thresher with a capacity of about 13,000 kg/day would be satisfactory for their work. Countries such as India, Pakistan, Ceylon, and the Philippines should have a market for such a machine for threshing wheat, sorghum, and rice.

Differential slip tiller. A four-wheel-drive machine with independently driven front and rear wheels was described in the 1969 Annual Report. Operating the front and rear wheels at different speeds gives a tillage effect. For mobility both sets of wheels can be run at the same speed.

This year several wheel designs were constructed to determine which would best combine traction and tillage. A drum wheel with tilling blades (fig. 7) was the most satisfactory in

7. Differential slip tiller.

very soft soil. Tilling was accomplished when the front wheels were operating at 55 to 60 rpm and the rear wheels at 30 to 35 rpm, and ground speed was about 0.8 m/sec. The machine bogged down in soft clay soils when the sinkage was equal to the wheel diameter.

Tractor mobility studies

An experiment for determining the rolling resistance of a standard 35-hp tractor in three Institute fields was reported last year. The data indicated a relationship between the rolling resistance and the area under the penetrometer curve (pressure vs. depth).

An experiment was conducted to determine the correlation between the amount that a rear wheel of a standard 55-hp tractor sinks and the area under the penetrometer curve between 0 to 23 cm deep in the soil. We felt that such a study would help to predict tractor wheel sinkage by the use of penetrometer readings. An additional objective of the experiment was to determine the correlation between tractor wheel sinkage and rolling resistance. A 55-hp tractor with a unidirectional strain-gauge, load-cell transducer was used to measure the rolling resistance.

A simple method of measuring sinkage of the rear tractor wheel was developed. A beam with nine deflectable pointers was placed on the ground. The tractor was fitted with extensions on the two rear wheel axles to deflect the pointers on the beam. Each pointer was installed with a single bolt to the beam and the bolt tension was carefully controlled to retain the deflected position of the pointers. These beams were positioned longitudinally along the travel path, one on each side of the tractor, so that the axle extensions deflected the pointers as the tractor was towed (fig. 8). The average height of the deflected pointers from the water surface plus the average water depth was used to calculate the axle height in the field. To obtain the axle height at zero sinkage, a similar experiment was performed on a flat concrete surface. Wheel sinkage was computed by subtracting the average axle height above the water surface plus the average depth of water from the average axle height above the concrete floor.

Four flooded fields were used to obtain a wide range of wheel sinkage. Fields F3 and F10 had not been planted for over a year and were thickly covered with vegetation. Field F1 was in the softest condition because it had been repeatedly used for testing wetland tillage implements. Field F11 had been recently harvested and had rice stubble.

Figure 9 shows a typical curve between penetrometer readings, p , and the depth of penetration, x . The curve crosses the abscissa at zero penetration resistance which represents the soil surface level, x_0 . From this intercept, the line representing 23 cm depth was marked to the right. The shaded area, A , was integrated by planimeter.

Figure 9b shows regression lines between area A and wheel sinkage. We originally felt that a single line could be drawn to represent the readings from all the four fields. The data, however, indicated two distinct groupings, one for fields F1 and F11 and one for F3 and F10. The vegetative cover forms a reinforcing mat on the soil surface which partly supports the tractor weight. This was not obvious in the penetrometer readings. Because of the small

8. Setup for measuring tractor wheel sinkage.

9a. A typical cone diagram of a test field (x =depth of penetration, p =penetrometer reading, Area A=shaded area).

9b. Regression line between wheel sinkage and area under the penetrometer curve.

size of the cone it was able to penetrate the soil between the roots.

The results indicate a definite linear correlation between the area and the sinkage. Figure 10 shows the regression between sinkage and the rolling resistance of the same tractor.

Drying and processing

Accelerated drying. In the tropics at the village or farm level, a simple, continuous-flow drier is needed for drying rough rice. The drier should be capable of quickly reducing the moisture content of freshly harvested rice to a safe level in a single pass. Conventional heated-air driers operate slowly to avoid lowering head rice yields and milling recovery. Last year work was begun on two accelerated drying methods: heated sand and flame exposure (1969 Annual Report).

Taste tests. When high-moisture paddy is dried with the heated-sand and the flame exposure methods, the starch granules are gelatinized. This converted rice was subjected to taste preference tests this year to determine the effect of accelerated drying on eating quality.

Three IR22 rice samples of 2 kg each were dried by the heated-sand method, the flame-exposure method and the air-drying method (control). The samples were cooked and tested at the Home Technology Department, University of the Philippines, College of Agriculture. The control sample was dried in an air-conditioned room and was artificially aged in a sealed jar at 120 C for 2 hours. Cooked rice samples were served to the tasters, first when the rice was freshly cooked and still hot, and second when it had cooled to room temperature.

Two separate panels participated in the tests: a consumer preference panel and a laboratory taste panel. The consumer preference panel was composed of 50 persons. They graded the cooked rice samples according to their preference. A laboratory taste panel of six judges studied the differences in one or more attributes, such as odor, flavor, tenderness, and cohesiveness of the samples. The judges on the taste panel were selected for their experience in recognizing differences among samples.

The consumer preference panel failed to detect any differences in taste between the hot and cold servings of the heated-sand, the flame-exposed, and the control samples. The laboratory taste panel, however, detected differences in aroma and color when the rice samples were served hot. They found the converted rice stronger in aroma than the control and they called the color of the converted rice creamy while calling the control white. They failed to detect any significant differences in flavor, off-aroma, tenderness, cohesiveness, and gloss.

In the cold samples, the laboratory panel detected differences in cohesiveness and gloss in addition to aroma and color. When the converted rice cooled it was less sticky and more glossy than the control sample.

Heated-sand drier. A project was begun to develop a continuous-flow drier utilizing the heated-sand process. A rotary-drum drier (fig. 11) has been completed. The drier has been designed for manufacture by small machine shops in developing countries.

The machine has a horizontally rotating drying cylinder mounted on top of a semi-circular sand pan. The sand is heated by a heat source placed below the sand pan. The drying cylinder is fitted with an internal spiral and has a set of externally mounted paddles. Two sets of scoops at one end of the drying cylinder transfer

10. Relationship between tractor wheel sinkage and rolling resistance.

the heated sand and grain into the drying cylinder. As the drum rotates, the sand and grain are mixed and move axially. After the desired grain-sand exposure, the sand is screened out through a rotary screen portion at one end of

11. Schematic drawing of the continuous-flow, heated-sand drying and parboiling equipment.

Table 1. Germination of IR22 seeds soaked in nitric acid solution (0.1N and 0.2N) followed by different drying methods (dormancy is considered broken when germination is 80%).

Soaking duration (hr)	Germination (%)							
	Sun drying		Heated-air at 43-46 C		Unheated-air at 29 C		Shade drying	
	0.1N	0.2N	0.1N	0.2N	0.1N	0.2N	0.1N	0.2N
	<i>Stored for 2 days after drying</i>							
12	61.0	73.0	39.0	55.5	15.5	22.2	26.5	29.5
18	75.0	85.0	64.0	76.5	34.5	63.5	35.0	41.0
24	86.0*	91.0*	78.5	87.5*	43.0	62.0	45.5	64.0
	<i>Stored for 2 weeks after drying</i>							
12	88.0*	93.0*	77.0	86.5*	59.5	71.5	63.5	75.5
18	91.0*	95.0*	87.5*	92.0*	73.0	88.0*	67.5	78.5
24	94.5*	95.0*	91.5*	96.5*	74.5	88.5*	79.0	84.0

*Significantly higher than 80% at the 5% level.

the cylinder. The sand falls back into the sand pan and is gradually moved by the externally mounted paddles toward the sand scoops for recycling through the drying cylinder.

Initial trials with the experimental unit indicated that the grain fed into the drying cylinder irregularly. The design is being modified with an auger-feed arrangement to permit a uniform flow of grain. This drier is designed with a liquified petroleum gas burner, however arrangements will be made to utilize other low-cost fuels such as rice hulls, wood, coal, and kerosene.

Drying sorghum. Since conventional heated-air driers requiring large investments are not

well suited for farm level drying, the heated sand process was evaluated for drying sorghum.

Experiments were conducted by mixing sorghum at 35 to 42% (dry basis) moisture and heated sand for 15, 30, or 45 seconds. The sand was heated in an oven to temperatures of 180, 200, or 240 C. A sorghum-to-sand ratio of 1:20 by weight was used during the entire study. Samples from two freshly harvested sorghum varieties were cleaned and the initial moisture contents were determined by the oven method. Drying tests were conducted by simultaneously pouring 200 g of sorghum and 4,000 g of heated sand in a flask. The recording of time for sorghum-sand exposure was started after half of the sorghum had been transferred into the flask. The flask was shaken vigorously to mix the sorghum and sand evenly. The temperature of the sorghum-sand mixture was measured by inserting a glass thermometer into the flask.

For 15 seconds exposure, there was no significant difference in moisture removal at sand temperatures from 180 to 240 C (fig. 12). Some slight popping of sorghum was observed beyond 200 C. With the 30 seconds exposure, moisture removal increased significantly as sand temperatures rose. Above 200 C, increased popping of grain was observed. Exposure for 30 seconds seemed satisfactory provided the sand temperature was below 200 C.

Although the heated-sand method of drying can be used with sorghum, the experiment indicated that the moisture removal is not as high with sorghum as it is with paddy.

12. Reduction in moisture content of sorghum (39% moisture, dry basis) with heated sand as affected by temperature and exposure time.

Table 2. Mean percentage germination of IR22 seeds soaked in nitric acid (0.1N and 0.2N) solution followed by heated-air and sun drying methods (dormancy is considered broken when germination is 80%).

Soaking duration (hr)	Germination (%)					
	Heated-air at 49 C		Heated-air at 60 C		Sun drying	
	0.1N	0.2N	0.1N	0.2N	0.1N	0.2N
	<i>Stored for 3 days after drying</i>					
12	65.0	72.5	62.5	75.0	78.5	81.0
18	58.0	72.0	62.5	70.5	68.0	85.0*
24	74.0	78.0	67.0	63.0	83.0	81.5
	<i>Stored for 10 days after drying</i>					
12	86.0*	88.0*	73.0	83.0	93.5*	90.5*
18	80.5	87.5*	82.5	85.5*	90.5*	92.5*
24	79.0	79.0	73.5	60.0	90.0	88.5*

*Significantly higher than 80% at the 5% level.

Breaking seed dormancy on a large scale. In small lots, seed dormancy can be broken by heat treatment or chemical treatment. In the heat treatment method, freshly harvested seeds are air-dried and then placed in an oven for 4 to 5 days at 50 C. In the chemical treatment method, freshly harvested seeds are air-dried, soaked in dilute nitric acid solution for about 24 hours, and then dried in the sun for 3 to 7 days. Neither of these methods is well suited to large-scale operations.

If freshly harvested seed could be soaked in nitric acid solution and dried with heated air, the process of breaking dormancy would be faster and easier on a large scale because the seed would not have to be dried before soaking, because conventional heated-air driers could be used, and because the process would be independent of the weather.

To examine this possibility we soaked about 25 kg of freshly harvested IR22 seeds with an initial germination of 6 to 8 percent in 0.1N nitric acid (240 ml concentrated nitric acid in 38 liters of water) for 12, 18, or 24 hours. Another 25 kg was soaked in 0.2N nitric acid. After soaking the seed lots were dried in the sun, in the shade, with unheated air, or with heated air.

For sun drying, the rice was spread in a 2.5-cm layer on a concrete floor, stirred every hour, and dried for 6 to 8 hours until the moisture content dropped to 14 percent. The shade drying was done in the same way except under cover. For the air drying methods, a small

flat-bed, two-compartment drier was used with a blower. One compartment was for unheated-air (about 29 C) drying; in the other the air was heated with an electric coil with a variable transformer which kept the air temperature between 43 and 46 C.

Dormancy is normally considered broken when 80 percent of the seeds germinate. At 2 days after drying in the sun, the dormancy of seeds soaked in 0.1N or 0.2N nitric acid solution for 24 hours was broken (Table 1). Heated-air drying of seeds soaked in 0.2N solution for 24 hours also broke dormancy by 2 days after drying. Neither unheated-air drying or shade drying broke dormancy by 2 days after drying.

By 2 weeks after drying, the dormancy of all seed dried in the sun and of almost all seed dried with heated-air was broken. The dormancy of shade-dried seed had not broken by 2 weeks after drying and the dormancy of seed dried in unheated air broke only for seeds soaked in 0.2N solution for 18 or 24 hours.

To determine the effect of higher drying air temperatures on the viability of the seeds, a second experiment was conducted using the same procedure as the first, except that three drying methods were used: heated-air drying at 49 C, heated-air drying at 60 C, and sun-drying.

By the third day after drying, none of the heated-air treatments had broken dormancy and only one of the sun-dried treatments had (Table 2). By 10 days after drying the dormancy of all sun-dried treatments had broken. But with the heated-air treatments, the dormancy of only

13. Schematic drawing of the rice hull furnace.

four out of 12 treatment combinations was broken. The decline in germination of seeds soaked for 24 hours and dried with heated air at 49 C or 60 C indicates that the drying-air temperature should be below 49 C to maintain the viability of the seeds.

These experiments showed that the dormancy of IR22 could be artificially broken within 4 days after harvest (2 days after drying) by soaking freshly harvested seed in 0.2N nitric acid solution for 24 hours and drying the seed in a batch drier with 0.8 to 1.1 m³/min of heated air (43 to 46 C) for 6 hours. The dormancy was also broken by soaking freshly harvested seed in 0.1N to 0.2N nitric acid solution for 24 hours and drying the seed in the sun for 6 hours.

Unheated-air drying (ambient air temperature of 29 C) for 48 hours following soaking in nitric acid solution failed to break dormancy when tested 2 days after drying. This indicates the importance of heat in the process.

The drying-air temperature for a flat-bed, batch-type drier should not exceed 46 C (115 F) to maintain the viability of the seed.

Rice hull furnace. A furnace using rice hulls as fuel was constructed (fig. 13). The furnace consists of two 580-liter (55-gal) oil drums which are connected by an air duct. Rice hulls are

shovelled into the furnace where they burn on a sloping grate in the first drum. The second drum serves as a trap to arrest ash and other combustion products. A centrifugal blower is connected to the furnace to draw some of the heat of combustion from the furnace and blow it into a grain drier.

A preliminary test of the furnace with a small blower gave a heat rate of 125 to 500 kcal/min. The average heating value of rice hulls was 2,780 kcal/kg. Based on these values, the furnace can heat 85 m³/min of ambient air to 49 C. This amount of heated air (which requires 50 kg/hr of rice hulls) can dry 1.5 to 2.0 tons of wet paddy (25% moisture content) in 6 hours when the grain is placed 0.3 m deep in a batch drier. The tests also indicated that with the help of an aspirator, complete combustion can be achieved, thereby eliminating the need for a heat exchanger.

Because the rice hulls are fed by hand the operator must attend the furnace continuously. We are considering the use of a large rotary feeding wheel to continuously feed the hulls into the furnace with the help of gravity.

Manually operated grain cleaner. Traditional winnowers in Asia have no provisions for mechanical screening, they do not remove large

impurities, nor do they function well with wet or high-moisture crops.

A manually operated cleaner which combines mechanical screening and pneumatic cleaning is being developed (fig. 14). It consists of a grain-tumbling cylinder with a coaxial fan. Part of the cylinder has a rotary screen. The grain hopper is supported on the cylinder by a pair of rollers which activate the seed metering mechanism. A fluted metering device uniformly feeds the grain into the cleaning cylinder. The metered grain drops on the outside of the screen and is introduced into the cylinder. The repeated tumbling of the rotary cylinder winnows the grain in the air stream.

The cleaner uses a single cylinder for screening and tumbling the grain. It has a single shaft on which the fan and the cleaning drum are mounted.

Economics of mechanization

Seeder for pregerminated paddy. While little evidence is available on the use or costs of the mechanical seeder, the widespread interest generated by this machine prompted a review of its economic feasibility. Table 3 contains estimates of the fixed and operating expenses of the seeder. Figure 15 indicates that, considering only planting costs, with annual use on over 2.5 hectares, it is more economical to employ the seeder than to transplant manually. The contract cost of transplanting was obtained from farmers' interviews in Laguna and Central Luzon. Thus it would pay a farmer with as little as 1.5 hectares, double cropped, to buy the machine.

Hand tractor survey. In recent years, the number of hand tractors on farms in certain areas of the

14. Schematic drawing of the manually operated grain cleaner.

Table 3. Annual costs of the eight-row seeder (estimated service life, 4 years).

Item	Cost ^a (P)
Purchase price	350.00
Fixed costs:	
Depreciation	87.50
Interest ^b	21.00
Total	108.50
Variable costs:	
Repairs and replacements ^c	30.88
Labor (per hour)	0.50

^aUS\$1 = P6.10 (approx.). ^bEstimated at 12% per annum. ^cEstimated replacement cost for parts: fluted roller, P5/year; brush cut-off, P4.50/year; paint, P5/year; skid, P80 before the fourth year.

Philippines has increased rapidly. To assess the pattern of ownership and use, a survey of hand-tractor operators was conducted in Laguna province in 1969-70. From information supplied by hand-tractor dealers and distributors, a sample of 140 tractor owners was selected for personal interviews. (Table 4).

Nearly all the tractors were found on irrigated, two-crop farms, most of which were operated by share tenants or lessees. Average tractor size tends to increase slightly with increases in the size of the farm (hand tractors can be classi-

15. Average total cost per hectare of the eight-row seeder.

Table 4. Hand tractor ownership patterns, labor requirements, and machine performance, Laguna, Philippines, 1969.

Item	Hand tractor type			All types
	Small ^a	Medium ^b	Large ^c	
<i>Tenure</i>				
Share tenant (%)	57	51	20	48
Lessee (%)	30	31	12	27
Part owner (%)	4	9	4	6
Owner-operator (%)	9	9	64	19
<i>Farm characteristics</i>				
Rainfed (%)	0	3	4	2
Irrigated one-crop (%)	2	6	12	6
Irrigated two-crop (%)	98	91	84	92
Average size (ha)	4.0	4.4	4.8	4.3
Operators (no.)	2	2	2	2
Labor (man-hr/ha)	88.2	88.4	63.1	83.8
<i>Tractor characteristics</i>				
Use (machine-hr/ha)	44.1	44.2	31.5	41.9
Power (Avg hp)	5.3	5.5	7.5	5.8
(Rhp-hr/ha)	235.5	244.4	235.4	243.4
Fuel consumption				
(liter/hr)	1.18	1.18	1.06	1.16
Lubricants (liter/hr)	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.07

^a47 observations. ^b68 observations. ^c25 observations.

fied as "small," "medium," and "large" based on horsepower, transmission system, and steering system: "Small" tractors are lightweight, they are usually equipped with 4-hp to 6-hp gasoline engines, they have no differential mechanism in the axle, and they have no provision for steering clutches; "medium" tractors are relatively more powerful [up to 8 hp] and have multi-speed shifting transmissions and are equipped with steering clutches; "large" tractors have the same provisions as medium tractors but are equipped with diesel engines with ratings of 8 to 14 hp.)

Table 5 presents the fixed and variable costs for the three types of hand tractors included in the survey. Prior to devaluation of the Philippine peso in February 1970, tractor contract costs varied from P25 to P35 per 8-hour day. The latter was typical of rates in which meals of two men who jointly operate the tractor are not included. Using these costs, the break-even point for small and medium tractors was 230 hours of annual use and for large tractors it was 490 hours. On this basis more than 50 percent of the tractors were used economically (Table 5). Except for large tractors, economies of scale are negligible above 800 hours of use.

Table 5. Average costs of hand tractor ownership and operation, Laguna, Philippines, 1969.

Item	Hand tractor type			All types
	Small	Medium	Large	
Estimated service life (yr)	8	8	10	8
Annual use (hr)	486	442	641	492
Purchase price (P) ^a	3367	3420	7319	4098
<i>Fixed costs (P):</i>				
Depreciation ^b	379	385	659	461
Interest ^c	222	226	483	271
Total	601	610	1142	732
<i>Variable costs (P/hr):</i>				
Fuel	0.32	0.32	0.18	0.29
Lubricants	0.09	0.11	0.11	0.10
Repairs	0.35	0.29	0.76	0.39
Labor	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Total	1.76	1.72	2.05	1.78

^aUS\$=P3.90. ^bStraight-line; salvage value=10% of purchase price. ^c12% per annum.

Above this level of usage, there are only marginal cost reductions resulting from the spreading of overhead costs over more hours.

The relative importance of individual cost factors such as the price of fuel, wage rates, custom charges, and interest rate were obtained by varying each factor above and below its observed value while holding all other costs constant (fig. 16). For example, a P5 increase in the custom rate reduces the break-even point by 43 hours for small tractors and by 103 hours for large tractors.

After the devaluation of the peso, the price of new hand tractors and standard attachments increased by an average of 30 percent. The cost of spare parts has also increased by about 30 percent, the price of gasoline by 18.5 percent, and the price of diesel fuel by 29 percent. In addition, during 1970 the minimum legal daily wage was set at P8 for industry and P4.75 for agriculture. These price and wage increases have raised the cost of custom land preparation by an average of P10 per day. This is an increase of 28 percent over the rate before devaluation.

The effect of devaluation on average costs of ownership and operation of hand tractors may be examined from two perspectives: the effect on those who purchased tractors prior to devaluation and the effect on those who obtained machines after devaluation.

Annual fixed costs are a constant determined by initial purchase price and the useful life of a

16. Relative importance of hand tractor costs on hours of annual use necessary to break even.

17. Average total costs of hand tractors before and after devaluation of the Philippine peso.

machine. So for farmers who purchased tractors before devaluation, changes in operating costs are the only relevant consideration in assessing changes in total average costs. Given the average annual use of 492 hours (Table 5), the costs of tractor owners who purchased machines before devaluation rose by ₱0.60 per hour. Those who purchased machines after devaluation suffered an increase of ₱1.11/hr — 32 percent above the level before the floating rate.

The possible outcomes of increased and fixed variable costs and the impact on annual-use

requirements are presented in figure 17. Taking large tractors as an example, annual use must increase from 490 to 696 hours to justify investment in a machine of this type given the pattern of increased costs. This means that with no corresponding increase in custom rates, power tillers must be used more intensively to cover both the rise in the purchase price and the cost of labor, fuel, and lubricants. Custom operators, however, have raised the contract rate by ₱10/8-hr day since devaluation and this will more than compensate for the increase in costs.

Agricultural Economics

This year's report concentrates on some of the socio-economic issues associated with the introduction of the new technology. Particular attention has been given to the changes in labor utilization that have been occurring since the introduction of the high yielding varieties.

Results of farm surveys in progressive regions of Luzon indicate that there has been relatively little change in preharvest labor requirements. The seasonal distribution of labor use has shifted, however, principally because more farmers are using machines for land preparation and because demand for labor for weeding has increased. The demand for harvest labor has increased because yields have risen. The areas surveyed also showed a marked increase in hired labor as a percentage of total labor output.

In Laguna, Philippines, farm surveys show that farm returns and farm practices vary considerably with the soil-water resource base. Nevertheless, farmers in all localities invested more heavily in fertilizer than in insecticides. Analyses of costs and returns for fertilizers and insecticides, based upon experimental results from local farmers' fields, confirm the economic rationale of farmer decisions in this area.

Although evidence exists that higher yields are being capitalized into rising land values, tenants and landless laborers have also shared in the benefits of the new technology.

A survey of local rice mills indicates that the expansion in milling capacity has more than kept pace with supply in this region. The economic advantage of the several new modern milling complexes capable of producing high quality rice has yet to be demonstrated.

Production of rice in Asia

Table 1 updates the available information on increased rice production for specified countries of Asia. In the unfavorable climate of monsoon Asia, where 80 percent of the rice-growing area is rainfed, upland, or deep water, production gains have not been dramatic. In the monsoon tropics, the Philippines so far seems to be the greatest beneficiary of the new technology with about 40 percent of its rice area (1.3 million out of 3.2 million hectares) planted to high yielding varieties during the 1969/70 crop season.

Changes in farming practices

The results of several surveys were analyzed to get detailed information on changes occurring in farm production, input use, and income level. All but one of the surveys were conducted in the Philippines. The areas surveyed in the Philippines are not typical of rice farming in the country. They were chosen principally because they

1. Location of 118 farms in a survey of changes in farming practices. Central Luzon and Laguna, Philippines, 1968/69.

represent progressive areas where change is taking place and hence the impact of the new technology can already be observed.

Labor utilization on Luzon farms. Does the new technology require more labor due to more intensive crop practices? Or is the introduction of these improved practices accompanied by labor saving devices such as tractors, threshers, and the like? We hypothesized that the degree to which the new “seed-fertilizer” technology is accompanied by labor-displacing mechanization depends very much upon the institutional structure of farming (such as farm size and tenancy) in the area and upon the economies offered by mechanization. These economies in turn depend upon the relative availabilities of capital, labor, and land, and the prices of these factors. Factor and product prices tend to be distorted by subsidization programs, minimum wage policies, and over-valued exchange rates, making unemployment and underemployment potentially more of a problem.

The new rice technology emphasizes increased land productivity. Over time farmers should be able to produce the needed amount of food with relatively larger amounts of purchased capital inputs and relatively smaller amount of land and labor. Thus, even though the labor required per hectare of rice may increase, the total labor required to meet rice requirements (assuming national self-sufficiency) should be less. Importing countries will experience an initial growth in labor demand until self-sufficiency is reached.

We made a study in the Philippines to determine what changes are taking place in labor requirements and utilization of labor on rice farms adopting the new rice technology, and to determine how the new technology will affect the aggregate labor requirements for rice production. Only the results of analysis related to the first objective are presented in this year’s annual report.

A survey was made in Central Luzon and Laguna province (fig. 1) on labor practices for the 1968/69 crop year. It involved farmers who had been interviewed previously in a study by the department of agricultural engineering. Records of labor use and farming practices were

available on 92 farms for the wet seasons of 1966 and 1968.

The survey area varied considerably in terms of resources and farming practices. The bulk of the farms in Laguna are double-crop, irrigated. In Nueva Ecija, at least one crop of rice normally is irrigated. Many of the farms along the main highway in Bulacan, Tarlac, and Pangasinan are rainfed.

No clearly defined change in total labor utilization occurred during the survey period. Changes, however, do appear to be occurring in the total amount of labor employed and in the quantity of labor employed for specific practices.

Land preparation. The amount of labor used in land preparation has declined. The decline is confirmed by the increase in the use of tractors (Tables 2 and 3) and in the amount of labor hired for land preparation (Table 4).

More tractors are being used on both rainfed and irrigated farms. This is associated with the introduction of high-yielding varieties (Table 2). The pattern of mechanization varies throughout the survey area. In Laguna, small hand tractors (6 to 14 hp) are usually owned by tenants. They use them for harrowing after the field has been plowed by a carabao. In Central Luzon, large four-wheel tractors (40 to 60 hp) owned by landowners are used principally for plowing before the soil is completely saturated. Where tractors are used farmer-owners normally rent services, but the carabao (water buffalo) is still

Table 1. Production of rough rice and contribution of area and yield to production increase for selected Asian areas, 1960-64 and 1968-69.

Area	Annual production ^a (1000 t)		Increase (%)	Change in production due to change in	
	1960-64	1968-69		Area (%)	Yield (%)
Burma	7925	8187	3	100	0
Ceylon	963	1346	40	87	13
Malaysia	840	1344	60	77	23
India	53105	61351	16	39	61
Indonesia	12718	16577	30	40	60
E. Pakistan	14702	17259	17	69	31
W. Pakistan	1837	3417	86	34	66
Philippines	3883	4857	25	20	80
Thailand	10074	12300	22	89	11

^aSource: U.S. Dept. of Agriculture and Government of Pakistan.

used for land preparation on the majority of farms.

The estimated reduction in labor for land preparation from 18 to 11 man-days per hectare between 1966 and 1968 (Table 2) seems not quite realistic. Since only about 30 percent of the farms were using tractors and since these tractors were used principally for plowing or harrowing (not both) a reduction from 18 to 14 or 15 man-days per hectare seems more reasonable. Where small hand tractors are used, two operators frequently take turns operating the tractor. In this study, however, only the time of one operator was counted. Thus, man-hours and machine-hours were essentially the same.

Weeding. The 45 farmers planting high-yielding varieties were asked to compare the

Table 2. Labor inputs and mechanization of 92 farms. Central Luzon and Laguna, Philippines, 1966 and 1968 wet season.^a

Year	Farms ^b (no.)	Area (ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Labor use (man-days)					Machine users (%)			
				Land prepar- ation	Trans- planting	Weeding	Other pre-harvest	Harvesting and threshing	Total	Tractors	Weeders	Threshers
<i>Rainfed</i>												
1966	32	1.9	2.1	17	16	5	9	17	64	9	3	84
1968	38	3.0	1.9	11	16	6	7	13	53	32	3	92
<i>Irrigated one-crop</i>												
1966	39	2.6	1.9	20	15	6	8	17	66	5	10	95
1968	32	3.7	2.1	11	17	8	9	15	60	22	19	81
<i>Irrigated two-crop</i>												
1966	21	2.2	1.9	16	12	5	8	22	63	43	10	0
1968	22	3.0	2.4	9	13	12	12	22	68	50	41	50
<i>All farms</i>												
1966	92	2.3	2.0	18	15	5	8	18	64	15	8	69
1968	92	3.2	2.1	11	16	8	9	16	60	33	17	78

^aFrom 118 farms surveyed in 1968, 92 usable records were available in 1966 and 1968. ^bIncrease in rainfed farms and decrease in irrigated farms in 1968 mainly a result of drought.

Table 3. Labor inputs and mechanization of 118 farms growing local and high yielding varieties (HYV). Central Luzon and Laguna, 1968 wet season.

Variety	Farms (no.)	Area (ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Labor use (man-days)					Machine users (%)			
				Land preparation	Trans-planting	Weeding	Other pre-harvest	Harvesting and threshing	Total	Tractors	Weeders	Threshers
<i>Rainfed</i>												
HYV	15	1.6	1.9	11	14	6	8	12	51	20	7	87
Local	46	2.5	2.0	11	16	5	7	13	52	26	0	85
<i>Irrigated one-crop</i>												
HYV	14	3.5	1.9	10	18	8	9	14	59	28	36	86
Local	34	2.6	2.1	12	16	6	10	16	60	20	12	56
<i>Irrigated two-crop</i>												
HYV	16	2.8	3.0	8	16	16	12	27	79	56	50	38 ^b
Local	22	2.7	2.7	11	16	8	12	19	66	41	36	50
<i>All farms</i>												
HYV	45	2.6	2.5	9	16	11	10	18	64	36	31	69
Local	102 ^a	2.5	2.3	11	16	6	9	15	57	27	12	68

^a Some farms grew both local and high yielding varieties. ^b Many of these farms are in Laguna where mechanical threshers are not used.

labor requirements for new and local varieties. They reported an average increase of 6 man-days per hectare, half of which was devoted to weeding. Apparently more labor is also being employed in weeding particularly on double-cropped, irrigated farms (Tables 2 and 3). Much of the increased labor input is being hired (Table 4). Increased weeding has been accompanied on many farms by the use of mechanical weeders.

Harvesting and threshing. On most of the survey farms in Central Luzon, harvesting was done by hand with a sickle while threshing was done by machine. The harvester was normally paid in kind—5 kg of rough rice for every 1 kg of rice planted. If paid in cash, he received approximately ₱2.50/day for cutting the crop.

The thresher's share is normally 5 percent of the harvest. The large stationary thresher used

in Central Luzon is fabricated in the Philippines but patterned after the McCormick thresher. In Laguna, where no mechanical threshers are employed, and on those farms in Central Luzon where harvesting and threshing are done by hand, the laborers receive one-eighth to one-sixth of the crop for harvesting, threshing, and hauling rice from the field.

Other research in Laguna (see Table 10) shows a clear association between the yield increase and the amount of labor required for harvesting and threshing. Unfortunately, however, in our Central Luzon study, two factors have clouded the results. First, a severe drought occurred in the 1968/69 crop season, which affected yields particularly in rainfed and single-crop, irrigated farms (Table 2). Second, the use of threshers increased somewhat so labor requirements dropped where yields increased. This seems to have occurred in the double-cropped, irrigated farms in Central Luzon. But threshers are still not being used in Laguna which has experienced one of the sharpest yield increases.

Thus, although total labor per hectare for producing rice does not appear to have changed substantially, more mechanization and a shift in the seasonal pattern of labor use has occurred. In particular, the labor used for land preparation has declined and the labor for weeding on irrigated farms has increased. The impact of increased rice production on harvesting and threshing labor is difficult to assess for Central Luzon from the survey.

Table 4. Importance of family and hired labor for farms growing local or high yielding varieties (HYV). Laguna and Central Luzon, 1968 wet season.

Operation	HYV ^a		Local ^b	
	Family labor (%)	Hired labor (%)	Family labor (%)	Hired labor (%)
Land preparation	64	36	85	15
Transplanting	5	95	5	95
Weeding	59	41	86	14
Other pre-harvest	91	9	94	6
Harvesting and threshing	11	89	15	85
All tasks	39	61	46	54

^a 45 farms; average size: 2.6 ha. ^b 102 farms; average size: 2.5 ha.

Three municipalities of Laguna. Just before high-yielding varieties were introduced, Liao made a study of rice farming in three municipalities of Laguna. The study was based upon a survey in which information was obtained regarding farm production practices, costs, and returns on 155 farms for the crop year 1966/67. This survey provided an excellent benchmark. We have made subsequent surveys annually after the wet season harvest to examine the pattern of adoption of the high-yielding varieties and the changes that have occurred in farming practices, rice production, costs, and returns (1967 and 1968 Annual Reports).

In his original survey, Liao chose seven barrios or villages which were among the villages that Von Oppenfeld et al. had surveyed in 1954-55. Liao drew a random sample of 60 farms from each of three municipalities—Biñan, Cabuyao, and Calamba. The municipalities were selected principally on the basis of their differences in water resources. Calamba has a gravity system with water available the year-around. Most Cabuyao farms are irrigated by low lift pumps. In Biñan, water from the gravity system is available only for two crops in 3 years.

Eighty-eight of the 155 farms were in the 1954-55 sample of Von Oppenfeld et al. Information obtained from Biñan shows clearly how the irrigation system has deteriorated since the mid-1950's and influenced crop production (Table 5). The amount of double-cropped land fell from 95 to 64 percent and the yields appear to have declined.

2. Typical wet-season and dry-season cropping pattern for rice in three municipalities of Laguna, Philippines.

The surveys of Von Oppenfeld and Liao both show that farm size and effective crop area are greatest in Biñan and smallest in Calamba. However, the intensity of land use as indicated by resource use and adoption of improved practices tends to be greatest in Calamba.

Figure 2 shows the typical cropping pattern throughout the calendar year for each of the municipalities. As indicated above, variations in this pattern among municipalities appear to be dictated principally by the water resource situation.

Ninety percent of the farmers surveyed in 1966-67 were share tenants. In spite of the declaration of Laguna as a land reform area in 1968, the percentage of share tenants in the sample has declined only slightly. Landowner and tenant share equally the major costs and the output. The major costs include seed, fertilizer, other chemicals, transplanting, and harvester's and thresher's share. Sometimes the landlord pays the cost of transplanting while the tenant pays for land preparation and hand

Table 5. Comparison of farm size, rice yields and double cropping in three municipalities of Laguna, Philippines. 1954-55 and 1966-67.^a

Year	Farm size (ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Land double-cropped (%)	Labor input (man-days/ha)	Cash expenses ^b (₱/ha)	Adoption of improved practices ^c (%)
<i>Biñan (24 farms)</i>						
1954-55	3.2	1.98	95	57	57	13
1966-67	3.2	1.75	64	75	85	50
<i>Cabuyao (31 farms)</i>						
1954-55	2.7	1.94	16	57	41	10
1966-67	2.6	2.08	58	82	131	55
<i>Calamba (33 farms)</i>						
1954-55	1.7	2.32	98	86	80	16
1966-67	1.8	2.94	98	101	106	74

^aAdapted from S. H. Liao, *Factors Affecting Productivity and Adoption of Improved Farm Practices in Rice Farms*, unpublished M. S. Thesis, U.P. College of Agriculture, Los Baños, Philippines, 1968. ^bBased upon 1966-67 prices. ^cThe index indicates the percentage adoption of five "improved" practices: 1) use of chemical fertilizer, 2) pest and disease control, 3) land preparation by hand tractor, 4) straight row planting, and 5) chemical weed control. Each practice is given equal weight in the index.

Table 6. Percentage of area planted to high yielding, glutinous, and other local rice varieties in three municipalities of Laguna, Philippines. 1966 to 1969 wet season, and 1967 to 1969 dry season.

Type of variety	Wet season (%)				Dry season (%)		
	1966	1967	1968	1969	1967	1968	1969
<i>Biñan</i>							
High yielding	0	39.2	92.0	80.2	3.8	58.0	96.7
Glutinous	0	2.3	4.8	1.8	3.0	0.0	0.0
Other local	100	58.5	3.2	18.0	93.2	42.0	3.3
<i>Cabuyao</i>							
High yielding	1.9	63.6	69.8	68.0	18.0	57.8	42.5
Glutinous	26.6	27.7	30.2	28.0	9.5	3.1	4.5
Other local	71.5	8.7	0.0	4.0	72.5	39.1	53.0
<i>Calamba</i>							
High yielding	1.2	59.6	50.0	60.7	15.0	55.3	58.1
Glutinous	92.7	28.2	48.5	38.7	5.0	8.2	10.0
Other local	6.1	12.2	1.5	0.6	80.0	36.5	31.9

weeding. Either the landlord or the tenant pays the irrigation fees (but often the fees are unpaid) and both usually share the cost of operating a pump. The tenant in the survey area usually has the prerogative to decide which variety and inputs to use, whereas in other parts of the Philippines, the landlord frequently exercises the key management function. The landlord, however, is the principal source of credit for operating expenses. Usually the landlord advances cash or inputs to the tenant and deducts the costs at harvest with or without interest charges before the one-to-one sharing.

Diffusion of the high yielding varieties. IR8 seed became available to all rice producers in the Laguna area in the 1967 wet season.

Between 1966 and 1969, high yielding varieties were substituted for local varieties during the wet season on over 80 percent of the rice land of Biñan (Table 6). Likewise, in Cabuyao, high yielding varieties replaced local varieties, but the area of glutinous rice remained almost constant. In Calamba, the high yielding varieties were substituted principally for glutinous rice.

The dry season patterns were somewhat similar (Table 6). In Biñan IR8 almost completely replaced the local variety, Binato. In Cabuyao and Calamba the high-yielding varieties replaced Binato and Wagwag. Farmers in both areas, however, still produce a substantial amount of Intan although the area planted to this traditional variety has declined.

The two major influences on the change in

varieties planted are prices and yields. The substantial decline in area planted to glutinous rice in 1967 caused a sharp rise in the price of the glutinous rice, Malagkit. Farmers responded to the higher price by planting a larger area of Malagkit in 1968 than in 1967.

Intan remained a popular local variety in the dry season. At the input levels used by farmers, yields of Intan were about 10 percent lower than those of IR8 and the price received was at least 10 percent higher.

Contrary to what might be expected, high yielding varieties were adopted most widely in Biñan, the area with the poorest irrigation. Due to the shortage of water, the length of the growing season is critical and IR8 has a shorter growing season than local varieties like Intan or Malagkit.

In summary, the farmers of Laguna appear to have been extremely selective in their acceptance of the high yielding varieties. The low yielding or low-priced local varieties (Wagwag or Binato) have almost completely disappeared. The better yielding or higher priced local varieties (Intan and Malagkit) continue to be planted on about one-quarter of the land in the survey area.

Costs and returns. Differences in variable costs of production—hired labor, fertilizer, chemicals, and seed—between municipalities are not large although in all three municipalities they rose by about 90 percent during the 4-year period (Table 7). The rise in costs is mainly the result of larger inputs of fertilizer and chemicals, increased contracting of tractors for land preparation, added labor input for harvesting the increased production, and the rise in farm wage rates. The last seems to be more a result of inflation than of an increased demand for agricultural labor.

Gains in yield per hectare and in gross returns have differed significantly between municipalities. Biñan has had the smallest increase in both absolute and relative terms, while Cabuyao has had the largest. Gross returns in Cabuyao and Calamba were higher in 1969 not only because of a higher yield but also because of a higher price for glutinous rice.

Net returns above variable costs have followed the same pattern as gross returns. In 1966 net returns per hectare in Cabuyao were

Table 7. Returns and costs per hectare for rice farms in three municipalities of Laguna, Philippines. 1966 and 1969 wet season.

Year	Farm size (ha)	Land in HYV ^a (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Standard deviation of yield (t/ha)	Price of rough rice (₱/kg)	Gross returns (₱/ha)	Variable costs ^b (₱/ha)	Net returns ^c (₱/ha)	Net return based on 1966 prices ^d (₱/ha)
<i>Biñan (45 farms)</i>									
1966	3.3	0	1.93	0.78	0.40	772	247	525	525
1969	3.4	80	2.54	1.34	0.41	1042	477	565	509
Increase (%)			32			35	93	8	0
<i>Cabuyao (56 farms)</i>									
1966	2.5	2	2.23	0.72	0.40	892	267	625	625
1969	2.4	68	4.25	1.41	0.45	1914	557	1357	1223
Increase (%)			91			115	109	117	96
<i>Calamba (51 farms)</i>									
1966	1.8	1	2.98	0.67	0.41	1221	266	955	955
1969	1.8	61	4.02	1.92	0.45	1809	526	1283	1156
Increase (%)			35			48	98	34	21

^aHigh yielding varieties. ^bIncludes costs for seed, fertilizer, chemicals, and hired labor. ^cGross return less variable costs. ^dNet return deflated by the consumer price index of all items including rice. Jan. 1967=100, Jan. 1970=111.

only slightly better than those in Biñan. However, in 1969, wet season returns on Cabuyao farms matched those of Calamba. If net returns are deflated to take account of the rise in prices of things other than rice, the real income of the farmers surveyed in Biñan did not rise between 1966 and 1969 in spite of the widespread adoption of high yielding varieties (Table 7). The modest gains in yield were offset by rising costs. This does not imply that the Biñan farmers were wrong in adopting the high yielding varieties. Had they continued to plant traditional varieties, their real income might have declined.

Most farmers in the survey area increased their returns from rice production since 1966 (Table 7). But the varieties they chose to plant and their success in increasing their returns appear to be related to the resources of the particular location. Because the price of glutinous rice fluctuates widely (partly as a result of the introduction of high yielding varieties), the best variety for high returns has not always been obvious.

Use of fertilizer. Over 70 percent of the farmers in the area studied used fertilizer in 1966. Farmers typically applied one to three bags (45 kg/bag) of ammonium sulfate per hectare. However, in the past 2 to 3 years, urea has become readily available and is being supplied to farmers by both domestic producers and importers (complete mixed fertilizer is seldom used because lowland rice soils in Laguna usually do not show a yield response to

the application of phosphorous and potassium). More than 90 percent of the fertilizer users in the sample area applied urea in the 1969 wet season. The typical application was two to four bags per hectare. Because of the switch to urea, the price paid for nitrogen fell from about ₱1.70 to ₱1.20/kg. Farmers normally split the application. They apply two or three times, but the time of application varies widely.

The quantity of nitrogen applied per hectare has increased by two to three times on most farms (Table 8). In 1966, the Calamba barrios were applying the most fertilizer, and Biñan barrios, the least. But in 1969 the amount of fertilizer used either by location or by level of

Table 8. Fertilizer use and yield of rice by location and by adoption of high yielding varieties (HYV) in three municipalities of Laguna, Philippines. 1966 and 1969, wet season.

Category	Fertilizer users (%)		Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1966	1969	1966	1969	1966	1969
<i>Location</i>						
Biñan	80	98	8	47	1.9	2.5
Cabuyao	75	91	16	51	2.2	4.3
Calamba	84	94	22	44	2.9	4.0
<i>HYV adopters 1969</i>						
Full adopters	73	94	14	49	2.3	3.8
Partial adopters	84	96	17	46	2.5	3.5
Non-adopters	95	90	19	45	2.5	2.8
<i>Full adopters by location 1969</i>						
Biñan	72	100	8	52	2.0	2.9
Cabuyao	65	86	15	44	2.1	4.6
Calamba	83	95	21	51	2.9	4.3

adoption was not significantly different. Farmers applied an average of 45 to 50 kg/ha N. They spent about ₱50 to ₱55/ha for fertilizer and only rarely more than ₱100/ha. Table 8 also shows that on farms adopting the high yielding varieties (principally IR8 and C4-63) the lower yields experienced in Biñan are not the result of lower nitrogen application.

Use of herbicides. In 1966, about as many farmers used herbicides as used fertilizer. Liquid 2,4-D has been the most popular herbicide. Although the number of herbicide users has risen (Table 9), the level of use has not increased as dramatically as that of nitrogen. Farmers typically applied under ₱10 of herbicide per hectare. Occasionally the expense was as high as ₱20/ha. Nearly all farmers apply herbicide in liquid form after weeds emerge. In 1969, they spent less than ₱10/ha.

The widespread adoption of herbicides in this area undoubtedly reflects in part the relatively high cost of labor. Even in 1966 only 27 percent of the farms used hand weeding.

Use of insecticides. The major insect pest in this area is the yellow stem borer. In 1966, about half of the farmers used insecticides. The number of insecticide users has increased sharply since then. As a result the average insecticide expenditure per hectare has more than doubled (Table 9). The increased expenditure per hectare by those applying insecticide in 1966 has been far less dramatic, however. Farmers apply liquid insecticides

such as folidol and thiodan to protect seedbeds and to kill stem borers when they see severe infestation. Few farmers use granular insecticides. Typically farmers spend less than ₱10 per hectare for insecticides although a few spend as much as ₱50 or ₱60.

Biñan farmers applied the least insecticide in 1966, but they have shown the largest increase in insecticide use (Table 9). Conversely, Calamba farmers had the highest level of use in 1966, but they have shown the smallest increase.

Labor utilization. The only significant changes in labor utilization were for land preparation and harvesting (Table 10). The increased use of the hand tractor in harrowing explains this reduction in labor input. The increase in harvesting and threshing labor was related to the increase in yield per hectare. While yields increased by over 70 percent, labor for harvesting and threshing increased by about 50 percent.

Based on the findings from the Central Luzon survey, an increase in the use of labor for weeding might have been expected. But although more weed control was used, labor input did not increase because labor-saving chemicals and mechanical weed control were substituted for some hand weeding.

Total labor input for rice production has increased only slightly since 1966, but hired labor has increased significantly. This increase stems from the greater need for harvesting labor and some substitution of hired labor for family labor in land preparation and weeding.

Table 9. Use of herbicides and insecticides by location and by adoption of high yielding varieties in three municipalities of Laguna, Philippines. 1966 and 1969 wet season.

Category	Herbicides				Insecticides			
	Users (%)		Expenses (₱/ha)		Users (%)		Expenses (₱/ha)	
	1966	1969	1966	1969	1966	1969	1966	1969
Location								
Biñan	71	100	2	6	38	96	2	9
Cabuyao	75	96	6	9	52	84	3	10
Calamba	86	84	7	5	71	76	4	6
HYV adopters 1969								
Full adopters	74	93	4	7	53	90	3	9
Partial adopters	89	98	6	6	51	84	2	7
Non-adopters	80	85	5	9	70	65	3	8
Full adopters by location 1969								
Biñan	70	100	2	6	41	97	2	10
Cabuyao	70	97	6	9	52	93	3	9
Calamba	83	78	5	4	69	78	4	8

Table 10. Labor use for specific practices on 42 farms planting high yielding varieties in 1969. Laguna, Philippines, 1966 and 1969 wet season.

Farm operation	Labor (man-days/ha)		Hired labor (%)	
	1966	1969	1966	1969
Land preparation ^a	22	16	5	38
Transplanting	10	10		100
Weeding	14	14	35 ^b	79
Other pre-harvest	10	11		54
Harvesting and threshing	23	34	100	100
Total	79	85	46	79
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.5	4.3		

^aTractor users: 1966, 31%; 1969, 62%. ^bTransplanting, weeding, and other pre-harvest operations are combined in the 1966 records.

How the returns are shared. On the 42 farms discussed in the previous section, the gross return was divided between the landowner, the tenant, hired labor, and operating capital (Table 11 and fig. 3). The landowner receives payment for contributing land and capital in the form of credit, the tenant for contributing labor and capital equipment such as carabao, plow, and harrow. Hired workers are paid for their labor. Operating capital consists of items such as fertilizer, chemicals, and fuel.

Between 1966 and 1969, capital and labor showed the largest percentage increase (Table 11). Nevertheless the share of the gross returns going to capital and hired labor changed only slightly. It is not surprising, however, to find that the landowner received the largest share of the increase, followed by the tenant, hired labor, and operating capital in that order (fig. 3).

Change in a Central Luzon village. San Bartolome, Mayantoc, Tarlac is a village or barrio where the farmers have had considerable experience with the high yielding varieties of rice. The agricultural practices and farm economics of the barrio were surveyed in both 1965 and 1967 by the National Economic Council and the Agency for International Development. We also surveyed a random sample of 100 of the barrio's 150 farm families from February to May 1970.

The study area. From the original settlement in about 1860 by Ilocano-speaking settlers until about 1950, the barrio grew constantly, but in

Table 11. Share of output going to specified claimants based on records of 42 farms shifting from local varieties in 1966 to high yielding varieties in 1969, Laguna, Philippines. Wet season.

Output share	1966 ^a		1969 ^b		Increase from 1966 to 1969 (%)
	(P)	(%)	(P)	(%)	
Operating capital	69	7	147	9	113
Hired labor	183	18	341	20	86
Tenant	348	35	540	32	65
Landowner	393	40	648	39	55
Total	993	100	1676	100	

^aLocal varieties. ^bHigh yielding varieties.

recent years its population appears to have stabilized. San Bartolome has always been a barrio where rice was raised to the exclusion of all else except some vegetables and fruit produced for local consumption.

San Bartolome receives 2,200 mm of rainfall annually, most of it from May to November. The farmers developed a communal irrigation system in 1907 to provide water to 70 of the barrio's 345 hectares of rice land in the wet season. In 1957, the government-sponsored Camiling River Irrigation System brought reliable wet season water and alternate-year dry season water to an additional 215 hectares. No changes in water supplies have been made since 1957. For all three survey years, 82 percent of the rice land had adequate water in the wet

3. How increased returns on 43 farms in Laguna, Philippines are divided among the four claimants. 1966 vs. 1969 wet seasons.

season. With only minor changes in the farming population and with assured water supply, it appears reasonable to postulate that productivity changes over a 5-year period in San Bartolome were due in large part to the adoption of new high yielding varieties and of new rice technologies which accompanied the introduction of high yielding varieties.

Change in production and production practices. The yield of all rice varieties increased from 1.7 to 3.0 t/ha in 4 years (Table 12). The mean yield of IRRI varieties was even higher. It reached 3.4 metric tons during the 1969 wet season. The yield of non-IRRI varieties also increased greatly, from 1.7 to 2.7 t/ha. The remarkable increases of traditional varieties occurred because the technology advocated for the IRRI varieties has, in San Bartolome, been applied to all varieties to approximately the same degree, and because several of the lower yielding local varieties were totally displaced by the IRRI varieties. The low yields formerly obtained from several other local varieties have improved significantly with modest applications of nitrogen and the use of insecticides.

By the 1967 wet season, the second year IRRI varieties were planted in the barrio, 40 percent of the farmers had adopted the new rice, but they planted it on only 14 percent of the barrio's rice land. The typical adopter planted only one-third of his small farm to the "new" rice in 1967. By the 1969 wet season, 78 percent of the farmers had adopted IRRI varieties and they planted 44 percent of the barrio's rice land to them. By then, the typical adopting farmer had enough confidence to plant over half of his land to the "new" high yielding varieties.

During 1969-70, 90 to 99 farmers, on whom reliable data covering wet and dry seasons are available, used an IRRI variety for at least part

of their plantings. The mix of varieties produced a yield 30 percent higher than that achieved by the three leading non-IRRI varieties even though the farm practices and nitrogen inputs used were almost identical for all varieties.

Most farmers plant more than one variety in each cropping season. The most common combination is IR5 and Intan—IR5 for sale because of its high yield and Intan for home consumption because of its reputed eating quality. Small areas of IR20 were harvested in late 1969 and early 1970; this variety seems soon destined to replace a significant portion of the area planted to local types because it yields well, commands both a higher farm price and a higher retail price than most local varieties, and is known locally as "IRRI Wagwag," an indication that, in Tarlac at least, IR20 has been widely accepted as having excellent eating quality.

Table 13 indicates the date of first use of insecticide by farmers at San Bartolome. During the first 13 years that spray insecticide was used at San Bartolome about 45 percent of the farmers adopted the practice; the number of adopters doubled in the 4 years since the introduction of IRRI varieties in 1966.

Land values. Land values have increased remarkably at San Bartolome. Prices paid for farm land have traditionally been based on quality as reflected in the "expected yield" of the plot and on the recent history of rice prices. Half the farmers in the barrio own all the land they farm and an additional one-third own at least part of their land. Farm land transfers, except through death and inheritance, have been minimal. Several pieces have been sold, however, and most farmers have firm perceptions of the price they would be willing to pay if additional land were available. The increase in values has

Table 12. Type of rice varieties planted in San Bartolome, Tarlac, Philippines, 1965, 1967, and 1969 wet seasons.

Year	Farm size ^a (ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)			Rice area in IRRI varieties (%)	Farmers using IRRI varieties (%)	Nitrogen applied (kg/ha)
		All varieties	IRRI varieties	Other varieties			
1965	2.2	1.7	—	1.7	0	0	10
1967	2.4	2.3	2.8	2.2	14	40	22
1969	2.4	3.0	3.4	2.7	44	78	34

^aRice area.

been particularly rapid since the introduction of IRRI varieties (Table 14).

Other changes. In the 4 years since adoption of high yielding varieties began, more labor has been required for harvesting and threshing than could be conveniently managed under the traditional *bayanihan* system of labor exchange. In 1966, the first privately-operated mechanical thresher was introduced at San Bartolome with modest success. By early 1970, six large machines were operating in the barrio and all rice except seed grain and malagkit (glutinous rice) was mechanically threshed. During 1969, the barrio council paid for a new cement-surfaced plaza from a tax of 4.5 centavos per 100 kg of rice paid by thresher operators. Plans called for major school improvements to be completed with the 1970 tax money. During 1969 and the first half of 1970, 30 percent of all homes in the barrio were completely rebuilt with sawn lumber and cement blocks in place of rough lumber and bamboo. The average cost per home for this new construction was ₱11,000.

San Bartolome is not an "average" barrio. It has received more than a normal share of extension effort, it has an energetic and devoted farm technician, it has a reliable irrigation system, and it has a very high proportion of owner-operators. Despite these advantages, the productivity gains and the economic change over recent years have been impressive.

Resource use on Bicol rice farms. Last year's annual report presented the preliminary results of a study conducted in the Bicol region of the Philippines. This year, the level and efficiency of resource use on these farms are reported in more detail.

Four types of farms are considered: lowland rice farms, lowland rice farms growing rice in rotation with other crops (lowland rice in rotation), lowland rice farms growing other crops on land not normally planted to rice (lowland rice diversified), and upland rice farms growing rice and other crops (upland rice and other crops). The distinction between the second and the third type of farm is important. The farm that grows lowland rice in rotation follows the normal concept of multiple cropping. One or, more frequently, two rice crops are

Table 13. Date of first use of any insecticide by farmers in San Bartolome, Tarlac, Philippines.

Year	New users (no.)	Cumulative total
1952	1	1
1955	2	3
1957	24	27 ^a
1959	2	29
1960	9	38
1961	0	38
1962	0	38
1963	2	40
1964	0	40
1965	6	46
1966	15	61 ^b
1967	16	77
1968	7	84
1969	5	89
Non-users		9
Inadequate data		3
Total		101

^aOpening of the Camiling River Irrigation system. ^bIntroduction of high yielding varieties.

being grown in combination with one or two vegetable crops. Cabbage and tomatoes are two of the most successful vegetable crops in this area. Those farms identified as diversified are growing crops other than rice because a part of their farm is not suited to rice production.

Although the lowland rice farms in rotation are smaller than the other farm types on the average, these farms were able to obtain higher farm incomes primarily by using land more intensively. Both capital and labor inputs per hectare were significantly higher on farms growing lowland rice in rotation (Table 15). The yield per hectare of rice was also higher which explains some of the income advantage and suggests that the farmers are better managers.

Table 14. Land values in San Bartolome, Tarlac, Philippines.

Year	Mean price of land (₱/ha).	Price per ton of expected yield (₱)
1936—40	600	700
1950—56	2000	1150
1957—59 ^a	3200	1850
1967—69 ^b	7500	2300

^aCamiling River Irrigation system completed. ^bIRRI varieties introduced.

A Cobb-Douglas function was fitted for each farm type:

$$Y = a X_1^{b_1} X_2^{b_2} X_3^{b_3} X_4^{b_4}$$

where

- Y = gross receipts in pesos per farm
 X_1 = size measured by effective crop area in hectares per farm
 X_2 = labor in man-days per farm
 X_3 = capital operating expenses in pesos per farm
 X_4 = machinery, tools, and equipment inventory in pesos per farm

For two types of farm (lowland rice and lowland rice in rotation), functions were also fit according to farm size. Farms with 1 hectare or less were classified as small farms, while those with more than 1 hectare were classified as large farms.

The marginal productivity of capital (Table 16) is greatest on lowland rice farms and lowland rice farms diversified, suggesting that more operating capital could profitably be used on these farms.

The marginal productivity of labor is greatest on the rice farms growing other crops in rotation. These farms are already using more labor per hectare than other types of farms. The return for the addition of labor is close to the factor cost (₱2.09 vs. ₱2.26/day). Thus labor utilization and total productivity of labor apparently could be increased through multiple cropping. But this opportunity may be limited. The farmers who grow vegetables like cabbage and tomatoes appear to be the better farm managers in the area. Also, the total market for vegetables is not large.

Changes in rice technology in Java. The Indonesian government is attempting to increase domestic rice production by encouraging farmers to use high yielding varieties and modern inputs. The now familiar BIMAS (*Bimbingan Massal* which stands for *mass guidance*), a program designed to provide modern inputs and credit to rice growers, was expanded to cover more than 1 million hectares in 1969. A large amount of inputs were moved rapidly into the hands of farmers. The government was able to collect only a small portion of the total cost from farmers, however, and no procedures were established by which to evaluate the success of the program in raising production. It soon became apparent that the program offered only a temporary solution or perhaps an initial "pump priming." A more permanent long-run solution must be found to insure the steady flow of new technology, cash inputs, and credit to the farmer.

A study in 1969 examined the potential of the new rice technology in two districts—one in Central Java and one in East Java. The BIMAS Gotong Rojong was in operation throughout much of Java at the time the study was started. However, the districts investigated purposely were chosen from those *not* under the BIMAS program.

Study area. The two districts chosen for investigation in this study were Porong in East Java and Prembun in Central Java. The districts were drawn randomly among those in the two provinces that were not under the BIMAS program that were served by technical

Table 15. Annual return to variable costs and level of resources use on four farm types. Albay, Bicol, Philippines, 1968/69.

Type of farm	Farm size (ha)	Crop area ^a (ha)	Grain yield ^b (t)	Operating capital ^c (₱)	Labor (man-days)	Net return ^d (₱)
<i>Per farm</i>						
Lowland rice	1.4	2.7	5.0	101	276	916
Lowland rice in rotation	1.2	2.3	4.1	161	314	1264
Lowland rice diversified	1.6	2.5	4.6	144	286	1079
Upland rice and other crops	2.3	2.8	0.7	21	142	254
<i>Per hectare</i>						
Lowland rice			2.2	73	200	662
Lowland rice in rotation			2.5	135	263	1060
Lowland rice diversified			2.2	93	185	698
Upland rice and other crops			0.8	9	63	112

^aTotal area cropped during the year. ^bPer hectare yields are the average for one crop. ^cIncludes all variable costs except wages for hired labor and value of shares for harvesting and threshing services. ^dReturn above variable costs which include expenses for fertilizers, insecticides, wages of hired labor, and value of shares for harvesting and threshing.

Table 16. Marginal returns, factor costs, and marginal returns to factor costs by types of rice-growing farms. Albay, Bicol, Philippines, 1968-1969.

Type of farm	Units of inputs ^a		Marginal returns (P)		Factor costs (P) ^b		MR/MC	
	Labor (days)	Capital (P)	Labor	Capital	Labor	Capital	Labor	Capital
All lowland rice two crops ^c	209	69	<i>g</i>	4.07	<i>g</i>	1.12	<i>g</i>	3.63
Lowland rice and other crops in rotation ^d	278	111	2.09	<i>g</i>	2.26	<i>g</i>	0.89	<i>g</i>
Lowland rice and other crops diversified ^e	191	58	<i>g</i>	7.78	<i>g</i>	1.12	<i>g</i>	7.07
Upland rice and other crops ^f	74	9	1.28	<i>g</i>	2.50	<i>g</i>	0.51	<i>g</i>

^aLabor and capital inputs per hectare measured at geometric mean. ^bBased on average wage rate prevailing for labor and 12% interest rate. ^c46 farms, 2.7 ha effective crop area. ^d32 farms, 2.3 ha effective crop area. ^e24 farms, 2.5 ha effective crop area. ^f23 farms, 2.8 ha effective crop area. ^gCoefficients are not significant in the estimating equation.

irrigation (irrigation involving water storage and permanent distribution channels), and that were situated in an area of regosol soil type.

Three villages were selected randomly in each of the districts, and in turn a total of 60 farms were drawn randomly from the three villages.

Income from rice production. Rice was grown on all farms in both areas during the wet season. In Prembun, most of the sample farmers grew rice during the dry season although not much water was available. In Porong, only half of the sample farmers grew rice during the dry season. Instead, many farmers planted soybeans, vegetables, and fruit crops such as melons which could be sold in a nearby city. In both areas, approximately half the farms received income from non-farm employment of family labor.

The yields and income per hectare in Porong were quite different from those in Prembun (Table 17). Even though both districts are

served by technical irrigation, the soil-water conditions are unfavorable for rice in Prembun. Farmers built high dikes around the paddy fields to conserve water which percolates through the soil fairly rapidly. The high dikes keep the water deep in the paddy fields during the middle of the wet season so the area is not well suited for the new short-strawed varieties. In 1968, 11 of the 60 farmers surveyed in Prembun planted the new varieties, but by 1969 only four did. In contrast, among the 60 farmers in Porong, the number planting high yielding varieties had increased from two to 19 during the same period.

Differences in environmental conditions influenced not only the choice of varieties but also fertilizer use. The principal fertilizer element used in both areas was nitrogen supplied in the form of urea. Prembun farmers applied 68 kg/ha N while Porong farmers applied 93 kg/ha.

Farm size. Farms in both areas were very small. The average size was close to the average 0.4 hectare for all rice farms in Java. It is import-

Table 17. Yield and return above variable costs in rice farms. Porong, East Java, and Prembun, Central Java, 1968 wet season.

Items	Porong			Pembun		
	Per farm	Per hectare	Percent of total cost	Per farm	Per hectare	Percent of total cost
Yield ^a	2.2	3.1	—	1.0	1.7	—
Gross income ^b (Rp)	39600	55800	—	18000	30600	—
Costs (Rp)						
Seeds	750	1610	6.4	620	980	5.4
Fertilizer	1660	2860	11.3	1160	2240	12.3
Insecticides	140	230	0.9	30	110	0.6
Interest ^c	460	850	3.4	330	600	3.3
Hired labor	10310	19670	78.0	11860	14280	78.4
Total	13320	25220	100.0	14000	19210	100.0
Returns (Rp)	26280	30580	—	4000	12390	—

^aRough rice. ^bPrice of rough rice is Rp 18/kg. US\$1.00=Rp 378. ^c18%/season.

Table 18. Relationship of size of farm to labor, capital, and return above variable costs, Porong, East Java and Prembun, Central Java. 1968 wet season.

Size of farm ^a	Mean size (ha)	Farms (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Capital inputs (Rp/ha)				Hired labor (man-days)	Return ^b above variable costs	
				Seeds	Ferti-lizer	Insect pests	Total		Rp/farm	Rp/ha
<i>Porong</i>										
Small	0.20	35	2.9	1810	2550	140	4500	210	8364	41820
Medium	0.45	16	3.2	1430	3580	350	5360	140	23580	52400
Large	1.16	9	3.5	1120	2430	160	3720	120	65076	56100
<i>Prembun</i>										
Small	0.17	25	1.4	1000	2580	200	3780	100	2368	13930
Medium	0.49	21	1.6	990	2290	80	3360	132	9369	19120
Large	1.37	14	1.4	960	1540	10	2510	170	15974	11660

^aSmall: <0.35 ha; Medium: 0.35-0.70 ha; Large: >0.70 ha. ^bPrice of rough rice is Rp 18/kg. US\$1.00=Rp 378.

ant to establish whether farm size itself has an impact on input use and on farm income per hectare. That is, does the smaller farm have a relative disadvantage for obtaining modern inputs and increasing yield per hectare?

Farms were grouped into three categories—small (less than 0.35 ha), medium (0.35 to 0.70 ha), and large (more than 0.70 ha). For Porong (Table 18), the returns above variable costs per hectare of the small farms are significantly different from those of the medium and large farms ($t = 2.45$ and 2.79 , respectively). The difference appears to be due to differences in expenses for hired labor and in yields. Small farms do not seem to be at a disadvantage in procuring cash inputs other than labor, however. In fact, for all categories except insecticides, small farms had larger inputs per hectare than large farms.

For Prembun, the returns above variable costs per hectare for small farms are significantly different from those for medium farms ($t = 2.15$) apparently because of yields which are also significantly different. Here again, however, small farms seem to have no disadvantage in

procuring inputs. For all cash inputs, use per hectare is higher on small farms than on medium or large ones.

Yield expectations for the high yielding varieties. Farmers were asked to estimate the most likely, best possible, and worst possible yields for the 1969 wet season. The yield expectations for high yielding varieties (IR5 and IR8) and local varieties were significantly different only in Porong (Table 19). In Porong, under the worst expected outcome, the yields for high yielding and local varieties are not significantly different. But under the most likely and best conditions the yield expectations for the high yielding varieties are significantly larger. In Prembun, on the other hand, the expected yields were not significantly different regardless of the anticipated outcome. Farmers in this district apparently see little, if any, potential for the high yielding varieties.

Economic analysis of rice experiments

The analysis in this section is based on the results of experiments conducted at the IRRI experimental farm and a farmer's field in the neighboring town of Calauan.

Yield, nitrogen input, and solar energy. The response of rice to nitrogen differs considerably between the wet and the dry season. "Wet season" and "dry season" are useful descriptive terms. But differences in yield response can be defined or explained more precisely in terms of specific factors such as weather or disease and

Table 19. Yields expected by farmers for local and high yielding varieties. Porong, East Java. 1969 wet season.

Category of expectation	Yield expectation (t/ha) ^a	
	Local varieties	High yielding varieties
Worst	2.8	2.8 ^{ns}
Most likely	3.5	5.3 ^{**}
Best	4.4	6.6 ^{**}
Range	1.6	3.8 ^{**}

^aYields were computed at the arithmetic mean. ^{**}Difference between local and high yielding significant at 1% level. ^{ns}Difference between local and high yielding not significant.

insect damage which may be highly variable from one wet or dry season to another or within a given season.

One of the principal weather variables is solar energy. The level of solar energy varies both within and between years. The seasonal fluctuation is frequently more pronounced and depends on variation in day length as well as cloud cover. The variation in the level of solar energy affects the nitrogen response and hence the optimum economic level of fertilizer input.

We attempted:

—To determine the relationship between rice yield and nitrogen input at different levels of solar energy. The relationship between yield response and level of solar energy is not well understood, and the way solar energy affects nitrogen response has, to our knowledge, not been quantified.

—To establish the probability that a specified level of solar energy for 45 days before harvest will occur. The 45 days before harvest is the most critical period in terms of availability of solar energy for grain production.

—To determine the optimum level of fertilizer input to maximize the expected net return at a given harvest date. This optimum will vary according to the level of solar energy and the nitrogen response.

Data on the nitrogen response of IR8 from the monthly planting experiments of the agronomy department were used. IR8 was chosen because its yield variability is not affected by lodging. Only data from the last 2 years' harvests (May 1968 to April 1970) were used because data for this period do not include spacing as variable and because more effective rat and insect controls were present during this period than in earlier years.

The cultural practices and sequence of farm operations were relatively uniform during the 2-year period. The principal changes that occurred were in insecticides used, from diazinon to Dolmix, and in herbicide used, from MCPA to Eptam/MCPA to 2,4-D. These changes could have somewhat affected the yield at zero fertilizer and the slope of the response to fertilizer. In addition, the highly variable level of insect and disease incidence could have

4. Yield response of IR8 to nitrogen at various levels of solar radiation taken as total of the 45-day period before harvest. IRRI, 1968 and 1969.

significantly affected the nitrogen response on these "controlled" plots.

Solar energy and nitrogen response. For each monthly planting experiment, the daily readings of solar radiation for the 45-day period before the date of harvest were summed. The nitrogen response functions for each solar radiation total (fig. 4) were then separated into four groups according to the solar radiation level and the slope of the functions. Functions that appeared to have the same slope were assigned to the same group, each of which represents a solar radiation range (in $\text{kcal cm}^{-2} 45 \text{ days}^{-1}$). The statistical test of the homogeneity of slopes or regression coefficients showed non-significance with all groups except the one for 16.0 to 18.9 $\text{kcal cm}^{-2} 45 \text{ days}^{-1}$.

The pooled regressions for each group (fig. 5) clearly demonstrate how nitrogen response is influenced by solar energy level. At the same time, the comparatively low R^2 values indicate that factors other than solar energy account for

much of the variance in yield response, which unfortunately cannot be identified.

Other weather variables such as temperature and humidity also are highly correlated with solar energy at Los Baños. At the temperature ranges found in Los Baños, temperature variation is not considered by the agronomists to be a significant factor explaining variation in nitrogen response. Temperature and humidity, however, can indirectly affect both the level and slope of the functions by their influence on insect populations and hence on the amount of disease and insect damage. Since the effect of these other variables on yield response could not be identified, our results should be used with caution.

A sidelight of this study is that as solar energy increases at a high level, it increases yield even without fertilizer on Maahas clay which has high natural fertility. That is, when over 22 kcal/sq cm occur in the 45 days before harvest, grain yield is positively correlated with solar energy (fig. 5). Below this level yield without fertilizer is not related to solar energy. Of course, the gain in yield above 22 kcal/cm may be in part related to factors other than solar energy, such as less disease incidence.

Variability in solar energy. Figure 5 suggests that the profitability of fertilizer application varies with the level of solar energy. The level

5. Yield response of IR8 to nitrogen at different levels of solar radiation totals for the 45-day period before harvest. IIRRI, 1968-1969.

of solar energy in turn varies widely within a year, and, to a lesser extent, from year to year.

On the average, solar radiation for the 45 days before harvest in Los Baños (fig. 6) follows a typical pattern throughout a year. Starting with a low value of about 14 kcal/sq cm in January, it rapidly increases until it reaches a peak in the middle of May. It abruptly decreases until about the last week of June. Then, it gradually drops until November after which it falls steeply until the end of the year, returning to its lowest value of about 14 kcal/sq cm.

Thus based on the solar radiation totals for 45-day periods before harvest high yields can be expected with crops harvested in April, May, and possibly in March and June. On the other hand, for crops harvested in November through February, low yield can be expected.

But the variation in years that deviate from the average, can be enough to give good prospects for yields and profits even for crops harvested in November and December. Conversely, the solar radiation value during these months can be so low in some years that the profitability of fertilizer application is greatly reduced.

Solar radiation obviously varies with location. For example, in 1967, the solar radiation at Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center in Muñoz, Nueva Ecija ($15^{\circ} 42'N$) was higher than that in Los Baños ($14^{\circ} 10'N$) during January, February, March, and April.

Although some months have better prospects for high yields and profits than others, the solar radiation on a given harvest date is also subject to yearly variability as indicated by the standard deviation of the 11-year data in figure 6.

The variation in standard deviation appears to be related in part to daylength, with the highest standard deviations occurring in December. Standard deviations of from 2 to 3 kcal cm^{-2} 45 day $^{-1}$ occur from November through May, while standard deviations range from 1 to 2 kcal cm^{-2} 45 day $^{-1}$ the rest of the year.

To determine, for a given harvest date (and hence a given variability in solar energy from year to year), the optimum level of fertilizer to apply, a computer program was used to determine the probability of occurrence of each level of solar radiation. Then the results were used to compute the fertilizer levels for each

6. Yearly variability of 45-day solar radiation totals in weekly time points throughout the year at Los Baños, Laguna and sequence of 45-day periods for which total solar radiation associated with various probability levels was computed.

planting and harvest date which would give the highest expected return to fertilizer.

The computer program was designed to compute amounts of solar radiation (in 45-day totals) associated with various probability levels for 26 time periods throughout the year (fig. 6). From the start of one period to the start of the next is an interval of 14 days. A 45-day period corresponds to the 45-day period preceding a supposed harvest date which, in turn, corresponds to a given date of planting. The date of the end of each period was marked off as a harvest date.

The probability of occurrence of each of the four solar radiation ranges and, hence, of the four production functions (fig. 5) were determined for each time period from the computer program. A routine procedure was followed to get the level of fertilizer input that would give the highest expected monetary value.

Optimum nitrogen level under risk situation.

The optimization strategies based on expected net returns were laid down in 26 payoff tables or matrices equivalent to the 26 harvest dates. Table 20 shows a payoff matrix made for a February 15 harvest. A state of nature is associated with a given production function (fig. 5). For example, solar radiation of 22 kcal/sq cm or more corresponds to function A. Thus, the probability of getting production function A when harvest is made on February 15 is 0.01; the probability of getting function B, 0.14; and so on (Table 20).

Actions refer to the different levels of nitrogen applied. Payoff or returns to fertilizer at each action, a_i , was computed for each state of nature θ_j , or production function. The probability of getting a production function at a given action also means the probability of getting a payoff at that production function. To get the expected

monetary value for each action, the payoff for each action was multiplied by the corresponding probability and the products summed. For example, the expected monetary value of action a_2 is ₱168:

$$429 (0.01) + 279 (0.14) + 159 (0.48) + 132 (0.37) = 168$$

Action a_6 (apply 90 kg/ha) provides a maximum expected monetary value of ₱239. So, for a February 15 harvest, the optimum input level is 90 kg/ha N assuming that whoever applies the nitrogen has a linear utility function for money and has subjective probabilities equal to the empirical probabilities, $P(\theta_i)$.

With this procedure, the optimum nitrogen level and expected net returns to fertilizer were obtained for 24 harvest dates (Table 21). August 2 and January 31 were omitted due to an error in the computer program.

The optimum N levels and expected net returns to fertilizer follow the average trend of solar radiation throughout the year (compare Table 21 and fig. 6).

Data from IRRI have led to the observation that with sufficient water rice responds to fertilizer and gives maximum yields when the ripening period falls in May. So the expected net returns, with yearly variability in solar radiation considered, could be maximized during this month. The results also indicate the advantage gained by early wet season planting to avoid harvest in the period of low solar energy. Many farmers, of course, lack adequate irrigation facilities to take advantage of this situation.

Additional factors. If solar radiation were the only limiting factor the optimum date of planting and of harvest could easily be deter-

mined on the basis of available data. Other influences on the optimum fertilizer level and the date of planting exist; they include rainfall, typhoon, pests and diseases, and seasonal price fluctuations.

The relationship between level of solar energy and yield at zero fertilizer level appears to have an important effect. At high levels of solar energy (and low humidity and high temperature) a yield gain occurs that is not associated with fertilizer input. This situation needs further study.

We assumed prices to be constant throughout the year in this analysis. Allowing for seasonal variation would provide a more realistic picture since most rice is sold shortly after it is harvested. Farmers who are able to avoid the main harvest season (November to January) will avoid both low prices and low levels of solar energy.

Yield of rice in relation to water input. During the past 2 years, research has been conducted to test the hypothesis that under a given climatic and soil condition, rice varieties respond differently as the level of water is varied below soil saturation. That is, Variety A produces the highest yield when water supplies are ample. Variety B, however, is less sensitive to drought conditions and produces a higher yield than A when water supplies are inadequate. Hence, the best choice of variety may not be the same in environments where water is likely to be in short supply as in environments where a good water supply is assured. The 1969 results were discussed in last year's annual report. The experiment was conducted in a section of the

Table 20. Payoff table for rice production (February 15 harvest) with prior probabilities of solar radiation.

State of nature θ_j	Net returns to fertilizer ^a (₱)									Prior probabilities $P(\theta_j)$
	Actions: Nitrogen applied (kg/ha (a_j))									
Solar radiation total of 45-day period before harvest (kcal/sq cm)	a_1 20	a_2 40	a_3 60	a_4 70	a_5 80	a_6 90	a_7 100	a_8 110	a_9 120	
θ_1 22.0 and above	207	429	517	546	619	658	687	708	721	0.01
θ_2 19.0 to 21.9	154	279	376	414	445	469	485	495	497	0.14
θ_3 16.0 to 18.9	89	159	209	227	240	248	252	250	244	0.48
θ_4 <16.0	81	132	152	152	144	128	105	74	36	0.37
Expected value	96	168	215	229	237	239	234	224	206	1.00

^aBased on yield due to fertilizer. Output is reduced by one-sixth to allow for the normal harvester's share. Assumed prices: paddy—₱0.40/kg; nitrogen—₱1.77/kg.

Table 21. Optimum nitrogen levels for IR8 and the corresponding expected net returns to fertilizer based on solar radiation probabilities at various harvest dates, IIRRI.

Harvest date	Optimum N (kg/ha)	Expected net returns to fertilizer (₱/ha)
Feb. 15	90	239
Mar. 1	90	385
Mar. 15	120	478
Mar. 29	120	598
Apr. 12	130	673
Apr. 26	130	703
May 10	130	717
May 24	130	706
June 7	130	665
June 21	130	600
July 5	120	490
July 19	120	466
Aug. 16	100	327
Aug. 30	100	305
Sept. 13	100	293
Sept. 27	100	291
Oct. 11	100	289
Oct. 25	100	298
Nov. 8	100	298
Nov. 22	90	254
Dec. 6	80	215
Dec. 20	70	177
Jan. 3	70	167
Jan. 17	70	166

IIRRI farm that is somewhat isolated from other plots and is comparatively high in elevation. The site was chosen to minimize the effect of underground water movement.

Rice was grown under puddled and under upland conditions. For puddled rice, eight water application treatments ranged from 4.5 to 8.0 mm depth per day at 0.5 mm intervals. For upland rice, four treatments ranged from 4.5 to 7.5 mm depth per day at 1-mm intervals. Six varieties were planted at random positions within each of the plots. The treatments were not replicated.

Each plot was bounded by a strip of galvanized iron sheet 45 cm in height buried to a depth of 30 cm to control seepage. Soil moisture content was estimated for each treatment at regular intervals by the gravimetric technique (oven-dry basis). Soil samples within the 10-cm to 20-cm profile were taken the day before every irrigation schedule. Water was applied every 7 days. The application levels were adjusted for rainfall during the 7-day period prior to irrigation.

Seedlings were transplanted at 25 x 25 cm

spacing on Feb. 2, 1970 and 100 kg/ha N was applied basally. Rats, insects, and weeds were controlled by standard methods.

Although the weather in 1970 reduced the demand for water it also decreased the yield potential of the crop compared with the 1969 crop (fig. 7). The total rainfall during the cropping period was 25 mm in 1969 and 50 mm in 1970. Not only did more rain fall in 1970, it was more evenly distributed. As a result, the number of hours of sunshine and the potential evaporation was less in 1970. The total solar energy for 45 days prior to harvest was 25.0 kcal/sq cm in 1969 compared with 22.5 kcal/sq cm in 1970.

In 1970, as a result of the weather, soil moisture rarely fell below field capacity or 50 percent moisture even at the lowest level of water treatment, 4.5 mm/day (fig. 8). In 1969, however, in both the 4 mm/day and 5 mm/day treatments, soil moisture fell to as low as 40 percent. This explains the major differences in the responses in the 2 years.

7. The yield response of IR8 under lowland culture to water application intensity. IIRRI, 1969 and 1970 dry seasons ($t = 1$ for 4.5 mm/day, $t = 2$ for 5 mm/day, $t = 8$ for 8 mm/day).

8. Soil moisture content (at 6-inch depth, oven-dry basis) at different levels of water application to lowland IR8, and the 5-day average rainfall pattern throughout crop's growth. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Grain yields were not reduced if the total water reaching the field equalled or exceeded 864 mm per crop (6.0 mm/day). Below this level total grain yield and grain yield per day declined rapidly (Table 22). Decline in water use efficiency or grain yield per mm of water was far less pronounced.

Table 22. Effect of different water application treatments on the yield of IR8 (planted as 11-day-old seedlings and harvested 114 days after transplanting). IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Water treatment ^a (mm/day)	Water (mm)				Grain yield		
	For land preparation ^b	Potential for crop ^c	Applied to crop ^d	Total reaching the field	Total (t/ha)	Per day (kg/ha)	Per mm water (kg/ha)
8.0	134	898	870	1004	5.8	51	5.8
7.5	171	898	818	989	5.7	50	5.7
7.0	188	898	765	953	5.9	52	6.2
6.5	151	898	713	864	6.0	53	7.0
6.0	170	898	660	830	5.0	44	6.0
5.5	138	898	608	746	5.2	45	6.9
5.0	190	898	555	745	4.7	41	6.3
4.5	122	898	503	625	3.8	33	6.0

^aIrrigation treatments were made every 7 days. Thirty millimeters of water was provided for all the treated plots at 3 days after transplanting and the regular treatments were made from 8 up to 106 days after transplanting. ^bFor soaking and puddling of fields prior to treatments. ^cMaximum water that could be lost through field evaporation due to solar energy (excluding the effects of other weather elements) within the same period that the crop was being provided with experimental water. ^dTotal water reaching the crop after transplanting (including rain water)

Varietal difference in yield response for lowland rice. IR22, IR579-48-1, and IR8 gave the highest yields at nearly all levels of water input. C4-63G lodged at higher levels of water input (usually 10 days before harvest). M1-48 and IR478-68-2 also lodged (10 days and 15 days before harvest respectively).

IR22, the IR579 line, and IR8 responded similarly to water input (fig. 9). IR22 and the IR579 line matured 2 weeks earlier than IR8 which seemed to be an advantage.

M1-48 and the IR478 line, however, produced low yields and showed little response to water level. This can be explained, in part, by the lodging of these varieties with adequate levels of water input.

Varietal differences in yield response for upland rice. In the upland plots there was a rather dramatic difference between the yield response of M1-48 and the other varieties. The yields of M1-48 remained higher than 2 t/ha at the lowest level of water treatment, 4.5 mm, while the yields of all other varieties were close to zero (fig. 10). Figure 11 indicates that soil moisture for IR8 under upland conditions in 1970 was well below field capacity or 50 percent for nearly all levels of water input.

Implications. Yield response to water treatments does differ by variety. The early maturing varieties give the best results under puddled conditions. The experimental plots dried out gradually as the season progressed, hence the 2- to 3-week shorter maturity of a variety such as IR22 appears important for high yields. No

varieties, however, performed better than others under high levels of water input and worse than others under low levels as originally hypothesized. IR22, for example, performed better than other varieties at both high and low levels of water input.

The results for upland varieties come closer to conforming with our initial hypothesis. M1-48 gave substantially higher yields than the other varieties at low levels of water input. Not surprisingly, however, when water input was increased beyond 7.5 mm/day, varieties such as IR8 and IR22 yielded more than M1-48, a so-called upland variety. This confirms results of IRRI agronomists who have compared yields of different varieties of rice under upland conditions during the wet season.

Our findings suggest the possibility of identifying "drought resistant" varieties at least for upland conditions. The results, however, do not explain why yields decline when water is reduced or why one variety behaves differently than another. For example, is the yield decline due to plant moisture stress itself, iron deficiency, loss of fertilizer efficiency, or other factors? Answers to these questions may in the future benefit many Asian farmers.

Profitability of insecticide use. During the 1970 dry and wet seasons, experiments on insecticide use were continued on a farmer's field in Calauan, about 10 km from the IRRI experimental farm.

The experiment was changed from the one in 1969. The 1970 experiment included both fertilizer and insecticide treatments so that the interaction between fertilizer and insecticide could be assessed. Five levels of fertilizer and insecticide were applied in an incomplete factorial design (13 treatment combinations with every other potential combination omitted). Plots were split between varieties and the experiment was replicated three times. In the dry season IR8 and Intan were planted while in the wet season IR8 and IR20 were planted.

Lindane was applied one to four times at 2 kg/ha active ingredient at each application.

In 1970, as in 1969, infestation levels were generally very low. Estimates of damage by stem borers (sum of three counts of dead hearts and two counts of white heads) did not exceed

9. Yield response to water input of IR22, IR579-48-1, and IR8 under lowland culture. IRRI, 1970 dry season ($t = 1$ for 4.5 mm/day, $t = 2$ for 5 mm/day,, $t = 8$ for 8 mm/day).

3 percent in either season (fig. 12). Low infestations were also found in neighboring farmers' fields (Table 23).

The analysis of variance showed that the insecticide treatment was significant only for IR8. Furthermore, the interaction between fertilizer and insecticide was significant only for IR8 in the wet season.

The main attack of stem borers did not occur at the same time during the dry and the wet season (figs. 12 and 13). If the growth

10. Yield response to water input of IR8, IR22, IR579-48-1 and M1-48 under upland culture. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

11. Soil moisture content (at 6-inch depth, oven-dry basis) at different levels of water application to upland IR8, and the 5-day average rainfall pattern throughout crop's growth. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

stage of the plant at which the insect infestation is likely to be most severe could be predicted, the profitability of applying insecticides could be greatly increased. However, no available data suggest that stem borers have the same infestation patterns from year to year or from location to location.

Since there was no significant yield response to insecticide application on Intan during the dry season or on IR20 during the wet season, economic analysis was conducted only for IR8 (Tables 24 and 25). The results showed that the highest profit would be obtained with 160 kg/ha N and four applications of insecticide in the dry season and 90 kg/ha N and four

Table 23. Average dead heart and white head counts and yields in 12 locations. Calauan, Laguna, 1969 and 1970.^a

Year	Season	Dead hearts ^b (%)	White heads ^c (%)	Yield (t/ha)
1969	Dry	1.42	0.43	5.17
1970	Dry	1.85	0.55	5.12
1969	Wet	2.08	1.26	4.24
1970	Wet	1.48	1.08	4.16 ^d

^aPrincipal varieties are IR8, IR20, C4-63, and Intan. ^bSum of counts at 45, 55, and 65 days after transplanting (1969) and at 45, 59, and 73 days after transplanting (1970). ^cSum of counts at 95 and 105 days after transplanting. ^dAverage yield on 10 farms estimated by crop cutting. Yields on two farms were badly damaged by a typhoon close to harvest.

applications of insecticide in the wet season. But the benefits from application of insecticide relative to fertilizer are very low. If a farmer has only ₱100 to spend on fertilizer and insecticides, how should he allocate it between insecticides and fertilizer? The answer is clear. Both the level of profitability and the assurance of a return favor the purchase of fertilizer and no insecticide when credit is limited. In fact, the payoff for insecticide beyond one application does not appear to warrant the risk.

The general level of insect damage in this area (Table 23) and throughout Laguna is relatively low. Hence, the farmer's decision as observed in our Laguna survey (Tables 8 and 9) to spend a high portion of operating capital for fertilizer and little for insecticide seems to be justified on economic grounds.

Rice processing

Modernization in Laguna. Modernization of the processing industry does not necessarily mean installing mechanical dryers, bulk storage, and rubber-roller huskers—equipment capable of producing export quality rice—if the domestic market does not demand export quality rice. A major question facing the Asian rice industry is whether the installation of modern bulk handling equipment will significantly reduce the cost of processing or add to the benefits of processing either through reduced transportation cost, higher recovery, smaller loss, or improved quality.

In the Philippines, a few attempts were made to modernize the processing industry before the nation reached self-sufficiency in 1969. Four large silo storage units for rice and corn were constructed in the 1950's but they operated only for one or two seasons primarily because the units were poorly located, because the dryer units were not matched to the silo storage capacity, because of lack of know-how for handling bulk stored rice, and because of inadequate domestic demand for high quality rice.

A survey was made of rice processing and milling in Laguna to identify the changes taking

12. Yields of IR8 and IR20 and development of infestation of stem borers at 45, 59, 73, 95, and 105 days after transplanting (DAT) after lindane was applied at 2 kg/ha a.i. once (at 50 DAT), twice (at 50 and 80 DAT), three times (at 35, 55, and 75 DAT), and four times (at 15, 35, 55, and 75 DAT) to IR8 and IR20 (at mean of nitrogen application). Calauan, Laguna, Philippines. 1970 wet season.

13. Yields of IR8 and Intan and development of infestation of stem borers at 45, 49, 73, 95, and 109 days after transplanting (DAT) after lindane was applied at 2 kg/ha a.i. once (at 50 DAT), twice (at 50 and 80 DAT), three times (at 35, 55, and 75 DAT), and four times (at 15, 35, 55, and 75 DAT) to IR8 and Intan (at mean nitrogen application). Calauan, Laguna, Philippines. 1970 dry season.

Table 24. Returns above costs for cash inputs of fertilizer and insecticides for IR8. Calauan, Laguna, Philippines, 1970 dry season.

Insecticide applications (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cash costs ^a (P)	Net return ^b (P)
<i>0 kg/ha N</i>			
0	3.5	0	1260
1	4.0	50	1390
2	4.4	100	1484
3	4.5	150	1470
4	4.5	200	1420
<i>40 kg/ha N</i>			
0	4.5	53	1567
1	5.1	103	1733
2	5.4	153	1791
3	5.6	203	1813
4	5.6	253	1763
<i>80 kg/ha N</i>			
0	5.4	106	1838
1	6.0	156	2004
2	6.4	206	2098
3	6.5	256	2084
4	6.5	306	2034
<i>120 kg/ha N</i>			
0	6.3	160	2108
1	6.9	210	2274
2	7.3	260	2368
3	7.4	310	2354
4	7.4	360	2304
<i>160 kg/ha N</i>			
0	7.0	213	2307
1	7.8	263	2545
2	8.1	313	2603
3	8.3	363	2625
4	8.2	413	2539

^aUrea in 50-kg bags costs P1.33/kg N; insecticide costs P25/kg of active ingredient and labor for application costs P50/ha. ^bAt P16/cavan of IR8 or P0.36/kg rough rice.

Table 25. Returns above costs for cash inputs of fertilizer and insecticides for IR8. Calauan, Laguna, 1970 wet season.

Insecticide applications (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Cash costs ^a (P)	Net return ^b (P)
<i>0 kg/ha N</i>			
0	3.3	0	1188
1	3.3	50	1138
2	3.4	100	1124
3	3.6	150	1146
4	3.9	200	1204
<i>30 kg/ha N</i>			
0	4.0	40	1400
1	4.1	90	1386
2	4.2	140	1372
3	4.4	190	1394
4	4.8	240	1488
<i>60 kg/ha N</i>			
0	4.5	80	1540
1	4.5	130	1490
2	4.7	180	1512
3	5.0	230	1570
4	5.4	280	1664
<i>90 kg/ha N</i>			
0	4.5	120	1500
1	4.7	170	1522
2	4.9	220	1544
3	5.2	270	1602
4	5.7	320	1732
<i>120 kg/ha N</i>			
0	4.3	160	1388
1	4.5	210	1410
2	4.8	260	1468
3	5.1	310	1526
4	5.6	360	1656

^aUrea in 50-kg bags costs P1.33/kg N; insecticide costs P25/kg of active ingredient and labor for application costs P50/ha. ^bAt P16/cavan of IR8 or P0.36/kg rough rice.

place since 1965 (Table 26). Between 1965 and 1970, milling capacity increased by 46 percent which is more than the increase in production in the area served. But the marketed surplus increased much more rapidly than production. The 25 mills installed between 1965 and 1970 are all of the traditional *cono* type. A typical *cono* mill consists of a rough rice cleaner, one or two composition-stone hullers, a shaker separator, and one or two emery-stone polishers. Five rice-processing complexes were under construction at the time of the survey (Nov. 1970). They all were modern, employing mechanical dryers and bulk storage. Two had rubber-roller mills.

Only half of the mills in 1970 had drying facilities. However, most mills constructed after 1965 had mechanical dryers or space for

sun drying. Mechanical dryers are operated October through December.

On the average, Laguna mills operate about 265 days a year or about 2,100 hours. They typically work a 6-hour to 8-hour day in January, February, June, and July. They operate longer hours during the harvest periods, March through May and October through December. Mills operate less than normal hours in August and September.

The major source of finance for mill construction is the Development Bank of the Philippines, which since 1965 has financed construction of eight of the 25 *cono* mills and four of the five modern mills. Nine mills were financed by other banks, and nine by private capital sources, principally the owner's own capital.

Table 26. Processing, storage, and drying capacities of rice mills, Laguna, Philippines, in operation, 1965 and 1970, and under construction, 1970.

Year	All mills			Mills with drying facilities			
	No.	Total processing capacity (t/12 hr)	Total storage capacity (1000 t)	Sun drying		Mechanical	
				No.	Total capacity (t/12 hr)	No.	Total capacity (t/12 hr)
1965	63	394	22.6	23	217	2	13
1965-1970							
Addition	25	214	5.6	19	272	7	63
Subtraction	6	31	1.7	1	3	0	0
1970	82	577	26.5	41	486	9	76
1970 adjusted ^a	87	767	37.1	41	466	14	580
Increase (%)							
1965-1970	30	46	17	78	124	350	485
1965-1970 adjusted ^a	38	95	64	78	115	600	4361

^aIncluding mills under construction.

Mill operations differ greatly from one area to another within Laguna. From San Pedro to Calauan, an area about 70 km south of Manila, over 30 percent of the rice milled is transported from outside of the province, principally from Central Luzon. The major source of supply for 10 of the 36 mills in this region was outside Laguna. Rough rice is hauled by truck from as far away as the Cagayan Valley (450 km north of Manila) at a cost of ₱2.50 per cavan (sack of 44 kg) and from other points in Central Luzon at ₱1.50 to ₱2.50 per cavan.

In the municipalities of Laguna beyond Calauan the mills are supplied by local production. Drying and milling equipment and storage facilities are in general not as adequate as in the area closer to Manila.

The construction of the modern milling facilities will increase the amount of rough rice hauled from distant points to Laguna. Since it is more costly to haul unmilled rice, why are milling facilities not closer to the source of supply? Millers say they pay a lower price for rough rice at the major supply points than in Laguna and this more than offsets the transportation cost. This apparent imperfection in the market needs further investigation.

The major factor limiting the use of facilities in Laguna is supply. Expansion of facilities has more than kept up with the local increase in production and many millers are working

fewer days than they did 5 years ago. Twenty-four mills were milling approximately 40 percent less rice than in 1965 while 15 mills were milling 15 percent more rice. There was a shortage of drying facilities in parts of Laguna. Some millers indicated difficulty in financing new drying facilities as well as other costs and carrying charges for mill operation.

It remains to be seen how effectively the five modern mills, which were not yet in operation at the time of the survey, can compete. Part of their success will undoubtedly be related to the ability to establish markets, either domestically or abroad, for quality rice.

Rice quality and retail prices. In November 1969, we obtained samples of milled rice from eight retail outlets in major cities and towns in Central Luzon. We recorded the price of each sample and classified the samples by variety and by the degree of milling (Table 27).

In general, the "higher quality" varieties received a "first class" treatment at the mill. That is, these varieties were more highly polished in the milling process. Thus at the retail level, quality reflects not only the quality of the variety, but also the quality of milling. Poor quality varieties, such as IR8 and IR5, normally receive second-class milling.

Of the various quality characteristics that distinguish first and second class milling, the

Table 27. Classification of rice samples by variety and degree of milling. Central Luzon, Philippines, November 1969.

Variety	Samples (no.)	
	1st class	2nd class
IR8	0	7
IR5	3	9
C4-63	13	3
BE-3	7	0
Intan	2	0

more important ones appear to be yellow and damaged rice and chalky grains (Table 28). Surprisingly, the percentage of brewers grains is significantly greater in the first class milling, while the percentage of brokens is essentially the same in the two classes.

The relationships were also analyzed using least squares regression. For first class milling

$$\hat{Y} = 91.5 + 0.245 X_1 - 1.372 X_2 - 0.367 X_3 - 2.111 X_4 + 1.783 X_5$$

(0.149) (0.645) (0.647) (0.632) (0.926)

$$R^2 = 0.59$$

while for second class milling

$$\hat{Y} = 81.4 - 0.086 X_1 + 0.387 X_2 - 0.021 X_3 - 1.080 X_4 - 0.118 X_5$$

(0.290) (1.261) (0.061) (0.983) (0.929)

$$R^2 = 0.27$$

Table 28. Grain characteristics and average wholesale price of 50 samples of first- and second-class milled rice in eight Central Luzon retail outlets. November 1969.

Degree of milling	Grain characteristic (%)						Price (₱/kg)
	Head rice	Broken grains	Brewers	Yellow and damaged	Chalky kernels	Red rice	
First class ^a	62.2	24.2	3.8*	2.9**	3.4	1.1	0.86*
Second class ^b	57.5	23.8	2.2	5.3	4.7	1.3	0.76
All samples	60.4	24.0	3.2	3.8	3.9	1.2	0.82

*Significantly different from second class milling at the 5% level. **Significantly different from second class milling at the 1% level. ^a31 samples. ^b19 samples.

where

$\hat{Y}$ = The retail price or the selling price reported at the retail outlet in centavos/kg

X_1 = Percent brokens when brokens are milled rice grains whose sizes range from three-fourth to one-half of a whole grain

X_2 = Percent brewers or binlids which are milled rice grains whose size ranges from one-half to one-fourth of a whole grain

X_3 = Percent yellows and damaged grains which are grains damaged by fermentation or heat, by water, by insects, or by mechanical means

X_4 = Percent chalky grains or milled rice kernels with 25 percent or more white portion

X_5 = Red rice or rice with any degree of redness

and values shown in parentheses are the standard errors of the coefficients.

The quality characteristics tested have a greater effect on the price of first class milled rice as can be seen by comparing the R^2 values for the two equations. Chalkiness (X_4) is the most important influence on retail price and it is also an important determinant of wholesale rice price.

This analysis tends to confirm the previous findings that the relationship between price and many quality characteristics is not well defined in the domestic Philippine market. In particular, the percentage brokens which is a critical factor in the export trade is not a significant determinant of retail rice prices in the Philippines.

Varietal Improvement

The Institute's long-range breeding program aims to incorporate into improved plant type lines such essential traits as (1) growth duration, including photoperiod sensitivity, to best fit different rice-growing areas, (2) disease and insect resistance, (3) improved grain characteristics, including higher protein content, (4) adaptability to deep water, (5) adaptability to upland culture, and (6) cold resistance.

Today lines of improved plant type are available which combine resistance to blast, bacterial leaf blight and leaf streak, and green leafhoppers, and clear or translucent grain appearance. Examples are lines from IR841 (Peta/3 x TN1) x Khao Dawk Mali which combine resistance to blast and to green leafhoppers, translucent grains, and aroma. IR759 lines [IR8 x (Peta/3 x Dawn)] combine the blast resistance of Dawn with resistance to bacterial leaf blight and leaf streak and to green leafhoppers, and translucent grains. Brown planthopper resistance is being transferred to IR22 by the backcrossing method. Crosses of IR759 lines to brown planthopper-resistant lines developed from IR22 backcrosses, will combine essential traits into single strains.

In cooperation with rice breeders from other countries, strains adapted to many environments and management practices are being developed. Cooperative work is being done on the development of high-yielding, non-lodging indica x japonica lines adapted to Korea, early maturing strains adapted to East Pakistan and other areas, photo-period-sensitive strains with deep-water genes adapted to heavy rainfall areas where seeding dates vary widely and where the rice crop must mature after the rains have diminished, and insect- and disease-resistant lines.

Growth duration

Early maturity. Rice varieties that mature in 100 days or less (seeding in seedbed to maturity) are needed in many countries. For several years an experiment in which four crops are grown per year on the same field has been used for evaluating yield and other characteristics of early maturing lines.

Several promising lines have been identified, but most must have improved resistance to insects and diseases before they can be considered for commercial production. IR747B2-6 is one of the better early lines.

Photoperiod sensitivity. Photoperiod-sensitive varieties are needed in parts of Burma, East Pakistan, India, Thailand, and other countries. In these areas, rice may be sown from late June to early August and where the crop must ripen before mid-November or after the monsoon rains have diminished. The harvest must not be delayed beyond early December because of possible water shortages. Also, since sun-drying is practiced, the crop must be harvested during sunny days.

In parts of East Pakistan and probably in other countries, IR20, a weakly photoperiod-sensitive variety, is well suited. In areas like the lower Delta of South Vietnam where the harvest must be delayed until flood water recedes and rainfall diminishes, highly photoperiod-sensitive varieties may be needed.

We are seeking both weakly and highly photoperiod-sensitive varieties. A screening program to identify the desired growth period has been started in East Pakistan and will be extended to other countries. Photoperiod-sensitive and weakly sensitive lines can be identified at Los Baños by growing the varieties in the wet and dry seasons. Some photoperiod-sensitive lines that flower in 75 days when sown in mid-December (dry season), require more than 140 days to flower when sown in May (wet season).

Highly sensitive dwarf lines have been selected from Wagwag x IR8, Wagwag/2 x IR8, Wagwag/3 x IR8, and from crosses between several highly sensitive Thailand varieties crossed with IR8 or IR262-43-8, or with both.

Disease and insect resistance

Many selections from crosses involving disease- and insect-resistant parents were evaluated. Selections of improved plant type were identified which are resistant to one, two, or three diseases and one or more insect species. These selections are being evaluated for yielding ability and grain quality. Several new crosses were made to combine resistance to all major diseases and insect pests into a few improved varieties.

Blast. The varieties Tetep and Carreon which have a broad spectrum of resistance to blast were crossed with high yielding dwarf selections. Tetep was crossed with IR400-28-4 and with IR661-1-140-3 while Carreon was crossed with IR661-1-140-3. F₃ and F₄ selections from IR400 x Tetep were grown during the year.

The plant pathologists planted the F₄ selections in the blast nursery in different months to evaluate their resistance to blast. Several lines with good plant type and a level of resistance to blast equal to that of Tetep were identified. Since IR400-28-4 is resistant to green leafhoppers, all its hybrid lines were evaluated for resistance to this pest. In addition, the appearance of the grains of several of these lines is excellent, with no white belly or white center.

At least half a dozen lines were identified which have resistance to blast and to green leafhoppers and good grain quality. They are being used as parents in new crosses to combine blast resistance with resistance to bacterial leaf blight and tungro virus. F₃ selections from IR661-1-140-3 x Tetep are resistant to blast, green leafhoppers, tungro virus, and bacterial leaf streak. In addition, they have excellent long, slender grains, and some may have intermediate amylose content. F₃ selections from IR661-1-140-3 x Carreon were also evaluated but most had poor plant type.

Tungro. F₄ and F₅ lines from IR262-43-8 x HR21 were grown during the year and evaluated for tungro resistance. HR21 is resistant to tungro but susceptible to the green leafhopper, the vector of tungro virus. On the other hand, IR262-43-8 is resistant to green leafhoppers and moderately resistant to tungro. Several

lines of this cross are resistant to tungro and the green leafhopper, and have improved plant type and excellent grains. F₄ and F₅ lines from IR305-4-2 x IR127-80-1 were also evaluated for tungro resistance and several lines which are equal in tungro resistance to IR127-80-1 were identified. All these lines are resistant to the green leafhopper, bacterial leaf blight, and bacterial leaf streak.

Shortly after IIRRI pathologists reported in 1966 that Pankhari 203 is highly resistant to tungro virus, it was crossed with IR8 which is moderately susceptible. The F₁ plants were highly sterile and little seed was produced. Consequently F₁ plants were backcrossed to IR8, to IR262-43-8 (Peta/3 x TN1), and to an F₂ plant of Peta/6 x TN1.

About 2,100 plant selections from the three combinations from the F₂ through the F₈ generation have been screened for reaction to tungro. In addition about 1,000 plants from other Pankhari 203 crosses were screened. From the large number of lines tested, only an occasional line approached the resistant reaction of the Pankhari 203 parent.

In recent seasons, Pankhari 203 was found to have a high level of resistance to the green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, which transmits tungro virus. IR8 is also resistant to the insect, as are IR262-43-8 and the line from IR564. Consequently, 380 F₈ lines from IR822, IR825, and IR564 were screened for reaction to green leafhoppers and the virus. The F₅ and F₇ generation of 87 selected lines were screened for insect and virus reaction under uniform conditions. An occasional line was susceptible to the insect. This was expected since IR8 and Pankhari 203 have different genes for resistance to the insect. IR262-43-8 and the IR564 line have the same gene for resistance as IR8.

Also in cooperation with IIRRI pathologists, 62 F₃ lines from Mudgo x Pankhari 203, were tested for resistance to the insect and virus. Mudgo is susceptible to green leafhoppers and the virus; Pankhari 203 is resistant to both (Table 1). Several lines were nearly as resistant to the virus as Pankhari 203 when combined with insect resistance. Resistance to green leafhoppers and to tungro virus were inherited independently.

Grassy stunt. Last year several varieties were reported to have a good level of field resistance to grassy stunt. But it was not known whether this field reaction was caused by resistance to the virus or by resistance to the vector. These varieties were therefore tested for resistance to the brown planthopper. Only four varieties were resistant to the vector (Table 2). The rest must have had some resistance to the virus although none were as resistant as *Oryza nivara*.

O. nivara, a wild species of *Oryza*, grows as a weed in central India. This species has many undesirable agronomic traits (Table 3). Its desirable traits, besides resistance to grassy stunt, are a high tillering ability and grain dormancy. To transfer its desirable traits into the genetic background of high yielding varieties, the resistant accession of *O. nivara* (Acc. no. 101508) was crossed with IR661-1-140-3. A backcrossing program using IR661-1-140-3 as the recurrent parent has been followed. F₁, BC₁, and BC₂ progenies were grown during the year. The F₁ plants were resistant to grassy stunt but intermediate between the two parents in most of the other traits (Table 3). They showed much heterotic vigor.

The first backcross plants showed considerable variation in the traits (Table 3). Only the plants of good plant type that were high-tillering, that had less panicle sterility and shattering than *O. nivara* were selected for the second backcross.

Table 1. Lines representing different combinations of tungro virus and green leafhopper reactions.

Material	Green leafhopper reaction ^a	Virus infection (%)
Mudgo	S	80
Pankhari 203	R	8
Mudgo x Pankhari F ₃ lines		
M-10	R	52
M-18	S	93
M-28	S	24
M-59	R	15
Taichung Native 1	S	88
Peta/6 x TN1	R	<i>b</i>
IR8	R	50
Pankhari 203	R	14
IR825-11-2 ^c	R	52
IR854-16-2 ^d	S	95
IR854-16-1 ^d	S	25
IR854-119-2 ^d	R	16

^aR=resistant, S=susceptible. ^b=Not tested but it should have the same reaction as IR8. ^c=(IR8 x Pankhari) x (Peta/6 x TN1). ^d=(IR8 x Pankhari) x (Peta/3 x TN1).

Table 2. Reaction to the brown planthopper of varieties that are resistant to grassy stunt.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Virus-infected plants (%)	Reaction to brown planthopper ^a
Nga-kywe Tawng Pyan	11142	20	S
Tjere Mas	34	35	S
Co-13	10633	16	R
T 608	10604	23	S
No. Ch. 47	10612	30	S
PB76-66D-113	10295	36	S
PB76-66D-14	10296	39	S
HP 134	10160	36	S
Bhurci	10138	37	MR
HP 129	10156	24	S
Abor 'A'	10043	36	S
Sail Paddy ? Bao Paddy	9934	27	S
Dumai	9953	32	S
J. C. 49	9108	35	S
J. C. 50	9109	33	S
T. D. 55	8286	16	S
J. C. 125	9064	44	S
UCP 13	8719	32	S
Dahanala 2014	3469	28	S
Murunga 308	3473	29	R
No.10022	249	23	R
Chianung 242 (check)	87	97	S

^aS= susceptible, R= resistant, MR=moderately resistant.

Fifteen BC₂ families were grown. Three of them did not carry the gene for grassy stunt resistance; all their plants were infected. Most plants of the BC₂ families are dwarf, high tillering, non-awned and non-shattering. Most have normal fertility and excellent, long, slender grains. Only a few have a red pericarp. In addition, several families have a good level of grain dormancy. BC₃ families have been planted.

Bacterial leaf blight. IR497-84-3 and IR498-1-88 have consistently shown resistance to bacterial leaf blight. They also are resistant to blast and to bacterial leaf streak, and have grains with clear texture. Both have low tillering ability and poor plant type however. They were crossed with several high tillering and improved plant-type selections and the F₃ selections were evaluated.

These disease-resistant selections did not combine well in several cross combinations. Nevertheless, some selections with very good plant type and disease resistance were obtained from IR497-84-3 x IR442-2-50 and IR498-1-88 x IR442-2-50. These selections are resistant to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, blast,

and green leafhoppers, and they have good grains. F₃ selections from IR127-80-1 x IR442-2-50 were also evaluated during the year. They are resistant to bacterial leaf blight and streak, green leafhoppers, and tungro, and have good grains and plant type.

Variety DZ 192, which is resistant to bacterial leaf blight in several countries, was crossed with IR661-1-140-3. Several selections resistant to bacterial leaf blight were identified in the F₃ progeny. They have good plant type and grains and are resistant to green leafhoppers. Several bacterial leaf blight resistant selections from IR8/4 x Zenith and IR8/4 x Wase Aikuku crosses supplied by the plant pathology department were evaluated for plant type and other traits. Selected lines are being used as parents in crosses.

A nursery of 127 varieties and selections from seven different crosses found resistant to bacterial leaf blight at Los Baños was sent to several countries so lines with a broad spectrum of resistance could be identified. To date, results have been received only from India. Some lines resistant at Los Baños are susceptible at Hyderabad while others are resistant at both places. In general, lines from Tadukan, BJ-1, and Sigadis were resistant at both localities but lines from Zenith and B589A4-18 were susceptible at Hyderabad.

Based on observations at several localities in the Philippines and in other countries, IR22 appears to have a broad spectrum of resistance to bacterial leaf blight. Consequently it is being used as a resistant parent in new crosses.

Bacterial leaf streak. Screening for resistance to bacterial leaf streak is done in the field during the wet season when natural infection on susceptible varieties is quite severe. Several of the improved lines used as parents in new crosses are resistant to this disease. They include IR661-1-140-3, IR127-80-1, IR497-84-3, and IR498-1-88. Many resistant lines from such crosses have been identified.

Sheath blight. Sheath blight is serious in many rice-growing countries. A good source of resistance to this disease is not known. Plant pathologists are screening the world collection

bacterial diseases. These insect-resistant lines are being used as parents.

Stem borers. Since IR747B2-6 appears to be resistant to stem borers, F₅ lines from IR579-48-1 x IR747B2-6 will be evaluated for resistance to stem borers in 1971. Similarly F₇ lines from (Luang Tawng x IR8) x EK 1263 will also be evaluated for resistance to stem borers since EK 1263 is resistant to stem borers.

Grain characteristics

Amylose content. IRRI chemists recently revised the test for determining amylose content, making it possible to distinguish more accurately between lines with high amylose and lines with intermediate amylose content. In many countries lines with intermediate amylose content (25%) are preferred to high amylose lines (30%), so it is important that high yielding lines with this trait be developed.

Aroma. A series of improved plant-type aromatic lines is being developed with dwarf aromatic lines selected from Basmati 370 crosses as parents. Promising aromatic lines are being selected from crosses between aromatic Thailand varieties and IR8 or IR262-43-8. They include both common- and waxy-endosperm lines.

A method of detecting degree of aroma was developed in the quality laboratory: Place 20 to 30 recently harvested milled rice grains in a 50-ml test tube. Add 20 ml of distilled water and cover the test tube with aluminum foil. Place the test tube in a boiling-water bath for 10 minutes (brown rice can be used, but it requires about 20 minutes to cook because of the bran layers). When the rice is cooked, remove the test tube from the water bath and cool it to room temperature. Rate the aroma of samples as strong, intermediate, slight, or no aroma. Use a strongly aromatic variety, such as Basmati 370, Leuang Hawm, or Khao Dawk Mali, as a check variety in each tray of 24 samples.

Waxy endosperm. Promising waxy lines with improved plant type have been selected from crosses involving waxy varieties from Thailand.

They include IR253 (Gam Pai/2 x TN1); IR789 (IR8 x Muey Nahng 62M); IR833 (Peta/3 x TN1) x Gam Pai; IR846 (Peta/3 x Khao Pah); IR848 (Peta/3 x TN1) x [(CP 231 x SLO-17) x Gam Pai]; and IR887 (IR8/2 x Muey Nahng 62M). The waxy lines include early midseason and late-maturing strains. Many are resistant to green leafhoppers and have aroma. Many IR789 and IR887 lines were resistant to bacterial leaf blight in Laos, where they look promising, and compare favorably with IR8 in field performance.

Protein content. Over 40 lines from crosses between IR8 and six high protein varieties described in previous annual reports were grown in replicated yield trial experiments in both the dry and wet seasons. In the wet season, 23 lines from BPI-76-1 crosses were tested, too. Basal applications of 80 kg/ha N were made in both seasons and in the dry season an additional 40 kg/ha N was topdressed at maximum tillering while in the wet season an additional 10 kg/ha was used. Table 4 shows grain yield and protein content of eight high protein lines.

A statistical analysis of the experiments showed that over 50 percent of the phenotypic variability was due to factors other than genotype. Consequently future experiments must be refined to reduce environmental variability.

Promising lines from other crosses being tested include IR480-5-9 (Nahng Mon S-4/2 x TN1) and IR160-27-3 (Nahng Mon S-4 x TN1).

Pedigree nurseries of 1,379 lines from the six high protein crosses were grown in the dry season. In the wet season 1,615 lines were grown. Three plant selections were made from each pedigree line saved. Seed from the plant selections was used for planting in the next pedigree nursery and for protein evaluation. Average protein contents by crosses and seasons are shown in Table 5.

The protein content of all lines tested from the six crosses averaged 10.3 percent compared to an average of 8.6 percent for IR8 checks. Lines with high protein content, when tested in yield trials, usually produce lower yields than IR8. It must be determined whether the higher protein content is a result of lower grain yield or whether it is controlled by specific genes.

The wide range in protein content of IR8 check rows (7.5 to 10.8% in dry season and 6.9 to 10.3% in wet season) indicates that environmental variability was high. A plant spacing of 30 x 15 cm was used. In 1971 a 20- x 20-cm spacing will be used in pedigree nurseries as well as in yield trials in an attempt to reduce environmental variability. All nitrogen fertilizer will be applied as basal applications.

Some of the more promising strains which might have high protein content are BPI-76-1, IR160-27-3, IR480-5-9, and lines from IR1006, IR1103, and IR1163. New crosses are being made which combine several unrelated sources of high protein content.

Special breeding programs

Deep-water dwarfs. As described in previous annual reports lines from Peta/3 x Leb Mue Nahng (IR442) were selected which combine dwarf and floating (deep-water) genes. Recently breeders in Thailand identified several extremely promising lines from this cross that will be useful as parents.

New crosses to breed disease and insect resistance into deep-water dwarf IR442 lines are being made. Advanced generation lines of IR701 (Pingaew 56/2 x Tainan 3) should serve as parental sources to combine tough leaves and slower senescence; IR435, (CP 231 x SLO-17) x Pingaew 56, should combine tough leaves and nonpubescence. Other parental sources include deep-water varieties from East Pakistan and other countries that might possess traits superior to those of Leb Mue Nahng or IR442 lines.

In areas where rice fields occasionally flood to depths of 90 to 120 cm for short periods or where water remains as deep as 60 to 120 cm for most of the growing season, deep-water genes may be beneficial.

Deep-water dwarfs possessing photoperiod sensitivity and weak sensitivity should be developed. IR442 lines include some lines of this type but more combinations are needed.

Upland rice. Agronomists and rice breeders have been evaluating breeding lines for adaptability to upland rice culture for several years. The

Table 4. Rough rice yield and protein content of selected lines from replicated yield trials. IRRI, 1970 dry and wet seasons.

Line	Dry season		Wet season	
	Grainyield (t/ha)	Protein (%)	Grainyield (t/ha)	Protein (%)
IR1100-89-2	3.91	13.0	2.63	10.2
IR1101-18-3	5.51	11.5	2.64	10.4
IR1102-27-2	2.06	12.8	1.98	11.6
IR1103-15-8	4.83	12.6	2.62	12.4
IR1103-15-9	3.48	13.6	1.84	13.4
IR1103-15-10	4.71	12.7	2.80	12.3
IR1103-66-4	4.11	12.6	2.83	12.8
IR1105-12-2	3.39	12.8	1.50	13.4
IR8	6.11	11.4	—	—
BPI-76-1	3.67	12.3	1.16	11.4

results of the 1970 trials conducted are reported in the agronomy section. Several lines were higher yielding than a leading Philippine upland variety. A set of leading upland varieties from the world collection will be used in crosses with these promising lines. World collection varieties to be used will include promising upland varieties from Africa and other countries.

Japonica x indica breeding program. The cooperative japonica x indica breeding program started in 1965 between the Republic of Korea and IRRI has led to the development of IR667-98, selected from a cross between IR8 x (Yukara x TN1). The Korean agencies cooperating with IRRI are the Office of Rural Development,

Table 5. Average protein content of brown rice (three plants per line) of six high protein crosses in the dry season (F_4) and wet season (F_5), 1970.

IRRI cross no.	Season	Lines (no.)	Brown rice protein ^a (%)	
			Range of row ^b means	Overall mean
IR1100	Dry	102	6.6 to 13.3	10.5
	Wet	61	6.8 to 12.7	9.6
IR1101	Dry	119	8.6 to 14.0	10.8
	Wet	67	6.4 to 11.6	9.6
IR1102	Dry	72	8.1 to 13.8	10.7
	Wet	46	7.5 to 11.4	9.7
IR1103	Dry	129	7.4 to 12.9	10.3
	Wet	107	7.8 to 14.4	10.6
IR1104	Dry	34	8.3 to 13.5	10.9
	Wet	12	8.8 to 12.3	10.0
IR1105	Dry	42	8.6 to 13.4	11.2
	Wet	14	8.2 to 10.1	9.1
IR8 (check)	Dry	20	7.5 to 10.8	8.8
	Wet	33	6.9 to 10.3	8.4

^a12% moisture. ^bThree plants per row.

Ministry of Agriculture, and the College of Agriculture of the Seoul National University.

The major objectives of this program are to develop high yielding, nitrogen responsive, non-lodging, blast resistant varieties adapted to Korea but with a dwarf plant type similar to IR8. IR667-98 meets these specifications. It matures slightly earlier than Jinheung, a leading japonica variety, is resistant to blast, is more resistant to sheath blight than japonica varieties, and has the short, sturdy stems of IR8, and the low amylose content of japonica varieties. IR667-98, however, has several defects including fast leaf senescence and poor grain size and shape. It has low amylose content so it cooks like japonica varieties.

Many line selections from IR667-98 have been grown in Korea and in the Philippines. Five of the most promising lines were grown in replicated fertilizer experiments at 12 locations in Korea. A leading japonica variety adapted to each area was grown as a check variety in each experiment. With 150 kg/ha N the average brown rice yield of the IR667-98 lines was 4.85 t/ha while with 200 kg/ha N they yielded 4.78 t/ha. The japonica check varieties averaged 4.11 t/ha with 150 kg/ha N and 3.86 t/ha with 200 kg/ha N.

A new series of crosses has been made to incorporate into IR667-98 other important traits such as cold resistance, earlier maturity, improved resistance to diseases, to leafhoppers and planthoppers, tougher leaves, smooth leaves and hulls, slow leaf senescence, and grains more typical of japonica varieties.

Cold resistance. A nursery of 463 selected lines from indica x japonica crosses was grown at Joydevpur station in East Pakistan for low temperature evaluation during the boro season (November 1969 seeding). The traits used for determining resistance to low temperatures were leaf yellowing and degree of stunting in vegetative growth stage. Reproductive stage symptoms, such as poor panicle exertion from sheath and panicle sterility, were not used since low temperatures do not occur during the reproductive growth stages of the boro crop.

The lines included in this nursery were selected on the basis of leaf-yellowing notes from Korea. In many instances the leaf yellowing symptoms

recorded in Korea and East Pakistan did not agree.

The degree of stunting appeared to be the most effective means of classifying breeding lines for resistance to low temperatures. Resistance to low temperatures may be controlled by a few genes. At Los Baños differences in growth duration in the dry and wet seasons appeared to be associated with the degree of stunting observed in East and West Pakistan.

Uniform nurseries made up of the more promising lines selected from the East Pakistan boro crop were sent to Afghanistan, India, Korea, Nepal, Peru, U.S.A., and West Pakistan.

In West Pakistan under low temperatures many lines showed severe stunting, incomplete panicle emergence from sheath, delayed flowering, and sterility. The temperature of irrigation water used in this experiment varied from 17 to 19 C. The only lines showing full panicle exertion from the sheath were japonica varieties and japonica x indica lines from japonica/2 x indica crosses. Many lines from indica/2 x japonica crosses failed to emerge from the sheath.

In Nepal delayed heading was more pronounced in single indica x japonica crosses and indica/2 x japonica or indica/3 x japonica crosses.

Developing and testing hybrid lines

During the year 117 new crosses were made. The total number of crosses made at the Institute in 8 years is 1,745 (Table 6).

F₂ populations. F₂ populations of many cross combinations were seeded in November 1969, and in January and July 1970. The populations were made up of single-cross combinations, three-way-cross combinations, and first-back-cross combinations. Approximately 4,000 to 5,000 plants of each single-cross F₂ population were grown, while much smaller populations of the other combinations were grown. Parents used in most of the crosses grown were dwarf lines with improved plant type. These crosses were made to combine such desirable traits as grain quality and disease and insect resistance of different lines. Tall conventional varieties from

the world collection were used as parents in a few of the new crosses. The improved plant-type selections used as parents in the new crosses included IR661-1-140-3, IR127-80-1, IR497-84-3, IR498-1-88, IR667-98, IR8 x Mudgo lines resistant to green leafhoppers and brown plant-hoppers, and IR22. The tall varieties used in the crossing program were T 141, DV 133, Carreon, DZ 192, and T 608.

Bulk hybrid populations. A limited number of bulk hybrid populations were grown. These had been grown from bulked seed of selected plants of the previous generation. Thus a modified bulk hybrid procedure is used. The bulk hybrid populations are carried to F₄ or F₅ when selections are made and grown in the pedigree nursery. Sometimes plant selections for pedigree nursery as well as bulk seed for growing the next bulk hybrid generation are harvested. In some crosses, seed from bulked hybrid populations is sent to other countries.

Pedigree nurseries. Pedigree nurseries were sown in November 1969, and January, May, and July 1970. In these four plantings, 36,416 pedigree rows were grown of which 1,820 rows consisted of parental check varieties planted every 20th row.

Most breeding lines grown in pedigree rows were dwarf and had other improved plant-type traits such as high tillering, dark-green and erect leaves, and sturdy stems. Non-dwarf plants with droopy leaves and other undesirable agronomic traits are discarded in the earlier generations. The pedigree selections are evaluated for grain quality and grain dormancy, and notes are taken on growth duration. Lines from selected crosses are evaluated for resistance to various diseases and pests.

Replicated yield trials. A total of 189 varieties and lines were grown in both the dry and wet seasons. Of this number 67 new lines were added in the dry season and 77 in the wet season. All the new lines were selected from the pedigree nursery. The management practices and plot sizes were the same as in previous years. During the dry season yields were low probably because of late infestations of brown planthoppers.

During the wet season, yields were considerably lower than usual because several typhoons caused severe lodging, particularly among the mid-season and late-maturing strains. More cloudy days occurred during the wet season than usual and this may have partly caused the yield reduction.

The data on yield, agronomic traits, disease and insect resistance, and grain quality of promising lines and check varieties grown in the dry and wet season trials are given in Table 7. IR579-48-1 is an early maturing line with long, slender grains; it has yielded well at several locations in the Philippines. It is resistant to bacterial leaf blight but susceptible to streak, tungro, and blast. IR305-3-17 is another high yielding selection. It is resistant to blast, bacterial leaf blight, and green leafhoppers. However, it has poor grain quality. IR661-140-3-58 is also a high yielding selection. It has long, slender, translucent grains and resistance to bacterial leaf streak, tungro virus, and green leafhoppers. RD-1 and RD-3 are the new dwarf varieties from Thailand with long, slender, translucent grains and resistance to green leafhoppers. IR665-40, IR1093-49-1, IR1093-104-2, IR1093-148-3, IR841-67-1, and IR881B₂-25-2 are other promising selections with satisfactory grain appearance and resistance to green leafhoppers.

Observational yield trials. Including checks, 783 lines were grown in the dry season and 1,048 lines in the wet season. Plot size, plant spacing, and fertilizer applications were the same as for the replicated trials.

In the wet season, about 30 percent of the lines grown were discarded. This is about the average number of lines discarded each season.

Table 6. Crosses made at IRRI since 1962.

Year	Total crosses (no.)	IRRI cross numbers
1962-1963	86	IR1 to IR86
1964	215	IR87 to IR301
1965	282	IR302 to IR583
1966	345	IR584 to IR928
1967	359	IR929 to IR1287
1968	171	IR1288 to IR1458
1969	170	IR1459 to IR1627
1970	117	IR1628 to IR1745

Table 7. Agronomic, disease, insect, and quality data on selected varieties and lines grown in replicated field trials. IRR1, 1970 wet and dry seasons.

Variety or selection	Parents	Grain yield (t/ha)		Maturity ^a (days)		Plant height (cm)		Panicles (no./plant)	Lodging (%)	
		Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season		Dry season	Wet season
TN1		6.71	5.05	123	111	107	107	14	36	86
Peta		3.70	2.85	132	138	151	165	13	100	100
C4-63	Peta x BPI-76	6.30	2.84	128	128	127	130	13	63	100
BPI-76-1		4.98	2.30	131	126	144	150	10	68	100
IR5	Peta x T. Rotan	7.20	2.59	131	128	130	132	14	75	100
IR8	Peta x Dee-geo-woo-gen	7.29	4.16	128	130	97	104	12	0	14
IR20	(Peta/3 x TN1) x TKM-6	6.99	3.13	121	126	110	114	14	35	100
IR22	IR8 x Tadukan	7.64	3.97	116	123	96	108	16	0	33
IR579-48-1	IR8 x Tadukan	6.80	3.76	116	112	88	97	17	10	51
IR262-43-8	Peta/3 x TN1	5.38	3.76	117	114	89	94	14	0	93
IR400-5-12	Peta/4 x TN1	5.80	4.63	117	111	89	94	14	0	48
IR127-80-1	CP-SLO x Sigadis	6.25	5.06	117	116	103	112	9	0	3
IR140-136	CP-SLO x Mas	5.65	4.37	117	111	119	123	13	46	100
IR305-3-17	Sigadis/2 x TN1	6.70	4.21	124	126	95	104	16	0	40
IR661-1-140-3	IR8 x (CP-SLO x Sigadis)	7.26	5.10	122	112	90	97	11	0	0
IR506-1-36	IR8 x (B589A4-18-1/2 x TN1)	7.50	4.82	119	120	102	110	14	77	100
RD-1	Leuang Tawng x IR8	7.80	2.46	131	131	129	127	12	54	100
RD-3	Leuang Tawng x IR8	7.29	4.23	127	131	107	101	14	0	45
IR665-40	IR8 x (Peta/5 x Belle Patna)	7.08	3.44	127	127	101	114	14	0	97
IR95-42-13	Peta/2 x TN1	6.82	5.02	117	111	88	90	16	50	100
IR1093-49-1	IR8 x Intan	9.08	4.32	136	126	100	111	14	10	87
IR1093-104-2	IR8 x Intan	7.49	4.00	133	126	91	110	15	0	93
IR1093-148-3	IR8 x Intan	7.07	3.19	124	126	102	119	13	0	100
IR874B2-87-1	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO/2 x N. Mon S-4)	6.65	4.52	123	123	95	102	14	0	0
IR878B1-15-2	IR8/2 x (CP-SLO x N. Mon S-4)	6.71	5.17	123	123	102	107	11	0	40
IR841-67-1	IR262-43-8-11 x Khao Dawk Mali	7.99	5.05	123	118	97	107	16	60	57
IR937-76-2	IR8/2 x (Dawn x TN1)	7.52	5.04	124	125	97	104	12	0	20
IR881B2-25-2	IR8/3 x Wagwag	6.88	4.59	129	131	100	105	11	0	0
IR887-53-1	IR8/2 x Muey Nahng 62M	8.23	4.73	124	120	100	109	13	0	6

	Diseases ^b			Insects ^b		Seed dormancy (%)	Brown rice protein (%)		Milled rice (%)		Gel. temp. ^d	Amylose (%)
	Tungro (%)	Blight ^c	Blast	Brown plant-hopper	Green leaf-hopper		Wet season	Dry season	Head	Total		
TN1	90	S	S	S	S	7	9.4	9.4	54	70	L	30.6
Peta	21	S	S	S	R	84	9.2	10.0	58	67	I	32.1
C4-63	58	S	S	S	R	—	9.4	10.1	55	67	H	25.1
BPI-76-1	100	MS	MR	S	S	76	10.5	12.0	44	67	I	29.6
IR5	100	MS	MS	S	R	79	8.8	10.6	46	71	I	33.6
IR8	73	S	MS	S	R	43	7.7	9.4	54	69	L	29.6
IR20	77	MR	R	S	S	65	9.0	8.9	13	66	I	29.7
IR22	96	MR	S	S	S	81	9.3	9.5	35	70	L	32.0
IR579-48-1	76	S	S	S	S	45	9.0	9.2	54	68	L	27.4
IR262-43-8	62	MS	MR	S	R	94	7.6	7.9	42	64	I/L	32.8
IR400-5-12	57	S	R	S	R	93	7.3	8.1	42	68	L	31.3
IR127-80-1	28	MR	MR	S	R	11	5.9	7.8	58	71	H	19.2
IR140-136	59	S	S	S	R	94	7.4	7.4	54	67	H/HI	19.4
IR305-3-17	65	MR	R	MS	R	17	8.6	8.7	8	66	L	32.0
IR661-1-140-3	38	MS	S	MS	R	38	6.4	7.4	52	59	L	21.6
IR506-1-36	48	MS	MS	S	R	30	9.3	8.8	45	71	L	28.8
RD-1	90	S	S	S	R	56	8.9	9.9	51	63	L	31.1
RD-3	88	S	S	S	R	43	9.6	9.3	57	68	L	31.1

continued on next page

Table 7 continued

	Diseases ^b			Insects ^b		Seed dormancy (%)	Brown rice protein (%)		Milled rice (%)		Gel. temp. ^d	Amylose (%)
	Tungro (%)	Blight ^c	Blast	Brown plant-hopper	Green leaf-hopper		Wet season	Dry season	Head	Total		
IR665-40	48	S	MS	S	R	68	8.9	9.7	50	68	I	27.6
IR95-42-13	54	S	R	S	R	76	10.3	8.2	51	73	L	27.9
IR1093-49-1	—	MR	S	S	R	71	—	8.1	21	68	L	29.9
IR1093-104-2	—	R	S	S	R	85	—	8.7	36	67	HI/I	31.3
IR1093-148-3	—	MR	S	S	R	91	—	8.4	16	70	L	32.5
IR874B2-87-1	97	MS	S	S	R	65	8.0	9.0	35	59	I	32.8
IR878B1-15-2	38	MR	S	S	R	49	8.8	9.7	59	70	L	31.1
IR841-67-1	—	S	R	S	R/S	77	—	8.2	8	69	L	22.4
IR937-76-2	—	MS	R	S	R/S	56	—	8.9	14	72	L	28.7
IR881B2-25-2	54	MS	MS	S	R	32	8.7	8.9	56	70	L	32.0
IR887-53-1	—	MS	S	S	R/S	3	—	8.8	39	71	L	30.5

^a Seeding to harvest. ^b S=susceptible, R=resistant, R/S=segregating, MS=moderately susceptible, MR=moderately resistant. ^c Bacterial leaf blight. ^d Gelatinization temperature based on alkali digestion. L=low, H=high, I=intermediate.

The lines grown were mostly from the same crosses as lines grown in the replicated trials.

IRRI-BPI cooperative yield trials. Yield evaluation and testing for disease and insect resistance is expedited by concurrent testing of selected promising selections at IRRI and at stations of the Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI). The environmental conditions at the BPI stations are quite different from those at IRRI and the performance of breeding lines under varied environmental conditions gives some idea about their adaptability. Moreover, the selections can be evaluated for resistance to diseases and insects which sometimes have a greater natural incidence at these stations than at IRRI.

During the 1970 dry and wet seasons, cooperative yield trials with breeding lines were conducted at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija and at the Rice and Corn Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur. The dry season and wet season trials consisted of 45 and 50 entries from IRRI. At Maligaya, 10 breeding lines from BPI were included. The wet season trial at Pili was destroyed by the typhoons and the data on yield were not obtained. IR661-1-140, IR790-28-2, and IR579-48-1 gave high yields at both stations and in both seasons (Table 8).

A serious outbreak of bacterial leaf blight occurred at Maligaya during the wet season. The leaves of all susceptible entries were dead

before maturity. Several entries showed a very high level of resistance to the disease and had green leaves with no or only small bacterial leaf blight lesions. These included IR22, IR790-28-2, IR579-48-1, IR878B2-62-2, and IR506-1-89.

Yield trial of PARC mutants. The Philippine Atomic Research Center (PARC) has induced several mutants of IR8 with irradiation treatment. It supplied IRRI with seed of 51 mutants for initial evaluation of agronomic traits and grain quality. Thirty-six mutants belonging to three different groups were received in 1969 and

Table 8. Yield data of some promising entries included in IRRI/BPI cooperative yield trials, 1970 dry and wet seasons.

Selection	Yield (t/ha)		
	Dry season		Wet season ^a
	Maligaya	Pili	Maligaya
IR790-28-21	7.17	8.22	4.96
IR661-1-140-3	7.94	8.56	4.51
IR665-58-2	6.06	7.76	4.68
IR665-40-1	6.59	7.86	4.48
IR878B2-73-3	6.08	6.23	3.61
IR747B2-6-3	6.02	6.11	3.59
IR579-48-1	6.14	8.83	4.91
IR773A1-36-2	6.53	6.82	4.77
IR8	6.74	7.86	3.98
IR20	5.84	7.22	4.78
IR22	6.28	7.16	4.95
Peta	2.53	2.69	2.50
RD1	6.42	6.72	3.22

^a Yield data not obtained at Pili due to typhoon damage.

15 mutants belonging to another group were received in 1970. The entries of the first three groups were grown in replicated yield trials in 1970 dry and wet seasons and those of the fourth group in the 1970 wet season only. There was very little variation within each group. Between different groups there were clear-cut differences for several traits. It appears that the entries in each group are descendants of a single M_1 plant.

All entries are similar to IR8 in most traits. The selection pressure seems to have been applied in favor of earlier maturity and grain appearance (Table 9). The yielding ability of all the entries is comparable to that of IR8. All the entries were evaluated for disease and insect resistance and were found to be similar to IR8 except in resistance to green leafhoppers. The entries belonging to PARC 1(8) and PARC A40(X) families are resistant to green leafhoppers while those belonging to L and R families are susceptible. Obviously the parental seed source used for irradiation treatment was heterogeneous for leafhopper resistance. The PARC scientists used seeds of original IR8, and it seems that the original IR8 was a mixture of resistant and susceptible genotypes. IR8 (68), the base line for source of pure seed now used at IIRRI for IR8 multiplication, is homozygous resistant, however.

The maturity differences range from a few days earlier to a few days later than IR8. In appearance, the grains of PARC 1(8) family are identical to those of IR8. Those of L and R families are rather slender while those of PARC A40 are longer and more slender than those of IR8. The white belly spot, characteristic of IR8 grains, has been reduced in L and PARC A40 families.

Seed program

Purification of new lines. Promising new lines from replicated yield trials usually need to be purified further before they are test-grown in farmers' fields and ultimately released to farmers for commercial production. To accomplish this, seed from 30 plant selections of each line are grown in four-row plots 5 m long.

If segregation within lines is found, one or more of the selections are saved for retesting in yield trials and the procedure is repeated. If most of the plots appear similar and are breeding true to type, any off-type or segregating plots are discarded and seed of the balance is bulked to form base seed for producing breeder seed. Fifty lines were purified during the wet season and 56 in the dry season. Following purification, base seed for the production of breeder seed

Table 9. Growth duration, yield, resistance to green leafhopper, and grain appearance of irradiated mutants of IR8. IIRRI, 1970 dry and wet seasons.

Selection	Days to flowering		Yield (t/ha)		Resistance to green leafhopper ^a	Grain size and shape
	Dry season	Wet season	Dry season	Wet season		
PARC 1(8)-16	93	91	7.18	4.28	R	Like IR8
PARC 1(8)-17	92	91	6.85	3.92	R	Like IR8
PARC 1(8)-19	92	92	7.15	4.33	R	Like IR8
PARC 1(8)-21	92	92	6.38	4.25	R	Like IR8
PARC 1(8)-22	92	91	6.45	4.20	R	Like IR8
L ₄ -40-1915-12	86	92	6.19	3.98	S	Medium long, slender, small white belly
L ₅ -40-1915-12	86	92	5.70	3.75	S	Medium long, small white belly
R2	73	91	5.41	4.40	S	Somewhat slender
PARC A40-(X)-1117						Long, slender, very
-10-9-6	—	98	—	4.36	R	small white belly
PARC A40-(X)1117						Long, slender, very
-17-14-6	—	103	—	2.83	R	small white belly
PARC A40-(X)1117						Long, slender, very
-17-15-6	—	97	—	4.34	R	small white belly
IR8 (check)	95	95	6.04	4.47	R	

^aR=resistant, S=susceptible.

Table 10. Background of seven IRRI lines named varieties by other countries.

IRRI selection	Parents	Country where named and being grown	Name
IR5-114-3	Tankai Rotan x Peta	India	Pankaj
IR5-278	Tankai Rotan x Peta	Malaysia	Bahagia
IR160-27-4	Nahng Mon S-4 x Taichung Native 1	Mexico	Sinaloa A68
IR160-25	Nahng Mon S-4 x Taichung Native 1	Ivory Coast	CS-2
IR253-4	Gam Pai 15/2 x Taichung Native 1	Thailand	RD-2
IR532-1-176	IR262-24-3 x TKM-6	Pakistan (east)	Chandina
IR6-156-2	Siam 29 x Dee-geo-woo-gen	Pakistan (west)	Mehran 69

will be available when a new line is considered for on-the-farm testing, thus saving time between the period when a promising new line is first yield-tested and the time it is ready for release.

Production of breeder seed and purification of IR20. Breeder seed of IR20 and IR22 was produced during the dry and wet seasons. Approximately 330 progeny-row plots of a variety were grown. Off-type plots were discarded. Only the seeds from plots with uniform maturity and "true-to-type" plant type were bulked to form breeder seed. Plant selections from uniform plots were saved for growing the subsequent breeder seed blocks. Besides IR20 and IR22, breeder seed of IR579-48-1, a promising selection, was also produced during the year.

The base line of IR20 (IR532E576) used for seed multiplication and purification in 1968 was segregating for resistance to the green leafhopper. This breeder seed was used for large-scale seed multiplication in the dry season of 1969. In 1970, individual plant selections from the breeder seed field were tested for resistance to green leafhoppers. Only 30 percent of the plant selections were resistant. Since all IR20 now grown in the Philippines as well as in other countries descended from the original breeder seed, it is a mixture of resistant and susceptible genotypes. We have selected resistant lines for breeder seed of this variety. The foundation seed produced in 1971 wet season will be resistant to green leafhoppers.

IRRI lines named in other countries. Seven varieties named and used in other countries are listed in Table 10. In some cases selection within the original IRRI line occurred while in others the original line was named as a variety.

World collection

Systematic efforts were made to acquire indigenous varieties in various national collections which were not in the Institute's world collection. About 1,530 accessions were received during the year, increasing the total number of accessions to 12,880. The major donations came from Ceylon, East Pakistan, India, Japan, Laos, Malagasy, Nepal, South Vietnam, Thailand, and U.S.A. During the year, we sent 5,660 packages of seed from the collection to foreign researchers. Other research departments of the Institute received nearly 16,000 packages for various tests and chemical analyses.

About 2,400 plots were planted during the year so that varietal characteristics could be recorded or for seed renewal. Records on 614 accessions were completed in 1970, increasing the number of recorded varieties to 10,326. A catalog describing 8,626 accessions was published and about 600 copies were distributed to agricultural research institutions and rice researchers throughout the world.

Periodic checks on the viability of seeds stored in glass jars containing silica gel showed that 6-year-old seeds of Peta and Siam 29 gave more than 95 percent germination when the initial moisture content of the seeds was 7 or 11 percent. Seeds of a japonica control variety, Chianan 8, produced variable germination percentages which averaged above 70 percent. The seeds are stored in a vault at constant temperature and humidity (3 to 4 C, 60% relative humidity).

The viability of seeds of similar age or of more recent origin that were stored in the air-conditioned seed laboratory (21 to 25 C) was much lower. Dipping these seeds in a 0.03

percent organo-mercurial solution for 2 minutes raised the germination of several varieties from 0 to 5 percent in untreated samples to 70 to 80 percent. Obviously, part of the reduction in germination had been caused by phytopathogenic factors rather than by loss in biological activity.

From the collection of wild forms and genetic markers, 91 seed packages were supplied to nine requesting agencies in eight countries.

Comparison of lowland and upland varieties

The morphology and growth characteristics of 13 upland varieties from Africa, China, Japan, and the Philippines were compared with those of 12 lowland types. The two sets of varieties were also planted in pots and subjected to water stress to determine their recovery from desiccation and to estimate damage by drought. The studies were aimed at identifying characteristics that might be useful in improving upland rices.

Rate of emergence and tillering. The upland varieties differed appreciably in rate of seed germination and of seedling emergence. Although Palawan and Td6 in the upland group had the highest rate of seedling emergence, several lowland types, such as IR747B2-6-3, IR5, Taichung Native 1, Peta, IR532-1-218, IR579-48-1, and Dular, surpassed most of the upland varieties in rate of emergence from direct seedings in upland soil.

The upland varieties generally had low tillering capacity, producing one to five tillers per plant (drilled at 100 kg/ha in rows 25 cm apart). The lowland varieties produced four to 10 tillers per plant in the same experiment, except for Dular, a drought-resistant lowland variety. The difference in rate of tiller formation was obvious 20 days after seeding: the upland varieties had one to two tillers, the lowland types had two to four tillers. This difference was consistent in upland plantings made on three dates in the wet season.

Leaf characters. Most of the upland varieties had rather long and droopy leaves. Measurement

of transmitted light at ground level 40 and 60 days after seeding also showed that the leaves of upland varieties shaded the ground more.

The leaves of a large proportion of the upland varieties rolled or folded in mid-morning under intense sunlight and when the soil was relatively dry. In the lowland group, only Peta and Dular showed leaf rolling. Peta leaves began to roll early in the morning on sunny days. The leaves of Taichung Native 1, IR747B2-6-3, and IR579-48-1 also rolled under severe water stress.

Recovery from desiccation. Early in the dry season, germinated seeds of 20 upland and 12 lowland varieties were planted in pots containing about 10 kg of granulated soil. Five plants were grown in each pot along with one or two seedlings of *Mimosa pudica* L. Water was added through a glass tube to the bottom of the pot which was lined with a layer of gravel.

The mimosa plants do not respond to mechanical stimulus when the soil reaches the physiological wilting point, thus they served as a biological indicator. The application of water to the pots was stopped in two sets of potted plants at 45 and at 65 days after seeding. When the mimosa plants failed to respond, soil samples were taken from the middle portion of the pot and dried for determination of moisture content. Recording began when the soil moisture reached 13 percent by weight. Water was withheld from the pots for another 48 hours and records were taken of the loss of green color from the leaf sheaths and leaf blades or of the death of the plants. Twelve hours after water was applied to the pots, records were taken of the degree of recovery and the extent of damage by desiccation.

Damage was considered extreme when plants or leaf tissues that had earlier lost all green color died (fig. 1). Damage was intermediate if the older leaf sheaths and blades turned yellow and only part of the younger sheath or the blade regained the normal green color, but subsequent growth was adversely affected. Damage was light if most of the leaf tissues became ashen blue but regained the green color at the end of the water-withholding treatment (fig. 1). The normal color usually returned within 12 hours after watering. Only the tips of young leaves

died after treatment. When rated in the above manner, the varieties were grouped as follows:

Light damage and quick, full recovery: IR8, IR5, Taichung Native 1, Peta, IR20, IR22, Palawan, Jappeni Tunkunoyo, IR579-48-2-1-3.

Appreciable damage, full but slow recovery: Magsanaya, Bir-me-fen, OS4, Hirayama, Td3, Td6, OS6, Azmil, RT1095, Tsai-yuan-chon, Agbede, N.A.R.B.

Significant damage and partial recovery: Azucena, 81B-25, IR747B2-6-3, a strain of *O. glaberrima* (Acc. 101438), E425, Urasan.

Death of plants: Miltex, M1-48, Rikuto Norin 21, Dinalaga, Custugulcule, PI215936, CI5094-1.

Resistance to drought in an upland field. The 13 upland varieties and 12 lowland types were planted in the field on June 11, July 2, and July 22 in cooperation with the agronomy department. Nitrogen was applied to the four-row plots at 30 kg/ha of nitrogen and the plots were seeded at 100 kg/ha in rows 25 cm apart. One row of IR8 was planted between adjacent plots to reduce competition.

Some varieties in the first planting had mild drought symptoms from August 9 to 12, when little precipitation fell. Drought-susceptible varieties, such as Taichung Native 1, IR579-48-1, and IR747B2-6-3, showed yellowing and extreme rolling of leaves. Plant growth became noticeably stunted later. More severe drought symptoms appeared in susceptible varieties from September 9 to 15. Drought-susceptible varieties, which headed during or shortly after this period, such as Taichung Native 1, IR532-1-218, IR579-48-1, IR20, Jappeni Tunkunoyo, and N.A.R.B., had 14 to 35 percent sterile panicles.

These varieties subsequently yielded from 215 to 1,400 kg/ha of grain. The extremely low yields of Taichung Native 1 (215 kg/ha) and IR579-48-1 (448 kg/ha) were partly due to damage caused by a typhoon on October 13 and by leaf blast. On the other hand, the drought-resistant upland varieties, such as Miltex, M1-48, Rikuto Norin 21, and Hirayama, which escaped damage by an earlier (September 6) typhoon, yielded from 1,955 to 2,810 kg/ha. IR5 and Peta were two late maturing entries that did not show severe drought symptoms during the dry spells, but the October 13 typhoons affected their yields.

Varieties planted on July 2 also had drought symptoms on September 22 and on September 28. Water stress symptoms again showed up among 80-day-old plants of Taichung Native 1, Jappeni Tunkunoyo, IR747B2-6-3, N.A.R.B., RT1095, IR579-48-1, Sintianne Diofor, and

1. Potted plants of four varieties, top, showed slight damage and quick recovery from desiccation. Only the lower leaves of Peta and IR5 (back row) and older leaves and some young leaves of IR8 and Taichung Native 1 (front row) died. Plants of Dinalaga, M1-48, Rikuto Norin 21 and Miltex, bottom, all died after the desiccation treatment, while the mimosa plants fully recovered.

IR532-1-218. Drought-resistant varieties, such as Agbede, Miltex, M1-48, and Peta, showed only moderate rolling of leaves. White panicles later occurred in the drought-susceptible varieties, except IR747B2-6 which was attacked by neck blast. Azmil also produced whitish sterile panicles. The proportion of white panicles to total panicle number varied from 10 to 21 percent in these varieties. The highest yielding entries in the second planting were Rikuto Norin 21, Dular, Hirayama, IR773A1-36, and IR5; their yields ranged from 1,616 to 2,280 kg/ha. All entries, except Dular and Rikuto Norin 21, suffered varying degrees of damage from typhoons between heading and harvest and, therefore, yield levels were not directly comparable.

The July 22 planting also ran into the September 8 and September 25 dry spells, but the water stress symptoms were less severe than in the two earlier plantings. Whitish panicles, ranging from 5 to 30 percent, showed up in IR747B2-6-3 (30%), IR579-48-1, IR532-1-218, Taichung Native 1, Sintianne Diofor, and Jappeni Tunkunoyo. The grain yields ranged from 205 kg/ha (IR532-1-218) to 1,144 kg/ha (Jappeni Tunkunoyo). IR8 produced 1,678 kg/ha, similar to the yields of Rikuto Norin 21, Palawan, Dular, and Miltex. IR5 obviously benefited from the frequent rains which occurred after October 27 and yielded 2,922 kg/ha, despite the November 19 typhoon which came at the flowering stage.

In terms of field resistance to drought, the 25 entries may be classified into four groups:

Resistant: IR5, Peta, Rikuto Norin 21, IR773A1-36, Hirayama, Dular, E425, RT1095, and Palawan.

Moderately resistant: Agbede, Miltex, M1-48, OS4, IR8, IR305-4-20, and Azmil.

Moderately susceptible: IR22, IR20.

Susceptible: IR579-48-1, N.A.R.B., IR532-1-218, Jappeni Tunkunoyo, Sintianne Diofor, IR747B2-6-3, and Taichung Native 1.

Field resistance to blast. Leaf blast appeared the third week in August and by early September the susceptible varieties were seriously infected. Applications of Benlate stopped the epiphytotic. Among the three plantings, the third planting

was most heavily infected. The most susceptible entries were IR22, IR579-48-1, Peta, and IR305-4-20. Susceptible lesions occurred on Taichung Native 1, IR20, IR532-1-218, and IR773A1-36. IR8, N.A.R.B., Rikuto Norin 21, Hirayama, Jappeni Tunkunoyo, and Sintianne Diofor showed intermediate lesions. Palawan, Azmil, and Miltex were moderately resistant. Dular, M1-48, and IR747B2-6-3 showed only resistant lesions. E425, Agbede, IR5, RT1095, and OS4 gave mostly resistant lesions and a few intermediate lesions. Thus most of the upland varieties probably had adequate resistance to leaf blast.

Grain-to-straw ratios. In the upland plantings, the grain-to-straw ratios were generally low. Among plots that did not suffer severe drought damage or typhoon injury, the ratios of upland varieties in the first planting varied from 0.31 (Azmil) to 0.81 (Rikuto Norin 21). The average was 0.45 for 10 varieties. Another planting made on the same date and transplanted in continuously irrigated beds produced much higher grain-to-straw ratios for all varieties concerned. The average ratio for 13 upland varieties was 0.78 and for 10 lowland types, 0.75.

In the second upland planting, only Dular and Rikuto Norin 21 escaped typhoon damage and their grain-to-straw ratios were 0.51 and 0.49, respectively. All other tropical upland varieties gave ratios below 0.21. Among the lowland types, IR773A1-36 produced the highest yield (1,834 kg/ha) and had a ratio of 0.42.

In the third upland planting, 12 upland varieties gave an average ratio of 0.41; E425 had the highest ratio, 0.63. Among the lowland entries, IR5 produced a yield of 2,922 kg/ha and a ratio of 0.23. IR8 produced 1,680 kg/ha and a ratio of 0.41.

Root development. The root systems in seedlings and in adult plants were compared under puddled and upland conditions. Roots of 2-week-old seedlings, were sampled from plantings made inside a cylindrical tube (10.2 cm in diameter) filled with soil and watered from the bottom.

Between the puddled and the upland soils, the varieties generally did not differ significantly in

length of the longest root or the number of thick primary roots. The puddled soil frequently favored an appreciably larger number of roots and thicker roots, however.

More obvious differences were observed among the varieties. Several upland varieties, such as Dinalaga, RT1006, Elliot, and Jappen Tunkunoyo, had roots as long as 15 cm, while the roots of IR20 and IR579-48-2 were from 6.1 to 7.5 cm long. Most other varieties were distributed between these extremes.

The varietal differences in the length of the longest roots under the two soil conditions were proportional, except that Peta produced much longer roots in the upland soil. IR5, IR8, Taichung Native 1, and Td-6 (upland) produced the largest number of thick secondary roots (about seven) in the upland soil, while IR20 and CI5094-1 averaged two thick roots. On the other hand, in the puddled soil, IR20 and Taichung Native 1 averaged more than eight thick roots, while most of the upland varieties had five to six roots. The thick roots of plants of the same variety generally had a larger diameter in the puddled soil than in the upland soil. The mean thickness of large roots in the puddled soil exceeded 1 mm in Agbede, Azucena, Azmil, Palawan, Dinalaga, Urasan, Hirayama, Rikuto

Norin 11, Miltex, and Yogaga, all upland types. The roots of Taichung Native 1 and IR579-48-1 averaged less than 0.5 mm. Under upland conditions, Rikuto Norin 11 had thick roots, averaging 1 mm, the roots of E425 (upland), IR8, 81B-25, and Gbonata (upland) ranged from 0.90 to 0.97 mm. Miltex (upland), Durado, and IR532-1-218 produced rather thin roots—0.53 to 0.55 mm.

Root samples of adult plants were taken during harvest of the first upland planting which suffered the most severe drought. Because of the complexity of the root system, the root samples were scored for the thickness of the predominant roots, or, the density of roots at the crown, the degree of branching as indicated by the number of rootlets, the mode and maximum root length, and the mean and extreme diameter of the thick roots (Table 11). When the data are compared with the rating of field resistance to drought, several features appear associated with drought resistance: predominantly thick roots, dense formation of roots at the crown, and deep roots (fig. 2). Dry weight of roots and drought resistance apparently are not associated.

Root samples were taken from seven varieties in the third planting. During the seedling-to-

Table 11. Root development of upland and lowland varieties in an upland planting made on June 11. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Predominant type ^a	Density ^b	Rootlets ^c	Length (mm)		Diameter (mm)	
				Mode	Max.	Avg.	Thickest
<i>Upland varieties</i>							
Azmil	6	5	1	18	25	1.40	1.6
Hirayama	4	3	3	18	21	1.00	1.2
Jappen Tunkunoyo	2	2	4	15	24	0.88	1.0
M1-48	6	5	2	18	25	1.22	1.4
N.A.R.B.	1	2	2	16	19	0.88	1.0
Palawan	6	4	1	18	34	1.38	1.6
OS-4	6	4	3	17	36	1.16	1.3
Rikuto Norin 21	6	2	2	19	22	1.04	1.2
<i>Lowland varieties</i>							
Dular	5	2	2	16	22	1.14	1.4
IR5	4	3	4	13	24	1.18	1.4
IR8	3	1	2	12	24	0.94	1.3
IR20	1	1	1	10	15	0.66	0.8
IR579-48-1	1	2	4	16	21	0.74	1.2
IR747B2-6-3	1	2	2	12	19	0.48	0.6
IR773A1-36-2	5	3	2	17	31	1.08	1.3
Peta	5	4	4	17	26	1.14	1.3
Taichung Native 1	2	1	2	14	21	0.88	1.0

^a 1=very fine, 6=very thick. ^b 1=very few, 5=very dense. ^c 1=very few, 2=from lower portion of root only, 3=midportion to root tip, 4=uniformly branched from base to tip.

2. Roots of three upland varieties (N.A.R.B., OS4, and Palawan) and of five semi-dwarf lowland varieties in the June 20 upland planting. OS4 and Palawan have especially dense and thick roots.

heading period 1,209 mm of precipitation was recorded, as compared to the 670 mm in the first planting. In the third planting, the lowland types produced more roots, a larger proportion of thick roots, and longer roots than in the first planting. The roots of the two upland varieties (Palawan and OS-4) were about the same in the first and third plantings. On the other hand, the lowland varieties in the third planting showed a decrease in average diameter of the thick roots, whereas the upland types gave similar values. Thus the root system of most lowland varieties was better developed in the puddled soil; their root development was noticeably poorer under soil moisture conditions of upland planting. Under puddled conditions, most of the upland varieties had longer and thicker roots than the lowland types but not more numerous roots.

Four major conclusions can be drawn from these studies. First, there is a continuous variation in plant characteristics and growth features between the so-called lowland and upland varieties. That is, one or more varieties in one group fall in the range of the other group in one or more major characteristics. Second,

under severe water stress, most upland varieties showed less drought damage and produced more fertile panicles, but lowland types, such as Dular, IR5, and Peta, performed as well as the upland varieties in upland culture. Third, varietal differences in recovery from desiccation in pots are not necessarily related to drought resistance in the field. Fourth, drought resistance appears associated with a high proportion of thick roots, a dense root system, and a high proportion of deep roots.

Genetics and cytogenetics

Photoperiod sensitivity. Many tropical varieties respond weakly to photoperiod. That is, they flower under any natural daylength, although their seeding-to-heading period is markedly extended by long daylength, and they have a short basic vegetative phase (BVP) when a daylength shorter than 11 hours occurs. Improved tropical varieties, such as Peta, IR5, C4-63, BPI-76-1, Tjere Mas, and Sukanandi, belong to this class. The adaptability of this group is limited to the tropics.

We made crosses between Peta and completely insensitive varieties, such as Milfor-6(2), IR12-178-2, Chianung 242, and Kaohsiung 68, to elucidate the genetic mechanism of the weak photoperiod response. The parents, the F_1 hybrids, and the F_2 progeny were planted under a 10-hour photoperiod. Primary tillers were separated into pots which were grown to heading under three photoperiod treatments: 10-, 12-, and 14-hour. The seeding-to-heading period under the 10-hour photoperiod gives an estimate of the BVP, while the two longer photoperiods provide a measure of the photoperiod-sensitive phase under a lengthening photoperiod.

Crosses of Peta with Chianung 242 and with Kaohsiung 68 were analyzed during the year. Because the parents and the hybrid progeny showed a greater difference in photoperiod-sensitive phase under a 14-hour treatment, the index of photoperiod response is calculated by subtracting the days to heading under 10-hour photoperiod from days to heading under 14-hour photoperiod and dividing by days to heading under 10-hour photoperiod.

The data obtained from the two crosses were similar. Those from Peta x Chianung 242 are shown in fig. 3. The distribution of the F_2 plants under the 10-hour photoperiod agrees with previous findings that a short BVP is dominant to a long one, that several *Ef* genes control the total variation in BVP, and that the *Ef* genes have unequal action but cumulative effect. Therefore, the F_2 distribution could be bimodal or multimodal with more individuals having a short BVP. The F_1 hybrid may be earlier or as early as the Peta parent under the 10-hour photoperiod.

Only a few F_2 plants showed less sensitivity than the insensitive parent, but several plants exceeded Peta in the index of sensitivity. All F_2 plants flowered under the 14-hour photoperiod. But no linear association between a short BVP and a long photoperiod-sensitive phase occurred, though most of the late progenies under the 14-hour treatment showed a relatively short BVP. These findings suggest multigenic control of the weakly sensitive response with a slightly larger number of F_2 progenies in the low sensitivity range. One or more of the genes for weak

3. Relation between the estimated basic vegetative phase (BVP) under 10-hr photoperiod and the photoperiod-sensitivity index in the F_2 population of Chianung 242 x Peta.

4. Variation in heading date among 11 IR20 lines when grown under three photoperiods.

sensitivity are likely to be associated with a short BVP or the dominant *Ef* alleles.

From panicle rows of IR20 F_8 lines grown in the 1969 wet season, a number of lines which headed at distinctly different dates (up to 16 days apart) were sampled and the progenies were tested under three photoperiods: 10, 12, and 14 hours. A sample of IR20 breeder seed was included in the test. The 18 lines differed by not more than 7 days in the 10-hour photoperiod treatment. However, the maximum difference among lines was increased to 25 days under the 14-hour photoperiod. The delaying effect of the 14-hour photoperiod over the 10-hour treatment was similarly extended from 27 to 53 days (fig. 4). The breeder seed stock showed a delay of 36 days under the 14-hour treatment. In contrast, the difference in heading date between the 10-hour and 12-hour photoperiods varied from 1 to 10 days, while the difference between the 14-hour and 12-hour treatments ranged from 20 to 45 days.

The range of 12 to 14 hours of photoperiod is similar to the total variation in natural daylength within the tropics. But outside the tropics, the time of year suitable for growing a variety like IR20, which has a considerable delay in heading at daylengths longer than 12 hours and which contains some residual genetic variability in response to photoperiod, is much more restricted than that of a less sensitive variety like IR8. Institute plant physiologists therefore have systematically tested promising selections from the breeding programs for photoperiod response before subjecting them to large-scale testing and seed increase.

Grain dormancy and growth duration. Germination tests on grains harvested from 10 crosses involving parents differing in grain dormancy and grown in the 1969 wet season were completed during the year. The tests were conducted at 14, 35, 50, and 80 days after harvest to trace the changes in dormancy with time. The general distribution of F_2 plants by germination percentages at different dates is illustrated in fig. 5. Hybrid populations involving strongly dormant x non-dormant and dormant x dormant crosses differed in the relative frequency of dormant, intermediate, and non-dormant plants, but the genetic mechanism appears similar. In freshly harvested grains, dormancy is controlled by dominant genes which show cumulative effect. As time passes, one or more chemical inhibitors of germination cease to function, indicating a differential rate in the loss of gene-controlled inhibitors. The strongly dormant parents may differ only in one or a few genes for dormancy. The multigenic postulate agrees with chemical studies by other workers who found that several germination-inhibitors are involved. But, because of the continuous distribution in germination percentages at different dates of testing, the number of controlling genes could not be precisely determined.

Workers in Ceylon and India have reported a strong association between dormancy and late maturity in tropical varieties and in hybrid selections. Our data on dormancy and heading date in the F_2 populations indicate that such association among varieties or hybrid progeny may not apply to all the hybrid progeny of a

5. Distribution of parents and F_3 grain samples by germination percentage in the cross of Seraup 27 x Taichung Native 1 at 14, 35, and 80 days after harvest. Horizontal lines show the germination range of samples of the parent varieties about the means (dotted circles).

cross between a strongly dormant, late maturing variety and a nondormant, early maturing variety (fig. 6). The lack of a marked association between strong dormancy and late maturity would increase the chance of recovering dormant and early segregates from distant crosses when selection is made early in the segregating generations.

The breeding behavior of dormant, early segregates and nondormant, late segregates was tested by growing F_3 progeny in the wet season. Lines were drawn at random from four crosses to represent five combinations: early maturing and dormant, early maturing and non-dormant, late maturing and dormant, late maturing and nondormant, and intermediate in maturity and moderately dormant. Early maturing plants flower in 72 to 124 days; the late maturing lines, from 95 to 152 days. Within each line, 10 to 20 plants were sampled for comparison with the parent varieties.

6. Relation between the seeding-to-heading period and the residual dormancy of F_3 grains in Seraup 27 x Taichung Native 1 cross at 80 days after harvest. Each dot, square, or triangle represents germination percentage of one F_2 or parent plant.

Most F_3 lines segregated for heading date or dormancy, or both. Heading dates varied less within a line. The initial germination tests showed that several dormant plants occurred in non-dormant lines. The late lines tended to produce a higher proportion of dormant plants. Similarly, a few non-dormant plants showed up in the dormant families. On the other hand, the early lines were all early and most plants in the late lines remained late. All the F_3 lines that were intermediate in dormancy and in maturity in the preceding generation showed distinct segregation for both traits.

The predominance of dormant plants in the F_3 populations could be affected by the unusually rainy weather which prevailed from October through December.

Component characters of plant type. Studies on the inheritance of the principal component characters of plant type were continued in the

F₂ populations of varieties showing extreme contrast in plant type. Additional backcrosses were made to facilitate biometrical analysis. The traits studied were leaf characters and other agronomic traits. Data on the parents and F₂ plants of two crosses (IR160-27-3 x Bengawan and IR400-5-12 x BJ-1) were collected in the dry season. To minimize competition among F₂ plants of different height and tillering ability, each F₂ plant was surrounded with plants of PI215936, an intermediate variety.

The distribution of tiller number (70 days after seeding) in the F₂ populations was essentially normal, but the direction in which transgressive segregates frequently appeared was related to the tillering ability of the parents. In the IR160 x Bengawan cross, where both parents produced a mean value of 29 tillers, the F₂ population averaged 38 tillers and the transgressive segregates were in the direction of higher tiller number. In the IR400 x BJ-1 cross, where IR400 produced 35 tillers and BJ-1 produced 59 tillers, the F₂ mean of 50 tillers was slightly higher than the mid-parent value, but the transgressive segregates were found in classes of low tiller numbers.

The skewness of the F₂ distribution in IR160 x Bengawan indicates an additive type of gene action with some loci showing dominance in the direction of higher tillering ability. On the other hand, the dominance of low tillering is indicated in the IR400 x BJ-1 cross. The discrepancy in the two crosses seems due to the different genetic background of the four parents.

The distribution of leaf length for the blade

below the flagleaf was normal in both crosses. The extreme leaf dimensions of the F₂ plants was within the range of the long-leaved parent in both crosses. Only in the IR160 x Bengawan cross did several F₂ plants have very short leaf blades.

The width of the leafblades (measured at the widest point of the blade) showed multimodal distribution in both crosses but it was within the range of the parents. The F₂ distribution suggests some degree of dominance for narrower blades.

The blade area of the leaf below the flagleaf was estimated from the leaf's length and width and was adjusted by a correction factor based on actual area measurements. The F₂ distribution in both crosses was essentially unimodal. While the two parents in each cross differed little in leaf area, the F₂ distribution is distinctly transgressive on both ends of the distribution. Large leaf areas appeared predominant among the F₂ plants.

The parents and F₂ plants in both crosses showed a wide range of variation in leaf angle (of openness) when measured at 45 days after seeding. Droopy-leaved individuals were predominant in the F₂ populations. But when leaf angles were measured at heading on the leaf below the flagleaf, both crosses showed a narrower range of variation and essentially normal distributions. In each cross, more F₂ plants had leaves as erect as the IR400 or IR160 parent than had droopy leaves.

The angle of the flagleaf showed a skewed distribution in the F₂ populations. Although both BJ-1 and IR400 have erect flagleaves, the transgressive segregates were more droopy. In the IR160 x Bengawan cross, where the parents differed markedly in flagleaf angle, a greater portion of the F₂ plants had more droopy flagleaves than the erect IR160 parent.

Estimates of heritability in the IR400 x BJ-1 cross based on parental variability indicated fairly high values (51 to 70%) for tiller count at 75 days, for leaf angle at 75 days, for leaf area at 75 days, for flagleaf angle, for flagleaf area, and for panicle number. Higher values (75 to 88%) were obtained for the period from seeding to heading, for number of persistent leaf sheaths at maturity, and for plant height at 60 days

Table 12. Pollen and spikelet sterility of F₂ plants from selected crosses differing in F₁ fertility.

Cross	Pollen sterility (%)		Spikelet sterility (%)	
	Mean	Range	Mean	Range
Fertile crosses				
IR8 x Rodjolele	20	10 to 41	22	5 to 56
Basmati 370 x Pankhari 203	20	11 to 32	6	1 to 16
Partially sterile crosses				
IR8 x Boegi Imba	37	8 to 86	29	5 to 75
Basmati 370 x TN1	42	17 to 80	20	4 to 52
Sterile crosses				
IR8 x Pankhari 203	47	15 to 78	18	3 to 73
Pankhari x Rodjolele	30	14 to 63	10	1 to 36

after seeding. The estimate of effective loci by the Castle-Sewall formula indicates a minimum range of one to two loci.

In the IR160 x Bengawan cross, the highest heritability estimates (above 90%) were obtained for heading date and number of photosynthetic leaves at maturity. Flagleaf angle and tiller number also showed high values (72 to 89%), followed by flagleaf area (76%), leaf area (67%), and leaf angle at heading (50%). Leaf area at heading and panicle number gave estimates of about 50 percent. The number of effective loci for the above traits ranged from one to eight.

Sterility in F₂ hybrids. Cytogenetic investigation of hybrid sterility among tropical and subtropical varieties was continued in cooperation with geneticists of the College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Six crosses representing fertile, partially sterile, and sterile combinations were selected on the basis of F₁ fertility. About 240 F₂ plants from each of the indica x indica and indica x javanica crosses and their parents were grown during the wet season. Pollen and spikelet sterility were measured on at least 30 plants from each cross.

Table 12 shows the percentages of pollen and spikelet sterility in the six crosses. Plants in the two fertile crosses did not vary much in pollen and spikelet sterility; the partially sterile and sterile combinations varied widely. The sterile crosses, however, produced more sterile plants than the partially sterile crosses. For example, all 10 plants in one row of IR8 x Pankhari were sterile.

Preliminary data on pollen and spikelet sterility indicate that most F₂ plants from the F₁ fertile crosses would be fertile, while the partially sterile and sterile F₁ hybrids would produce highly variable F₂ progenies. The partially sterile and sterile crosses cannot be fully compared until more F₂ plants are scored for sterility.

Resistance to grassy stunt. The mode of inheritance of resistance to grassy stunt virus was investigated in IR661-1-140 x *Oryza nivara* crosses and backcrosses. IR661-1-140 is susceptible to the virus and to the brown planthopper, the vector of grassy stunt. When

IR661-1-140 is artificially inoculated with the virus, about 10 to 15 percent of the plants escape infection and do not become diseased. *O. nivara* is susceptible to the brown planthopper but highly resistant to the virus. Less than 6 percent of its plants become diseased when artificially inoculated.

F₁, F₂, and backcross progenies of IR661-1-140 x *O. nivara*, when examined, revealed that a single dominant gene in *O. nivara* conveyed resistance to the virus. All the F₁ plants tested were resistant. The F₂ data (276 resistant:71 susceptible) reveal a deficiency of the recessive (susceptible) class which is barely significant ($\chi^2 = 3.92^*$). A similar deficiency of the recessives is revealed in the BC₁ and BC₂ families—that in the BC₂ family being significant ($\chi^2 = 5.3^*$).

These deviations towards the deficiency of the susceptible individuals in the segregating progenies are undoubtedly caused by the failure of some of the genetically susceptible plants (about 10 to 15%) to get the disease. For this reason they are classified as resistant. Thus 10.7 percent of the susceptible parent plants (Table 13) do not get the disease. If the same proportion of the susceptible plants in the segregating progenies is misclassified as resistant, and if the corresponding adjustment is made, the χ^2 values become non-significant.

The progenies of three out of 15 BC₂ families were uniformly susceptible—providing direct evidence that some susceptible plants in the segregating progenies were indeed misclassified. Thus although the parental BC₁ plants of these

Table 13. Proportion of plants resistant to grassy stunt in parents, F₁, and segregating populations.

Material	Plants tested	Non-infected plants (no.)	Infected plants		χ^2 (3:1 or 1:1)
			(no.)	(%)	
<i>Parents</i>					
IR661-1-140-3	149	16	133	89.3	—
<i>O. nivara</i>	94	94	0	0.0	—
<i>Progeny</i>					
F ₁	23	23	0	0.0	—
F ₂	347	276	71	20.5	3.92*
BC ₁	48	28	20	41.6	1.32
BC ₂	244	140	104	42.8	5.30*

*Significant at the 5% level.

Table 14. Classification of Pankhari x Mudgo F₃ lines according to reaction to the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper (R = resistant, Seg = segregating, S = susceptible).

Brown planthopper reaction	No. of lines			
	Green leafhopper reaction			
	R	Seg	S	Total
R	5	13	9	27
Seg	15	28	11	54
S	7	15	2	24
Total	27	56	22	105

P value for 1:2:1:2:4:2:1:2:1=0.70—0.80

three families were not diseased, they did not carry the resistance gene and were misclassified.

Resistance to bacterial leaf blight. Studies on the genetics of resistance to bacterial leaf blight were started during the year to determine: 1) the mode of inheritance of resistance; 2) whether the resistance to two isolates of the pathogen is controlled by the same gene or by different genes; 3) whether the genes in different resistant varieties are allelic or nonallelic; and 4) the heritability values of resistance.

The resistant varieties included in the study belong to three groups: BJ-1, Sigadis, DZ 192, and TKM-6 are indica varieties; Wase Aikuku and PI 215936 are japonicas; and Zenith and B589A4-18 are of indica-japonica hybrid origin. Taichung Native 1 is the susceptible parent in the crosses. Two isolates of the bacterium B6 and B15-37 are being used. The pin prick method of inoculation is used for determining the disease reaction of parents and hybrid populations. The

Table 15. Classification of F₃ lines of crosses and their parents according to reaction to the brown planthopper (R=resistant, Seg=segregating, S=susceptible).

Variety or cross	No. of lines				<i>P</i> value for 1:2:1
	R	Seg	S	Total	
<i>Parents</i>					
TN1	—	—	51	51	—
ASD7	14	—	—	14	—
CO22	12	—	—	12	—
MTU15	13	—	—	13	—
MGL2	12	—	—	12	—
<i>F₃ lines</i>					
TN1 x ASD7	34	77	40	151	0.70—0.80
TN1 x CO22	32	63	22	117	0.30—0.40
TN1 x MTU15	35	65	30	130	0.80—0.90
TN1 x MGL2	32	54	31	117	0.70—0.80

reaction of F₁ hybrids of resistant x susceptible crosses shows that resistance is dominant. A study of F₂ populations is under way.

Insect resistance. The resistance of Mudgo to the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens*, and the resistance of Pankhari to the green leafhopper, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, are each governed by a single major dominant gene (1969 Annual Report). In tests this year, the seedling reaction of 105 F₃ lines from a cross between Pankhari and Mudgo showed that the single genes for resistance to the two insects are independently inherited (Table 14) and can therefore be easily combined in one line.

Studies were continued in cooperation with the entomology department to confirm the inheritance of resistance of several other varieties to the two insects. The bulk seedling test and the tiller test were used in these studies.

The seedling reaction of random samples of F₃ lines of crosses of varieties that are resistant to brown planthoppers, Karsamba Red ASD7, Manavari CO22, Dalwa Sannam MTU15, and Kayama MGL2, with the susceptible variety, Taichung Native 1, confirmed that the resistance in each cross was controlled by a single major gene (Table 15). The resistance of ASD7 behaved as recessive while that of CO22, MTU15, and MGL2 behaved as dominant.

F₃ lines of crosses among resistant varieties were studied to identify the number of independent genes for resistance to the brown planthopper. None of the 124 F₃ lines of Mudgo x ASD7, 127 F₃ lines of Mudgo x CO22, 133 lines of Mudgo x MTU15, and 129 F₃ lines of ASD7 x CO22 were homozygous susceptible. The results so far obtained suggest that the single dominant genes for resistance in Mudgo, CO22, and MTU15 are allelomorphous. They also seem to be identical. That can be conclusively established, however, only when planthopper races differing in ability to attack resistant varieties are available. Although no evidence is available to show that the ASD7 gene is not allelic to the other genes, it appears to be genetically different from others because it is recessive. The resistance gene in Mudgo, CO22, and MTU15 may be designated as *Bph 1* and the one in ASD7 may be designated as *bph 2*.

In studies with insects, it is difficult to determine whether dead seedlings occasionally observed in crosses among resistant varieties are the result of genetic recombination between non-allelic genes or whether they were killed by a disease organism or by an unusually heavy insect infestation. It is not uncommon to find 1 or 2 percent susceptible seedlings in a variety known to be resistant. Several crosses involving ASD7 and other resistant varieties were intensively studied for segregation to the brown planthopper reaction to determine the relationship between *Bph 1* and *bph 2* genes.

Only one of the 486 F_2 seedlings of Mudgo x CO22 was susceptible while nine of the 592 F_2 seedlings of Mudgo x ASD7 were susceptible. But in the cross ASD7 x CO22 which was expected to show a behavior similar to that of Mudgo x ASD7, only two of the 497 F_2 seedlings were susceptible. The results resemble those reported last year.

The F_2 segregation of these crosses was also studied with the tiller test. Plants about 6 weeks old are used for the tiller test. After caging an equal number of insects on individual plants the reaction of the plants is classified on the basis of insect survival. None of 88 F_2 plants of Mudgo x CO22 or of 90 F_2 plants of ASD7 x CO22 were as susceptible as Taichung Native 1. Among 90 F_2 plants of Mudgo x ASD7, the reaction of four plants resembled or approached that of Taichung Native 1, but the seedling reaction of F_3 progenies of these plants showed that they were not susceptible. All available data indicate that recombination between *Bph 1* and *bph 2* loci is rare or absent. Therefore these two genes possibly are either allelomorphous or strongly linked.

When adequate populations of the brown planthopper are present in the field, the genetic material can be classified for its field reaction to the planthopper which kills adult plants and causes hopper burn. We tested 102 F_4 lines of Mudgo x Taichung Native 1 with known seedling reaction in the field. The greenhouse and field reactions were strongly correlated and no line showed a susceptible reaction in the greenhouse and a resistant reaction in the field or vice versa.

Table 16. Classification of F_3 lines of crosses and their parents according to reaction to the green leafhopper (R=resistant, Seg=segregating, S=susceptible).

Variety or cross	No. of lines				P value for	
	R	Seg	S	Total	1:2:1	15:1 ^a
<i>Parents</i>						
TN1	—	—	30	30	—	—
ASD7	42	—	—	42	—	—
IR8	41	—	—	41	—	—
Pankhari	27	—	—	27	—	—
<i>F₃ lines</i>						
TN1 x ASD7	40	71	41	152	0.70-0.80	—
TN1 x IR8	31	69	35	135	0.80-0.90	—
Pankhari x ASD7	64	37	4	105	—	0.30-0.40
IR8 x Pankhari	44	59	5	108	—	0.40-0.50
IR8 x ASD7	62	38	8	108	—	0.60-0.70

^aRefers to resistant and segregating lines combined versus susceptible lines.

Additional data were obtained on the inheritance of resistance to green leafhoppers in ASD7 and IR8. Random samples of F_3 lines of Taichung Native 1 (susceptible) x ASD7 and Taichung Native 1 x IR8 were tested for seedling reaction to the leafhopper. The results confirmed the presence in ASD7 and IR8 of one major dominant gene for resistance (Table 16). The F_3 breeding behavior of crosses among the resistant varieties, Pankhari, ASD7, and IR8, showed that the resistance genes were non-allelic and independently inherited. The independent genes for resistance to green leafhoppers may be designated as *Glh 1* (in Pankhari), *Glh 2* (in ASD7), and *Glh 3* (in IR8).

ASD7 is resistant to both the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper. The classification according to seedling reaction of 100 F_3 lines of Taichung Native 1 x ASD7 to both insects showed that the ASD7 genes for resistance to the brown planthopper and green leafhopper (*bph 2* and *Glh 2*) are independently inherited (Table 17). The Pankhari gene for resistance to the green leafhopper (*Glh 1*) has already been found to be inherited independently of the Mudgo gene for resistance to the brown planthopper (*Bph 1*). Plant breeders have had no difficulty in combining IR8's resistance to the green leafhopper with the resistance of Mudgo to the brown planthopper. Thus several combinations of *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3* among themselves as well as with *Bph 1* or *bph 2* can be incorporated in future varieties.

Table 17. Classification of F₃ lines of Taichung Native 1 x ASD7 according to reaction to the brown planthopper and the green leafhopper. (R=resistant, Seg=segregating, S=susceptible).

Green leafhopper reaction	No. of lines			
	Brown planthopper reaction			Total
	R	Seg	S	
R	8	11	7	26
Seg	8	27	14	49
S	7	14	4	25
Total	23	52	25	100
<i>P</i> value for 1:2:1:2:4:2:1:2:1 = 0.80—0.90				

Male sterility. The development of two male-sterile lines, D320 and D388, was reported last year. They were crossed with IR8 and the F₁ plants were partially sterile. Two backcrosses have been made with IR8 to combine the male sterility of D388 with the semi-dwarf plant type. Further studies will be carried out to determine whether the male sterility is under genetic or cytoplasmic-genetic control.

Japanese workers recently reported that an Indian variety, Chinsura Boro II, is a source of cytoplasmic male sterility and of a fertility-restoring gene. The cytoplasm of Boro II, when transferred to Taichung 65 (a ponlai variety from Taiwan), produced a fully male-sterile line. U.S. workers have found that another indica variety from Taiwan, Birco

(P.I. 279120), possesses a male-sterile cytoplasm.

In attempts to develop improved cytoplasmic male-sterile lines and fertility restorers, 72 crosses involving Boro II, P.I. 279120, and many other varieties were studied. Crosses that showed some reciprocal differences in pollen sterility were selected for backcrossing and further studies. The preliminary results indicate that the semi-dwarf variety, Taichung Native 1, might be a source of cytoplasmic male sterility and of a fertility-restoring gene or genes. In the F₁ generation of Taichung Native 1 x Pankhari, 47 percent of the pollen was sterile, compared with 36 percent in its reciprocal cross. The gradual substitution of the Taichung Native 1 nucleus with the Pankhari nucleus through backcrossing rapidly increased the level of pollen sterility and several plants in the progeny of the second backcross had 99 to 100 percent sterile pollen (Table 18). Further backcrossing to Pankhari should produce completely male-sterile lines. On the other hand, the backcrosses with Taichung Native 1 are approaching complete fertility. In addition to the cytoplasm and fertility-restoring genes, other genes for sterility in F₁ seem to be operating. This may explain why the reciprocal crosses between Taichung Native 1 and Pankhari do not show a large difference in pollen sterility.

Table 18. Variation in pollen sterility of parents, F₁, F₂, and backcrosses of Taichung Native 1 x Pankhari 203.

Material	No. of plants in different pollen sterility classes										Total	Mean pollen sterility (%)
	0-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70	71-80	81-90	91-100		
<i>Parents</i>												
TN1	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5	4
Pankhari	5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5	4
<i>F₁ plants</i>												
TN1 x Pankhari	—	—	—	—	3	1	—	—	—	—	4	47
Pankhari x TN1	—	—	—	4	—	—	—	—	—	—	4	36
<i>F₂ plants</i>												
TN1 x Pankhari	17	11	10	6	6	1	—	—	—	—	51	21
<i>Backcrosses</i>												
(TN1 x Pankhari) x TN1	15	4	8	4	5	1	1	—	—	—	38	21
(TN1 x Pankhari) x Pankhari	—	5	2	1	6	3	3	4	4	3	31	57
(TN1 x Pankhari) x Pankhari/2	—	—	—	—	2	—	3	5	2	20 ^a	32	88

^a14 plants had 99 to 100% pollen sterility.

Entomology

The rice variety, IR20, an outcome of the project on varietal resistance to stem borers, is now planted on vast areas in East Pakistan and in the Philippines. Its broad resistance to pests and diseases appears to be the main reason for its success. In 1970 efforts were expanded to include identifying sources of resistance against other insect pests, studying the bases of resistance, and combining the resistances against various insects. Combining sources of resistance to the stem borers, the green leafhopper, and the brown planthopper appears feasible.

Research was continued to develop better insecticidal control of rice pests. Carbofuran appears very promising for stem borers, leafhoppers, and the brown planthopper. Treatments combining other selected insecticides provided highly effective control of common pests.

Studies on changes in the population of the brown planthopper on different varieties and under different insecticide treatments showed that high density is associated with a large number of nymphs. A high density occurred on diazinon-treated IR8.

Research on the biological control of stem borers was continued. No parasites have recently been found that are suitable for field release.

Varietal resistance

Stem borers. Screening of the world germ plasm of rice for resistance to the striped rice borer, retesting of the selected lines, and analyses of the factors of resistance and of the effect of resistant varieties on the borer were largely completed during 1970. The details of these results are reported in IIRI Technical Bulletin No. 11 (in press). The sources of resistance identified in these studies were used in breeding for resistance to striped borers, a study which yielded the rice variety IR20.

Highly significant differences were found in the susceptibility of rice varieties to striped rice borers. In field tests these differences are seen in the incidence of dead hearts and in greenhouse experiments in the survival and weight of larvae caged on different varieties. In some varieties, however, the resistance to borers changes with the stage of plant growth, and in field plantings even resistant varieties occasionally have a high incidence of white heads because even limited feeding by larvae seems to cause

white heads. Thus the larvae on resistant varieties cause white heads before they are affected by the resistance of the plants. This emphasizes the importance of the *nonpreference* type of resistance supplemented with *antibiosis* for reducing white head damage. A project has been started to combine these types of resistance and to build up the existing level of resistance by intercrossing the resistant varieties. Also, a general decline in the incidence of the stem borers and an increasing incidence of brown planthopper and of the grassy stunt virus at the IIRI farm are forcing us to study resistance to stem borers in the greenhouse.

Table 1 shows the borer resistance of some of the varieties selected for these studies. Most of the test varieties had less than 3 percent dead heart or white head incidence, while the susceptible variety, Rexoro, was heavily damaged. In the greenhouse where individual plants of each variety were artificially infested with the same number of newly hatched borer larvae, the survival and body weight of the larvae differed widely among varieties.

Table 1. Percentages of dead hearts, white heads, and larval survival of *Chilo suppressalis* on selected resistant varieties. IIRI, 1969 and 1970.

Variety	Field experiments				Greenhouse experiments	
	1969 wet season		1970 dry season		Larval survival (%)	Larval wt. (mg)
	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)		
Rexoro ^a	22.6	9.4	12.8	5.5	<i>b</i>	69
TKM 6	1.9	2.0	1.5	1.8	54	39
Chiang-an Tsao Pai ku	0.4	2.0	2.4	0.6	58	25
CO 21	1.6	1.3	1.7	2.2	65	47
HBJ Boro II	2.0	0.9	0.5	0.8	40	30
C 409	2.7	1.6	1.9	1.0	84	37
Su yai 20	2.0	0.9	0.5	0.8	90	41
Szu Miao	3.1	2.4	2.2	1.7	5	25
JC 148	1.4	1.2	1.2	1.4	49	39
Patnai 6	1.7	2.0	0.9	4.5	15	35
Bir-co 884	1.6	0.2	1.1	1.9	24	41
DNJ 97	2.8	1.9	1.4	2.9	83	50
DZ 41	2.5	0.7	1.0	0.9	24	29
DD 48	2.0	1.3	0.9	1.5	65	42
DV 88	0.6	1.1	1.3	1.9	41	40
Ti Ho Hung	1.7	0.9	1.6	1.3	63	31
Pai Hsu	1.2	1.6	0.9	1.3	18	27
PI 160, 638	0.9	1.0	2.1	2.9	23	31
ASD 8	<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	2.2	1.4	30	29
Tadukan	3.9	0.3	2.2	2.5	75	39
IR20	3.3	1.9	1.0	3.4	56	49
IR22	<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	1.6	0.9	76	32

^a Susceptible check. ^b The plants were killed before dissection thereby affecting the recovery of the surviving larvae. ^c Not tested.

Performance of IR20. Although specifically resistant to stem borers, IR20 also possesses field resistance to several other insect pests and diseases. It has performed extremely well in Vietnam and East Pakistan, has been approved for cultivation in India, and is being planted widely in the Philippines. This general acceptability of IR20 emphasizes the importance of broad resistance to insect pests and diseases in rice varieties.

The complementary effects of IR20's varietal resistance and insecticidal treatments were investigated. IR20 and a few other varieties were protected with insecticides at different stages of plant growth. Each of these varieties were transplanted in field plots in a randomized block design which received different Dolmix treatments.

Without insecticide, IR20 produced 1.5 t/ha more rice than IR8 and about 0.7 t/ha more than IR22. Plots of IR20 and IR22 that were protected with Dolmix every 20 days produced identical yields, but the yield of IR20 was consistently higher in all other treatments. This indicated that IR20 responds better to insecticidal treatment than the other test varieties.

The major problem during these experiments was grassy stunt virus. Only about 10 percent of the plants in the untreated plot of IR20 were infected with grassy stunt, but 20 to 50 percent of the untreated plots of the other varieties were infected (Table 2). The borer infestation and the grassy stunt infection were so severe in this experiment that the varieties Taichung Native 1 and Rexoro were severely damaged and produced little rice.

Leafhoppers and planthoppers. The screening tests for resistance to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper were continued. Similar studies were undertaken for the white-backed planthopper, *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath). Several varieties resistant to these insects were identified. Some of them were used for investigating the basic aspects of resistance.

In one experiment, the survival and rates of development of the first-instar brown planthopper nymphs were investigated on resistant and susceptible varieties. The insects suffered

high mortality and grew more slowly on varieties Balamawee, Kuruhondarawala, Babawee, Dikwee, Seruvellai, Mudgo, and Thirissa. By 14 days after caging, only 30 percent of the insects on these varieties were alive and few had become adults. During the same period, however, 93 percent of the insects caged on susceptible varieties had survived and about 70 percent had become adults. The varieties Balamawee, Kuruhondarawala, and Babawee had even greater resistance than Mudgo (fig. 1).

In a similar experiment, 12 varieties were identified that possess almost the same level of resistance to the brown planthopper as Mudgo. A total of 18 varieties have been found to be highly resistant to the brown planthopper. Fourteen of the varieties were tested in a series of experiments and were less preferred by the brown planthopper than susceptible varieties

Table 2. Resistance of five varieties to stem borers when grown under different levels of insect control (Dolmix at 2 kg/ha a.i.). IRRRI 1970.

Variety	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Virus (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>No application</i>				
IR20	8.3	1.4	8	3.63
IR22	7.7	2.3	20	3.08
IR8	9.1	2.1	28	2.32
Taichung Native 1	9.9	4.4	32	1.37
Rexoro	40.4	16.3	42	0.05
<i>One application^a</i>				
IR20	12.8	2.5	1	3.82
IR22	10.8	2.1	7	3.25
IR8	9.1	2.1	28	2.32
Taichung Native 1	9.9	4.4	32	1.37
Rexoro	40.4	16.3	42	0.05
<i>Two applications^b</i>				
IR20	3.8	1.6	1	3.93
IR22	2.3	0.3	15	3.71
IR8	3.7	2.5	30	2.57
Taichung Native 1	5.5	1.8	26	2.19
Rexoro	21.0	18.0	24	0.21
<i>Three applications^c</i>				
IR20	2.1	0.9	1	4.42
IR22	1.5	1.0	6	4.27
IR8	2.1	1.4	23	3.46
Taichung Native 1	2.9	3.5	23	2.92
Rexoro	19.3	30.0	18	0.12
<i>Five applications^d</i>				
IR20	1.3	0.3	2	4.90
IR22	1.2	0.3	6	4.68
IR8	3.2	0.8	16	3.70
Taichung Native 1	3.7	1.8	19	3.16
Rexoro	29.7	18.8	19	0.17

^a 20 days after transplanting. ^b 5 and 55 days after transplanting. ^c 5, 45, and 75 days after transplanting. ^d 5, 25, 45, 65, and 85 days after transplanting.

1. Survival and growth of first-instar brown planthopper nymphs at 14 days after caging on selected resistant and susceptible rice varieties. IIRI, 1970.

(fig. 2)—the insects caged on them had lower survival rates, grew slower, and laid fewer eggs. Furthermore even a large number of adults or nymphs caged on these varieties frequently caused insignificant plant damage.

The ability of the brown planthoppers to multiply on resistant and susceptible varieties was investigated by caging a pair of newly emerged adults on individual plants. The number of nymphs hatching on these plants was recorded at frequent intervals and after each observation the nymphs were removed from the plant. On the susceptible variety, Taichung Native 1, there were 10 times as many nymphs as on the resistant varieties, and nymphs hatched for over a period of 23 days while on the resistant varieties nymphs hatched for only 15 days.

All these effects combined make the brown planthopper unable to maintain populations on the resistant varieties of rice.

Causes of resistance. Morphological differences in varieties are not correlated with differences in the resistance of the varieties to the green leafhopper or the brown planthopper (1968 Annual Report). When caged on plants of resistant varieties, brown planthoppers generally feed little and die out, while green leafhoppers do some feeding but die within a few days

2. Preference of female brown planthoppers for selected resistant and susceptible rice varieties. IIRI, 1970.

after caging. This suggests that Mudgo, which is resistant to brown planthopper, possesses one or more factors that strongly deter the brown planthopper from feeding or that Mudgo lacks the phagostimulatory factors. Pankhari 203 and IR8, which are resistant to the green leafhopper, apparently have a factor that is deleterious to insects, or the two varieties lack nutrients vital to the insects. Thus, varietal resistance to both these insects appears to be biochemical.

In further studies, we bioassayed the plant sap from resistant and susceptible varieties. Plant extracts were taken from the leaf sheaths (for the brown planthopper) and the leaf blades (for the green leafhopper) with either hot or cold water. Small wads of cotton soaked

in the extracts were placed equidistantly around a large petri dish and adult test insects were released in the center of the dishes. The dishes were placed in the dark and the number of insects on the different wads was counted periodically.

The insects did not differ significantly in their preference for extracts from susceptible or resistant plants. But they strongly preferred the fresh pieces of the leaf sheaths to pieces that had been extracted with either hot or cold water (fig. 3). Apparently extraction of the leaf sheaths with water removed some factor that was attractive to the brown planthopper.

So far, attempts to bioassay the extracts of resistant or susceptible plants by using brown planthoppers have failed because the insect suffers high mortality even when caged on extracts of susceptible plants. The exact cause is not fully understood, but the nutritional requirements for a standard synthetic diet for the brown planthopper are not known.

To determine the optimum nutritional requirements of brown planthoppers, several standard nutrients, such as sucrose, glucose, fructose, starch, and different amino acids, were studied. Various concentrations of the solutions of each nutrient were placed inside a "sachet," made of Parafilm-M film. This sachet was held between two glass tubes and the insects were released in one of the tubes to feed on the solution through the film (fig. 4). More brown planthoppers survived when they were released in the test tube above the sachet. The survival of the green leafhopper, however, was not affected by the position of the sachet. When fed on a 10-percent sucrose solution, about half the caged brown planthoppers lived up to 7 days while about 90 percent of the green leafhoppers lived up to 10 days. Both test insects, however, died within 24 hours if nothing was enclosed inside the sachet.

The alighting and the feeding behavior of the brown planthopper was investigated on the susceptible variety, Taichung Native 1, and on the resistant variety, Mudgo. Adult brown planthoppers kept for 1½ hours without food were caged on individual potted plants of these varieties and their feeding behavior was observed frequently.

3. Preference of brown planthoppers for fresh and water-extracted pieces of leafsheaths of Taichung Native 1 plants.

4. Brown planthoppers feeding on test solution sandwiched between layers of Parafilm-M membrane.

Since each cage contained only one variety, the insects had to feed on it or starve. The number of insects consistently increased on Taichung Native 1 plants during the first 10 hours after caging, at the end of which more than 95 percent of the insects caged were on the plant. With Mudgo, comparatively fewer insects settled on the plant. Also, although the number of insects attracted to Mudgo reached 75 percent 7 hours after caging, the insects left the plants later. At 24 hours after caging, only 44 percent of the insects were on Mudgo (fig. 5), 13.6 percent were dead, and the rest were sitting on the cage. During the same period, only 2.8 percent of the caged insects died on Taichung Native 1 plants.

Apparently the lack of a feeding stimulus or the presence of one or more feeding deterrents in Mudgo was so distinct that the insects starved to death rather than feed on it. These findings support the theory that Taichung Native 1 plants possess attractants for the brown planthopper. The attractants were removed or inactivated by extracting the leaf sheaths with hot or cold water. Brown planthoppers however fed less on the extracts than on distilled water and they died faster on the extracts than on water alone. The cause is being investigated.

Cross-resistance. Since several species of insect pests cause economic losses to the rice crop, a

5. Brown planthopper adults that settled on resistant (Mudgo) and susceptible (Taichung Native 1) plants. A total of 100 insects kept without food for 1 hour were caged with each variety in separate cages. IRRI, 1970.

variety with resistance to many species is obviously more advantageous than a variety that is resistant to only one. We are attempting to identify varieties resistant to several pests and to combine many sources of resistance in one variety. The cross resistance of some varieties to the common stem borer species was described in the 1969 annual report. To combine additional sources of resistance, the following crosses of Mudgo x IR8 were investigated.

Mudgo is highly resistant to the brown planthopper but susceptible to the green leafhopper. On the other hand, IR8 is highly resistant to the green leafhopper. Mudgo is a typically tall and lodging-susceptible variety with poor agronomic characters, while IR8 has excellent plant type. These varieties were crossed.

After several generations of selections based on good plant type and resistance to brown planthoppers and green leafhoppers, the plants from F₅ pedigree lines were exposed to both insects in the greenhouse (fig. 6). A total of 294 lines were resistant to both insects, 153 were resistant to the green leafhopper only, 28 were resistant to the brown planthopper only, and 51 were resistant to neither insect.

Based on their resistance and other plant characters, 1,605 plants were selected and tested in pedigree rows. A row of IR8 was planted alternately between these test lines to encourage the development of brown planthoppers. The field was treated with 2 kg/ha a.i. diazinon every 20 days. Diazinon treatments do not control the brown planthopper at IRRI, but they protect the crop from other common insects.

The population of the brown planthopper during the experiment was very high. Most of the IR8 rows suffered severe hopperburn but few Mudgo x IR8 lines were damaged (fig. 7). From this experiment about 100 lines have been selected that possess resistance to both the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper, and which have excellent plant type and good grains. Several lines have also been selected that are resistant only to the brown planthopper or the green leafhopper but possess excellent plant type and good grains. These lines will serve as specific sources of resistance to the green leafhopper and brown planthopper and also

6. Resistance of Mudgo x IR8 F₄ progeny to the brown planthopper, left, to the green leafhopper, right.

will constitute valuable materials for studying the chemical bases of resistance.

The progeny of Mudgo x IR8 were crossed with an IR841 line [(Peta/3 x Taichung Native 1) x Khao Dawk Mali] that has excellent grain type. About 500 F₃ pedigree lines are being investigated in the field. Many have excellent plant type and grains, and are resistant to both the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper.

IR20 also was crossed with Mudgo x IR8 plants to combine the desirable qualities of IR20 with high levels of resistance to green leafhoppers and brown planthoppers. The F₃ and F₄ progenies of this cross were evaluated for their resistance to brown planthopper and general plant type. Several selections appear to have the general desirable qualities of IR20 in addition to being resistant to the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper.

Cooperative variety trials. The general performance of IR8, IR20, and IR22 in relation to insect attack was evaluated at two field stations of the Bureau of Plant Industry, Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, and Visayas Rice Experiment Station, Iloilo City, in the 1970 wet season. Insect conditions at these stations are different from those at IRRI (1969 Annual Report). Dolmix was applied to half the plots four times during the crop's growth. In the other half, no insecticide was applied.

At Maligaya (Table 3), the three varieties showed insignificant differences in their resistance to the whorl maggot. The overall infestation by stem borers was relatively low as shown by the dead-heart and white-head counts. On the average, the lowest infestation of stem borers was found in IR22. IR20 yielded

7. Mudgo x IR8 has produced progeny of good plant type that are resistant to the green leafhopper and brown planthopper. Most F₅ lines were not damaged by the brown planthopper while IR8 planted as guard rows, left, and in between the lines, right, suffered hopperburn.

Table 3. The performance of three varieties with and without insecticide. Maligaya, Philippines, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Whorl maggot damage ^a (%)	Dead hearts ^b (%)	White heads ^c (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Treated^d</i>				
IR20	76	1.2	4.3	3.63
IR22	89	0.1	0.7	3.42
IR8	92	4.2	4.7	2.05
<i>Untreated</i>				
IR20	100	7.1	8.2	3.15
IR22	100	2.6	6.1	1.68
IR8	100	5.7	8.8	1.39

^aPercent of hills showing damage 20 days after transplanting. ^b55 days after transplanting. ^cBetween 90 and 100 days after transplanting. ^dDolmix applied at 2 kg/ha at 10, 30, 50, and 70 days after transplanting.

much better than either IR22 or IR8 when no insecticide was applied. With insecticide, however, no statistical difference was found between the yield of IR20 and that of IR22.

At the Visayas station (Table 4), whorl-maggot damage was not severe and little difference in resistance to this insect was noticeable among the varieties. Even though the percentage of dead hearts was very low, IR22 showed a lower infestation of stem borers than IR8 when treated with insecticide. This difference is not reflected by the data for white heads, however. When grown without insecticide the varieties did not give statistically different yields. When treated with Dolmix, IR8 yielded more than IR22.

Declining effectiveness of diazinon

Two major factors appear responsible for the marked decline in the effectiveness of diazinon for controlling the brown planthoppers: microbial degradation of diazinon and development of a diazinon-resistant strain of brown planthoppers (1969 Annual Report).

Microbial degradation of diazinon. Studies this year confirmed that microbial degradation of diazinon in the soil and paddy water was the primary reason the insecticide has less residual effectiveness in rice fields. This microbial factor was minimal in fields that were not previously treated with diazinon but it built up rapidly after three to five applications of diazinon. It

Table 4. The performance of three varieties with and without insecticide. Visayas, Philippines, 1970 wet season.

Variety	Whorl maggot damage ^a	Dead hearts ^b (%)	White heads ^c (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Treated^d</i>				
IR8	1.3	1.0	0.4	5.93
IR20	1.0	0.0	0.4	5.36
IR22	1.0	0.0	0.6	4.80
<i>Untreated</i>				
IR8	3.0	2.2	3.1	4.45
IR20	3.0	0.8	3.4	4.22
IR22	3.0	0.9	4.7	3.91

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number means greater damage. Reading at 20 days after transplanting. ^b56 days after transplanting. ^cBetween 90 and 99 days after transplanting. ^dDolmix applied at 2 kg/ha at 10, 30, 50, and 70 days after transplanting.

occurred in the paddy water, in rhizosphere soil, and in non-rhizosphere soil (fig. 8). It also occurred in fields at experiment stations at three locations in the Philippines where diazinon has been used for several seasons.

In laboratory experiments, the microbes collected from diazinon-treated fields failed to metabolize diazinon in aqueous solution but did so readily when ethyl alcohol or glucose was added to the incubation mixture. Apparently the microbes could not multiply on diazinon alone. Their multiplication under field conditions may be brought about by other microorganisms or other agents in the paddy water.

We used an enrichment culture technique to increase the concentration of the microbial population in the paddy water. This culture had abundant Gram-positive cocci. Several isolates from it readily degraded diazinon dissolved in ethyl alcohol. The most active isolate was identified as *Arthrobacter* sp. Another bacterium, *Corynebacterium* sp., was isolated from paddy fields at Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija. The microbial populations from the diazinon-treated rice fields at IRRRI degraded diazinon but not other insecticides closely related to it (Table 5). Also, this population was found only in plots treated with diazinon and not in plots treated with related compounds (Table 6).

Pathway of diazinon degradation. Incubation of radioactive diazinon with paddy water containing the microbial degradation factor, or factors, caused the release of 66 percent of the ¹⁴C as

$^{14}\text{CO}_2$ in 5 days. During the same period, the release of CO_2 was nonsignificant if the incubation mixture was treated with streptomycin or if the water used for incubation came from a field that had not previously been treated with diazinon (Table 7). Autoradiograms showed that the diazinon from the incubation mixture containing water from diazinon-treated fields disappeared completely while most of the diazinon in other incubation mixtures was retained (fig. 9). This indicated that the microbes metabolized the pyrimidine ring completely, leaving no intermediate metabolite.

Furthermore, by 3 days after incubation, 90 percent of the added diazinon was degraded, but only 10 percent of the ^{14}C was released as $^{14}\text{CO}_2$. Two days later, however, although all diazinon had disappeared from the incubation mixture, only 66 percent of the added ^{14}C was recovered as $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ (Table 7). This indicated that diazinon was first converted into some metabolite which in turn, was mineralized to CO_2 within a few days.

In another experiment we extracted the incubation mixture periodically with chloroform diethyl ether and measured the radioactivity of the extracts (fig. 10). The amount of the insecticide decreased progressively as the level of the hydrolysis product increased for 75 hours, after which most of the insecticide disappeared. The hydrolysis product that formed was rapidly metabolized, evidently to $^{14}\text{CO}_2$, between 75 and 100 hours after incubation began. No radioactive metabolite other than the hydrolysis product appeared on the auto-

8. Diazinon degradation after incubation with paddy water and soils from rice fields previously treated with diazinon or from previously untreated rice fields. IRRI, 1970.

radiograph. About 10 percent of the added radioactivity remained in the water phase after solvent extraction.

Resistant brown planthoppers. Microbial degradation is not the only cause of the ineffectiveness of diazinon to control brown planthopper at IRRI since it was effective against the rice whorl maggot and the stem borers. This obviously suggests that diazinon-resistant populations of brown planthoppers have developed. Brown planthoppers complete one life cycle in about 25 days and at the IRRI farm they remain active throughout the year. Theoretically they complete about 15 generations a year. So

Table 5. Persistence of diazinon and related insecticides when incubated with paddy water from field plots previously treated with diazinon and from plots not previously treated. IRRI, 1970.

Insecticide	Days after incubation	Insecticide recovered (ppm)	
		Diazinon	
		pre-treated field ^a	Untreated field ^b
Diazinon	0	38.2	43.8
	12	0.0	40.7
Dursban	0	7.2	7.2
	12	3.3	4.8
Ethyl parathion	0	9.8	9.8
	12	9.9	10.1

^a Each insecticide was incubated with 5 ml of paddy water from a field plot that had previously received four applications of diazinon. ^b Not previously treated with insecticide.

Table 6. Persistence of diazinon when incubated with paddy water from field plots treated with different insecticides. IRRI, 1970.

Water ^a obtained from plots treated with	Diazinon recovered (ppm)		
	Days after incubation		
	0	3	12
Dursban	27.8	27.5	24.0
Carbofuran	27.2	27.2	25.5
Sandoz 6626	27.7	26.8	24.5
Phosvel	27.8	28.2	26.2
Gamma-BHC	27.0	27.0	24.8
Diazinon	25.5	0.0	0.0
No insecticide	27.2	26.5	25.7

^a Collected 10 days after three applications of each insecticide at 2 kg/ha a.i. at 20-day intervals.

9. Autoradiograph of paddy water plus ^{14}C -labelled diazinon at 5 days after incubation. Std. = ^{14}C ; T = paddy water from treated field + ^{14}C diazinon; U = paddy water from untreated field + ^{14}C diazinon; TS = water from treated field + streptomycin + ^{14}C diazinon; US = water from untreated field + streptomycin + ^{14}C diazinon.

10. Autoradiograph of paddy water from diazinon-treated field plus ^{14}C -labelled diazinon at different incubation periods. D = Diazinon; H = Hydrolysis product.

Table 7. Release of $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ from ^{14}C -labelled diazinon incubated with water from different rice fields.

Tagged diazinon incubated with water from plots previously:	Streptomycin added	Diazinon ^a (ppm)	$^{14}\text{CO}_2$ (count/min)
<i>At zero time</i>			
Treated with diazinon	No	24.0	0
	Yes	24.0	0
Untreated with diazinon	No	22.5	0
	Yes	30.0	0
<i>After 1 day of incubation</i>			
Treated with diazinon	No	22.0	100
	Yes	24.0	100
Untreated with diazinon	No	22.8	100
	Yes	29.3	100
<i>After 3 days of incubation</i>			
Treated with diazinon	No	2.3	9100
	Yes	25.0	500
Untreated with diazinon	No	21.5	800
	Yes	29.3	500
<i>After 5 days of incubation</i>			
Treated with diazinon	No	0	51700
	Yes	22.8	100
Untreated with diazinon	No	22.8	100
	Yes	29.3	100

^aDetermined by gas-liquid chromatography.

during the 3½ years that IRRI used diazinon as the standard control brown planthoppers went through over 50 generations. If variations in populations of brown planthoppers susceptible to diazinon occur, 50 generations is more than adequate for resistant individuals to be selected and for their population build-up.

We investigated whether this actually happened. Brown planthoppers were collected from the IRRI farm and from several other locations in the Philippines. The insects were reared for one generation or more at IRRI and then tested for susceptibility to diazinon. One- to 2-day-old brachypterous females were used in these studies. The insects were anaesthetized by exposing them for 15 seconds to a 2.5 ml/sec flow of carbon dioxide in a Buchner funnel. Technical diazinon dissolved in acetone was applied on the abdominal terga of the insects with a glass syringe attached to an electrically operated micrometer. The instrument was calibrated to deliver 195×10^{-6} ml of the insecticide per stroke. Different concentrations of the insecticide were used to vary the amounts of the actual diazinon in each treatment.

Twenty-five insects, treated individually, constituted one replication. Insects treated with

Table 8. Resistance to diazinon of the brown planthopper population at IIRRI, IIRRI, 1970.

Source of brown planthopper	Resistance factor ^a	Regression coefficient
IIRRI Laguna		
Untreated control plots	4.25	0.989
Gamma-Mipcin plots	4.68	0.896
Diazinon-treated plots		
6 kg/ha a.i.	4.03	0.848
10 kg/ha a.i.	5.16	0.700
16 kg/ha a.i.	4.49	0.973
Sta. Rosa, Laguna	1.37	0.965
Maligaya, Nueva Ecija	1.12	0.987
Imus, Cavite ^b	1.00	0.966

^aLD₅₀ of field strain ÷ LD₅₀ of laboratory strain. ^bSusceptible check.

acetone alone made up the untreated checks. After the treatment, the insects were transferred to bottles containing rice seedlings. The bottles were placed for 24 hours in an incubator adjusted to 29 ± 2 C and 45 to 75 percent relative humidity during the day, and 25 ± 2 C and 75 to 100 percent relative humidity during the night. A 12-hour day was simulated by fluorescent light tubes.

At 24 hours after treatment the number of insects that died was recorded and the LD₅₀ values were calculated. The level of diazinon resistance in different populations were determined by the ratio of the LD₅₀ value of the

test populations to the LD₅₀ value of the most susceptible strains.

Since brown planthoppers from the IIRRI farm that had not been exposed to diazinon were not available, several populations were collected a few kilometers from IIRRI. These populations were evaluated to identify a susceptible check. Brown planthoppers from several other locations in the Philippines were also tested.

The brown planthoppers from IIRRI were four to five times more resistant to diazinon than the other populations. However, the populations from IIRRI did not exhibit different levels of resistance regardless of the insecticidal treatments they were exposed to (Table 8).

Microbial degradation and diazinon-resistant insects. Both the microbial degradation of diazinon and the occurrence of a diazinon-resistant strain or strains of the brown planthoppers appear important in rendering diazinon ineffective against this insect at IIRRI. The relative importance of these factors was investigated in a field experiment involving the treatments listed in Table 9. Plants generally grew more luxuriantly in the plot that received four diazinon applications before transplanting. Also the control of stem maggots and stem

Table 9. Effectiveness of diazinon applied as granules to the paddy water in controlling the brown planthoppers. IIRRI, 1970.

Chronological treatment ^a	Objective	Whorl maggot damage ^b 25 DAT ^c	Grassy stunt hills (%) 38 DAT ^c	Brown planthoppers (no./hill) 72 DAT ^c		Hopperburned area (%)	
				Adults	Nymphs	70 DAT ^c	77 DAT ^c
Diazinon (4x)	Standard treatment	0.5	35	3	340	12	21
Diazinon (4x) incorporated	To place insecticide in anaerobic zone of soil.	2.0	50	5	370	12	43
Diazinon (4x [every 5 days before transplanting] and 4x after transplanting).	To build up diazinon-degrading microbes.	0.5	34	9	390	18	43
Diazinon + hyamine (4x)	Hyamine to suppress microbes.	0.5	37	59	36	5	23
Diazinon (3x), drain, and diazinon (1x)	Drainage to suppress microbes.	0.5	35	39	167	0	17
Diazinon (3x), drain, and diazinon + hyamine (1x)	To further suppress the microbes.	0.5	35	5	190	2	12
Dolmix (3x) and diazinon (1x)	To minimize the build-up of diazinon-degrading microbes.	0.0	26	5	6	0	0 ^d
Diazinon (3x) and Dolmix (1x)	Check	0.5	39	40	230	8	30
Dolmix (4x)	Check	0.0	31	4	5	0	0
No insecticide	Check	4.0	44	34	223	7	28

^aThe insecticides were applied at 2 kg/ha a.i. at 11, 35, 59, and 79 days after transplanting. ^bOn a scale of 0 to 5. The larger number means greater damage. ^cDays after transplanting. ^dThe plot suffered hopperburn later.

borers was as highly effective as it was in the other diazinon treated plots. Thus in spite of the presence of diazinon-degrading microbes in these plots, the diazinon treatments were still

effective in controlling pests other than the brown planthopper (Table 9). Plots that received more diazinon applications had greater populations of brown planthoppers and were the

Table 10. Insecticides tested on various insects at IRRI. (BP=Nilaparvata lugens, GL=Nephotettix impicticeps, SB=Chilo suppressalis, √=effective (50% or higher mortality), X=not effective, —=not tested.)

Insecticide	Topical application (0.04%)	Foliar spray (0.04%)		Rootdip treatment of seedlings (0.04%)	Applied to paddy water (2 kg/ha)		
	BP	BP	GL	BP	BP	GL	SB
Abar	√	X	√	—	X	√	√
Azinophos ethyl	√	√	√	—	X	X	X
Basrex	√	X	√	—	—	—	—
Bayrusil	—	X	√	—	X	√	X
BPMC	√	X	X	√	√	√	X
Bux 300	—	X	√	—	—	—	—
Carbamult	√	—	—	√	X	√	X
Carbaryl	X	√	√	—	X	√	X
Carbofuran	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Cartap	—	√	√	—	X	√ ^a	√
Birlane	X	—	—	—	X	√	√
Chlorphenamide	X	X	—	—	X	X	√
Chlorphenamide + MIPC	—	—	—	—	X	√	√
Diazinon	X	X	X	—	√	X	√
Dimethoate	X	X	√	√	—	—	—
Dursban	√	X	X	—	X	X	X
Dyfonate	—	—	—	—	√	X	X
FAC-40	X	X	√	—	—	—	—
Fenthion	X	X	√	—	—	—	√
Gardona	X	√	√	—	X	√	X
GS 13006	—	—	—	—	√	√	√
Imidan	X	X	√	X	X	X	√
Imidan + Dyfonate	—	—	—	—	X	√	—
K-57	—	X	√	—	—	—	—
K-673	—	—	—	—	X	√	X
K-1025	—	—	—	—	X	√	X
Lindane	X	X	X	—	X	X	√
Lindane ^b	—	—	—	—	√	X	X
Lindane + carbaryl	—	—	—	—	X	√	√
Lindane + Dimethoate	—	—	—	—	√	√	—
Lindane + mecarbam	—	—	—	—	X	√	—
Lindane + MIPC	—	—	—	—	√	√	—
Lindane + Promecarb	—	—	—	—	√	√	—
Lindane + Uden	—	—	—	—	√	√	√
Malathion	X	X	√	X	—	—	—
Metacrate	—	—	—	—	X	√	X
MC-2420	X	—	—	—	X	√	X
MIPC	√	X	√	√	√	√	—
Monocrotophos	√	√	√	√	√	X	X
N-2596	—	—	—	—	X	√	X
NC-6897	√	—	—	√	√	√	—
Phosalone	√	X	√	—	—	—	—
Phosphamidon	X	X	√	√	X	√	X
Quickbal	√	X	√	√	—	—	—
S-6626	—	X	√	—	X	X	√
Talcord	X	X	√	X	—	—	—
Telothion	—	X	√	—	—	—	—
Tsumacide + carbaryl	—	—	—	—	√	√	—
Uden	—	—	—	—	√	√	X
Vamidothion	X	√	√	√	—	—	—

^a 4 kg/ha. ^b Effervescent granules, 9.4%.

first to suffer hopperburn. But even the treatments designed to prevent the microbial build-up suffered severe hopperburn later (fig. 11). Also, the plots that had received only one diazinon treatment suffered hopperburn within a few days after the insecticidal application. These data suggest that the occurrence of diazinon-resistant strains of the brown planthopper was more important than microbial degradation in rendering diazinon ineffective.

Insecticides

About 40 insecticides were evaluated for control of the green leafhopper, the brown planthopper, and the striped rice borer.

In laboratory tests, the insecticides were sprayed directly on the insects from a Potter's spray tower, sprayed on rice plants on which the test insects were later caged, applied to the irrigation water of potted plants, or used for dipping the roots of rice seedlings. The systemic effectiveness of the insecticides in the latter two treatments was evaluated by caging test insects on the leaf sheaths or leaf blades of the treated plants. The detailed techniques for these experiments were described in previous annual reports.

Many insecticides effectively controlled the green leafhopper but few controlled the brown planthopper (Table 10). Two new compounds appear particularly promising for controlling the brown planthopper: carbofuran and GS-13006. Both also were effective against the green leafhopper and the striped rice borer. Two other compounds, cartap and chlorphenamide, were highly effective against the striped rice borer but not against the green leafhopper and the brown planthopper.

When applied to the paddy water as granules, insecticides are generally more effective and longer lasting than when applied as foliar sprays. Granular insecticides are, however, more bulky and more costly than emulsifiable concentrates or wettable powders.

One possible alternative is to develop a highly concentrated liquid formulation that can be applied to the paddy water. In our previous studies, such formulations had a short residual life probably because they floated on

11. In an experiment in which the development of diazinon-degrading microbes was minimized all plots treated with diazinon had hopperburn, indicating that degradation of diazinon was not the only cause of its ineffectiveness against brown planthoppers. IRRI 1970.

the water surface where they were broken down by sunlight and heat. Also, because the formulations floated they tended to drift more than granules.

A formulation that sinks in water and forms a thin film on the soil surface should not have these problems. We tested such formulations of diazinon and GS-13006 and the results were encouraging (Table 11).

The regulated (slow or fast) release of insecticide in granular formulations can provide long-lasting control. Although several such formulations have been tried, so far the results of slow- or fast-release formulations have not been quite satisfactory. On the other hand, the use of effervescent granular formulations have occasionally improved insecticidal effectiveness considerably. Effervescent granules may have an additional advantage: they release carbon dioxide in the rice environment which may increase the photosynthesis of the rice plant.

In field experiments, brown planthoppers were the most predominant species so the overall field performance of the selected compounds was greatly influenced by their ability to control brown planthoppers.

Foliar sprays. Nineteen insecticides were field tested as 0.05 percent foliar sprays. These were applied to field plots of IR8 15, 30, 55, 77, and 90 days after transplanting. In the first two applications, 900 liters/ha of spray material were used but in later treatments 1,100 to 1,275 liters/ha were used. Plots receiving no insecticidal treatment constituted the control.

All compounds tested provided the rice

Table 11. Selected data from greenhouse evaluation of insecticides applied to the paddy water at 2 kg/ha a.i. for the control of *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix impicticeps*, and *Chilo suppressalis*. IRRI, 1970.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a (%)	Mortality (%)							
		N. lugens			N. impicticeps			C. suppressalis	
		1 DAT ^b	5 DAT ^b	10 DAT ^b	1 DAT ^b	10 DAT ^b	20 DAT ^b	7 DAT ^b	14 DAT ^b
Carbofuran	10 G	100	92	97 ^c	100	100	95	47	44
Diazinon									
A3721 BP4	30 ES ^d	98	25	2	88	38	32	75	42
A3721 P3	30 ES	90	65	5	96	52	37	78	64
A3721 BP4	30 ES	82	52	3	96	75	10	97	64
A3721 P3	30 ES ^d	76	28	10	92	53	24	95	65
GA 428	14 G ^e	55	40	2	80	59	32	87	71
GS 13006									
A3741 BP2	30 ES ^d	95	92	30	96	100	96	34	6
A3741 P1	30 ES ^d	88	72	27	78	92	80	47	11
A3471 P1	30 ES	76	70	20	88	92	85	49	2
A3411 Mg. 1	30 ES	8	12	2	93	100	76	18	0
Lindane+Uden	6+5 G	95	85	39	100	63	71	72	64
Lindane+Carbamult	6+6 G	72	25	2	100	68	52	58	57
N-2596	10 G	40	18	8	100	100	62	2	12

^aG=granular; ES=emulsifiable solution. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cAt 15 days after treatment mortality was 38%. ^dHeavier than water. ^eSlow release on corn cob.

crop with significant protection against the whorl maggot, but carbofuran, monocrotophos, C17475, and Bayrusil were the most effective. The incidence of stem borers, as evidenced by dead heart and white head formations, was comparatively low in all plots but significantly lower in several treatment plots than in the untreated control (Table 12).

The overall population of the brown planthopper was lower in plots treated with carbofuran, Bux 300, and MIPC than in other treatments. The residual period of all insecticides was rather low, however, and the populations of adult brown planthoppers in the treated plots were statistically similar at or beyond 10 days after treatment (Table 13). The nymphal

Table 12. Effect of 0.5% insecticidal spray applied 15, 30, 55, 77, and 90 days after transplanting (DAT) on rice pest control. IRRI 1970 dry season.

Insecticide	Formulation (%)	Whorl maggot damage ^a	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Hopperburned area (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
		25 DAT	70 DAT	98 DAT	105 DAT	105 DAT
C-10015	50 WP	2.0	2.3	1.5	12	4.65
Carbofuran	75 WP	0.5	0.5	0.3	7	4.62
Bux 300	30 EC	1.0	1.7	0.7	3	4.16
MIPC	50 WP	1.5	3.0	1.9	13	3.41
Tsumacide	50 WP	2.0	2.6	2.0	33	3.16
Carbamult	50 WP	2.0	3.8	1.9	8	3.09
Bayer 5546	50 EC	1.5	1.9	1.0	42	3.02
Zolone	35 EC	3.0	4.8	2.5	32	2.73
C-17018	50 WP	1.5	2.4	1.8	33	2.46
Kilval	40 EC	1.0	3.5	1.5	27	2.20
Z-8797	50 WP	1.0	3.0	1.9	28	2.19
Monocrotophos	60 WP	0.5	1.0	0.9	36	2.03
C-17475	45 WP	0.5	2.8	1.9	57	1.52
C-8353	50 WP	1.5	3.6	4.2	75	1.06
Gardona	75 WP	2.0	1.8	1.5	75	0.94
Cytrolane	25 EC	1.0	1.6	2.7	82	0.89
Bayrusil	25 EC	1.0	2.5	2.3	96	0.80
Hoe-2960	40 EC	1.5	2.0	<i>b</i>	99	0.13
K-57	25 EC	2.5	3.9	<i>b</i>	100	0.05
Control	—	4.0	3.7	2.2	27	2.75

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number means greater damage. ^bHopperburn.

Table 13. Effect of 0.5% insecticidal sprays applied at 14-day intervals for brown planthopper control. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Insecticide	Formulation ^a (%)	Adults ^b (no./hill)				Nymphs ^b (no./hill)				Hopper- burned area (%) ^c
		74 DAT ^c	83 DAT ^c	88 DAT ^c	Total	79 DAT ^c	83 DAT ^c	88 DAT ^c	Total	
C-10015	50 WP	1	3	4	10	2	7	11	26	12
Carbofuran	75 WP	1	1	2	4	1	1	5	9	7
Bux 300	30 EC	1	1	2	6	2	1	4	11	3
MIPC	50 WP	1	3	1	6	2	4	4	12	13
Tsumacide	50 WP	1	8	2	11	1	14	13	31	33
Carbamult	50 WP	1	4	4	10	2	10	9	25	8
Bayer 5546	50 EC	1	1	5	9	1	6	18	28	42
Zolone	35 EC	1	5	6	14	6	10	27	50	32
C-17018	50 WP	1	2	7	12	4	4	13	25	33
Kilval	40 EC	1	3	5	10	2	7	17	35	27
Z-8797	50 WP	2	3	3	11	13	5	8	38	28
Monocrotophos	50 WP	1	3	6	14	3	14	25	54	36
C-17475	45 WP	2	13	5	23	7	41	7	69	57
C-8353	50 WP	2	10	5	19	5	28	18	60	75
Gardona	75 WP	1	22	6	31	6	74	16	103	75
Cytrolane	25 EC	2	6	6	16	4	20	19	51	82
Bayrusil	25 EC	1	16	7	27	4	45	19	79	96
Hoe 2960	40 EC	3	25	3	36	33	83	13	143	99
K-57	25 EC	2	28	3	36	3	59	6	83	100
Control	—	1	2	6	10	2	2	20	31	28

^aWP=wettable powder; EC=emulsifiable concentrate. ^bPopulations sampled at 61 and 67 days after transplanting, although significantly different in various treatments, were generally low. ^cDays after transplanting.

population in different treatment plots is a more definite criterion of an insecticide's effectiveness than the adult population because the nymphs must survive on treated plants, while the adults can migrate to other plants. None of the treatments eradicated the nymphal population. Possibly the foliar sprays did not reach the base of the plants where the nymphs generally feed but it also is possible that none of the insecticides were adequately translocated in the plant tissues.

The population of brown planthoppers was so large in this experiment that several plots had severe hopperburn (Table 13). The plots treated with carbofuran, Bux 300, MIPC and Carbamult, however, were only slightly damaged along the borders. This damage was caused by insects migrating from adjacent plots. The untreated control plot had a low population of brown planthoppers and suffered less hopperburn than several other treated plots, most probably because of differences in crop density among different treatments since the control plots were sparse in growth and therefore brown planthoppers were less likely to build up.

Applications to paddy water. Ten insecticides were applied to IR8 at 2 kg/ha a.i. every 20 days

from 15 days after transplanting to the harvest of the crop.

All compounds provided significant protection from the whorl maggot. Diazinon, carbofuran, Sapecron, Bayrusil, and Z-8797 were most effective. Imidan was the least effective (Table 14). The incidence of stem borers, as measured by dead hearts and white heads, was rather low in this experiment. The population of brown planthoppers however was very high and all plots treated with diazinon, Sapecron, and Bayrusil had hopperburn. Except for carbofuran-treated plots, about 15 percent of which had hopperburn along the borders, all treated plots suffered severe hopperburn.

The population of brown planthoppers in the untreated control plot was often lower than in any of the treated plots, primarily because the plants in the control plot were damaged by various other insect pests and had much lower foliar density than the treated plots. During the early stages of crop growth, the populations of the brown planthopper adults and nymphs were consistently lower in plots treated with carbofuran, Sapecron, Z-8797, and C-10015. The carbofuran-treated plots remained protected against the brown planthoppers through-

Table 14. Effect of insecticides applied to paddy water at 2 kg/ha a.i. at 15, 38, 68, and 89 days after transplanting (DAT) for insect pest control in IR8. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Treatment	Whorl maggot damage ^a 30 DAT	Dead hearts (%) 78 DAT	White heads (%) 110 DAT	Brown planthoppers (no./hill)						Virus (%) 110 DAT	Hopper-burned area (%) 115 DAT	Grain yield (t/ha) 115 DAT
				67 DAT		84 DAT		110 DAT				
				Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs			
Diazinon	0.0	0.3	<i>b</i>	5	2	26	116	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>	100	0.38
Carbofuran	0.0	0.0	0.0	3	1	2	4	3	3	33	15	3.49
Imidan	3.0	0.5	1.2	5	2	15	34	1	2	39	62	1.56
Sapcon	0.5	0.7	0.9	4	1	16	58	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>	13	100	1.31
Bayrusil	0.5	0.1	<i>b</i>	7	2	20	52	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i>	100	0.19
Gardona	2.5	0.7	2.0	5	2	3	13	1	2	36	65	1.70
Z-8797	0.5	1.2	2.5	3	1	3	6	1	1	42	37	2.09
C-10015	2.5	0.7	1.4	4	1	14	50	1	1	34	94	1.42
Monocrotophos	2.0	0.2	0.4	5	1	21	48	1	2	21	51	2.61
Control	4.0	1.2	1.6	2	1	2	6	1	1	40	53	2.28

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bHopperburned.

out the crop's growth, but the other plots suffered hopperburn later. Although the plots treated with monocrotophos had more adults than the other plots, they had consistently fewer nymphs. This indicated that the insecticide was highly effective in controlling the nymphs. Carbofuran, Z-8797, and monocrotophos were most effective in controlling the brown planthoppers. Large populations of brown planthoppers and a high incidence of grassy stunt virus adversely affected the yield of all the treated plots and even the most effective treatment (carbofuran) produced a yield of only 3.4 t/ha. This was about two to three times higher than the yields of most other treated plots, however (Table 14).

In another field experiment, several insecticides were further evaluated as granules applied

to the paddy water. All were highly effective in protecting the crop against the whorl maggot and stem borers (Table 15). Carbofuran and lindane + Unden were most effective against brown planthoppers and produced the highest yields. Gamma-BHC + MIPC, Dolmix, and S-6626 + MIPC were almost as effective but near harvest the edges of plots treated with these chemicals suffered hopperburn primarily because insects migrated from adjacent plots. The treatments of diazinon, gamma-BHC + BPMC, gamma-BHC + disulfoton, and gamma-BHC + Carbamult were not effective in controlling brown planthoppers.

The effectiveness of various insecticidal mixtures was evaluated in an experiment conducted during the dry season of 1970. Each of these insecticides was applied at 2 kg/ha a.i. every 20

Table 15. Effect of combinations of insecticides applied to the paddy water for rice pest control. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Treatment	Whorl maggot damage ^a 32 DAT ^b	Dead hearts (%) 69 DAT ^b	White heads (%) 108 DAT ^b	Brown planthoppers (no./hill)				Virus (%) 108 DAT ^b	Hopper-burned area (%) 104 DAT ^b	Grain yield (t/ha) 108 DAT ^b
				77 DAT ^b		105 DAT ^b				
				Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs			
Diazinon	0.5	0.7	0.5 ^c	42	29	<i>d</i>	<i>d</i>	5	99	0.43
Carbofuran	0.5	0.0	0.0	5	2	6	4	10	3	6.33
Gamma-BHC+MIPC	0.5	0.5	0.7	4	3	3	3	9	4	5.94
Gamma-BHC+BPMC	0.5	1.2	0.7	5	3	6	3	6	49	4.74
Gamma-BHC+Unden	0.5	0.3	0.3	5	1	1	1	9	1	6.15
Gamma-BHC+disulfoton	0.5	1.4	0.5	13	3	12 ^c	3 ^c	5	91	3.59
Gamma-BHC+Carbamult	0.5	0.2	0.5	12	9	<i>d</i>	<i>d</i>	6	100	3.30
Dolmix	0.5	0.7	0.4	7	4	2	2	8	6	5.86
S 6626+MIPC	0.5	0.1	1.0	7	2	4	2	3	60	5.58
Control	4.0	5.4	1.6	8	7	5	2	12	78	2.11

^aOn scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cBased on one replication. Others hopper-burned. ^dHopperburned.

days. All the mixtures were highly effective against the whorl maggot and stem borers, but they differed significantly in their effectiveness in controlling the brown planthopper (Table 16). At 50 and 62 days after transplanting the population of brown planthoppers was relatively low, although it differed significantly among various treatments. The population of brown planthoppers in all plots increased by 76 days after transplanting and was particularly large in plots treated with diazinon, gamma-BHC + disulfoton, and gamma-BHC + carbaryl. At 85 days after transplanting (3 days after the fourth application) it declined in all plots including the untreated controls.

Most treatments were effective against brown planthoppers. The decline in population in the control plots was probably caused by the insecticidal treatment in the adjoining plots and by the migration of planthoppers from the control to the comparatively insect-free plots treated with other insecticides. Subsequently, the brown planthoppers increased rapidly in several of the treated plots and 26 days after the last application the plots treated with diazinon, gamma-BHC + carbaryl, or gamma-BHC + disulfoton had severe hopperburn. The plots treated with carbofuran or gamma-BHC + MIPC had slight hopperburn along the borders.

In general the treatments that controlled

brown planthoppers best also produced the maximum rice yields (Table 16). Except for the diazinon plots in which about 90 percent of the crop had hopperburn, all treatments produced significantly greater yields than the untreated plots. The highest yields were obtained in plots treated with gamma-BHC + Promecarb, gamma-BHC + MIPC, gamma-BHC + Uden, carbofuran, or Dolmix.

Selected compounds from this experiment were further evaluated in the wet season, along with Dursban + Uden and S-6626 + Uden. All compounds were highly effective in controlling the rice whorl maggot. The incidence of stem borers in these plots was so low that no records of dead hearts or white heads were taken. The population of brown planthoppers was high and differed significantly in different treatments. The plots treated with carbofuran, Dolmix, or gamma-BHC + MIPC had lower planthopper populations than other treated plots. A severe typhoon brought several days of strong rains which caused the plots to overflow, washing away the insecticide. This caused erratic data on hopperburn and yields.

Imidan is highly effective in controlling the common insect pests of rice. During 1970, its effectiveness when applied to the paddy water was tested.

Imidan was not effective against the whorl

Table 16. Effect of applying insecticides to paddy water 17, 38, 62, and 82 days after transplanting (DAT) for pest control in IR8. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Treatment	Whorl maggot damage ^a	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Brown planthoppers (no./hill)								Virus (%)	Hopper-burned area (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
				50 DAT		62 DAT		76 DAT		85 DAT				
				Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs			
Carbofuran	0.5	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.7	0.1	0.8	0.3	2.4	0.1	1.2	14	3	6.16
Diazinon	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.1	1.3	0.3	6.2	2.9	14.0	0.5	3.2	9	88	3.03
Gamma-BHC + Promecarb	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.5	0.4	1.1	0.2	0.5	13	0	6.69
Gamma-BHC + Uden	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2	1.3	0.0	1.3	0.5	0.9	0.1	0.5	21	0	5.76
Gamma-BHC + MIPC	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.6	0.0	0.8	1.0	2.7	0.1	0.7	20	1	6.02
S-6626 + Uden	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.1	0.7	21	0	6.23
Gamma-BHC + carbaryl	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.3	1.9	0.1	2.2	2.6	7.9	1.1	1.5	14	51	4.80
Gamma-BHC + disulfoton	1.0	0.8	0.0	0.1	0.6	0.0	1.5	2.3	5.4	0.6	1.9	14	16	5.55
Dolmix	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.6	1.2	0.1	0.8	15	0	6.15
Control	4.5	4.1	1.1	0.3	1.4	0.2	2.2	2.3	5.7	0.3	1.1	18	0	4.35

^aOn scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage.

Table 17. Effect of applying different granular insecticides to paddy water every 20 days for brown planthopper control in IR8. IRRI 1970 wet season.

Treatment	Formulation (%)	Rate (kg/ha)	Whorl maggot damage ^a		Brown planthoppers (no./hill) 69 DAT ^b		Hopper-burned area (%) 70 DAT ^b
			36 DAT ^b	53 DAT ^b	Adults	Nymphs	
Imidan ^c	5	1.0	3.5	4.0	4	41	11
Imidan ^c	5	1.5	3.5	3.5	3	38	0
Imidan ^c	5	2.0	3.5	3.5	4	59	33
Imidan ^d	5	2.0	3.5	3.5	3	48	25
Imidan ^e	5	2.0	3.5	3.5	7	13	6
Dyfonate	5	2.0	0.5	0.5	25	249	66
Dyfonate+Imidan	5+5	2.0+2.0	0.5	0.5	17	152	86
Gamma-BHC+MIPC	6+4	2.0+2.0	0.5	0.5	8	145	20
Carbofuran ^d	10	2.0	0.0	0.0	39	38	1
Control	—	—	3.5	4.0	6	36	0

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cFast release. ^dSlow release. ^eSlow release, applied every 40 days.

Table 18. Effect of paddy water application of gamma-BHC and MIPC 24, 44, 64, and 84 days after transplanting (DAT) for pest control in IR8. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Treatment	Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Whorl maggot damage ^a	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Brown planthoppers (no./hill)				Virus (%)	Hopper-burned area (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
					55 DAT		71 DAT				
					43 DAT	45 DAT	80 DAT	80 DAT			
Diazinon	2	0.5	0.3	0.7	1.0	1.6	1.1	29.8	2	81	4.10
Gamma-BHC+MIPC	2+1	0.5	0.0	0.8	0.1	0.1	0.5	2.1	4	11	7.13
Gamma-BHC+MIPC	2+1.5	0.5	0.2	0.9	0.3	0.2	0.2	1.2	7	5	7.47
Gamma-BHC+MIPC	2+2	0.5	0.0	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.1	1.0	5	1	7.43
No insecticide	—	4.0	9.8	2.0	1.4	2.2	0.8	6.2	8	66	3.20

^aOn scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage.

Table 19. Effect of applying carbofuran to the paddy water at different rates and frequencies for pest control in IR8. IRRI, 1970 dry season.

Rate (kg/ha a.i.)	Whorl maggot damage ^a 40 DAT ^b	Dead hearts (%) 65 DAT ^b	White heads (%) 108 DAT ^b	Brown planthoppers (no./hill) 84 DAT ^b		Virus (%) 108 DAT ^b	Hopperburned area (%) 104 DAT ^b	Grain yield (t/ha) 108 DAT ^b
				Adults	Nymphs			
<i>Carbofuran at 12, 33, 54 and 74 DAT^b</i>								
0.5	1.0	1.1	2.5	2.4	3.2	22	5	3.83
1.0	0.5	0.5	0.8	1.9	2.1	20	5	4.83
1.5	0.5	0.1	0.3	1.6	1.9	16	1	5.54
2.0	0.5	0.0	0.3	2.3	1.1	19	1	5.52
<i>Carbofuran at 12, 42, and 72 DAT^b</i>								
0.5	1.0	0.9	2.0	2.4	3.4	20	3	3.69
1.0	0.5	1.9	1.9	2.0	3.1	17	12	3.84
1.5	0.5	0.7	1.1	2.6	3.0	18	2	5.18
2.0	0.5	1.2	1.5	2.1	2.1	19	1	5.04
<i>Carbofuran at 12 and 62 DAT^b</i>								
0.5	0.5	2.8	3.9	2.4	3.1	22	6	3.44
1.0	1.0	2.7	3.6	4.0	6.4	23	5	3.06
1.5	0.5	1.2	1.9	2.8	5.2	20	2	4.46
2.0	0.5	1.9	0.6	1.5	2.5	18	0	4.95
<i>Diazinon every 20 days</i>								
2.0	0.5	0.7	—	3.7	4.0	—	100	0.41
<i>Control</i>								
	3.5	2.4	3.4	2.2	3.1	23	5	3.25

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bDays after transplanting.

maggot (Table 17). However, the whorl maggot was effectively controlled by Dyfonate, Dyfonate + Imidan, gamma-BHC + MIPC, and carbofuran. Neither Imidan nor Dyfonate was effective against the brown planthoppers. The population of brown planthoppers was larger in the Dyfonate-treated plot than in any other plot, including the untreated controls. Most of the treated plots later had severe hopperburn. The carbofuran plot had lower planthopper population and did not suffer hopperburn, but when the crop was nearing maturity, a severe typhoon damaged the crop and no yield data could be taken.

Gamma-BHC + MIPC. Gamma-Mipcin (a 1:1 granular formulation of gamma-BHC + MIPC) is highly effective for controlling common pests of rice. Gamma-BHC controls the rice whorl maggot and stem borers, while MIPC is effective against brown planthoppers. An experiment was conducted to find out whether the rate of MIPC in this combination could be reduced to lower the cost of the insecticide.

The population of the brown planthopper was larger in the diazinon-treated and the untreated control plots than in plots treated with any rate of MIPC (Table 18). Although there were significant differences in the planthopper population among the MIPC-treated plots, only the plot receiving 1 kg/ha of MIPC suffered

hopperburn. The untreated control and diazinon-treated plots had severe hopperburn. All treated plots had significantly lower incidence of whorl maggots, dead hearts, and white heads than the untreated controls.

All plots treated with gamma-BHC + MIPC, irrespective of rate, produced significantly higher yields than the diazinon-treated and untreated control plots. There were no statistical differences among the yields of the plots that received gamma-BHC + MIPC.

At present, at 2 kg/ha a.i. carbofuran is the most promising insecticide for rice. During 1970, several experiments were conducted to determine appropriate formulations, rates, and intervals of applications. In the dry season carbofuran, when used at 1.5 or 2.0 kg/ha a.i. at 20- or 30-day intervals, was highly effective in controlling common rice pests. It was equally effective at 1 kg/ha when used every 20 days but was less effective at lower rates or when used at longer intervals (Table 19).

In an experiment in the wet season, 0.5 or 1 kg/ha a.i. of carbofuran was applied at 20-, 30-, 50-, or 90-day intervals. The 3-percent fast-release granular formulation that was used in this experiment apparently was not as effective as the 10-percent slow-release granules used in the dry-season tests. This was evident in the poor control of the rice whorl maggot (Table 20). The incidence of stem borers, as

Table 20. Effect of carbofuran (3%, fast release, granular) applied to the paddy water at different rates and frequencies for pest control in IR22. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

Application time (days after transplanting)	Whorl maggot damage ^a			Dead hearts (%)	Brown planthoppers (no./hill)				Hopperburned area (%) 95 DAT ^b
	25 DAT ^b	42 DAT ^b	53 DAT ^b		71 DAT ^b	77 DAT ^b		95 DAT ^b	
				Adults		Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs	
<i>0.5 kg/ha a.i.</i>									
14, 38, 56, 77	3.0	5.0	2.0	0.3	11	19	6	68	17
14, 50, 77	3.0	5.0	4.0	0.1	12	15	2	53	50
14, 55	3.5	5.0	4.0	0.1	<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	3	33	12
14, 60	3.0	5.0	4.0	0.3	<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	3	38	32
<i>1 kg/ha a.i.</i>									
14, 38, 56, 77	2.5	4.0	1.0	0.0	11	15	6	82	15
14, 50, 77	3.0	4.0	3.0	0.2	14	24	3	99	40
14, 55	3.0	4.0	3.5	0.5	<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	1	43	32
14, 60	3.0	4.0	2.5	0.9	<i>c</i>	<i>c</i>	2	87	26
<i>2 kg/ha a.i.</i>									
14, 38, 56, 77	2.0	3.0	2.0	0.6	5	6	1	33	0
No insecticide	4.0	5.0	5.0	0.2	10	14	1	31	29

^aOn scale of 0 to 5. Larger number indicates greater damage. ^bDays after transplanting. ^cNot sampled.

Table 21. Incidence of grassy stunt virus in rice plots treated every 20 days with different granular formulations of carbofuran. IRRI, 1970.

Formulation	Rate (kg/ha)	Grassy stunt (%)	
		Dry season 45 DAT ^a	Wet season 55 DAT ^a
10% slow	0.5	31	54
3% slow	0.5	31	51
10% fast	0.5	35	37
3% fast	0.5	32	43
3% extruded	0.5	34	41
3% oil	0.5	31	42
7.5% compressed	0.5	32	46
3% fast	2.0	32	50
10% slow	2.0	34	48
No insecticide	—	33	38

^a Days after transplanting.

shown by the formation of dead hearts, was too low to permit the evaluation of the various treatments. None of the treatments were highly effective against brown planthoppers and almost all plots had substantial hopperburn. The plots treated with 2 kg/ha a.i. every 20 days initially had no hopperburn but later the brown planthoppers which killed other plots migrated to them in large numbers and destroyed them as well.

Generally the carbofuran treatments did not protect the crop adequately from the grassy stunt virus which is transmitted by the brown planthopper. During the year, two different experiments were conducted with seven different granular formulations of carbofuran. Unfortunately, both these experiments were so severely

Table 22. Effect of applying insecticides at 2 kg/ha a.i. to paddy water 10, 30, 50, and 70 days after transplanting (DAT) for pest control in IR8. Maligaya, Philippines, 1970 wet season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a (%)	Dead hearts (%)	White heads (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
	20 DAT	55 DAT	102 DAT	107 DAT
Lindane+MIPC	11	1.9	4.3	3.44
Carbofuran	3	1.3	0.9	3.17
Lindane+Uden	21	1.3	3.7	3.10
Dolmix	12	1.6	3.8	3.10
Lindane+BPMC	37	1.1	4.4	2.97
S-6626	15	1.1	5.3	2.96
Lindane+Promecarb	33	1.7	4.3	2.78
Diazinon	15	4.8	6.4	2.53
Lindane	70	1.7	4.6	1.91
Control	100	21.6	5.6	1.22

^a Percent of hills showing damage.

affected by grassy stunt virus (Table 21) that meaningful data on other insects could not be obtained.

Cooperative trials. In addition to evaluating granular insecticides for pest control at IRRI, we tested promising ones at the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center and the Visayas Rice Experiment Station.

At Maligaya (Table 22) all chemicals decreased the damage from whorl maggots. Lindane was initially not as effective as the others. The low dead-heart counts in the treated plots indicated that all chemicals controlled the stem borers, but diazinon was the least effective. Carbofuran was the only insecticide that significantly decreased the percentage of white heads below that of the control. All insecticide treatments improved the yield when compared with the control. The best yields were obtained in the plots treated with lindane + MIPC and in the plots treated with carbofuran; the poorest yield was in the plots treated with lindane alone. The four highest yielding insecticide treatments also did well at IRRI.

At the Visayas station (Table 23), diazinon-treated plots were free from whorl-maggot damage. Several other insecticides also prevented much damage. The incidence of dead hearts was low and only plots treated with S-6626 and carbofuran had significantly fewer dead hearts than the untreated control plots. All insecticide treatments prevented some white heads, but carbofuran was the best. Although insecticide application increased the yield, there were almost no significant differences in yield among the treated plots.

Yields at the Visayas station were better than at Maligaya. A suspected infection of tungro virus and damage by insects other than the whorl maggot and stem borers may have reduced yields at Maligaya.

Ecology of the brown planthopper

We studied the density and age structure of *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) in relation to the age of the rice crop, variety of rice, and insecticidal treatment in a field where IR8, IR20, and IR22

Table 23. Effect of applying insecticides at 2 kg/ha a.i. to paddy water 10, 30, 50, and 70 days after transplanting (DAT) for pest control in IR8. Visayas, Philippines, 1970 wet season.

Insecticide	Whorl maggot damage ^a (%)		Dead hearts (%)		White heads (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	20 DAT	56 DAT	99 DAT	104 DAT	99 DAT	104 DAT	
Lindane+Uden	1.0	1.9	0.3	5.37			
S-6626	1.0	1.5	1.3	5.34			
Lindane+BPMC	1.0	2.2	0.7	5.28			
Lindane+Promecarb	2.5	2.8	0.4	5.25			
Lindane	2.0	2.2	1.8	5.23			
Carbofuran	2.5	1.5	0.0	5.15			
Dolmix	1.0	2.5	0.5	5.11			
Lindane+MIPC	1.0	2.9	0.8	5.05			
Diazinon	0.0	2.2	1.1	4.81			
Control	4.0	3.7	4.0	4.17			

^aOn a scale of 0 to 5. Larger number means greater damage.

were being grown with no insecticide or with 2 kg/ha of Dolmix applied at 6, 26, and 46 days after transplanting.

Each week we collected all nymphs and adults from 10 hills in each of six plots. A mouth aspirator was used to capture the planthoppers. Only healthy hills were sampled because grassy-stunt infection was high. The number of tillers on each hill sampled was counted. A few specimens of *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) were found but they were counted as *N. lugens* because of the difficulty of distinguishing between the lower instars of these two species.

The results from sampling a plot of IR22 that received no insecticide are shown in figure 12. The curves for the mean number per hill and for the mean number (total) per tiller do not agree completely because the number of tillers per 10-hill sample varied. The mean number of planthoppers per tiller is the best estimate of population density in relation to the amount of damage the insects are doing.

In the untreated plot (fig. 12), two major peaks in the population occurred later than 80 days after transplanting. A high number resulted when there was a large number of nymphs in the population. But hopperburn did not occur in this crop. The number of adults was low when the number of nymphs was high, but the number of adults became greater as the number of nymphs decreased, especially in a treated plot of IR22 (fig. 13). The peaks in the population and the synchronous changes in

the number of nymphs and adults suggest that at least three generations per crop occurred. There was some uniformity in the time of occurrence of the population peaks in the IR22 plots.

These facts suggest that if chemical control measures were carefully timed, they could inhibit subsequent population growth. They also suggest that the composition of the population must be considered when changes in insect numbers resulting from insecticide application are measured. The population in the untreated plot was larger than that in the treated plot during the last part of the crop period, despite the higher virus infection and, consequently, the poorer stand of the untreated

12. Change in planthopper density per hill and per tiller in an untreated plot of IR22. IIRRI, 1970 wet season.

13. Change in planthopper density in a Dolmix-treated plot of IR22. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

crop. Apparently the presence of infected hills in the crop did not prevent a high rate of reproduction or high nymphal survival on the healthy hills. It is unlikely that the insecticide lowered the population in the treated plot because the last application of Dolmix was made as early as 46 days after transplanting.

In the treated and untreated IR8 plots (fig. 14) the over-all population density was much lower than on IR22. The reason is not clear. IR8 is considered susceptible to the brown planthopper,

so a high population would be expected. IR8 had the highest virus infection and it gave the lowest yield of the three varieties, but this does not necessarily explain the low population of planthoppers. The number of planthoppers was high at about the same time after transplanting as in the IR22 plots (fig. 12 and 13) again because of a large number of nymphs. The over-all abundance of the planthoppers in the treated plot of IR8 was similar to that in the untreated plot.

In treated and untreated plots of IR20 (fig. 14) the population remained low during the sampling period. Even though these plots had a good stand, the number of planthoppers did not increase much. Nevertheless the same general trend of change was evident in the number of nymphs and adults, as was found in the other varieties. A relatively high density occurred around 90 days after transplanting. Applying Dolmix early in the growing period did not appear to affect the planthopper abundance later on.

In another experiment, IR8 was grown in

14. Change in planthopper density in Dolmix-treated and untreated plots of IR8 and IR20. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

single rows between double rows of a selection of IR8 x Mudgo. Diazinon was applied at 4 and 24 days after transplanting, and lindane at 84 days after transplanting, both at 2 kg/ha. Each week all the planthoppers on 10 healthy hills of IR8 were collected. The population on IR8 reached a peak at 70 and at 95 days after transplanting (fig. 15). The two peaks were directly associated with increases in the number of nymphs and decreases in the number of adults, which suggests the existence of two generations. Diazinon may have been a cause of the high population. Most of the IR8 plants were killed by the brown planthoppers during the last part of the growing period.

A selection of IR8 x Mudgo, grown in a solid block, was sampled weekly. Planthoppers were collected from 10 healthy hills. Diazinon was applied once, 5 days after transplanting. Because of a high infection of grassy stunt, the field was plowed up at 46 days after transplanting. Figure 16 shows the data that were obtained. The relationship between the number of nymphs and number of adults in figure 16 is different from that in figures 12 to 15. The adults, which originated outside the crop, produced only a few nymphs in the crop. The selection could be considered resistant to the brown planthopper since the insect did not multiply effectively on it.

Biological control of stem borers

Sturmiopsis inferens. A parasite of stem borers, *Sturmiopsis inferens* Townsend, has been reared in the laboratory and released in the field previously (1966-68 Annual Reports). More releases were made in 1969, and efforts to recover the parasite in the field continued in 1970. Although some parasitization occurred in the greenhouse, the parasite apparently failed to become established on Luzon Island. After releasing gravid females at six locations in Luzon no parasitized stem borers were found except at the IRRI farm. And, at the IRRI farm, less than 1 percent of the stem borers collected on two occasions were parasitized. In six other collections at the IRRI farm no parasitized stem borers were found. Presumably conditions were not favorable for the parasite's survival, although

15. Change in planthopper density on IR8 grown between rows of IR8 x Mudgo, a brown planthopper-resistant selection. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

perhaps too few were released to allow them to become established. No further work with this parasite is anticipated.

Other parasites. A chalcid from Africa, *Pediobius furvus* (Gah.), which is a pupal parasite, was imported but we were able to keep the population alive in the laboratory for only a short period. An introduced egg parasite, *Trichogramma fasciatum*, was reared through several

16. Change in planthopper density on IR8 x Mudgo, a brown planthopper-resistant selection. IRRI, 1970 wet season.

generations, but the culture was eventually lost. An unsuccessful attempt was made to culture the braconid, *Macrocentrus turkestanicus* Telenga, on *Sesamia inferens* (Walker).

Another braconid, *Apanteles flavipes* (Cameron), was imported from India. We reared it for two generations on *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker). Parasitization in the laboratory varied from 9 to 18 percent. When it was released in a greenhouse cage, no parasitization occurred. The culture was lost at the end of 1970

because not enough host borers were available.

The potential value of these parasites in the Philippines is still largely unknown because none of them were released in the field. Difficulties in laboratory rearing and in providing adequate host populations have forced a reappraisal of the research program. The direct release of imported parasites is being considered as a means of rapidly screening parasites for the biological control of stem borers in the Philippines.

Rice Production Training and Research

Six-month training program

Since 1964, 177 trainees from 20 countries have graduated from the IRRI 6-month rice production training program. This year 34 trainees from 12 countries attended the annual 6-month rice production training program.

The training program was reorganized during the year but continues to stress current rice science and technology, production and diagnostic skills, applied research technology, and the fundamentals of communication.

The practical examination which covers the identification of diseases, insects, and nutritional disorders of rice remains an important feature of the program. The practical examination given the first day of the program this year resulted in a class average score of 37.4 percent with a range of 9 to 95.5 percent. Results of this examination continue to show that the average "change agent" must improve his technical competence before he can properly assist farmers in growing the new high-yielding rices. The average score of 37.4 percent which is about 10 points higher than the average score of previous groups does, however, indicate that the rice production training programs conducted in the countries providing trainees to IRRI are effective in improving the competence of rice extension workers.

A similar practical examination given at the end of the course resulted in an average score of 81.4 percent.

Short courses

In October and November, two 2-week rice production training courses were conducted. The first course which began October 26 was organized to provide the 6-month rice production trainees with experience in planning and conducting a short course in rice production.

Staggered rice plantings had been made so that all the skills in growing a crop of rice, from selection of the seed to the drying of the harvested grain, could be practiced during the 2 weeks. Thirty-six persons took the first 2-week course.

The second course began November 16 and consisted of 28 trainees. This course was planned and managed by the RPTR staff, but most of the lectures were given by IRRI senior scientists.

Training programs outside IRRI

IRRI participated directly in training programs in two countries during 1970. In response to a request from the Government of Ceylon two RPTR staff members assisted with the training of 124 extension workers. In East Pakistan another staff member worked with East Pakistan trainers to train 361 workers.

Reorganization of the rice production training course

The reorganization of the IRRI rice production training course resulted in several innovations:

- Developing the general objectives of the training course.
- Deciding on topics to be covered.
- Developing specific behavioral objectives in cooperation with the proposed lecturer for each topic.
- Developing four-step lesson plans to achieve each teaching objective.
- Scheduling the lectures for the entire course and obtaining speakers 4 to 5 months before the start of the course, and coordinating and timing the sequence of lectures with the developing rice crop in the field.
- Providing an opportunity for the 6-month rice

production trainees to organize and conduct a 2-week rice production course as part of their training.

New teaching materials

A "Training Manual in Rice Production" and a "Syllabus for the Rice Production Course" have been developed. A four-step lesson plan has been developed for the teaching of the various skills in rice culture and these lessons have been compiled in the training manual. The syllabus contains the lectures given during the 6-month course. Together these two publications provide the basic resource materials needed in conducting short courses in rice production.

Applied research activities

Rice scientists are developing new means of increasing rice yields at a rate faster than they can be put to use by farmers.

To make maximum use of this new technology, massive field testing must be carried out in the rice-producing countries to determine its merits under widely varying conditions. In the Philippines, IRRI, the Bureau of Plant Industry, University of the Philippines College of Agriculture, Bureau of Soils, and Association of the Colleges of Agriculture in the Philippines cooperate with the National Food and Agriculture Council in an extensive applied research program. IRRI plays a major role in two programs: Farmers Evaluation of New Selections Applied Research Trial (Fensart) and Granular Herbicide Applied Research Trial (Ghart).

Fensart. New rice selections are becoming available at a rapid rate. To help the plant breeders evaluate these new materials quickly, Fensart plots are established every year in a number of locations in the Philippines to expose these new selections to widely differing environmental conditions and pests. Representatives of UPCA, BPI, and IRRI meet before each season

Table 1. Grain yield of 14 selections and varieties at 26 locations in the Philippines. 1970 dry season.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)									
	BPI-121-407 (NS)	C4-63G	C4-137	PB76-TB934	IR5	IR8	IR20	IR22	IR661-1-140-3-2	IR579-48-1
Agoo, La Union	7.2	6.3	6.3	6.9	5.1	7.2	4.7	7.0	7.3	5.1
Ormoc, Leyte del Norte	5.2	5.0	4.8	4.9	4.3	3.6	4.6	4.9	5.3	4.6
Manaoag, Pangasinan	6.6	6.3	6.3	6.5	6.7	7.1	6.6	7.5	7.5	7.0
Valencia, Bukidnon	4.4	5.1	5.6	5.0	5.0	5.5	6.2	4.4	6.4	5.3
San Manuel, Pangasinan	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.7	6.6	6.8	7.1	6.7
Pili, Camarines Sur	4.4	4.9	4.9	5.3	2.2	3.3	5.7	5.3	5.2	5.2
Alegria, Surigao N.	3.6	2.0	4.6	4.2	4.1	4.8	6.4	5.7	5.1	5.4
CLSU, Nueva Ecija	4.6	4.6	4.5	4.4	5.2	5.3	4.2	3.9	3.6	3.1
Sta. Rosa, Laguna	5.2	5.2	5.6	5.1	3.3	5.2	4.6	4.1	4.7	3.8
Teresa, Rizal	6.4	6.5	5.9	5.9	6.2	8.2	7.2	6.6	7.0	6.8
Sta. Ignacia, Tarlac	5.9	5.7	5.2	6.1	5.6	6.7	6.0	6.1	6.0	5.6
Tarlac, Tarlac	6.7	6.4	5.5	6.8	6.0	7.7	6.5	6.4	6.5	5.5
Abucay, Bataan	6.1	6.5	6.7	6.7	6.0	6.6	6.0	5.1	6.5	5.4
Dinalupihan, Bataan	5.4	5.5	6.2	6.2	5.7	5.7	5.6	5.2	5.7	4.7
Magalang, Pampanga	6.0	5.6	6.0	6.2	5.8	10.2	5.5	4.8	5.0	5.3
Polangui, Albay	6.1	5.6	4.4	4.0	4.9	7.8	7.3	5.9	6.9	5.9
Lasam, Cagayan	4.9	5.2	5.1	5.0	5.3	6.4	5.4	6.6	7.0	5.2
Solana, Cagayan	5.6	5.4	5.6	5.0	5.8	6.4	6.0	6.0	6.4	5.5
Tuao, Cagayan	6.3	7.7	6.3	6.2	6.2	7.5	7.8	7.9	8.0	5.8
Pototan, Iloilo	7.0	6.2	4.4	4.9	4.8	8.2	7.8	8.2	10.0	3.0
Candelaria, Quezon	7.4	4.1	6.4	6.7	7.2	5.6	5.8	8.0	10.0	8.2
Midsayap, Cotabato	6.7	5.3	5.1	5.2	3.7	2.9	6.9	6.2	5.2	6.4
Cuyapo, Nueva Ecija	4.6	5.6	6.0	5.1	5.1	5.2	5.7	5.4	4.5	5.0
Sto. Tomas, Pampanga	4.2	4.9	4.5	4.0	5.2	5.6	5.4	5.9	4.7	4.5
San Leonardo, Nueva Ecija	4.2	5.5	6.0	4.9	3.2	5.0	5.6	6.4	5.3	3.6
Sta. Rosa, Laguna	6.8	5.7	5.6	5.6	7.8	7.6	9.0	7.9	4.4	4.7
Average	5.7	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.3	6.2	6.1	6.1	6.2	5.3

Table 2. Performance of six granular herbicides in 19 locations in the Philippines, 1970 dry season.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	2,4-D IPE ^a (BAYER)	2,4-D IPE ^a (ESFAC)	EPTC/2,4-D ^b IPE	Trifluralin/ 2,4-D IPE ^c	TCE-Styrene/ 2,4-D IPE ^b	CP53619/ 2,4-D IPE ^d	Hand-weeded Control (2x)	
Angat, Bulacan	4.6	3.6	4.5	4.9	4.8	5.4	4.7	4.7
Angat, Bulacan	5.2	5.1	6.0	5.7	5.6	5.2	5.2	5.5
Baliuag, Bulacan	6.1	6.3	6.0	6.0	6.2	5.8	5.9	5.8
Bustos, Bulacan	4.5	3.8	3.9	4.4	4.8	4.7	4.1	3.0
Calumpit, Bulacan	4.0	3.9	4.0	4.5	3.8	4.6	4.0	4.1
Calumpit, Bulacan	4.9**	5.3**	5.1**	5.1**	5.1**	4.9**	5.2**	4.1
Guiguinto, Bulacan	4.4	4.2	4.2	4.9	5.1	4.9	4.2	3.4
Pulilan, Bulacan	5.2	5.3	5.2	5.4	5.1	5.9	5.0	5.0
Mayantoc, Tarlac	6.4	6.1	6.4	6.3	6.2	6.1	5.9	5.9
San Clemente, Tarlac	4.6	4.9	5.0	4.7	5.0	5.6	4.7	3.8
Tarlac, Tarlac	5.6	6.2	6.4	6.0	6.0	5.7	5.3	6.4
Camiling, Tarlac	3.8*	3.9*	4.7*	4.0*	4.3*	4.2*	3.8*	2.2
Magalang, Pampanga	4.5**	4.1**	4.4**	4.6**	4.4**	4.3**	4.2**	2.1
Minalin, Pampanga	5.6	5.7	4.8	5.4	5.3	5.1	6.1	5.1
Mexico, Pampanga	5.7	5.5	5.1	5.6	5.6	5.4	5.7	5.7
Sta. Rita, Pampanga	6.9	7.1	6.7	6.9	7.1	6.8	7.1	7.0
Lumban, Laguna	7.6	7.8	7.8	7.7	7.6	7.8	8.1	7.1
Sta. Maria, Laguna	6.7	6.7	6.8	6.6	6.6	6.6	6.4	6.7
Sta. Rosa, Laguna	4.3**	3.6**	4.6**	4.7**	4.8**	4.6**	5.2**	2.8
Average	5.3	5.2	5.3	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.3	4.8

*Significantly different from the control at the 5% level. **Significantly different from the control at the 1% level. ^a0.8 kg/ha active ingredient. ^b0.75/0.5 kg/ha active ingredient. ^c0.6/0.8 kg/ha active ingredient. ^d1.0/0.5 kg/ha active ingredient.

to decide on the selections to be included in the trial. Applied research kits containing seeds, fertilizers, insecticides, and herbicides are packaged and distributed to the provinces. BPI seed inspectors manage the plots since they will be involved in the field inspection activities if a selection is named a variety and certified seed is produced.

In the 1969 wet season, results of the trials from 16 locations showed that IR20, IR22, IR661-1-140-3-2, BPI-121-407 (NS), C4-137, and PB76-TB807 could produce yields at least equal to those of IR8. IR22 gave the highest yield with an average of 5.4 t/ha followed by IR20 and IR661-1-140-3-2 with an average yield of approximately 5 t/ha. IR8 produced 4.7 t/ha.

In the dry season, trials were conducted in 44 locations in 20 provinces. Fourteen rice selections and varieties were involved. Results from 26 locations showed that practically all the entries performed well (Table 1). IR8 and IR20 gave the highest average yields, approximately 6.2 t/ha. They were followed closely by an IR661 line and IR22 with an average yield of about 6.1 t/ha. There was no report of any significant disease or insect damage.

In the 1970 wet season, the Fensart trial was conducted in 48 plots in 30 provinces. Unfortunately, most of the plots were destroyed by a series of typhoons.

Ghart. Newly developed granular herbicide formulations, some of which have a wide range of effectiveness, are now available at relatively low cost.

To test six herbicides and determine their economic significance in farmers' fields, 19 plots were established in four provinces of Luzon during the 1970 dry season. The fields selected had reliable water supplies and were known to have been weedy in past seasons.

Significant yield differences between the treated plots and the control plots were obtained in four locations: one plot in Calumpit, Bulacan, one in Camiling, Tarlac, one in Magalang, Pampanga, and one in Sta. Rosa, Laguna (Table 2). Yields of the control plots were less than 3 t/ha while the yields of the treated plots ranged from 3.5 to 5 t/ha. No significant differences in yields were observed in the other 15 locations. Weed populations in these locations were not high enough to have significantly reduced yields in the control plots. These data probably

Table 3. Grain yields with various treatments of nitrogen and zinc.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Roots dipped in ZnO	Grain yield (t/ha)	Relative yield
0	No	3.2	100
0	Yes	3.1	97
100	No	3.4	106
100	Yes	3.8	119
100 ^a	No	4.1	128
100 ^a	Yes	4.4	138

^a 30 kg/ha N applied at 30 days after transplanting and 30 kg/ha N at 50 days after transplanting.

underestimate the impact of herbicides because farmers take better care of their plots once a scientist begins working with them. No significant yield differences were observed among the treated plots. All the herbicides were effective in controlling the weeds.

In the 1970 wet season, Ghart trials were conducted on 23 plots in five provinces but typhoons destroyed almost all plots, so no conclusions could be drawn.

IR127-80-1 broadcast kit. IR127-80-1 is a selection with desirable characteristics, like early maturity, extra large panicles, lodging resistance, tough leaves which resist shredding during typhoons, resistance to bacterial leaf blight and rice blast, and excellent grain quality. Its drawbacks are low tillering ability and susceptibility to rice stem borers.

To determine the yield potential of this selection when broadcast and grown under optimum insect protection, 10 plots of 1,000 sq m each were established in Batangas, Laguna,

Pampanga, and Tarlac during the 1970 wet season. Diazinon and furadan granules were used in all plots. Each plot was divided in half by a levee and one-half of each plot was treated with diazinon and the other half with furadan. Eptam M granules was applied at the rate of 40 kg/ha 14 days after seeding to control weeds. A seeding rate of 90 kg/ha was used.

Like most of the other applied research plots during the 1970 wet season, these plots were damaged severely by typhoons. Before the typhoons, the expected yields were estimated at approximately 5 t/ha in most plots. Except in one location where the plot was located in a problem soil area, all plots had a good stand.

No significant insect damage was observed, except in Alabang where the diazinon-treated plot suffered from a severe leafhopper attack. The yield of the furadan-treated plot at Alabang was about 1 t/ha more than the diazinon-treated plot.

Zinc trial. Growth of rice crops in some farms in Mexico, Pampanga had been reported to be very poor. Zinc deficiency was suspected to be the cause of the poor development. To test the effect of zinc on the growth of the rice crop, a trial was established on a farm in Mexico, Pampanga in the 1970 wet season. Seedlings were treated with a 1-percent zinc solution before transplanting and planted in plots treated with different levels of N-P-K combinations.

Significant differences in height and tillering were noted at the flowering stage. The split application of nitrogen plus zinc was effective in increasing yields (Table 3).

Training Programs

The Institute's training programs provide an opportunity for rice scientists and extension workers to acquire new knowledge and gain experience in their areas of activity. Both degree training and non-degree training are offered. For degree training, the Institute cooperates with the University of the Philippines and some universities in other countries. Degree candidates complete their course work at a university and carry out thesis research at the Institute under the guidance of its senior scientists.

The Institute accepts individuals with at least a bachelor's degree for training in any of the research areas. In 1970, 91 young scientists were in residence for a part or the whole of the year. Of the 40 who worked for a master of science degree one worked for a degree from Cornell University (U.S.A.) and another for a degree from the University of Queensland (Australia), and all others were enrolled at the University of the Philippines College of Agriculture. Two carried out thesis research for a Ph.D. degree from Cornell University, another did research for a Ph.D. degree from the University of Minnesota. Thirty-three young scientists received non-degree training and gained experience by working with Institute scientists. A degree candidate is in residence for about 2 years and a non-degree candidate for 6 months to 1 year. The Institute also had 15 post-doctoral fellows who carried out advanced research in their areas of specialization. The duration of a post-doctoral fellowship usually ranges from 1 to 2 years.

Individuals in the Institute training program who have a Bachelor's degree are usually designated "research scholars" and those with an M.S., Ph.D., or equivalent degrees, are called "post-M.S. fellows" and "post-doctoral fellows." Of the 91 young scientists in residence, 38 (20 research scholars, 11 post-M.S. fellows and 7 post-doctoral fellow) completed their training during the year. Table 1 shows the distribution of research trainees according to field of specialization. The largest number worked in agronomy, rice breeding and genetics,

plant physiology, agricultural economics, entomology, and plant pathology.

More and more requests are being received for training leading to a doctoral degree and for post-doctoral fellowships. The Institute has started a cooperative training program with the Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI) to train promising young individuals at the doctoral level. The Rockefeller Foundation provided a grant for this purpose. Under the program Ph.D. candidates will be selected each year from India and other Asian countries. They will complete their course work at the IARI Post-Graduate School, New Delhi, and then move to IRRI to do thesis research. The first group of scholars, two Indians and one Thai, are now enrolled for course work at IARI, New Delhi.

An important objective of the Institute training program is to encourage participants to work on research projects closely related to rice production problems in their home countries. Since the Institute research program is mainly devoted to rice production in the tropics, it provides ideal facilities for training scientists from tropical regions where most rice is grown.

Table 1. Distribution of different categories of scholars according to area of specialization.

Research area	Number of scholars			Total
	Research scholars	Post-M.S. fellows	Post-doctoral fellows	
Agronomy	8	6	5	19
Rice breeding and genetics	11	2	3	16
Plant physiology	5	2	1	8
Entomology	5	3	1	9
Plant pathology	4	1	2	7
Soil chemistry	3	—	2	5
Soil microbiology	1	3	1	5
Agricultural economics	8	2	—	10
Agricultural engineering	1	1	—	2
Chemistry	1	—	—	1
Statistics	4	1	—	5
Communication and extension	3	1	—	4
Total	54	22	15	91

The 6-month course in rice production is held every year to train participants to become qualified rice production specialists. The course includes classroom instruction as well as field work. It provides broad-based training in principles and practices of modern rice production and gives the trainees an opportunity to learn techniques of applied research and communication. Thirty-four participants from 12 countries attended the course. Most were extension workers or instructors involved with the training of extension agents and farmers. Nine participants possessed Master's degrees or the equivalent, 13 had Bachelor's degrees, and the rest had diplomas in agriculture.

The major aim of rice production training is to prepare the participants to conduct similar training in their home countries. The 1970 group of trainees were given the opportunity of organizing and conducting a short 2-week training course. Another 2-week course was held by the staff of the Office of Rice Production Training and Research. A total of 64 individuals from the Philippines and seven other countries participated in these short courses.

The 4-month Multiple Cropping Course which was first held in 1969 was repeated this year. The objective of this course is to train individuals in the theory and practice of multiple cropping systems with rice as the main crop grown during the rainy season. Twenty-one trainees from eight countries attended the course. Nine of them had Master's degrees, seven had Bachelor's degrees, and five were holders of diplomas in agriculture.

The Institute normally accepts for training only those individuals who belong to institutions concerned with rice and are sponsored and assured of a position upon their return by their employing organizations. Such a policy has facilitated the return of trainees to their home countries and ensured the proper utilization of their training. Most of the candidates selected from countries where the Institute has cooperative research programs are individuals involved in cooperative work. In selecting candidates the Institute gives special consideration to the training needs of individual countries. It tries to determine their training requirements on a long-

term basis and to provide training spaces to fulfill these requirements.

During 1970, 144 scholars, fellows, and other trainees were in residence for a part or the whole of the year. The number in residence at any one time ranged between 98 in July and 52 in December. The Institute's training program has gradually expanded. Eighty-one man-years of training was provided in 1970 compared with 69 man-years in 1969 and 62 man-years in 1968.

The 144 persons who studied at the Institute in 1970 came from 23 countries, mainly important rice-growing countries such as India, Pakistan, Thailand, Indonesia, Philippines, Ceylon, Taiwan, Japan, Korea, Vietnam, and Burma. Several came from Latin America and Africa. The names and home institutions of the research scholars, research fellows, and trainees who completed their training during the year are given below (those who completed a Master of Science degree are indicated by an asterisk). The major research of each research scholar or fellow is also indicated. In addition, information regarding individuals who came to the Institute for short-term study or observation programs is included.

RESEARCH SCHOLARS

Agronomy

Meehnon Khan Abbasi, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan. Chemical weed control in direct-seeded, flooded rice.

Alpha Diallo, project agronomist, Ministère del Economie Rurale, Guinea. Effects of management levels involving insect control, and of nitrogen level on the varietal performance; Performance of granular herbicides in transplanted rice.

*Samson Fagade**, research officer, Federal Department of Agricultural Research. Growth characteristics, grain yield, and quality of rice as affected by plant density and nitrogen level.

Kasuho-Makino, fraternal staff worker, Allahabad Agricultural Institute, India. Studies on some cultural practices for direct-seeded, flooded rice.

Enche Mohammed Tazuddin, rice agronomist, Department of Agriculture, Malaysia. Yield potential of rice varieties developed by IRRI and other countries; Weed control in transplanted rice.

Communication and Extension

Sosimo Pablico, Philippines. Evaluation of the "Mini-Kit" in an applied research program.

Agricultural Economics

Benjamin Gaon, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. The Philippine land reform program: its effects on productivity and farm income.

Carl Montañó, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Economic significance of the relationships between rice yield, nitrogen input, and solar energy.
*Dibjo Prabowo**, instructor, Gadjah Mada University, Jogjakarta, Indonesia. Farm income, resource use, and potential of new technology in two districts of Java.
Rodolfo Reyes, research assistant, The International Rice Research Institute, Philippines. Experiments on the economics of water distribution.

Entomology

Chang Jin Song, junior agronomist, Crop Experiment Station, Suwon, Korea. Resistance to *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) and *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) in some japonica rice varieties.

Plant Pathology

*Leonardo Santos**, plant entomologist, Bureau of Plant Industry, Philippines. Studies on the morphology, physiology, and pathogenicity of *Corticium sasakii* with special reference to the effect of nitrogen and carbon sources.

Tin Win, assistant mycologist, Agricultural Research Institute, Burma. Isolation, inoculation and test for resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and tungro and grassy stunt viruses.

Plant Physiology

Manuel Palada, instructor, Central Philippine University. Submergence and survival of rice plants.

Soil Chemistry

*Dae Young Cho**, assistant soil chemist, Institute of Plant Environment, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea. Influence of temperature regimes on the chemical kinetics of flooded soils and the growth of rice.

Soil Microbiology

*Ireneo Manguiat**, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Microbial transformation of nitrogen in flooded rice soils.

Statistics

Moo Sang Lim, assistant statistician, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Varietal-competition effects in rice experimental plots.

Varietal Improvement

Victoria Eugenia Kuri, laboratory technician, Instituto Colombiano Agropecuario, Colombia. Quality evaluation of the rice grain.

*Tomas Masajo**, instructor, College of Agriculture, University of the Philippines. Breeding behavior and relationship of white belly and gelatinization temperature to amylose content of the rice grain.

Shung Song, junior specialist, Taichung District Agricultural Improvement Station, Taiwan. Rice quality testing techniques.

RESEARCH FELLOWS

Victor Awoderu, research officer, Federal Department of Agricultural Research, Nigeria. Study of pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* derived from single-spore cultures.

Sanga Duangratana, statistician, Rice Department, Ministry

of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand. Field plot techniques for rice experiments.

Teh-Ming Chu, instructor, Department of Agronomy, Provincial Chung-Hsing University, Taiwan. Factors influencing shattering of rice grains.

Narendra Nath Kakati, assistant agronomist, Department of Agriculture, Assam, India. Weed control in transplanted rice; Germination characteristics of rice varieties.

Ghulam Nabi Kalwar, assistant agronomist, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan. Water management in puddled rice soils.

Dong Kyun Kim, assistant agronomist, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Korea. Sources of rock phosphate for flooded rice; Rates of EPTC/2, 4-D IPE herbicide for transplanted rice.

Milagrosa Martinez, instructor, Department of Biology, Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines. A survey of nitrogen-fixing bacteria in rice soil and rhizosphere.

Allaph Ditta Mastoi, research assistant, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan. Biology of *Tryporyza incertulas* (Walker) and testing of granular insecticides for its control.

Kazuo Nakabayashi, Hokkaido University, Japan. Relationship between nitrogen nutrition, chlorophyll content, and photosynthesis and photorespiration of rice leaves.

Raj Pal Puri, senior research assistant, Indian Agricultural Research Institute. Rice quality testing and rice breeding procedures.

S. S. Soundarajan, graduate student, University of Hawaii. Water use efficiency of rice at different nitrogen levels.

Post-doctoral

A. K. Bhattacharyya, reader in agronomy, Kalyani University, West Bengal, India. Effects of levels of nitrogen on the growth characteristics and grain yield of improved varieties and promising selections; Effects of soil temperature at different growth phases on nutrition, growth characteristics, and grain yield of flooded rice.

R. K. Jana, scientists' pool officer, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India. Effects of different environmental factors and soil water regimes on the growth and yield of rice; Effects of date of planting on the growth characteristics and grain yield of upland rice.

Muhammad Manzoor Khan, Lyallpur, West Pakistan. Yield and quality of shih-shih soybeans harvested for use as a vegetable.

Alejandro Hugo Manzano, head, soils program, Instituto Colombiano Agropecuario. Influence of water management on the chemical kinetics and the growth of rice on a problem soil from Nigeria.

G. N. Mitra, assistant botanist, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India. Rice quality testing and rice breeding procedures.

Myo Thant, assistant research officer, Agricultural Research Institute, Rangoon, Burma. Quality evaluation of the rice grain.

Muhammad Ehsan Ul Haq Tusneem, West Pakistan. Water management responses in broadcast-seeded rice; Nitrogen transformations in flooded soil.

RICE PRODUCTION TRAINEES

Saeed Ahmad, assistant agronomist, Government Rice Farm, Kala Shah Kaku, West Pakistan.

Abdulgani Kalam Iskandar, chief, Agricultural Extension Service, Karawang, Indonesia.

Cesar T. Chinte, agriculturist, A. Soriano y Cia, Philippines.
Tran Van Dat, deputy service chief, Department of Agriculture, Saigon, Vietnam.
A. S. D. De Silva, assistant agricultural officer, River Valleys Development Board, Embilipitiya, Ceylon.
Rizalino Dilag, Jr., International Rice Research Institute, Philippines.
Chau Kim Dinh, deputy chief, Agricultural Service, Department of Agriculture, Lam Dong, Vietnam.
M. L. P. Fernando, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Colombo, Ceylon.
Moh. Godjali, chief, Agricultural Extension Service, Indramaju, Indonesia.
Kailash Nath Gongal, district agricultural development officer, Department of Agriculture, Kathmandu, Nepal.
I. M. Gunawardena, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Ruwanwella, Ceylon.
Sun Bok Hwang, extension worker, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea.
Herman Soetari Kartosasmito, senior staff member, Agricultural Extension Service, Semarang, Indonesia.
Machrad Chozin, senior instructor, Agricultural Extension Service, Semarang, Indonesia.
Jose Mendoza, principal in-charge, Ilocos Sur Agricultural College, Philippines.
Nand Kumar Mishra, agronomist, Department of Agricultural Education and Research, Janakpur, Nepal.
U Mya Thien, district agricultural officer, Department of Agriculture, Minbu, Burma.
P. T. Patil, agricultural officer, Agricultural Research Station, Poona, India.
Pitoyo, leader of experimental farm, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia.
Vicente Ramirez, city agriculturist, Bacolod City, Philippines.
D. J. D. W. Rainayake, assistant agricultural officer, River Valleys Development Board, Embilipitiya, Ceylon.
Khamphon Rattanavong, provincial chief, Agriculture Extension Service, Directorate of Agriculture, Vientiane, Laos.
K. K. Sharma, assistant economic botanist (rice), Jawaharlal Nehru Agricultural University, Madhya Pradesh, India.
Thomas P. Sheridan, volunteer, U.S. Peace Corps in the Philippines.
Sirichai Somboonpong, 2nd grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand.
Siphon Souksamlan, agricultural extension agent, Directorate of Agriculture, Vientiane, Laos.
Jong Ro Suh, extension worker, Office of Rural Development, Chinchon-Kun, Korea.
Mohamad Sujuti, staff member, Directorate of Production Development, Department of Agriculture, Djakarta, Indonesia.
Boonrawd Thongdonphum, 3rd grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand.
G. K. Tibbotumunuwa, agricultural instructor, Agricultural Extension Centre, Nelundeniya, Ceylon.
U Tin Dwe, district agricultural officer, Department of Agriculture, Magwe, Burma.
Supawat Tipayarak, 2nd grade officer, Rice Department, Ministry of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand.
J. D. Tripathi, assistant professor, Uttar Pradesh Agricultural University, Uttar Pradesh, India.
W. A. S. Weerrakkody, agricultural instructor, Agricultural Extension Centre, Nikaweratiya, Ceylon.

MULTIPLE CROPPING TRAINEES

Saeed Ahmad, assistant agronomist, Government Rice Farm, Kala Shah Kaku, West Pakistan.

B. Aswathaiah, assistant crop scientist, Agricultural College, Dharwar, Mysore, India.
Santos Balderas, vocational agriculture teacher, Carmarines Sur National Agricultural School, Philippines.
Vicente Bonaobra, plant pest control officer, Bureau of Plant Industry, Camarines Sur, Philippines.
Amaratunga Dunusinghe, agricultural officer, River Valleys Development Board, Embilipitiya, Ceylon.
Surjatna Effendi, assistant corn agronomist, Central Research Institute for Agriculture, Bogor, Indonesia.
Alfonso Franco, agriculture coordinator, Tarlac College of Technology, Philippines.
Fabio Higuaita, associate geneticist, Colombian Institute of Agriculture, Bogota, Colombia.
Md Zahidul Hoque, teaching fellow, department of agronomy, E. P. Agricultural University, Mymensingh, East Pakistan.
Ghulam Nabi Kalwar, assistant agronomist, Rice Research Station, Dokri, West Pakistan.
Manir Uddin Khan, soil fertility assistant, East Pakistan Soil Fertility and Soil Testing Institute, Dacca, East Pakistan.
Vixayvong Kouthong, chief, crops and soils, Directorate of Agriculture, Pakse, Laos.
Pham Van Lam, chief, Phuyen Rural Affairs Office, Toy Hoa, Vietnam.
S. M. B. Makadawara, assistant, University Department of Agriculture, Peradeniya, Ceylon.
Nguyen Van Nhon, rice production field manager, National Rice Production Training Center, Bien Hoa, Vietnam.
Seneviratne Samarakoon, agricultural instructor, Department of Agriculture, Katugastota, Ceylon.
Arumugam Senthinathan, experimental officer, Department of Agriculture, Ambalantota, Ceylon.
Mervyn Sikurajapathy, lecturer, School of Agriculture, Kundasale, Ceylon.
A. I. Thomas, research officer, Central Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.
Selawa Hangrige Upasena, agricultural research officer, Department of Agriculture, Maha-Illuppallama, Ceylon.
Gustavo Villegas, researcher, Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Cali, Colombia.

SHORT-TERM VISITORS

Sung Ho Bae, chief, rice breeding division, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea, spent 1½ months observing rice breeding projects and seed production program.
Francis J. Bell, agronomist, U.S. Agency for International Development, Laos, spent 10 days becoming acquainted with varietal testing and multiple cropping programs.
Ahn Ja Cho, librarian, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea, spent 2 months receiving training in library operations.
Chang Sik Kang, research worker, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea, spent 2 weeks in the plant pathology department studying varietal resistance to major diseases of rice.
Charles Percy Kennard, deputy director of research, Guyana Rice Corporation, familiarized himself with programs of different departments and organizational set-up of the Institute during his 10-day stay.
Sung Rai Kim, chief, farm machinery division, Institute of Agricultural Engineering and Utilization, Office of Rural Development, Suwon, Korea, spent 3 weeks observing machinery research and development work in the agricultural engineering department.
Key Hong Lee, assistant agronomist, Yungnam Crop Experiment Station, Milyang, Korea, spent 2 weeks in the

plant pathology and varietal improvement departments studying varietal resistance to rice diseases.

Ridha Said Marouf, director, technical division, Ministry of Agriculture, Baghdad, Iraq, spent 3 weeks observing rice production techniques and reviewing programs of various departments.

Fukumatsu Suzuki, chief, localization section, department of farm management and land utilization, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Tokyo, Japan, spent 3 months familiarizing himself with the research program of the department of agricultural economics.

Tin Myint, Department of Agriculture, Burma, spent 2 weeks studying and observing rice breeding procedures.

International Activities

Cooperative research

The Institute's international activities are aimed at strengthening the rice research programs of cooperating countries. Informally, the Institute cooperates with many rice growing countries by providing seed samples, exchanging information on new techniques, and carrying out cooperative experiments. The Institute's senior staff make frequent visits to rice growing countries to exchange ideas with local scientists. Nearly any rice research center in the world can consult with the Institute's staff about national rice growing problems.

Staff members of the Institute are assigned to several national research programs, with funding by grants or contracts from international development agencies. Funds may also be provided for purchasing certain equipment not available in the host country and for short study and observation tours by senior members of the research team and by government officials.

In addition to doing research on local rice problems, advisers assigned by the Institute assist in the selection of young scientists for training in the Philippines and elsewhere.

Since the Institute's advisers work as members of national programs, the results of their research are not reported here. Persons interested in learning the details of the national programs and their findings should contact the officers of the programs directly.

Pakistan. Since 1966 a rice adviser from the Institute has been located in Dacca, East Pakistan to work with government authorities in accelerating rice research. He was joined in 1968 by a second adviser who is a specialist in entomology. Notable progress has been made towards the development of a fully integrated team approach to rice research. A grant from the Ford Foundation makes Institute participation possible.

In 1966 the Ford Foundation and the West Pakistan government signed an agreement under which a major effort would be made to accelerate rice research and production. Since then the

Institute has had an adviser stationed in West Pakistan to assist in these developments. Research capability has increased notably and excellent progress has been made in raising rice yields.

India. The All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), an agency of the Government of India, serves as the focal point for cooperative activities of the Institute in India. Through a contract with the U.S. Agency for International Development the Institute has four senior staff members stationed in India. They are in the fields of agronomy, plant pathology, entomology, and plant physiology. A fifth member of the team assigned by The Rockefeller Foundation, serves as joint coordinator of the project. This arrangement has been in force since mid-1967. The AICRIP project is broadly based in subject matter as well as in geographical extent. It has been notably successful in developing modern rice varieties specifically designed for Indian conditions.

Ceylon. A Ford Foundation grant enables the Institute to participate in the Ceylon Ministry of Agriculture's rice research and development programs. From 1967 to 1969, a member of the Institute's senior staff served in Ceylon as an adviser in agronomic research. From 1969 until the present, an adviser in rice production training and research has been in residence there. The program to train extension workers and farmers on handling the modern rice varieties for optimum results has been particularly successful.

Indonesia. In 1970 the Ford Foundation and the government of Indonesia agreed upon a program under which the Institute would assist in developing the national rice research program. In this coordinated effort several foreign aid agencies and various research units within Indonesia will work towards a nationwide integrated program. The Institute now has a rice adviser in genetics and breeding located at Bogor, Indonesia.

International conferences

In 1970, one major meeting, the annual "International Rice Research Conference," was held. Rice scientists from around the world gathered to discuss their work with particular attention to varietal improvement, agronomy, and plant pathology. Papers were presented on breeding for increased yields and for insect and disease resistance. In the agronomy sections, basic and applied aspects of soil chemistry and fertilizer use were examined with emphasis on nitrogen and phosphorus. Several speakers reported on the use of minor elements and the occurrence of deficiencies. There was a separate program on soil and water management. Weed control also received special attention. Temperature and photoperiod reactions, and the physiological bases for breeding for high yields and recent advances in studies of photosynthesis of the rice

plant were discussed, too.

The Institute took an active part in promoting national efforts to collect, evaluate, and preserve indigenous rice germ plasm, especially germ plasm of a primitive unimproved nature. The need to conserve the dwindling stock of genetic diversity was discussed at the International Rice Research Conference and received good response from the various national leaders present at the meeting. Subsequent contacts of the Institute staff with U.S. Department of Agriculture led to the First International Rice Collection and Evaluation Project Conference held at Hyderabad, India, which was partly supported by Institute funds. A committee was appointed to coordinate and assist regional activities, with the Institute's geneticist serving as the chairman. National activities were initiated in Laos, Nepal, Pakistan, and South Vietnam during the year.

Other Activities

Library and documentation center

International bibliography. The 1969 Supplement to the International Bibliography of Rice Research was completed in 1970. Consisting of 289 pages, including a list of translations and indexes, the supplement contains 2,855 bibliographic citations. Most of the references were taken from journals printed in 1969. An additional 66 serial titles were scanned and searched in the compilation. As in previous supplements, the citations in the 1969 supplement are arranged according to subject matter, and an author and a manually produced keyword index are provided. A list of rice literature translations to English is included.

The Bibliography is sent to libraries and documentation centers of the rice-producing countries for the benefit of rice research workers and those responsible for disseminating information on the crop. The basic volume and the annual supplements list virtually all the technical literature on rice published since 1951.

Reference and circulation. During the year the library received numerous requests for information and photocopying services, with the greatest number coming from India, Malaysia, and Brazil. The demand was mostly for Japanese literature on rice breeding, genetics, entomology, and pathology. A few requests for short bibliographies on specific subjects, and for assistance in solving problems of administration, organization, acquisition, and information retrieval were also received.

Circulation statistics within the Institute totalled 20,984. Figures on direct library use are not available because the library operates an open-stack system.

Library holdings. The addition of 1,893 monographs (books, pamphlets, and reprints) brought the over-all monographic collection to 25,746. Fifteen new periodical subscriptions were placed, 10 new exchanges were established, and 51 additional titles were received as gifts. The total number of serial titles is now 1,114. Other

library materials acquired were maps, theses and rice articles on microfilm, and translations. About 10,000 cards were added to the card catalogue.

Other activities. The routing of tables of contents of newly received journals was continued to keep the scientists informed of the latest publications on rice. As in previous years, this service was extended to the Rice Breeding Department of The Rockefeller Foundation Agricultural Program in Colombia and to the All-India Co-ordinated Rice Improvement Project in Andhra Pradesh, India. The monthly listing of new acquisitions of books, serial titles, translations, reprints, and microfilms was more widely distributed.

Copies of translations of foreign-language literature were sent regularly to the National Agriculture Library, U.S. Department of Agriculture, which in turn lists these in the Bibliography of Agriculture to make them readily available to scientists.

The library continued to purchase and distribute books to research scholars. Lectures on the use of the library and literature search were also conducted for the trainees.

Bindery. In 1970 the bindery output was as follows: periodicals, 724 volumes; theses, 44 volumes; field books, 55 volumes; pamphlets, 375 volumes; International Bibliography of Rice Research, 521 volumes; reprint file boxes, 73 pieces; slide boxes and albums, 18 pieces; folders, 39 pieces; mounting maps, four pieces; and name tags, 74 pieces.

Experimental farm

The Experimental Farm planted several promising IRRI selections for seed production in the dry season: IR665-24-1, IR747B2-6-1, IR579-E19, IR665-40-1, IR844-6-2, and IR790-28-6. Seed of the varieties IR8 and IR22 were also produced. In the wet season, IR579-1-2, IR579-3-1-2, and IR22 were grown for seed. The crops

were planted one plant per hill at 25 cm x 25 cm spacing with 80 kg/ha N in the wet season and 125 kg/ha N in the dry season. In cooperation with the varietal improvement department, 158 selections were planted in small plots for seed increase.

Seventy-six hectares were prepared and planted for the different departments of the Institute.

The water shortages that sometimes occur in some blocks were solved by installing one new pump, replacing another with one of a larger size, and installing additional underground irrigation pipes.

Typhoons caused great damage not only to crops but also to facilities. Several roads were eroded or washed away by overflowing creeks.

Infestations of leafhoppers, quite serious this year, contributed to the low yield of the wet season crop. For insect control, we used Sevin 85-S, lindane, Folidol M-50, Dolmix, and Mipcin. In all spraying operations, Tenac sticker was added so that the spray solution would stay on the plant longer.

For weed control in the experimental and production plots and levees, roadways, and ditches, we used 2,4-D granules, liquid Hedonal, and Gramoxone.

Rats did little damage to the rice plants in the experimental and production plots. We received a donation of 50 kg of zinc phosphide from Mr. Nelson Swink of the Rodent Research Center which we found to be very useful in our baiting program. The poison bait is made by mixing 333 g of zinc phosphide with 50 kg of milled rice and 500 g of corn oil. The addition of a sticker to the bait helped prolong the effect of the poison when exposed to the rain. This is the first year we have used this chemical and it gave better results than monosodium fluoroacetate (1080), an expensive and highly poisonous chemical. Over 4,500 rats were killed by the electric fence.

Information services

Revised versions of the general information bulletin and the training program brochure were published. A general information leaflet was

developed that can be economically distributed to the thousands of visitors who come to the Institute each year for guided tours.

Two new technical bulletins, *Marketing relationships for rice and corn in the Philippines* and *Nutritional disorders of rice in Asia*, were published. The latter contains 32 color plates of nutritional disorders. Another technical bulletin, *Resistance of rice varieties to striped rice borers*, is in press.

Catalog of rice cultivars, which contains 250 pages of computer print-outs of data about the rices in IRRI's world collection, was published and made available to rice breeders.

A 96-page handbook of rice pests and diseases, *Field problems of tropical rice*, is in press. This book has 90 color plates showing common insects, diseases, and nutritional disorders along with a brief description of each problem. The book is being published in English, but an Indonesian translation is planned.

More than 5,000 copies of a revised version of the leaflet, *Cultural practices for profitable rice production in the Philippines*, were distributed to meet requests of individuals and various agencies.

A preliminary draft of a 150-page *Training manual in rice production* was edited and a small number of multilith copies were printed.

By close consultation with the authors, we were able to cut the 1969 annual report to two-thirds the size of the previous year's report. Partly as a result of having fewer pages, the 1969 annual report was published 6 months earlier than the report the year before.

To provide IRRI authors with a standard style reference, the office of information services purchased copies of the *Style manual for biological journals* from the American Institute of Biological Sciences and distributed them to each department.

An internal newsletter was started to discuss special style problems of IRRI authors such as uniformity in spelling and punctuation of transliterated names of rice varieties. In addition, the newsletter comments on common problems of scientific writing such as jargon, citation style, and passive voice.

The visitors' demonstration plot was set up to show some of IRRI's more dramatic research

results: tall vs. short varieties, varieties resistant to insects and diseases, chemical weed control, etc. Tours of the Institute were taken by 10,000 visitors.

To ensure that persons on our mailing list have an active interest in the Institute's publi-

cations and that their addresses are correct, the entire list was circularized. A thousand names were dropped from the *IRRI Reporter* list and 700 from the annual report list. The *IRRI Reporter* list now has 4,000 names and the annual report list has 2,000 names.

Publications and Seminars

Staff publications

Agricultural Economics

- Barker, R. 1970. Green revolution. *Curr. Affairs Bull.* (Dept. of Adult Education, University of Sydney) 45:5.
- Barker, R. 1970. Economic aspects of new high-yielding varieties of rice: IRRI report, p. 29-53. *In* Avery Russel [ed.]. *Agricultural revolution in southeast Asia* (Vol. I). The Asia Society, Inc., New York.

Agricultural Engineering

- Khan, A. U. 1970. Mechanizing the tropical rice farm. *Agr. Eng.* 51(11): 640-642.
- Navasero, N., and A. U. Khan. 1970. Use of mechanical power for rotary weeding. *PANS* 16:87-92.

Agronomy

- De Datta, S. K., and P. M. Zarate. 1970. Environmental conditions affecting the growth characteristics, nitrogen response, and grain yield of tropical rice. *Biometeorology* 4(1):71-89.
- Nangju, D., and S. K. De Datta. 1970. Effects of varietal types and nitrogen level on the optimum time of harvest and the amount of breakage in transplanted rice. *Agron. J.* 62:468-474.
- De Datta, S. K., R. Q. Lacsina, and Ch. M. Ahmed. 1970. Water management for granular herbicides in transplanted rice. *Int. Rice Comm. Newslett.* 19(3):1-4.
- De Datta, S. K., and P. C. Bernasor. 1971. Selectivity of some new herbicides for direct-seeded flooded rice in the tropics. *Weed Res.* 11:41-46.
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Chemistry

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- Baun, L. C., E. P. Palmiano, C. M. Perez, and B. O. Juliano. 1970. Enzymes of starch metabolism in the developing rice grain. *Plant Physiol.* 46:429-434.
- Cartaño, A. V., and B. O. Juliano. 1970. Hemicelluloses of milled rice. *J. Agr. Food Chem.* 18:40-42.
- Cruz, L. J., G. B. Cagampang, and B. O. Juliano. 1970. Biochemical factors affecting protein accumulation in the rice grain. *Plant Physiol.* 46:743-747.
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- Raghavendra Rao, S. N., and B. O. Juliano. 1970. Effect of parboiling on some physicochemical properties of rice. *J. Agr. Food Chem.* 18:289-294.

Entomology

- Pathak, M. D. 1970. Stem borer and leafhopper-planthopper resistance in rice varieties, p. 789-800. *In* J. de Wilden and L. M. Schoonhoven [ed.]. *Insect and host plant: proceedings of the second international symposium on insect and host plant, Wageningen, the Netherlands, June 2-5, 1969.* North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam.
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- Bae, Sang Hee, and M. D. Pathak. 1970. Life history of *Nilaparvata lugens* (Homoptera: Delphacidae) and susceptibility of rice varieties to its attacks. *Entom. Soc. Amer. Ann.* 63(1):149-155.

Multiple Cropping

- Bradfield, R. 1970. Increasing food production in the tropics by multiple cropping, p. 229-242. *In* "Research for the world food crisis." Publication No. 92. American Association for the Advancement of Science, Washington, D.C.

Plant Pathology

- Ling, K. C. 1969. Virus diseases of rice in the Philippines and their effect on yield. *Sci. Rev.* 10(9):23-30.
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Seminars

The following topics were the subjects of seminars held at the Institute during 1970. Unless otherwise stated, the speakers were staff members.

Taal volcano, its history and recent activity. Dr. Arturo Alcaraz, chief volcanologist, Commission on Volcanology.

Nutritional disorders of rice in Asia. Dr. Yoshida.

Recent advances in chemical control of plant diseases. Dr. Otto Schultz, visiting professor in Plant Pathology, UP-Cornell Graduate Education Program.

Economic development of Laguna. Governor Felicisimo San Luis, Laguna.

Experiments on controlling blast with systemic fungicides. Dr. Ou.

The effects of simazine on the protein content of the rice grain. Dr. Vergara.

Activities of the United Nations Development Programme and its role in the Philippines. Mr. Gamil H. Hamdy, deputy resident representative, United Nations Development Program.

Dynamics of the population program in the Philippines. Dr. Jack P. Keeve, chief, Population/Family Planning Division, U.S. Agency for International Development, Manila.

Formulation and implementing an organization's strategy. Dr. Stephen H. Fuller, president, Asian Institute of Management, Manila.

Methods of evaluating crop yields in relation to nutritional needs in the tropics. Dr. Henry M. Munger, head, vegetable crops department, Cornell University.

The movement of the salt materials in soil—some theoretical and experimental results. Dr. Krupp.

Agricultural development in the Philippines: prospects and problems. Dr. Clark C. Bloom, representative, Ford Foundation, Philippines.

Social and health aspects of family planning. Dr. Jack P. Keeve, chief, Population/Family Planning Division, U.S. Agency for International Development, Manila.

Finger-printing plants—genetic control of isoenzyme polymorphisms in maize. Dr. James L. Brewbaker, professor of horticulture, University of Hawaii.

Management dynamics. Dr. Jim Culliton, head, Harvard Advisory Group, Inter-university Program of Graduate Business Administration, Ford Foundation.

Modernizing the grain processing industry in the Philippines. Dr. Dante de Padua, chairman, agricultural engineering department, UPCA.

Impact of devaluation on fertilizer use and profitability in the Philippines. Dr. Barker.

Tracer studies of N-transformation in flooded soils. Dr. Francis E. Broadbent, visiting soil microbiologist, University of California, Davis.

Sulfur nutrition of non-legumes. Dr. Graeme J. Blair, department of soil science, University of Guelph, Ontario, Canada.

High-yielding varieties and the barrio farmer. Dr. Robert Huke, visiting scientist, IRRI.

The Asian Development Bank and agriculture. Mr. Krishna Moorthi, vice president, Asian Development Bank.

Pilot rice processing plant concepts for the Philippines. Mr. Federico V. Borromeo, president, The Borromeo Corporation, Manila.

Philippine rodent research program. Mr. F. Nelson Swink, biologist, Rodent Research Center, UPCA.

The application of science to world food production: achievements and potentialities. Dr. Chandler.

The prospects of agriculture in the light of the challenges in the 70's. Dr. Faustino T. Orillo, dean, UPCA.

Towards the green revolution. Mr. Eliseo Ocampo, executive vice president and general manager, Greater Manila Terminal Food Market.

Recent advances in natural rubber and the role of the Rubber Research Institute of Malaya. Mr. Albert Ravenholt, journalist.

A new orientation for agricultural transformations. Mr. Arturo Tanco, Jr., undersecretary, Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources.

Factors limiting the production of tropical pastures in Brazil. Dr. Gerald O. Mott, visiting professor, Department of Agriculture, University of Queensland, Australia.

NSDB looks at the rural areas. Gen. Florencio A. Medina, chairman, National Science Development Board.

Not relief, but release. Dr. Y. C. James Yen, president, International Institute of Rural Reconstruction.

Towards the blue revolution. Dr. Lawrence B. Darrah, visiting professor, agricultural economics department, UPCA.

The development of industries as related to Philippine economy. Atty. Froilan M. Bacuñgan, executive secretary, Philippine Chamber of Industries.

The beef industry of the Philippines: present and potential. Dr. Joseph Madamba, assistant professor, animal husbandry department, UPCA.

The Philippine population problem: what it is and how it manifests itself. Dr. Mercedes B. Concepcion, director, Population Institute, University of the Philippines.

The Comprehensive Community Health Program of the University of the Philippines. Dr. LeRoy R. Allen, visiting professor for community medicine, College of Medicine, University of the Philippines.

The microclimate in relation to the development and behavior of two species of Canadian grasshoppers. Dr. Dyck.

The role of foreign investments in a developing economy. Mr. Vicente R. Jayme, executive vice president, Private Development Corporation of the Philippines.

Agricultural Development Council: its response to the changing Asian scene. Dr. Ray Borton, visiting professor, UPCA.

Economic development and the transfer of industrial technology: some historical perspectives. Dr. Nathan Rosenberg, visiting professor, School of Economics, University of the Philippines.

Censuses of population and housing. Dr. Tito A. Mijares, director, Bureau of Census and Statistics.

Feasibility of utilizing varietal resistance in insect pest control. Dr. Pathak.

U.S. foreign assistance policies for the seventies. Mr. Thomas C. Niblock, director, U.S. Agency for International Development, Manila.

Oxidation-reduction reactions in nature. Dr. Ponnampereuma.

Socio-cultural correlates for family planning education. Dr. Nena R. Bustrillos, chairman, home technology department, UPCA.

Malnutrition in the Philippines. Dr. Carmen Ll. Intengan, assistant research director, Food and Nutrition Research Center.

The implications of agricultural prices. Dr. Levy A. Trinidad, chief, Office of the Agricultural Marketing News Service, Bureau of Agricultural Economics, Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources.

Determining the mechanical properties of rice. Mr. James R. Hammerle, assistant professor of agricultural engineering, North Carolina State University.

CORRECTIONS / The International Rice Research Institute Annual Report 1970

- p. i. line 10. Should read:
stated. A double asterisk means significant at the 1% level; a single
- p. 42. Table 26. Under IR8, line 5, change L: 283 mg, M: 130 mg to:
L: 1150 mg, M: 130 mg
- p. 49. Fig. 3. On vertical axis change 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, to:
5, 10, 15, 20
- p. 77. Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Vertical axis. Change 10^3 conidia $28 \text{ liter}^{-1} \text{ air}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$ to:
 10^1 conidia $28 \text{ liter}^{-1} \text{ air}^{-1} \text{ hr}^{-1}$
- p. 85. Fig. 11, caption. Second line should read:
streak method (above) and dilution plate method (below)
- p. 142. Table 21. In grain yield column change (kg/ha) to:
(t/ha)
- p. 143. First column, line 16. Change NTN 5006/2,4-D to:
NTN 5006/MCPA
- p. 145. Table 26. Last line of caption should read:
varieties and three nitrogen levels). 1970 wet season.
- p. 168. Second column, line 13. Change 50 kg/hr to:
5 kg/hr
- p. 194. Fig. 11. On horizontal axis, change Days after transplanting to:
Days after seeding
- p. 208. Table 7, title. Change field trials to:
yield trials
- p. 251. First column, line 23. Change IR20 to:
an IR661 line
- p. 251. First column, line 25. Change an IR661 line to:
IR20